

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D6.3

MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics
Release 2.00

December 2023

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
CHS-RMC	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

GA#: 965422 **Start Date:** 01/04/2021
Topic: SC1-DTH-12-2020 **Duration:** 42 months
Type of Action: RIA **Coordinator:** NTUA

Deliverable Number	D6.3
Deliverable Title	MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics Release 2.00
Work Package Number	WP6
Task Number	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Date of Delivery	31/12/2023
Dissemination Level	Public
Work Package Leader	EVOLUTION
Lead Beneficiary	EVOLUTION
Authors	EVOLUTION
Contributors	NTUA
Reviewers	HSCSP, SIMAVI

Disclaimer

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the EASME nor the European Commission is responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Copyright Message

This report, if not confidential, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0); a copy is available here: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. You are free to share (copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and adapt (remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially) under the following terms: (i) attribution (you must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made; you may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use); (ii) no additional restrictions (you may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits).

Document History

Version	Date	Author (Partner)	Remarks/Changes
0.10	20/12/2023	Vassilis Stamoulos (EVOL)	Copied D6.2 to start and update it for D6.3
0.20	21/12/2023	Ioannis Matsoukas (EVOL)	Updated chapter 7.2, 7.5
0.30	21/12/2023	Michael Kontoulis (NTUA) George Doukas (NTUA) Theodosios Pountridis (NTUA) George Ladikos (NTUA)	Updated chapters 8.4, 8.5, 8.6, 10.2, 10.3
0.35	22/12/2023	Ioannis Matsoukas (EVOL)	Updated chapter 8.7
0.40	22/12/2023	Vassilis Stamoulos (EVOL) Ioannis Matsoukas (EVOL)	Updated chapters 8.7, 10.1
0.50	28/12/2023	Javier Arranz (IR-HSCSP)	Internal Review 1
0.60	28/12/2023	Iacob Crucianu (SIMAVI)	Internal Review 2
0.70	29/12/2023	Michael Kontoulis (NTUA) George Doukas (NTUA) Theodosios Pountridis (NTUA) George Ladikos (NTUA)	Comments consolidation
0.80	29/12/2023	Vassilis Stamoulos (EVOL) Ioannis Matsoukas (EVOL)	Comments consolidation
0.90	30/12/2023	George Doukas (NTUA) Michael Kontoulis (NTUA)	Quality Control
1.00	30/12/2023	Christos Ntanos (NTUA)	Final Version

Table of Contents

LIST OF Figures	9
LIST OF Tables	14
LIST OF Abbreviations	15
1 Introduction	17
1.1 Structure of the Deliverable	17
1.2 Relation to other deliverables/WPs/Tasks.....	18
2 Landscape Analysis	20
2.1 Evidence-Based Medicine	20
2.1.1 Definition of Evidence-Based Medicine.....	20
2.1.2 History of Evidence-Based Medicine	21
2.1.3 Analysis of the different steps of Evidence-Based-Medicine	21
2.1.4 Randomised control trials and observational studies.....	22
2.1.5 Advantages and limitations.....	22
2.2 Hypothesis Testing in Medicine.....	23
2.2.1 Definition of hypothesis testing	23
2.2.2 Errors in hypothesis testing.....	23
2.2.3 P-values	23
2.2.4 Significance.....	24
2.2.5 Statistical hypothesis tests	24
2.3 Process Modelling and Management	27
2.3.1 In Healthcare.....	27
2.3.2 In Medical Research.....	31
2.4 Data Analytics and Processing.....	32
2.4.1 Statistical methods and Data Analysis in Medical Research.....	33
2.4.2 Data visualizations.....	35
2.5 Artificial Intelligence.....	38
2.5.1 Theoretical Background	38
2.5.2 AI in Medicine.....	41
2.5.3 Trustworthy AI.....	42
2.5.4 Explainable AI.....	43
3 State-Of-The-Art Analysis	46
3.1 Expert System - Process Modelling and Management – Comparative Analysis	46
3.1.1 Overview	46
3.1.2 Process Modelling and Management Tools	46
3.2 Data Analytics and Visualisations – Comparative Analysis	54
3.2.1 Overview	54
3.2.2 Tools used for Data Processing and Analytics	54
3.2.3 Tools used for Data Visualisations	71
3.2.4 Analysis - Conclusions	77
3.3 Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning – Comparative Analysis.....	85
3.3.1 Overview	85
3.3.2 Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning Tools	85
4 Requirements’ Elaboration	92
4.1 Expert System - Process Modelling and Management	92
4.2 Query Builder	98
4.3 Data Analytics.....	98
4.4 Hypothesis Testing Interface	102
4.5 Data and Results Visualisation	103
4.6 Artificial Intelligence.....	106
4.7 Integration	108
4.7.1 Advanced Analytics Components’ Integration.....	108
4.7.2 Advanced Analytics and MES-CoBraD Platform Integration.....	109
5 Advanced Analytics Architecture	110
5.1 Overall Architecture.....	110

5.2	Components	111
5.2.1	Expert System - Process Modelling and Management	111
5.2.2	Query Builder	113
5.2.3	Data Analytics	114
5.2.4	Data and Results Visualisation	117
5.2.5	Artificial Intelligence	119
5.2.6	User Interface.....	120
6	Advanced Analytics Mockups.....	124
6.1	User Interface.....	124
6.2	Expert System - Process Modelling and Management	131
6.3	Query Builder	134
6.4	Data Analytics.....	135
6.5	Hypothesis Testing Interface	141
6.6	Data and Results Visualisation	152
7	APIs' Specification.....	158
7.1	Query Builder and MES-CoBraD Data Lake.....	158
7.1.1	Query Builder APIs	158
7.1.2	Components - Schemas	164
7.2	Expert System - Process Modelling and Management	171
7.2.1	Overview Paths.....	171
7.2.2	Components - Schemas	200
7.3	Data Analytics.....	202
7.4	Data and Results Visualisation	247
7.5	Artificial Intelligence.....	262
7.5.1	Overview Paths.....	262
7.5.2	Conclusion.....	279
8	Implementation.....	281
8.1	Overview	281
8.1.1	Placement in the overall architecture	281
8.1.2	Hardware infrastructure	282
8.1.3	Software infrastructure	282
8.2	Expert System - Process Modelling and Management	283
8.2.1	Overview	283
8.3	Query Builder	290
8.3.1	Overview	290
8.3.2	Functionalities.....	291
8.4	Data and Results Visualisation	297
8.5	Data Analytics.....	299
8.5.1	Overview	299
8.5.2	Function Finalisation and Automatic Re -Execution	300
8.5.3	EEG Functions.....	301
8.5.4	MRI Functions	325
8.5.5	Actigraphy Functions	335
8.6	Hypothesis Testing Interface	345
8.6.1	Overview	345
8.6.2	Functions and Methods.....	345
8.7	Artificial Intelligence.....	406
8.7.1	AI Integration and Interoperability for Data Analytics and Query.....	407
8.7.2	AI Algorithms and Modules	411
8.7.3	Data Acquisition and Preprocessing.....	413
8.7.4	Predictive Modelling	414
8.7.5	Application of Expert System in Medical Workflow Design and Prediction	416
8.8	User Interface.....	417
8.8.1	Technologies, packages	417
8.8.2	Portal UI.....	417
9	Integration.....	421

9.1	Integration between components	421
9.1.1	Integration challenges	421
9.1.2	Integration Principles.....	422
9.1.3	Integration Mechanisms.....	422
9.2	Integration with the MES-CoBraD Platform	424
9.2.1	Read data from other systems.....	424
10	Testing.....	425
10.1	Expert System - Process Modelling and Management	425
10.1.1	Database model testing	425
10.1.2	Endpoint response testing	427
10.1.3	Utility functions testing.....	429
10.2	Hypothesis Testing & Data Analytics Testing	429
10.2.1	End point testing and Content Visualisations	429
10.2.2	UI Performance Testing.....	430
10.3	Artificial Intelligence.....	435
10.3.1	Module testing	435
10.3.2	Endpoint Response Testing.....	435
11	Conclusions and Next Steps	436
12	References.....	438
ANNEX I :	Data Analytics Tools Information Collection	447
ANNEX II :	Metadata Manager OpenAPI v3.....	457

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 – Structure of the deliverable	18
Figure 2 – Relation of WP6 with other WPs and Tasks.....	19
Figure 3 – The benefits of digital transformation (Source: Deloitte research and analysis 2020)	27
Figure 4 – Stakeholders involved in the digital transformation of healthcare (Source: Deloitte research and analysis 2020).....	28
Figure 5 – Heatmap of a Correlation Matrix	36
Figure 6 – Hypnogram.....	37
Figure 7 – EEG Topography	37
Figure 8 – STFT spectrogram.....	38
Figure 9 – Key aspects of AI	40
Figure 10 – Main benefits of Trustworthy AI.....	43
Figure 11 – Benefits of Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI).....	44
Figure 12 – Advancement of Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) Source: DARPA[60]	45
Figure 13 – SpiffWorkflow’s optional UI.....	47
Figure 14 – Airflow: List of DAGs.....	48
Figure 15 – Airflow: DAG structure	48
Figure 16 – Airflow: Gantt diagram of execution times[68]	49
Figure 17 – ProcessMaker’s graphical interface	50
Figure 18 – N8n’s graphical interface	51
Figure 19 – Pipefly: Marketing campaign example.....	52
Figure 20 - MES-CoBraD Architecture	111
Figure 21 – Query Builder Component diagram.....	113
Figure 22 – Advanced Analytics Component diagram	115
Figure 23 – Data and Results Visualisation Component diagram	118
Figure 24 – Main Menu Presentation	122
Figure 25 – Home Page Mock-up.....	125
Figure 26 – Register Form Mock-up.....	126
Figure 27 – Login Form Mock-up	127
Figure 28 - Incoming Data Monitoring Page Mock-up.....	127
Figure 29 – Options Page Mock-up.....	128
Figure 30 – Article Page Mock-up	129
Figure 31 – Patient Profile Page Mock-up	130
Figure 32 – View Patient List Mockup Page	131
Figure 33 – Creation of a workflow	132
Figure 34 – List of all available workflows.....	133
Figure 35 – Clinical process execution	134
Figure 36 – Interface of the Query Builder	135
Figure 37 – List of all the available analyses for the electrophysiology signals	136
Figure 38 – List of parameters for the detection of spindles.....	137
Figure 39 – List of parameters for the computation of the STFT	138
Figure 40 – List of parameters given to an ARIMA model	139
Figure 41 – List of parameters for the computation of the Power Spectral Density using the Welch's method.....	140
Figure 42 – List of parameters for the computation of the autocorrelation function.....	141
Figure 43 – List of all the created hypothesis scenarios.....	142
Figure 44 – Initial Interface	143
Figure 45 – Methods for checking whether the data samples follow a normal distribution.....	144
Figure 46 – Q-Q plot	145
Figure 47 – Histogram	146
Figure 48 – Test statistic and p-value.....	146
Figure 49 – Methods for checking the assumption of homoscedasticity.....	148
Figure 50 – Levene Test	149
Figure 51 – Methods for calculating the correlations.....	150

Figure 52 – Options for parametric and non-parametric statistical tests	151
Figure 53 – Independent t-test.....	152
Figure 54 – Visualization Output of the ARIMA model.....	153
Figure 55 – Autocorrelation	154
Figure 56 – Detection of spindles	155
Figure 57 – Short-Time Fourier Transform	156
Figure 58 – Power Spectral Density using the Welch's method.....	157
Figure 59 - Expert System, Data Analytics and AI in the overall architecture.....	281
Figure 60 Create a workflow.....	284
Figure 61 XML diagram of a BPMN diagram	285
Figure 62 List of workflows.....	285
Figure 63 Edit a workflow	286
Figure 64 Delete a workflow	286
Figure 65 Tasks of the workflow.....	287
Figure 66 Run a workflow.....	288
Figure 67 Step of a workflow.....	288
Figure 68 Step with redirect to external module.....	289
Figure 69 Choose the next step of a workflow.....	289
Figure 70 Prediction.....	290
Figure 71 Build Select SQL query.....	291
Figure 72 Build Select SQL query with filtering	292
Figure 73 Preview the output of an executed Select SQL Query.....	292
Figure 74 Build Group by SQL query from one table.....	293
Figure 75 Build Group by SQL query from one table with filtering.....	293
Figure 76 Build Join SQL query.....	294
Figure 77 Build Join SQL query with filtering.....	294
Figure 78 Build Group by SQL query from multiple tables.....	295
Figure 79 Build Group by SQL query from multiple tables with filtering.....	295
Figure 80 Select file(s) from the Object Storage	295
Figure 81 Query Builder completes the step, and the Workflow Manager receives a message about the completion of the task and the location of the saved data	296
Figure 82 Query builder provides the list of the available sources of iceberg.staging_area.test_data.	296
Figure 83 Perform join query on tables that satisfy the condition PID = 'e7f6c011776e8db7cd330b54174fd76f7d0216b612387a5ffcfb81e6f0919683'	297
Figure 84 Freeview example page	299
Figure 85 EEG Edit Widget.....	302
Figure 86 Opened EEG Edit Widget.....	303
Figure 87 EEGViewer Timescale.....	304
Figure 88 EEGViewer Amplitude scaling.....	304
Figure 89 EEGViewer Scaling Configuration	305
Figure 90 EEGViewer Reference and Bipolar Channels.....	305
Figure 91 EEGViewer Add/Edit Filter Window	306
Figure 92 EEGViewer Annotation Editor and Viewer	306
Figure 93 EEGViewer Power Spectrum Window	307
Figure 94 EEGViewer CDSA Window	307
Figure 95 EEGViewer aEEG Window.....	307
Figure 96 Autocorrelation Page.....	308
Figure 97 Partial auto correlation page	309
Figure 98 Peak Detection page	310
Figure 99 Power spectral density page.....	312
Figure 100 Short Time Fourier Transform Page.....	313
Figure 101 Asymmetry indices Page.....	314
Figure 102 Spindle Detection Page	315
Figure 103 Slowwave Detection Page	317
Figure 104 Prediction Page	318
Figure 105 ICA Artifact Fix Page	319

Figure 106 Back Average page	320
Figure 107 Sleep Statistics Page	321
Figure 108 Spectrogram Bandpower Page.....	322
Figure 109 Automatic Sleep Stage Classification page.....	323
Figure 110 Manual Sleep Stage Classification	324
Figure 111 Envelop Trend page	324
Figure 112 Group Sleep Sensitivity page.....	325
Figure 113 Recon-All function page.....	327
Figure 114 Aseg.Stats Tab.....	329
Figure 115 Aseg Segmentation Volume Plot.....	329
Figure 116 brainvol.stats File	330
Figure 117 *h.aparc.a2009s.stats File	331
Figure 118 *h.w-g.pct.stats File	331
Figure 119 wmparc.stats File	332
Figure 120 Coreg function page.....	333
Figure 121 Samseg function page	333
Figure 122 Samseg Results page	334
Figure 123 MRIViewer example page	334
Figure 124 - Dataframe displaying initial actigraphy dataset.....	335
Figure 125 - Initial visualization results with marked sleep period.....	336
Figure 126 - Graphic representation of activity and assessment algorithm applied to the dataset	336
Figure 127 - Dataframe displaying the data after the user has altered the activity status.....	337
Figure 128 - Final visualization results after the user has altered the activity status.....	337
Figure 129 - Functional Linear Modelling applied to a single dataset.....	338
Figure 130 - Scree diagram of the Singular Spectrum Analysis.....	339
Figure 131 - W-Correlation matrix	339
Figure 132 - Graph showing the diagonal averaging	339
Figure 133 - Comparison between the original signal and its reconstruction.....	340
Figure 134 - Data profile of the Detrended Fluctuation Analysis	340
Figure 135 - Signal segmentation	341
Figure 136 - Graph displaying signal segmentation with various q-orders.....	341
Figure 137 - Cosinor analysis.....	342
Figure 138 - Actigraphy Metrics results	343
Figure 139 - Visualization of inactivity masking in the dataset (check for continuous inactivity for 20 minutes).....	344
Figure 140 - User adding a masking period for 19th of July 2022 from 9:30 to 17:30.....	344
Figure 141 - Average.....	346
Figure 142 - Min.....	346
Figure 143 - Max.....	346
Figure 144 - Standard deviation.....	347
Figure 145 - Z-score.....	347
Figure 146 Common interface for methods “Shapiro-Wilk”, “Kolmogorov-Smirnov”, “D’Agostino’s K^2 ” and “Jarque-Bera”	348
Figure 147 Result interface example using Shapiro-Wilk method.....	349
Figure 148 - Result interface example using Anderson-Darling method.....	350
Figure 149 - Result interface example using Log method.....	352
Figure 150 - Result interface example using O’Brien Transform.....	353
Figure 151 - Result interface example using Fligner-Killeen method.....	354
Figure 152 - Independent t-test.....	355
Figure 153 - Welch t-test.....	355
Figure 154 - RELATED samples t-test	356
Figure 155 - Mann-Whitney U rank test	357
Figure 156 - Wilcoxon signed-rank test.....	358
Figure 157 - one-way ANOVA test.....	358
Figure 158 - Kruskal-Wallis H-test.....	359
Figure 159 - Alexander Govern test.....	359

Figure 160 - Wilcoxon rank-sum test	360
Figure 161 - One-way chi-square test	360
Figure 162 - Anova Repeated Measures	361
Figure 163 - Mixed Anova	362
Figure 164 - Pairwise Tests.....	364
Figure 165 - Welch Anova.....	365
Figure 166 - Ancova	366
Figure 167 - Multiple Testing and P-Value Correction.....	367
Figure 168 - Pearson Correlation test.....	368
Figure 169 - Spearman Correlation test	369
Figure 170 - Biweight midcorrelation	369
Figure 171 - Percentage bend correlation	370
Figure 172 - Shephrd's PI correlation	371
Figure 173 - Skipped Spearman correlation	371
Figure 174 - Kendall's tau Correlation test.....	372
Figure 175 - Point Biserial Correlation	373
Figure 176 - Canonical Correlation	374
Figure 177 - Mediation Analysis	375
Figure 178 - Structural equation Model Creation.....	376
Figure 179 - Structural equation models Optimization.....	377
Figure 180 - Exploratory factor analysis extract latent structure	378
Figure 181 - K-means clustering	379
Figure 182 - Linear Discriminant Analysis	380
Figure 183 - Principal Component Analysis	381
Figure 184 - Factor Analysis	382
Figure 185 - Linear Regression analytics.....	383
Figure 186- Lasso Regression	384
Figure 187 - Elastic Regression.....	385
Figure 188 - Generalized Estimating Equations	386
Figure 189 - Ridge Regression Parameterisation	387
Figure 190 - SGD Regression Parameterisation	389
Figure 191 - SGD Regression Parameterisation	390
Figure 192 - LinearSVR Regression	392
Figure 193 - LinearSVC	393
Figure 194 - Logistic Regression	394
Figure 195 - Cox Regression.....	395
Figure 196 - Mixed Linear Effects Model Regression	396
Figure 197 - Granger Analysis	397
Figure 198 - Poisson Regression.....	398
Figure 199 - Risk ratio (L: using the dataset, R: using only the frequencies).....	399
Figure 200 - Risk Difference (L: using the dataset, R: using only the frequencies).....	400
Figure 201 - Number needed to treat(L: using the dataset, R: using only the frequencies).....	401
Figure 202 - Odds Ratio(L: using the dataset, R: using only the frequencies)	402
Figure 203 - Incidence Risk Ratio(L: using the dataset, R: using only the frequencies).....	402
Figure 204 - Incidence Rate Difference(L: using the dataset, R: using only the frequencies).....	403
Figure 205 - Kaplan & Meier test.....	404
Figure 206 - Fisher exact test.....	405
Figure 207 - Mc Nemar test	406
Figure 208 - AI Initialisation Page	407
Figure 209 - Landing page.....	418
Figure 210 - Main dashboard	418
Figure 211 - Dataset page	419
Figure 212 - Analysis page.....	420
Figure 213 - Clinical processes page	420
Figure 214 - Lighthouse Nabigation Testing results overview.....	431
Figure 215 - Lighthouse NavigationTesting results Performance	431

Figure 216 - Lighthouse NavigationTesting results Accessibility	432
Figure 217 - Lighthouse Navigation results Best Practices.....	432
Figure 218 - Lighthouse Navigation results SEO	433
Figure 219 - Lighthouse Timespan results	433
Figure 220 - Lighthouse Timespan results Performance.....	433
Figure 221 - Lighthouse Timespan results Best Practices	434
Figure 222 - Lighthouse Snapshot results.....	434

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 – General problems of process management[22]	29
Table 2 – Complexity areas of clinical processes.....	30
Table 3 – Key aspects of AI	40
Table 4 – BPMN and Workflow tools.....	54
Table 5 – Data Analytics and Visualisation Tools.....	79
Table 6 – Artificial Intelligence Tools.....	91
Table 7- Expert System requirements	92
Table 8 - Query Builder Requirement	98
Table 9 - Data Analytics Requirements	98
Table 10 - Data and Results Visualisation requirements	103
Table 11 - Artificial Intelligence requirements.....	106
Table 13 – Statistical Methods & Data Processing for Electrophysiology Data	447
Table 14 – Statistical Methods & Data Processing for MRI	449
Table 15 – Statistical Methods & Data Processing for General Analysis	453

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
Tx.y	Task number y belonging to WP x
GA	General Assembly
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
MES-CoBraD	Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
API	Application Programming Interface
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
CPU	Central Processing Unit
TPU	Tensor Processing Unit
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
CSF	Critical Success Factors
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
TAI	Trustworthy AI
XAI	Explainable AI
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ES	Expert System
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
RCT	Randomised Control Trial

Executive Summary

Expert Systems (ES) can provide an alternative methodology in analysing data to identify variables with the highest correlation to the outcome using the most appropriate data analysis and algorithms. By applying their effective machine learning (ML) abilities, significant research time and costs can be saved. The study aims to systematically review the applications of ES in neurological research and their methodological models for effective multi-variate analysis. Their domains, development and validity will be identified on WP6.

The scope of the ES is to:

- › Implement general problem-solving AI techniques and explicitly modelled hypotheticodeductive behaviour.
- › Maintain and update a central knowledge base, filtered by a fact checking database and an inference engine.
- › Handle the knowledge base acquired from WP4 and WP8, but also from the scientific community through regular integrations.
- › Provide symbolic rather than numeric representations of pertinent knowledge from domain of application.
- › Provide categoric schemes for dealing with domain uncertainty.

The ES is tested for accuracy, feasibility, and acceptability in real-world practice. Artificial Intelligence (AI) knowledge-based system for data analysis and interpretation includes an algorithm and software to emulate human cognitive functions in the analysis, interpretation, and comprehension of heterogenous data. Data analytics according to the definitions of previous WPs and especially WP4 include visualisation, query definition and multi-purpose analytics. Interactive and intuitive visualisations (dashboards) assist clinicians to develop actionable insights about patients' health condition and take the necessary corrective actions. The objective of the development of AI modules is:

- › To be updatable based on acquired RWD.
- › Improve data processing.
- › Advance development of knowledge databases.
- › Mimic human cognitive decision processes.
- › Rely on supervised and unsupervised deep learning and machine learning techniques.

The present deliverable provides the basic structure of the algorithm that includes all variables that have been identified and result in the creation of the basic structure that hosts the data analysis. The system can receive a variety of variables analysed through AI algorithm and provide the end users with the appropriate results.

Document Revision Note

This deliverable represents an evolutionary step from its predecessor, D6.2, embodying both continuity and advancement in its content and structure. Significant updates have been meticulously undertaken in Sections 7 (APIs Specification), 8 (Implementation), and 10 (Testing), reflecting the ongoing refinement of our system and the incorporation of feedback and new insights.

This formal statement acknowledges the iterative nature of the deliverable, specifying the sections that have been updated from the previous document version.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The deliverable is structured based on the content and its scope in the following sections:

- › **The Introduction:** defining the purpose, objectives, and relations with other WPs
- › **The Landscape Analysis:** including Evidence-Based Medicine, Hypothesis Testing in Medicine, Process Modelling and Management, Data Analytics and Processing and Artificial Intelligence
- › **State-Of-The-Art Analysis:** Expert System - Process Modelling and Management – Comparative Analysis, Data Analytics and Visualisations – Comparative Analysis, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning – Comparative Analysis
- › **Requirements' Elaboration:** Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence, Integration
- › **Advanced Analytics Architecture:** Overall Architecture, Components
- › **Advanced Analytics Mockups:** User Interface, Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data, and Results Visualisation
- › **APIs' Specification:** Query Builder and MES-CoBraD Data Lake, Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Data Analytics, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence
- › **Implementation:** Overview, Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence, User Interface
- › **Integration:** Integration between components, Integration with the MES-CoBraD Platform
- › **Testing:** Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence, Integration Testing
- › **Conclusions and Next Steps**
- › **References**

Figure 1 – Structure of the deliverable

1.2 RELATION TO OTHER DELIVERABLES/WPs/TASKS

The Expert System (ES) developed and validated, that is also used in WP4, relies on artificial intelligence algorithms that will guide decision making. The ES works as knowledge acquisition, model-based reasoning and system integration that gives decision support on diagnosis, prognosis, and therapy. Decision support will rely on RWD acquired through WP8 that leads to a flexible, hierarchical, and modular decision tree algorithm. This module is designed on a programmer-friendly Application Programming Interface (API) provided by WP7. The interactions of WP6 with other tasks and WPs is provided in the following figure.

Figure 2 – Relation of WP6 with other WPs and Tasks

2 LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

Landscape analysis provides an overview of the clinical decision-making process of evidence-based medicine with reference to the historical background, the methodological process, observation studies and advantages and limitations. Moreover, hypothesis testing is stated, indicating the significance and statistical analysis of the procedure. A state of the art of process modelling and management is reported with reference to healthcare systems, clinicians, and medical research. Data analytics and processing is provided including analysis of structured, inhomogeneous, and multimodal data, feature selection, diagnosis, Classification and visualisation and statistical overview. Updates would be based in acquired and reviewed RWD through the AI platform Artificial Intelligence and its role and benefits in medical systems in analysed with reference to explainable and trustworthy AI.

2.1 EVIDENCE-BASED MEDICINE

2.1.1 DEFINITION OF EVIDENCE-BASED MEDICINE

Evidence-based medicine, in healthcare, refers to the clinical decision-making process, which incorporates the latest and most accurate scientific evidence with the clinical experience and the patients' values, in a prudent and sensible manner[1][2]. The first key element of evidence-based medicine is scientific evidence, which should rely on current and precise scientific developments and can appropriately be integrated into the clinical practice. The procedure of finding out this evidence encompasses both the fundamental scientific research and the clinical studies on the effectiveness and safety of diagnostic, prognostic, and treatment methods and protocols. Clinical studies may be randomised clinical trials, observational studies if randomised trials are not accessible, or clinical observations and assessments, in case none of the previous studies can be obtained. Clinical experience, which is the next essential component, represents clinicians' knowledge, skills, and efficiency in medical problem solving, acquired during clinical practice. The last evidence-based medicine's critical element highlights the procedure of harmonising the patients' values, beliefs, desires, priorities, fears, concerns, and socioeconomic situation with the healthcare process. There is a continuous interaction of the above-described elements in evidence-based medicine[1].

Evidence-based medicine can be described as a method of identifying, evaluating, and applying accurate research outcomes in clinical procedure. To reach the point of application of scientific evidence, a long, systematic, and critical study of research advancements should precede. The core decision that evidence-based medicine must obtain is whether there is adequate evidence that specific diagnostic, prognostic, and treatment methods may be beneficial or not. Its main purpose is to support clinical decision-making operations by enhancing the use of significant, unbiased medical research developments. It is a patient-oriented process, which relies on the outlook that patients' care necessitates a systematic and lifelong education on clinical advancements[1][3].

Since evidence-based medicine is established on the integration of all these three elements: scientific evidence, clinical expertise, and patients' aspirations, none of them is treated as a priority. External scientific evidence works in a supportive way and feeds clinical practice with knowledge but can never substitute her. Clinical experience is also responsible for answering the critical question of whether specific evidence is indeed applicable to the treatment of the individual patient, but also to indicate the most appropriate way in which it will be put into practice and integrated into the clinical decision[3]. Similarly, patients' values should be considered in the way patients are diagnosed and treated, but they should not obstruct the clinical process's proper functioning [2].

Conventionally, health professionals' decisions regarding the diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis of patients are based solely on clinical knowledge and experience. The goal of evidence-based medicine is to transform the way these clinical procedures are performed. In fact, evidence-based medicine requires that clinical practice not only rely on conventional methods, but that it be carried out in the form of the

strongest evidence[1]. Moreover, it attaches great emphasis on the practice of medical science with compassion for patients, brings the patient at the centre of diagnosis and treatment and focuses on cost-effective, patient-centred healthcare[2].

2.1.2 HISTORY OF EVIDENCE-BASED MEDICINE

The journey of evidence-based medicine goes back to the seventeenth century. At that time, when comparing patients receiving bleeding during their cholera treatment with those who were not treated in this way, it was found that the mortality rate increased after treatment with bleeding. Gordon Guyatt of McMaster University pioneered the concept of "Scientific Medicine" in 1990. Guyatt, later, suggested evidence-based medicine as a compulsory subject in resident training programs.

The theory of "Clinical Epidemiology", was next introduced by Feinstein. It was a combination of epidemiological statistical techniques and clinical inference and was proposed as a new direction in clinical education. Feinstein criticised public medical studies for lacking academic rigor in terms of specified hypotheses, bias, inadequate data, and unsound inference of cause. Sackett et al. presented "Critical Appraisal" as a new approach of reading medical literature in a collection of articles published in the Canadian Medical Association Journal. They requested that the perspectives of not only readers of literature but also users of knowledge should be considered. As a result, they introduced the term "clinical practice guideline". According to them, this term could be used by all clinicians to comprehend a specific piece of literature.

Following this, the Cochrane Collaboration was established. The specific name of the institution was given in honour of Archie Cochrane and his efforts to eliminate bias in medical research through randomised controlled trials. The British National Health Service (NHS) subsequently adopted evidence-based medicine as the primary objectives and processes for the development of the medical system [4][5].

2.1.3 ANALYSIS OF THE DIFFERENT STEPS OF EVIDENCE-BASED-MEDICINE

Evidence-based medicine is carried out in five steps. The first step is to formulate the clinical question, while the second is to find the appropriate evidence to answer that clinical question. The third step consists of a thorough critical analysis of the evidence: the accuracy and usefulness of the evidence are evaluated. In the fourth step, the results of the evaluation of the previous step are applied in clinical practice. The fifth step entails assessing the overall performance of the preceding process.

› First step: Formulation of the clinical question

The necessary procedure to be carried out is to transform the clinical question into an answerable question. More specifically, the first step involves the formulation of an answerable clinical question which is based on a patient's case. A clinical question can be considered valid if it is precise, clearly communicated, meaningful, directly focused on the problem, clear in its purpose and need for research, answerable by searching the medical literature, and limits the effort required to obtain the answer.

The use of the PICO-SD standard is highly recommended when formulating a clinical question. The initials of this abbreviation represent the following: Patients or Population (e.g., patients undergoing sedation therapy), Intervention or Exposure (e.g., combination therapy with propofol and another sedative), Comparison or Control (e.g., propofol monotherapy), Outcomes (e.g., Risk of adverse effect), Study design (e.g., randomised controlled trial).

› Second step: Finding the right evidence

Having already formulated the clinical question, the next step is to look for evidence that will allow an answer this specific question, identifying resources, including scientific publications such as books, reports, and journals, individual experience, and peer perspectives. It also involves generating appropriate keywords, selecting a literature survey database (e.g., MEDLINE, EMBASE, CINAHL) and finally conducting the research.

› Third step: Critical appraisal of the evidence

Following the acquisition of the best evidence, the next step is to evaluate the evidence in terms of accuracy, importance, and clinical applicability to the patients of interest. Risk of bias reflects the quality of the research. The most common type of bias is known as selection bias. The presence of selection bias proves that proper randomisation was not done, and the sample of the study is not representative. A biased study may reach an invalid conclusion, overestimate, or underestimate the outcome.

› Fourth step: Application of the results of the previous step's evaluation in clinical practice

After conducting a survey and evaluating the evidence, the results are reviewed, and a decision is made about whether this evidence can be applied in clinical practice. This decision should consider the patient's values, desires, and priorities. The cost and availability of the specific treatment in each health facility must also be considered. The clinician should ensure that the patient makes an informed decision and is aware of both the effectiveness and risks of the evidence.

› Fifth step: Assessment of the overall evidence-based medicine procedure

As a particular evidence-based approach is integrated into regular clinical practice, a feedback mechanism should be developed to regularly evaluate this approach and suggest possible improvements [4][5].

2.1.4 RANDOMISED CONTROL TRIALS AND OBSERVATIONAL STUDIES

Clinical research questions in evidence-based medicine can be answered by evidence based on a variety of study designs. The most significant of these studies is the randomised control trial (RCT), in which participants are randomly assigned to either an experimental or a control group. The expected difference between these two groups is the outcome under investigation. RCTs sometimes are not indicated or ethically correct to address a clinical research question. At the next levels of the hierarchy, observational studies, which are also a significant type of research design, are placed. This kind of study is presented as the next more appropriate method for answering clinical questions.

Both randomised control trials and observational studies are grouped under the umbrella of analytic studies. The difference between these two studies is the presence or absence of an intervention. In observational studies, an observation and assessment of the significance of the association between an exposure and a disease variable is conducted, and no intervention takes place. The three types of observational studies are cohort studies, cross-sectional studies, and case-control studies. Case-control and cohort studies measure the disease occurrence and its association with an exposure (intervention/treatment or naturally occurring exposure) and focus on the time factor (i.e., prospective, or retrospective study design). Cross-sectional studies, on the other hand, focus on the study of the disease and its association with an exposure at a specific time point. At the lowest levels of evidence, we find non-analytical studies such as case reports, which are reports on diagnosis and treatment of a patient, and case series, which is a collection of case reports of patients given similar treatment.

A RCT is more appropriate when evaluating an intended effect, an outcome, of an intervention. For example, an intervention may be the prescription of a drug and the intended effect to be evaluated may be the prevention of mortality from that drug. On the other hand, in observational studies examine the effects of exposure: there are no intended or unintended effects, only outcomes [4][5].

2.1.5 ADVANTAGES AND LIMITATIONS

Implementing evidence-based medicine helps establish national standards for patient care at the lowest possible cost and develop specific criteria for measuring and rewarding performance-based clinical practice. Evidence-based medicine has also helped to reform medical ethics and ensure that the best

evidence is used in practice. Implementation of evidence-based medicine also promotes treatment consistency and optimal clinical outcomes. A significant contribution of evidence-based medicine is the Cochrane Collaboration, which produces more than four hundred systematic reviews of clinical trials of a variety of medical treatments each year.

The limitations of medicine include the possibility of insufficient evidence and the possible existence of obstacles to the application of that evidence in the treatment of an individual patient. Limitations may also include the lack of skills and time of clinicians, as well as the lack of resources in the clinical settings for adequate research and evaluation [4][5].

2.2 HYPOTHESIS TESTING IN MEDICINE

2.2.1 DEFINITION OF HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Healthcare providers rely on evidence-based medicine to support clinical decision-making procedures. Researchers conducting studies require research questions and hypotheses to guide their analyses. They often identify a gap in the existing clinical practice or research by starting with broad research questions. Research questions do not imply presumptions or projections. Instead, research hypotheses should be formulated. A hypothesis is a predefined declaration about a research question in which the researcher makes a precise, educated guess about the study's outcome. Subsequently, an explicit clinical question is formulated, and the appropriate research hypothesis is tested. The results are provided usually with p values, confidence intervals, or even both. Furthermore, the researchers estimate or determine the level of statistical or research significance [6].

In hypothesis testing, there are two statistical hypotheses, which should be defined explicitly and a priori. One of these two statistical hypotheses is called the null hypothesis (represented by the symbol H_0) and it is the one to be tested. The scientist conducting testing of a hypothesis will either end up rejecting the null hypothesis or failing to reject it. The null hypothesis is defined with the sole purpose of rejecting it. The other statistical hypothesis is named the alternative hypothesis, or the research hypothesis (often represented by the symbol H_A). The alternative hypothesis is the one that is sought to be proven. The testing of a hypothesis requires the finding of convincing evidence intending to accept the alternative hypothesis. In other words, hypothesis testing aims to reject the null hypothesis in favour of the alternative hypothesis [7][8].

For example, a common clinical research question may be whether a particular medication is effective in fighting a particular disease. The null hypothesis, in this example, can state that no statistical difference exists between two groups, the one receiving an already existing drug and the other receiving the new drug its effectiveness is being tested. The research hypothesis can state that the new drug, in comparison to the already existing drug, significantly reduces the disease's symptoms, based on specific statistic values [6].

2.2.2 ERRORS IN HYPOTHESIS TESTING

There are two types of errors that can occur during a hypothesis testing. A type I error (false-positive) occurs when the null hypothesis is rejected, but it is true in the population. A type II error (false-negative) occurs if the researcher fails to reject the null hypothesis, but it is false. It is easy to understand that by increasing the sample size, the range of these errors can be reduced, while they can never be avoided entirely [9].

2.2.3 P-VALUES

P-values and level of significance are two important tools needed during the decision-making process of rejecting or not the null hypothesis.

P-value is the probability of obtaining an effect at least as extreme (equal or rarer) as the one in the

sample data set, assuming that the null hypothesis is true. In a case that in a recent study the sample mean is quite different from the mean in the previous one, there are two possibilities: either the means are different, or this observation is a result of random sampling. Calculating the p-value, if it is small enough, the difference of means is quite unlikely to exist due to random sampling [10].

2.2.4 SIGNIFICANCE

The significance level, often noted as alpha “ α ”, is the probability of making a type I error. So, it is the probability of rejecting the null hypothesis when it is true in the population. A significance level of 0.05, for example, demonstrates a 5% risk of concluding that a difference was found (rejecting the null hypothesis), with regards to a statistical value, when there is no actual difference in the population. The significance level indicates the critical region in a statistical test. The critical region defines how far the sample statistic should deviate from the null hypothesis value, to reach the conclusion that it is unusual enough and therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. It is important that the significance level is chosen before the beginning of a study. It provides protection to the researcher against choosing a significance level because it conveniently delivers significant results. Statistical significance is the probability that the correlation or difference that is identified in a sample data set did occur by complete coincidence, and it does not exist in the general population. When a p-value is less than or equal to the significance level, the null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. If the p-value does not fall within the critical region, then the researcher fails to reject the null hypothesis. Data with a $p < 0.05$ or $p < 0.01$ level of significance is considered statistically significant [11].

It is very important that healthcare providers should consider, also, the clinical significance of statistical research findings. When evaluating biomedical research, clinicians must distinguish statistical from clinical significance. For example, a study with large sample size and statistically significant correlation findings may be meaningless and irrelevant to healthcare professionals. The evaluation of the practical significance of studies through a clinical judgment is of great value. Clinicians who perform evidence-based medicine to guide practice should carefully evaluate the design, the sample size, the probabilities of type I and type II errors, the process of data analysis, the statistical findings and finally evaluate the result using practical clinical evidence [12].

2.2.5 STATISTICAL HYPOTHESIS TESTS

Parametric statistical hypothesis tests are based on certain assumptions regarding the distribution of the population from which the sample was derived. All hypothesis parametric tests for means of continuous outcomes, are performed given the assumption that the outcome follows approximately a normal distribution in the population (i.e., most scores are around the mean, while fewer are at either extreme). Many parametric tests remain robust and maintain their statistical power, even though the normality assumption is violated, when the size of the sample is adequately large. On the other hand, non-parametric statistical tests rely on fewer assumptions and can be applied to population data that does not follow a normal distribution. In medical research, the use of non-parametric methods is recommended since normally distributed data is an exception rather than the rule. However, the fact that they are based on fewer hypotheses makes them lose some of their statistical power resulting in a lower probability of rejecting the null hypothesis when the alternative is correct [13][14][15].

2.2.5.1 Parametric hypothesis tests

2.2.5.1.1 T-test

Student’s t-test is a parametric statistical hypothesis test that is mainly used to examine if the two means of two samples are reliably different from each other. Student’s t-test compares the expectations of two populations and presupposes independent sampling from normal distributions with equal variation. The test statistic follows a student’s t-test distribution under the null hypothesis, with $n_1 + n_2 - 2$ degrees of

freedom: $T = \frac{m1-m2}{s \sqrt{\frac{1}{n1} + \frac{1}{n2}}}$, where m1 and m2 denote the observed sample means, n1 and n2 denote the

sample sizes of the two groups, s denotes an estimate of the common standard deviation.

There are three main types of t-tests: the one-sample t-test, the independent-samples t-test (also referred to as unpaired or two-sample t-test), and the paired-samples t-test.

- › One sample: The one-sample t-test examines if the mean of a population has a value specified in a null hypothesis.
- › Two-sample: The two-sample t-test examines if the means of two different groups are reliably different.
- › Paired samples: In paired samples t-tests, a sample of matched pairs of similar units or one group of units that has been tested twice is used. A common application of the repeated measures t-test is when participants are examined prior to receiving therapy, such as for high blood pressure, and then again after receiving treatment with a blood pressure-lowering medicine. The same patient's numbers are compared before and after therapy.

2.2.5.1.2 ANOVA

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is one of the most used statistical tools in medical research and can be described as an extension to t-test. ANOVA is a non-parametric statistical method for comparing the means of two or more samples. In this method, the variance is used to infer the means, rather than the analysis of means.

The method is based on the comparison of variances between groups and within each group. The test statistic is denoted by F and is the ratio of the between and within group variances. The F-value will be high if the variance between the groups is greater than the variance inside the group. The null hypothesis of the test claims that the groups' means are equal. A high F value provides evidence for the rejection of the null hypothesis [16].

2.2.5.2 Non-parametric hypothesis tests

2.2.5.2.1 Chi-squared test

Chi-squared test is a non-parametric statistical hypothesis test that is basically used to examine if two categorical variables are independent. It is, also, used, to test how closely a sample variable fits the distribution of a known population (goodness of fit test) or to examine whether the distributions of two or more independent samples differ on a specific variable (test of homogeneity). Therefore, it is used in hypothesis testing regarding one or two categorical variables. The null hypothesis of this test defines that the observed values match the expected values used for hypothesis testing regarding one or two categorical variables. All three tests in Karl Pearson family of chi-square tests (independence, goodness of fit, homogeneity) use the same formula. The most significant distinction between the three tests is in the different scenarios in which they should be applied. Following the rejection of the null hypothesis, each of these statistical tests has its own set of hypotheses and possibilities. The test statistic has a chi-squared distribution, and it is calculated using the formula below:

$$x^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

where n denotes the table's number of cells. The derived test statistic is compared to a critical value from the chi-square distribution with $(r - 1)(c - 1)$ degrees of freedom. The level of significance is, also determined at the beginning of the test. O_i denotes the observed values, while E_i denotes the expected values [17].

The chi-square test of independence is used to evaluate if two categorical variables in a sample are independent or related. An example could be a survey with each person responding with their marital status (e.g. never married, married, divorced, widowed) and qualification (e.g., middle school, high school, bachelor's, master's, PhD). The test could be used to examine if the marital status and the qualification level are independent. According to the null hypothesis, the one variable is not associated with the second variable, while according to the alternative hypothesis the variables of interest (marital status and qualification) are related. A chi-squared test with high significance that rejects the null hypothesis implies that the marital status is associated with the qualification level, and therefore there is not independence between the two variables [17].

2.2.5.2.2 Mann-Whitney U Test

The Mann-Whitney U Test (also named Wilcoxon rank-sum test) is a non-parametric alternative method to the unpaired (two-sample) Student's t-test, and it is used for the comparison of a continuous outcome in two independent samples. More explicitly, this method is performed to determine whether two samples belong out of the same population. The test statistic is denoted by U and is calculated using the following formula:

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m S(X_i, Y_j), \text{ with } S(X, Y) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } X > Y \\ \frac{1}{2}, & \text{if } Y = X \\ 0, & \text{if } X < Y \end{cases}$$

The null hypothesis claims that the two populations are equal, while the research hypothesis states that the two populations are different. The null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternative if the observed test statistic U is less than or equal to the critical value [13][14][15][18].

2.2.5.2.3 Wilcoxon signed-rank test

Wilcoxon signed-rank test is a non-parametric statistical hypothesis method, which is considered as an alternative test to the paired samples t-test, on a set of paired samples. Unlike the student's t-test it is not based on the assumption that the differences between matched samples follow a normal distribution. This non-parametric test is used to compare two paired samples of a continuous outcome.

The difference scores (concerning the two different situations) are calculated, ranked, and signed. The null hypothesis states that the mean difference is zero, while the research hypothesis could claim that there is a positive median difference. The sums of positive and negative ranks are calculated, and the test statistic (denoted as W) is defined as the smaller value of these two sums. The null hypothesis gets rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis, when there are more higher and positive ranks, and therefore the sum of positive ranks is substantially larger than the sum of negative ranks [13][14][15].

2.2.5.2.4 Kruskal Wallis test

The Kruskal-Wallis method, first introduced in 1952 by Kruskal and Wallis, is a non-parametric test for comparing median value among more than two groups. Here, The Mann-Whitney U test is expanded to include k>2 comparison groups. This method is, also, commonly referred to as an ANOVA with ranks instead of data. Unlike the ANOVA, the Kruskal-Wallis method does not assume that the underlying data are normally distributed.

The null hypothesis states that the means of k groups are equal, while the alternative hypothesis states that not all the medians are the same. According to the test technique, first all the groups' observations are combined into a single pool, keeping track of to which sample each observation belongs. Then, the observations are ranked lowest to highest. The test statistic is denoted by H and is calculated as follows:

$$H = \left(\frac{12}{N(N+1)} \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{R_j^2}{n_j} \right) - 3(N+1), \text{ where } k=\text{number of comparison groups, } N=\text{total sample size,}$$

n_j =sample size in the j^{th} group, and R_j is the sum of ranks in the j^{th} group. By establishing a critical value for the test statistic, obtained from a table of critical values for the Kruskal Wallis test or a software - for a specific predefined alpha level, the null hypothesis can be rejected in favour of the research hypothesis, if the observed test statistic exceeds this critical value [13][14][15].

2.3 PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

2.3.1 IN HEALTHCARE

Healthcare across Europe and globally faces a tremendous pressure. While the quantity and quality of healthcare has improved significantly, the scale and complexity of healthcare requirements have increased. Most countries have been oriented towards a digital transformation to close the gap between the supply of resources and the demand for healthcare. This will result to the increase of efficiency and effectiveness of service delivery benefiting both patients and clinicians.

Over the past decade numerous EU policies, directives, regulations, and funding programs have emerged to support the digitalisation of healthcare systems. Specifically, in April 2018, the European Commission published a definitive communication that included a comprehensive overview of previous actions taken to promote the digitalisation of health and several commitments to put forward digital transformation. A survey of 1.800 clinicians and interviews with over 40 stakeholders across seven countries (Denmark, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, and the UK demonstrated that the top three challenges faced by clinicians were bureaucracy in healthcare (57%), the cost of technologies (50%) and finding the right technologies (49%).[19] Figure 3 summarises the benefits of digital transformation. Digital transformation of healthcare involves multiple stakeholders from different disciplines. Fig. shows the benefits of digital transformation while Figure 4 presents the stakeholders involved in the digital transformation of healthcare.

Figure 3 – The benefits of digital transformation (Source: Deloitte research and analysis 2020)

Figure 4 – Stakeholders involved in the digital transformation of healthcare (Source: Deloitte research and analysis 2020)

Given the continuous challenges that healthcare faces in the past years, many interventions have focused on process improvements with the objective of enhancing efficiency and efficacy to improve patient outcomes while controlling costs. At the same time the quality of care and patient safety remain the major concern. In this context, several tools have been developed to support process improvement through process mapping.

Among the various application domains suitable to be addressed by a Business Process Management (BPM) approach, the healthcare domain is probably the most challenging. The emphasis of performance management in health care is shifting from an output-based to a system-based approach. Systems that follow a BPM approach improve their interoperability between other systems and applications, that is, the ability of one system to interact and communicate with another, due to the more uniform process management.

Healthcare faces difficulties and problems in process management. These management problems can be categorised in three main categories: strategic, tactical, and operational. From a BPM perspective, problems at a strategic level, which are at the highest level of importance in the categorisation, are related to process-oriented management, support and IT, organisation of processes and administration problems. The tactical level of problems addresses the difficulties in process modelling, measurement of process and methodological performance. Finally, at the operational level, the problems are related to difficulties in the technologies that support process management. Table 1 presents the general problems that fall within the categories mentioned above [20], [21]

Table 1 – General problems of process management[22]

Strategic Level	Tactical level	Operational Level
Lack of governance	Lack of standards and norms	Lack of support tools for process visualization
Lack of training for employees	Process specification weaknesses	Gaps between process design and process execution
Lack of knowledge sharing	Lack of methodologies	Lack of communication and tool handling capabilities
Connection failure between measures and organisational strategy		

Process-driven healthcare organisations can better take advantage of data, respond to developments in the industry, reduce errors, improve the bottom line, and provide a higher level of patient care. Process based change needs to begin with a shared understanding of the landscape and that in turn requires a common vocabulary when it comes to processes. Healthcare organisations can progress to modelling, analysing, redesigning, and automating critical business processes with BPM. BPM can also be instrumental in assuring compliance. it’s essential to ensure that operational processes remain in compliance with regulations and health-care professionals follow currently mandated procedures. BPM is now recognised as a major trend in technology and many healthcare organisations are looking to use BPM to improve the efficiency of operations[23]

The potential benefits of applying BPM in the healthcare environment include the following:

- › Automate non-value-added tasks and eliminate non-value-added ones
- › Monitor and improve care delivery as it occurs
- › Visualize functions and processes, for example by representing them as easy-to-understand flowcharts
- › Identify and avert resource bottlenecks
- › Redesign the processes suffering from inefficiencies and bottlenecks.
- › Analyse and measure the outcome of processes according to specific key performance indicators (KPIs) after executing and monitoring them.
- › Fine-tune these processes based on data gathered in the previous phases.
- › Automate the identification of critical conditions using analytics
- › Manage task assignments, statuses, roles, and history with intuitive dashboards
- › Monitor cost, quality, and compliance metrics

The biggest healthcare organisations have grown and complexity, integrating bigger care facilities that have been established to improve health quality and patient satisfaction in terms of accessibility, cost-effectiveness, and participation. Subsequently, medical treatments have become primarily multidisciplinary, including also social and daily life aspects. As a result, all the processes used to represent healthcare procedures have to consider numerous factors and must be able to harmonise human, physical, and informational resources. These facts suggests that the understanding of healthcare processes and related information, when combined with proper knowledge management, supports clinicians in scheduling and their work, making the right decisions. Indeed, a lot of clinical tasks, such as

clinical diagnosis and drug treatment are knowledge intensive by nature, that is, medical knowledge plays the most important role in driving care providers actions and decisions [24], [25].

A healthcare process, sometimes called a care-flow, is any set of activities performed to provide medical care for one or more patients presenting a specific clinical condition. Healthcare processes integrate medical and organisational tasks, and each one of them is performed by one or more process participants (agents), often covering a medical or administrative role in the organisation entitled of care provision.

2.3.1.1 Business Process Management Examples in Healthcare

As healthcare rapidly evolves, the industry requires tools that can keep up. Here are three examples of vital healthcare processes that can be improved with BPM[26].

2.3.1.2 Claims Processing

Claims processing is a complex task that also encompasses compliance and reporting activities and requires a smooth flow of information. BPM technology can simplify these processes by streamlining each associated activity. Claims and patient appeals can be handled more quickly and monitored at every step, to make it easier to track and prioritise claims.

2.3.1.3 Big Data

Big Data refers to the massive amount of data now available to businesses through the proliferation of the Internet. It is defined in terms of volume, velocity, and variety. Thanks to electronic health records, a rapidly growing amount of healthcare information is now available and shareable. BPM technology allows organisations to manage their data and improve the way it is utilised.

For example, monitoring regional disease trends can help gauge the effectiveness of certain vaccines and predict future needs. BPM offers opportunities to leverage big data to improve healthcare for individuals and the general population, through preventive care and proactive responses.

2.3.1.4 Software Applications

BPM can help fill in the gaps that occur when multiple software applications are used in performing routine healthcare processes. It forges links that capture information not covered by existing applications and provides information more quickly to expedite patient care. BPM also bridges gaps from manual functions, such as face-to-face or email patient interactions, that can raise costs and place an organisation at risk of non-compliance.

The following table (Table 2) provides a summary of the main complexity areas of clinical processes. For each of the sources of complexity, sub-areas are specified that become the requirement for the modelling effort[27][28].

Table 2 – Complexity areas of clinical processes

Clinical process complexity areas	Sub-areas	Modelling requirement to represent the sub-area
Medical knowledge	Evidence based medicine, guidelines, recommendations	R1: Compliance to guidelines R2: Deal with dynamic evolution of medical evidence-based knowledge
	Local practices	R3: Manage flexibility (from meta-model to local context)
	Clinician personal experience, habits and skills	R4: Bind the design to interaction and cooperation between analysts and domain experts

	Learning by practice	R5: Deal with learning curves (process change)
	Building evidence from practice	R6: Foresee process mining with big data analysis
Response to treatment	Timeframe short-term or long-term response	R8: Manage uncertainty
	Compliance – depending on patient’s engagement	R9: Manage indeterminacy
	Expected outcomes	R10: Define outcome variables
	Patient feedback to reshape therapy – depending on patient’s empowerment and education	R11: Integrate patient-reported outcome measures
		R8: Manage uncertainty
Personalization of care	Patient-centric approach – treatment definition considering patients preferences and history	R7: Manage exceptions
	Treatment adaptation considering occurring changes	R3: Manage flexibility

2.3.2 IN MEDICAL RESEARCH

Process management in medical research is fundamental in raising the efficiency of the decision-making process and performed actions, cost optimisation, time reduction, and reduction of used resources.

The initial phase attempts to describe patient treatment from a process-based perspective. This is achieved through the identification of diagnostic and therapeutic processes called clinical pathways, which are, in essence, the standard procedure in each healthcare unit. In effect, when implementing process management in healthcare, the following points should be taken into account:

- › The process should be patient and not disease oriented
- › Different clinical and extra-clinical pathways (management, support, logistics, and others) should comprise a cohesive system.
- › Clinical pathways should be reflected in IT systems, used on an ongoing basis by physicians and other relevant personnel.
- › The management of knowledge used in planning treatments and treating patients. From this perspective, clinical pathways should perform the role of a repository of knowledge and a model against which both current and new knowledge from patient treatment is verified.

The goal of the current research is to use various assumptions and models of situational awareness in combination with models of clinical decision making as a "theoretical lens" to capture and describe the decision-making requirements (i.e., knowledge/expertise, goals, resources, and information, communication/coordination needs) related to the perception, understanding, and projection of a situation leading to a critical decision. The goal is to explore how we can model these requirements as extensions of traditional process modelling languages (e.g., BPMN), possibly in the form of a discrete decision perspective. In MES-CoBraD preliminary research, we identified the following questions:

- › Will the advancement from written procedures and flowcharts to draw the detailed business process address the complexity of interrelations?

- › Will the implementation of dynamic BPM be performed in a way that matches its documentation?
- › Will the use of a discrete decision perspective in process models lead to a better understanding of how we can design information systems to support decision-making tasks in dynamic work environments?

To answer these questions, we need to design and evaluate a set of modelling constructs that allow us to represent aspects of coordination, communication, and decision making in clinical processes. This requires identifying relevant cases from the healthcare work environment and collecting data through participant observation and interviewing individuals in their natural work environment, which can serve as a basis for further research.

Critical success factors (CSFs) contributing to successful development and implementation of the clinical pathway include [29], among others:

- › Analysis of related works to determine the best clinical practice for each medical condition and incorporating it into the clinical pathways.
- › Definition of the care process in each clinical pathway.
- › Creation of the multi-disciplinary teams and granting ownership of each pathway disciplines involved in the care process.
- › Invitation of all medical professions to comment on each pathway before their implementation.
- › Incorporation of clinical pathways into the patients' medical records.
- › Implementation of the regular feedback loop to all health professionals involved in the clinical pathway.

Complexity issues require the development of the following:

- › Standard procedures dividing processes into hierarchical levels: maps, process models, and action.
- › Charts with information, with the adequate level of detail and adequate scope of subject matter.
- › Standard goals and rules of dividing the entire process into sub-processes on specific levels, and a clear presentation of their interrelations.

Notation of description of processes, independent of the country in question, the geographical area, and the IT tool used to model processes (e.g., Business Process Model and Notation—BPMN).

The issues of describing clinical pathways result from the lack of consequence in using methodologies and process tools, when dealing with diagnostic and therapeutic processes. To avoid such issues, descriptions of clinical pathways should be prepared with the use of principles, methodologies, and notations, commonly and successfully adapted in process management [30].

2.4 DATA ANALYTICS AND PROCESSING

Data analysis purpose is usually the extraction of information from data and to provide actionable input to a decision-making process. Usually it requires several steps, like cleaning and transforming the initial dataset before applying statistical methods to them. Visualisation is one of the key cognitive abilities that allows the humans to interpret and understand data. Visualisation tools' focus should be to provide

adequate interpretability and explainability of the data, especially those that have already been through the data analysis process.

Data analysis and visualisation applications in medical fields faces specific industry issues the platform aims to address[31]. Specifically:

- › Analysis of structured, inhomogeneous, and multimodal data
 - The platform should allow the users to create a model with the appropriate level of complexity to allow for robust results. Also choose the appropriate level of interpretability and provide the capability of assessing it in the context of the application domain. It should allow the choice of the correct model to represent specific biomedical data. Additionally, it should provide measure to detect similarity and dissimilarity of structured data.
- › Feature selection

The platform should aid with the identification, selection, and verification of relevant biomarkers in complex data structures. These features will be used for the data analysis and predictions about specific diseases or behaviours. It should also provide methods to infer the non-Euclidian structure of biomedical data in some manner.
- › Diagnosis Classification
 - The platform should allow classification that is robust with respect to noise and missing values. It should aid with improving their sensitivity for diagnostic processes. Additionally, it should allow the modelling of temporal aspect like stages and progression/regression under treatment.
- › Visualisation
 - The platform should aid with select the most appropriate visualisation techniques for heterogenous and structured data. It should allow the clear display of errors and uncertainties, especially those resulting from embedding high-dimensional data into low dimensional spaces.

Finally in the traditional application of data analysis in the medical sector there exists an additional sub cycle in the process, where medical experts seek several things from the data analysts, which the platform should consider. In this cycle of feedback, the data analyst is asked to, guarantee the interpretability and explainability of the models, to comply with clinical protocol and guidelines and comply with system human interaction workflow at the point of care. On the other hand, the medical experts need to, have a realistic understanding of the limitation and possibilities of analytical models, clearly state the medical requirements, clearly describe the medical decision process and verify the results [32].

2.4.1 STATISTICAL METHODS AND DATA ANALYSIS IN MEDICAL RESEARCH

In medical research, various statistical methods are used for the analysis of data as well as for the extraction of patterns and knowledge. In statistics, correlation is a well-known technique that is used to assess a possible two-way linear association or any other relationship between two continuous variables[33]. The correlation coefficient is the numerical measure of the correlation and reflects the linear association of two continuous variables. It is a dimensionless quantity and takes values from -1 to 1. The values ± 1 indicate perfect linear relationship, while 0 indicates no linear relationship[34]. There are two main types of correlation coefficients, Pearson's product moment and Spearman's rank, which are used depending on the types of variables [35].

Regression analysis is another process for accessing the possible relationships between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables [36]. The existence of a dependent variable constitutes the main difference between regression and correlation. In other words, Regression attempts to establish how one variable affects another variable, while Correlation measures the strength of the relationship between two variables. There are three types of regression analysis: Linear Regression, Multiple Linear Regression and Nonlinear Regression[36].

Moreover, in medical research the basic statistical methods and metrics, such as Variance and Standard Deviation, Mean, Method of Least Squares etc. are used for the extraction of information and for the analysis of data [37]. For instance, the standard deviation and the estimated standard error are used to interpret the results of a statistical analysis [38].

Regarding the Neuroimaging data, the clinicians and the researchers perform various transformations before the process and the analysis of the data. This step is a part of the pre-processing of the data, in which a large number of transformations takes place. The most important ones are the following:

- › Spatial Normalisation: Spatial normalisation is a special form of image registration, which is a process of transforming different sets of data into a single unified coordinate system [39], that maps a subject's PET or MRI image to a reference brain space in order to allow comparisons across subjects with varied brain morphologies.
- › Spatial Smoothing: Spatial smoothing is the process in which the data points are averaged with their neighbours acting as a low pass filter. This has as a result the sharp "edges" to be blurred and the spatial correlation within the data to be more distinct [40].
- › Coregistration: Coregistration is a process that implements the alignment of functional and structural images from the same subject to map functional information into anatomical space. It is applied in order to correct any movements of the head during an experimental run.
- › Generalised linear model (GLM): GLM can be thought of as an extension of a more familiar statistical technique, linear regression. Linear regression, sometimes called trend-line analysis, is a method used to calculate the "best fitting" line for a set of experimental data.
- › Slice time correction: Slice time correction is a transformation applied to correct slice-dependent delays, achieved by shifting the time series of each slice to temporally align all slices to a reference time-point [41].

Regarding the analysis of electroencephalograms (EEGs), the clinicians and the researchers are using specific methods for the handling of the signal. Some of these methods are presented below:

- › Time frequency analysis: The time frequency analysis of EEG signals provides the correct visualization of EEG signals to extract the various rhythms of frequencies like alpha, beta, gamma waves. The short-time Fourier transform (STFT) provides some information on both the timing and the frequencies at which a signal event occurs.

The Wavelet Transform (WT) can be thought of as an extension of the classic Fourier transform, except that, instead of working on a single scale (time or frequency), it works on a multi-scale basis. This multi-scale feature of the WT allows the decomposition of a signal into a number of scales, each scale representing a particular coarseness of the signal under study [42].

- › Time series analysis: Time series analysis involves developing models that best capture or describe an observed time series in order to understand the underlying causes. This field of study seeks the "why" behind a time series dataset.

- › Time series forecasting: Several approaches have been introduced for forecasting seizures, including ARMA, ARIMA models, etc.
- › Repairing artifacts: Artifacts are parts of the recorded signal that arise from sources other than the source of interest (i.e., neuronal activity in the brain). As such, artifacts are a form of interference or noise relative to the signal of interest.
- › Down-up sampling: As the name suggests, the process of converting the sampling rate of a digital signal from one rate to another is Sampling Rate Conversion. Increasing the rate of already sampled signal is Upsampling, whereas decreasing the rate is called downsampling.

What is more, the statistical tests constitute a significant part of the Medical Research. These tests are used to determine the strength of a relationship or to evaluate a hypothesis. A number of well-known tests are the following: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test, T-test, Z-test, Chi-square test, McNemar's test. These tests are presented in detail in Section 2.2.5.

Data analytics are used in Medical Research in order to provide insights about the trends as well as to facilitate in decision making. The health data contain information that must be interpreted in the most accurate and efficient way. The clinicians and the researchers cannot reveal the whole information since the data are in complex format and their correlation as well as trends are not easy to be understood. Therefore, the clinicians turn to Data Analytics in order to have accurate and insightful data alongside with the health data of the patients. Data Analytics can be categorised into 4 categories [43]:

- › Descriptive analytics: uses data from the past to extract knowledge about trends and patterns, helping the people to understand better what happened in the past.
- › Predictive analytics: uses forecasting models to predict what is likely to happen in the future.
- › Prescriptive analytics: uses machine learning to propose strategies and actions by analysing the potential impact of these actions.
- › Discovery analytics: uses machine learning to analyse raw data in order to identify patterns and relationships among the data. It helps people understand what is needed to be explored further.

There is a large number of applications of data analytics in healthcare, which attempts to facilitate the work of the clinicians by providing more accurate and correct data and techniques. For instance, some applications of the data analytics in Health aim at evaluating and developing tools and methods, which are used by Practitioners for the detection of anomalies in Scans as well as the Prediction of outbreaks [44]. Moreover, there are various techniques used in Medicine for data mining and extraction of knowledge [45]. In addition, in medical research and trials the survival analysis is used widely. The survival analysis is a branch of statistics for analysing the expected duration of time until one event occurs, such as death in biological organisms. Kaplan Meier analysis measures the survival time between a certain time and a significant event. Therefore, it is clear that the survival analysis is crucial in medical research [46].

2.4.2 DATA VISUALIZATIONS

In neuroscience, the clinicians use widely the visualisation of data in order to have a more complete view of the data, since patterns, trends, outbreaks and outliers are visible. In this subsection, some of these visualisations are presented below:

- › Heatmap: Heatmaps, which are also called intensity maps or point density interpolation, are visual structures for a spatial visualisation of the data. Figure 5 shows a heatmap of a correlation matrix.

Figure 5 – Heatmap of a Correlation Matrix

- › Hypnogram: Hypnogram is a graph that depicts the stages of sleep as a function of time. It was developed as an easy way to present the brain wave activity that has been recorded from EEG during a period of sleep. Figure 6 illustrates a hypnogram [47].

Figure 6 – Hypnogram

- › EEG Topography: EEG Topography is a neuroimaging technique in which the brain activity is presented with several tones of colour depending on the intensity of the brain activity. The input derives from EEG electrodes that have been placed onto the head of the patient. Figure 7 shows an EEG Topography.

Figure 7 – EEG Topography

- › Spectrogram: Spectrogram is a time-frequency image processing technique used for the analysis of EEGs. This technique is used in Short Time Fourier Transform, in which the signal is mapping into two-dimensional function of frequency or time. Figure 8 illustrates a STFT spectrogram.

Figure 8 – STFT spectrogram

2.5 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

2.5.1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a branch of computer science that focuses on developing computers and machines that can perform tasks that usually require human intelligence. Such software systems operate in an intentional, intelligent, and adaptive manner. Artificial intelligence has evolved dramatically in recent years and - although it is often the subject of exaggeration or even catastrophic scenarios - it is enough to focus on real technological advances to realise its exciting potential.

Avoiding technical terminology, an artificial intelligence system could be defined as a computer system that can perform cognitive functions while adapting and 'learning' to become more efficient. Modern artificial intelligence systems can 'understand' their environment in real time and make optimal decisions. 'Understanding the environment' is the efficient processing of multiple signals and data streams. Computer Vision and Natural Language Processing technologies allow computer systems to 'understand' images, videos, and speech and to react in the best possible way. The applications are unlimited and impressive: from autonomous cars that can 'see' and perceive their environment in real time, to special applications such as several AI systems that help people with severe visual impairments to better understand the environment. In this example, the visually impaired user can ask the system for a detailed description of the environment or brief updates of the changes that are taking place - by simply communicating in natural language. Computer Vision technology provides new capabilities in a wide range of applications such as navigation, robotics, medical diagnostics, more efficient management of online content, security systems, etc.

The ability of computers to 'see' is undoubtedly an important achievement. Image resolution algorithms can now identify the entities represented in a random image or video, with great accuracy and speed. For example, they can identify people, cars, houses, roads, trees, etc. in an image. In addition, they can estimate other parameters of the image and the entities it includes - in the example above, the make and

type of cars, the number of people, their gender, age or even their emotional state. The algorithm can also identify the occasion being depicted or implied - for example a children's party, a sporting event, a business meeting, or a gathering of people in a square.

Furthermore, Machine learning (ML) is the science of designing algorithms that learn on their own from data and adapt without human correction.

We can think of machine learning (ML) as the science of getting computers to learn automatically. It's a form of artificial intelligence (AI) that allows computers to act like humans and improve their learning as they encounter more data[48].

According to Encyclopedia Britannica, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is “the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings”.

Arthur Samuel defines AI as the “field of study that gives computers the ability to learn without being explicitly programmed”.

Tom Mitchell defines AI as a well-paced learning problem and gives a more streamlined approach to it. “A computer program is said to learn from Experience (E) with respect to some Task (T) and some Performance measure (P), if its performance on T, as measured by P, improves with experience E”.

From the above, we understand that AI is an algorithmic approach, so that the computer program executes algorithms with different mathematical and statistical methods in an intentional, intelligent, and adaptive manner. Since the founding of AI, various sub-objectives have been developed that focus on specific objectives and can be categorised in types, like:

- > Problem solving
- > Perception
- > Reasoning
- > Natural Language Processing
- > Machine Learning

Given a sequence of events of a running case, the objective of process prediction is to forecast how certain aspects of the case unfold in the future. Originally, the focus was to utilise deep learning for next-step prediction and outcome prediction, i.e., to predict the next activity or the last activity of a case based on a sequence of seen activities. This was motivated by the recent success of deep learning for language modelling in the field of natural language processing and its high similarity with process prediction from a conceptual point of view. Key aspects of AI are presented in Figure 9 and Table 3 show the main differences between AI and machine learning[49].

Figure 9 – Key aspects of AI

Table 3 – Key aspects of AI

Topic	Artificial Intelligence	Machine learning
Key Aspects	Artificial intelligence is a technology which enables a machine to simulate human behaviour.	Machine learning is a subset of AI which allows a machine to automatically learn from past data without programming explicitly.
	In AI, we make intelligent systems to perform any task like a human.	In ML, we teach machines with data to perform a particular task and give an accurate result.
	Machine learning and deep learning are the two main subsets of AI.	Deep learning is a main subset of machine learning.
	Based on capabilities, AI can be divided into three types, which are, Weak AI, General AI, and Strong AI.	Machine learning can also be divided into mainly three types that are Supervised learning, Unsupervised learning, and Reinforcement learning.
	It includes learning, reasoning, and self-correction.	It includes learning and self-correction when introduced with new data.
Goals	The goal of AI is to make a smart computer system like humans to solve complex problems.	The goal of ML is to allow machines to learn from data so that they can give accurate output.

	AI is working to create an intelligent system which can perform various complex tasks.	Machine learning is working to create machines that can perform only those specific tasks for which they are trained.
	AI system is concerned about maximising the chances of success.	Machine learning is mainly concerned about accuracy and patterns.
	AI has a very wide range of scope.	Machine learning has a limited scope.
Scopes	The main applications of AI are Siri, customer support using chatbots, Expert System, Online game playing, intelligent humanoid robot, etc.	The main applications of machine learning are Online recommender system, Google search algorithms, Facebook auto friend tagging suggestions, etc.
	AI completely deals with Structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data.	Machine learning deals with Structured and semi-structured data.

2.5.2 AI IN MEDICINE

Since the concept of “artificial intelligence” was introduced in 1956, it has led to numerous technological innovations in human medicine and completely changed the traditional model of medicine[50].

With the rapid development and advancement of artificial intelligence (AI), its influence on clinical diagnosis and treatment is growing. Machine learning and in particular deep learning, which are key digital technologies of AI, are being widely used to assist diagnosis and treatment[51].

Image recognition is the technology of processing and analysing images through computers. It is an important technology in the field of AI, which is based on deep learning. The development of image recognition technology includes three stages—text recognition, digital image recognition, and object recognition. The recognition process can be divided into five steps, including processing the input, image pre-processing, image extraction, classifier construction, and producing the output. This technology can process image data rapidly and efficiently. Image recognition technology has been highly significant in the diagnosis and treatment of intertrochanteric fractures. In addition, it is also widely used in disease prediction, diagnosis, and lesion identification.

Deep learning is a subset of artificial intelligence that is formally defined as “computational models that are composed of multiple processing layers to learn representations of data with multiple levels of abstraction.” A deep learning algorithm consists of a structure referred to as a deep neural network of which a convolutional neural network (CNN) is one type frequently used in imaging[52].

The key difference between deep learning and other types of machine learning is that CNNs develop their own representations needed for pattern recognition rather than requiring human input to structure the data and design feature extractors. In plain language, the algorithm learns for itself the features of an image that are important for classification. Therefore, the algorithm has the freedom to discover classification features that might not have been apparent to humans (particularly when datasets are large) and thereby improve the performance of image classification.

The expert system exhibits a strong ability of clinical decision-making and shows advantages in terms of identification and diagnosis of diseases. However, it is also necessary to enhance the accuracy of the system, combine the system with the patient's medical history, and simultaneously integrate the doctor's clinical experience. In addition, the knowledge and findings in medicine must be constantly updated to

provide doctors with frontier diagnosis and treatment plans.

2.5.3 TRUSTWORTHY AI

In recent years, the rapid spread of AI systems mainly arising from the needs created, it makes the presence of Trustworthy AI necessary. With the development of Trustworthy AI, we can answer reliability questions of the system, but also to prove that the algorithms run transparently. It was not a few, the times where in the past there were cases that the data collected was used for commercial purposes, violating users' personal data. For this reason, the independent High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligent (AI HLEG) was drafted by the European Union, which established some guidelines to produce Trustworthy AIs [53]–[55].

Trustworthy AI systems consist of three main components, so they should be legal, ethical, and robust. At every point of operation of the system, they must obey the relevant legislation, guarantee compliance with the moral principles and not to cause harm to society by having always good intentions. Finally, they should follow the following five (5) principles: Respect for the autonomy of the individual, the avoidance of harm, justice, and the ability to be explained.

Trustworthy AI (TAI) bases on the idea that trust builds the foundation of societies, economies, and sustainable development, and that individuals, organisations, and societies will therefore only ever be able to realise the full potential of AI, if trust can be established in its development, deployment, and use[56].

Trust in IT artifacts based on system characteristics:

Functionality: The belief that the specific technology has the capability, functionality, or features to do for one what one needs to be done.

Helpfulness: The belief that the specific technology provides adequate and responsive help for users.

Reliability / Predictability: The belief that the specific technology will consistently operate properly, and its behaviour can be forecast.

Main benefits of trustworthy AI are summarised in Figure 10.

Figure 10 – Main benefits of Trustworthy AI

2.5.4 EXPLAINABLE AI

Explainable AI (XAI) is a branch of Artificial Intelligence that aims to deconstruct processes in a system, to fully understand the operation, but also the result of this.

When designing and creating an AI system, many times it becomes difficult to interpret the algorithms, but also to explain how they came up with any result. In the literature these systems are called "black boxes". They are systems that on the one hand give great accuracy to the correctness of the results, but they are so complex that they prevent its full understanding on the other hand, the "white box" systems are simpler and quite straight forward without great complexity but lack flexibility and predictive capacity.

Using explainable AI models, we can use the positive elements from the black-box and white-box systems and manufacture models that have great accuracy and high accuracy, but at the same time they are understood by the final users, who can trust the result and evaluate it. This is very important in the field of medicine, since clinicians can with the representation of models accelerate the diagnosis, analyse more easily all the images, and make decisions with transparency and traceability.

To date, XAI is used in neuroscience and behavioural neurostimulation applications, genomics, breast cancer and public health intervention evaluation. In neuroscience, XAI interferes with Deep Learning Models, such as Deep Neural Networks (DNN), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), which contribute to image recognition, image classification and movement recognition. Diseases such as epilepsy have already benefited from XAI solutions, but diseases involving neurophysiological and behavioural data need room for improvement[57]–[66].

Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) is a set of processes and methods that allows human users to comprehend and trust the results and output created by machine learning algorithms. Explainable AI is used to describe an AI model, its expected impact, and potential biases. It helps characterise model accuracy, fairness, transparency, and outcomes in AI-powered decision making. Explainable AI is crucial for an organisation in building trust and confidence when putting AI models into production. AI explainability also helps an organisation adopt a responsible approach to AI development.

ML models are often thought of as black boxes that are impossible to interpret. Neural networks used in deep learning are some of the hardest for a human to understand. Bias, often based on race, gender, age or location, has been a long-standing risk in training AI models. Further, AI model performance can drift or degrade because production data differs from training data. This makes it crucial for a business to continuously monitor and manage models to promote AI explainability while measuring the business impact of using such algorithms. Explainable AI also helps promote end user trust, model auditability and productive use of AI. It also mitigates compliance, legal, security and reputational risks of production AI.

Explainable AI is one of the key requirements for implementing responsible AI, a methodology for the large-scale implementation of AI methods in real organisations with fairness, model explainability and accountability. To help adopt AI responsibly, organisations need to embed ethical principles into AI applications and processes by building AI systems based on trust and transparency[67].

- › Building trustworthiness: Humans are better able to trust the AI model when the characteristics and rationale of the AI output have been explained.
- › Satisfying legal requirements: Financial and healthcare industries may be required to incorporate machine learning models into their complex risk assessment strategies to fulfil regulatory requirements for effective risk management.
- › Providing ethics-related justification (and removing unconscious biases): Because XAI is transparent and able to more easily be debugged, unconscious biases can be removed, and ethical decisions explained.
- › Deriving actionable and robust insights: AI and Machine Learning (ML), provide the ability to derive actionable and robust insights, however, XAI enables humans to understand how and why the XAI algorithm was able to determine the “next best action.”

This is because the majority of AI with ML operates in what is referred to as a “black box,” that is, in an area that is unable to provide any discernible insights as to how it comes to make decisions. Many AI/ML applications are moderately benign decision engines that are used with online retail recommender systems, so it is not necessary to ensure transparency or explainability. For other, more risky decision processes, such as medical diagnoses in healthcare, investment decisions in the financial industry, and safety-critical systems in autonomous automobiles, the stakes are much higher. As such, the AI used in those systems should be explainable, transparent, and understandable to be trusted, reliable, and consistent.

Figure 11 Summarises the benefits of Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) and Figure 12 shows the advancement of (XAI).

Figure 11 – Benefits of Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI)

Figure 12 – Advancement of Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) Source: DARPA[60]

3 STATE-OF-THE-ART ANALYSIS

In this chapter a state of the art of expert systems is provided, identifying, analysing, and comparing their characteristics. Comparative analysis of process modelling management tools including data analytics and visualizations is also provided giving an overview of weaknesses and strengths. For each tool the features, compatibility, activity, open-Source information, analytics, and visualisations are summarised. A comparative analysis of Artificial Intelligence and machine learning is also provided.

3.1 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT – COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

3.1.1 OVERVIEW

All the tools that will be used in our final product, do not differ from a practical process, however they offer added speed and convenience for users, thus speeding up decision-making. The purpose of Machine learning is to allow a system to interpret information from the past or present and use that information to make predictions or decisions about known and unknown future class labels. The term “learning” refers to the process of extracting useful patterns from unstructured data. The three types of algorithms used in machine learning are supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning. In supervised learning patterns are inferred from the labelled input file, which aids in the prediction of outcomes from unexpected results. These tools depict the supervised machine learning workflow. Building, evaluating, and tuning the model, and then deploying it getting back predictions are all part of the supervised machine learning workflow. On the other hand, unsupervised learning uses machine learning algorithms to analyse and cluster unlabelled data sets. These algorithms discover hidden patterns in data without the need for human intervention. Unsupervised learning models are used for three main directions: clustering, association, and dimensionality reduction. In conclusion, in Supervised Learning, the goal is to generate formula based on input and output values. In Unsupervised Learning, we find an association between input values and group them. In Reinforcement Learning an agent learn through delayed feedback by interacting with the environment.

3.1.2 PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT TOOLS

In this section, we give a detailed perspective of the tools used for the process modelling stage, plus the tools for managing the whole expert system.

SpiffWorkflow: SpiffWorkflow is a BPMN and non-BPMN diagram application that organises business logic. Provides a graphical user interface, creates questionnaires with multiple complex paths and allows to create/modify processes without heavy technical knowledge.

SpiffWorkflow’s benefits:

- › Dynamically and programmatically create BPMN and Non-BPMN workflow models
- › Open source
- › Optional UI designer
- › Powerful API
- › Import/Export BPMN models from xml files
- › Import/Export Non-BPMN models from python classes or JSON files
- › Create custom task and executables

SpiffWorkflow’s limitations:

- › The tool can be used to create a variety of workflow patterns, but there is not capable of

scalable work of actions. Furthermore, there is not a big community for support, bugs and problem solving while that's an open-source software.

Figure 13 – SpiffWorkflow’s optional UI

Airflow[68]: provides a programmatic interface to create and manage workflows that follow the Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) properties. Airflow is Python-based but you can execute a program irrespective of the language. For example, the first stage of your workflow must execute a R-based program to perform analysis and then a Python-based program to transfer that information to storage.

Airflow’s benefits:

- › Programmatically create workflows as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) of tasks
- › Open source
- › Powerful Dashboards
- › Import/Export workflows from python files
- › Create custom task and executables
- › Can be extended with a variety of plugins

Airflow’s limitations:

- › Airflow is based on DAG representation and doesn’t have a concept of input or output, just of flow. Better for big scalable applications that fit well with 3rd party applications.

Figure 14 – Airflow: List of DAGs

Figure 15 – Airflow: DAG structure

Figure 16 – Airflow: Gantt diagram of execution times[68]

ProcessMaker: The modeler empowers business users to design business processes in days, not months. Drag and drop tasks and decision points on to the modelling canvas, and then add in your forms, users, data connectors and more. The ProcessMaker modeler is BPMN 2.0 compliant, intuitive, and powerful. Business users can easily design elegant forms and display screens that are used in the workflows with no-code. Forms are used to capture data, display data from other systems, and design approval screens for managers to make decisions. Furthermore, can connect to existing third-party systems via API and dramatically improve the way people work. You'll generate much greater value from the same data.

ProcessMaker's benefits:

- › Dynamically create BPMN models
- › Open source (with limited features vs the paid version)
- › Powerful Dashboards
- › UI designer
- › Import/Export BPMN models from xml files
- › Create custom forms, tasks, and UI screens
- › Limited code executions on data

ProcessMaker's limitations:

- › Difficult to develop and learn all the reporting features that's a big part of the tool.

- › ProcessMaker has limited features on the free plan and paid ones starts from high pricing plans.
- › Old model user interface.

Figure 17 – ProcessMaker’s graphical interface

N8n[69]: n8n (pronounced n-eight-n) helps you to interconnect every app with an API in the world with each other to share and manipulate its data without a single line of code. It is an easy to use, user-friendly and highly customisable service, which uses an intuitive user interface for you to design your unique workflows very fast. Hosted on your server and not based in the cloud, it keeps your sensible data very secure in your own trusted database.

N8n’s benefits:

- › Dynamically and programmatically create BPMN workflow models
- › Open-source – extend through code contribution (fair-code licensed under Apache 2.0 with Commons Clause)
- › Low-code UI designer – excellent integration with 3rd party providers
- › High-code integration if needed on each step
- › Implement custom integrations

N8n’s limitations:

- › Limited already integrated 3rd party providers
- › Steep learning curve, plus the interface is not mapped as a linear process but is based on a flowchart.

Figure 18 – N8n’s graphical interface

Lightflow[70]: Lightflow is a Python 3.5+ library and command-line tool for executing workflows, composed of individual tasks, in a distributed fashion. It is based on Celery and provides task dependencies, data exchange between tasks and an intuitive description of workflows.

Lightflow’s benefits:

- › Programmatically create workflows as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) of tasks
- › Open source
- › Low-level code execution and task monitoring
- › Import/Export workflows from python files and CLI
- › Create custom task and executables

Lightflow’s limitations:

- › Poor user interface.
- › Difficult development creations until you reach a good level of knowledge.
- › Poor documentation that includes just the basics.

Pipefy: Pipefy brings customers, vendors, and partners onto the same platform as your internal team, making it easy to collaborate and track a process from start to finish. Trade chaotic to-do lists and email threads for clean, repeatable workflows.

Pipefy’s benefits:

- › Dynamically create BPMN models
- › Paid only version

- › Powerful Dashboards
- › Includes a Kanban board management method
- › Low-code/no-code process orchestration
- › Create automation tasks, forms, and integrations with 3rd party applications

Pipefy's limitations:

- › Not easy usable for non-familiar users.
- › Poor expert advice and community.
- › Best use for small projects and businesses.

Figure 19 – Pipefy: Marketing campaign example

Kissflow: Kissflow is a best-in-class BPM software that enables organisations to reinvent existing business processes for digital optimisation. Its no-code development nature allows business users to automate process flows, enforce business rules, and make ad-hoc process changes without any coding. Best of all, Kissflow is not just restricted to structured and repeatable business processes, it also supports all types of work (process, case, projects, and more). Its intuitive process stream allows stakeholders to collaborate with each other efficiently and securely.

Some of the best features of Kissflow include user-friendly dashboards, custom report templates, and advanced workflow and form design. It also integrates with other software solutions and standard productivity apps seamlessly.

Kissflow's benefits:

- › Dynamically create workflows (BPM)
- › Low-code/no-code process orchestration
- › Visual forms and Designer
- › Algorithmic task management
- › Automated workflow routing

Kissflow's limitations:

- › Paid only version and every stakeholder needs another license.
- › There are no native integrations with several popular business applications, including major CRMs and other management systems.
- › Cannot Request tracking for external stakeholders.

Pm4py: PM4Py is a software product, developed by the Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Information Technology (FIT). PM4Py is developed by the process mining group of Fraunhofer FIT. PM4Py is created with a few goals in mind, for example:

Making state-of-the-art process mining algorithms available to the public; The process mining group of Fraunhofer FIT is affiliated with the Process and Data Science group of Prof. Wil van der Aalst. Together, they are considered the world-wide leading group in process mining research. Through this connection, novel developments are integrated in PM4Py extremely fast. Furthermore, some of the developers of PM4Py have been active in process mining research for several years and published in numerous scientific venues, on various process mining topics.

Supporting Collaborations between Academia and Industry; The development team of PM4Py develops numerous related products, e.g., connectors to several different enterprise systems such as SAP, Camunda, etc., a web-service that wraps around and a scalable cloud solution. All these products allow us to integrate the core of PM4Py, i.e., state-of-the-art process mining, within industrial enterprise. This allows us to actively integrate our solutions within the day-to-day operations of industry partners. Note that, the goal of these products is to foster industry-driven research, i.e., Fraunhofer is a non-profit research institute.

Pm4py's benefits:

- › Process Mining Tool – Discovers processes from event logs
- › Filters Event Data
- › Provides statistics (e.g., throughput time, case arrival, etc.)
- › Evaluates fitness, precision, generalisation and simplicity

Pm4py's limitations:

- › The documentation of the package is being re-written and is currently lacking clarity and examples.
- › Difficult to use and connect all the available modules to create a final workflow.
- › Few functionalities regarding DFG.

BPMN.io: is an opensource web-based tooling for BPMN, DMN workflows and Forms. Provides JavaScript based packages that can be integrated to any application and help to create dynamic workflows that follow the BPMN or DMN standards.

BPMN.io's benefits:

- › Open source
- › Provides a wide variety of independent libraries
- › Provides friendly and easy to use UI tools

- › Export workflows that can be used on any application.

BPMN.io’s limitations:

- › Poor user interface that makes it difficult for users that have not use a BPMN again.
- › Best for small workflows that will be used on unexperienced users.

3.1.2.1.1 Overview

Table 4 – BPMN and Workflow tools

Tool	Documentation	Activity	Open source	Ease of use
SpiffWorkflow	Good	Active	Yes	Easy
Airflow	Well	Active	Yes	Easy
ProcessMaker	Good	Active	Yes	Medium
n8n	Good	Active	Yes*	Difficult
Lightflow	Good	Archaic	Yes	Easy
Pipefy	-	Active	No	Difficult
Kissflow	-	Active	No	Difficult
Pm4py	Well	Active	Yes	Medium
BPMN.io Tool case	Well	Active	Yes	Easy

3.2 DATA ANALYTICS AND VISUALISATIONS – COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

3.2.1 OVERVIEW

As we already discussed in the previous section, data analysis and visualisation applications in the healthcare research sector, face sector - specific challenges. As such the tools that will be used in the platform need to be able to support certain functionalities, especially those tools that have not been natively designed around the healthcare sector.

The platforms’ application veers from this traditional process, but should still take into account the necessities and requirements in that process for they still exist in our implementation [32].

After conducting an extensive state-of-the-art analysis about the methods used for the analysis of electrophysiology, actigraphy, MRI data and hypothesis testing, we had a first in-depth discussion with the clinical partners. The results of this discussion are reported in ANNEX I :. More specifically, the methods used for the analysis of electrophysiology and actigraphy data are reported in Table 12, while the methods used for the analysis of MRI data are reported in Table 13. Finally, Table 14 reports some general methods, which are used for statistical analyses.

3.2.2 TOOLS USED FOR DATA PROCESSING AND ANALYTICS

In this section, we present some libraries and tools used for statistical analyses, hypothesis testing, and analyses of neuroimaging and electrophysiological data.

3.2.2.1 General Tools/Libraries used for Data Processing, Statistical Analysis, and Hypothesis Testing

NumPy: NumPy is an open-source Python library providing a multidimensional array object along with array-aware functions that operate on it [71]. This library has been used as a foundation, over which other libraries have been created including scikit-learn, SciPy, statsmodels, Matplotlib, etc.

NumPy's Benefits:

- › Through NumPy the user has the ability to have access to specific elements of arrays via indexing. In addition, NumPy offers the functionality of broadcasting, meaning that the dimensions of the arrays may differ. Also, the NumPy library provides the user the opportunity to apply reduction operations along one or more axes. Operations include amongst others the summation, mean, etc.
- › Also, the NumPy Python library offers the opportunity to the users to apply statistics, including order statistics, averages and variances, correlations, and computation of histograms. In terms of the order statistics, one can compute the minimum, maximum, range of values (maximum – minimum), q-th percentile of the data, etc. When it comes to the correlation functions supported by the NumPy library, one compute the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients, the Cross-correlation of two 1-dimensional sequences and estimate the covariance matrix given data and weights. Finally, one can compute the histogram of a dataset, the bi-dimensional histogram of two data samples, the multidimensional histogram of some data, etc.

NumPy's Limitations:

- › One limitation of NumPy is the fact that there is not a wide range of implementations for pure statistical purposes. Since statistical analyses comprise a fundamental part of the MES-CoBraD project, we intend to use the SciPy and statsmodels libraries in Python, which are presented in detail in the following sections.

Pandas: Pandas is an open-source Python library used for working with structure datasets pertinent to statistics, finances, and many other fields [72]. Functionalities offered by the Pandas library include among others: handling missing data, operations between different datasets (add, concatenation, etc.), access to specific columns, rows, group data by identifiers, etc. Below we mention some of the advantages and limitations of this library, which will be used throughout the MES-CoBraD project.

Pandas Benefits:

- › In medical data, the phenomenon of missing values is widely known. In Pandas, one can deal with missing values by using the *dropna* and *fillna* methods. Specifically, the *fillna* method is equipped with some interpolation methods to propagate values forward and backward, which is really important in time series data. The same functionality is offered via the method called *reindex*.
- › In statistical data analysis problems, one simple phenomenon is to group data by some identifiers and then apply aggregations, transformations, or visualisations. Similar to SQL, one can use the method *groupby* in the Pandas library, in order to group data based on some characteristics. Also, the user may use the *describe* method, in order to get the descriptive statistics of a specific column, row, etc.
- › Similar to SQL, one can combine, merge, or join related datasets.

- › Moreover, one can compute correlations via the Pandas library, including the Pearson correlation, Spearman rank correlation, and Kendall Tau correlation. It is worth mentioning that the user may create also his/her own correlations via a callable function. The correlations can be computed between two Series, DataFrames, or columns.

Pandas Limitations:

- › As it is highlighted in the documentation, *pandas* may not be the ideal tool for all the situations. For instance, if one works with very large datasets and a tool like PostgreSQL fits the needs and requirements of the project, then this tool may be the right choice. What is also worth mentioning is the fact that the documentation recommends the usage of other libraries, including *Dask*, which can operate more efficiently with larger datasets in parallel.
- › Although using the Pandas library, one can deal with missing values, the methods supported by the library are not always ideal when dealing with patient data.

DASK: Dask is a Python library used for parallel computing [73], [74]. This library consists of two parts, namely the dynamic task scheduling, which is optimised for computation, and the big data collections, which aim to extend the capabilities and utilities provided by other libraries, such as NumPy, Pandas, and more.

DASK's Benefits:

- › Dask arrays implement most of the NumPy utilities, including reduction along axes, arithmetic and scalar mathematics, slicing, linear algebra, and many more. In addition, Dask Array provides the capability to compute on arrays larger than memory. This is achieved by using blocked algorithms.
- › Dask can use multiple threads or processes on a single machine, or a cluster of machines to process data in parallel. The Dask DataFrame provided many utilities offered via the Pandas library, including pearson correlation, drop duplicates, row-wise selections, and many more.

DASK's Limitations:

- › Some of the functions provided by the NumPy library are not available in Dask Arrays which may narrow down the available option for the users. For instance, utilities via the module `numpy.linalg`, operations like *sort* or *tolist*, and more are not available via the Dask library.
- › Dask DataFrame does not implement all the functionalities provided via the Pandas library. For example, setting a new index from an unsorted column is expensive and as a consequence performing operations like `groupby-apply` and `join` on unsorted columns is expensive too.

SciPy: SciPy [75] constitutes an open-source Python library offering a wide number of algorithms for many problems, including optimisation, integration, interpolation, eigenvalue problems, algebraic equations, differential equations, signal or image processing, etc. SciPy started in the year 2001 and throughout the years it has become one of the most famous libraries due to the variety of possibilities it offers to the user. Moreover, SciPy is built upon NumPy, while it has been used in other libraries, including `scikit-learn`. In addition, several packages are available through SciPy, which will be mentioned in detail below. The benefits of SciPy rendering it a useful library for the implementation of the requirements of the MES-CoBraD project are as follows:

SciPy's Benefits:

- › One of the packages of SciPy, which is pertinent to the MES-CoBraD project, is undoubtedly the *signal* package. Specifically, this package is focused on signal processing and basic linear systems theory. It includes among others: convolutions, splines, filters, peak finding, spectral analysis, etc.
- › The *fft* package is also highly related to the MES-CoBraD project, since it implements Fast Fourier Transforms, including 1-D, 2, and N-D discrete Fourier transforms, Discrete Cosine Transforms, Discrete Sine Transforms, and the Fast Hankel Transform.
- › The *stats* package includes probability distributions, summary and frequency statistics, correlations functions and statistical tests, etc. Regarding statistical tests, which will be used extensively in the MES-CoBraD platform, some typical examples are the following: t-test, Mann-Whitney U rank test, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, Kruskal-Wallis H-test, etc. In terms of the frequency statistics, one can plot cumulative frequency histograms, and more, while with regards to summary statistics, mean, variance, kurtosis, skewness, etc. can be computed. Some of the available correlation functions are the point biserial, Spearman, Pearson, etc. which return the correlation value along with the p-value (used for test significance).
- › SciPy may also be used for image processing via the package called *ndimage*. It is used mainly in medical and biological imaging, where images of high dimensionality need to be analysed. This package offers some of the following functionalities: linear and non-linear filtering, i.e., Gaussian, median, Sobel filter, etc., region labelling and processing, B-spline interpolation, etc.

SciPy's Limitations:

- › To the best of our knowledge, one disadvantage of SciPy is the fact that it does not support multiple tests for hypothesis testing and consequently the correction of p-values. This functionality is offered by another Python library called *statsmodels*, which will be presented in detail below.

Scikit-learn: Scikit-learn [76] is an open-source Python library providing a wide number of functionalities, including classification or regression algorithms, clustering techniques, dimensionality reduction methods, algorithms for model selection, and methods for preprocessing the data. Scikit-learn is accessible to everyone and is built upon NumPy, SciPy, and matplotlib.

Scikit-learn's Benefits:

- › Scikit-learn provides algorithms targeting the imputation of missing values, which is a common problem in real-world datasets. Some of the algorithms offered by scikit-learn are the following, univariate-multivariate imputation, nearest neighbours imputation, etc.
- › Scikit-learn provides also functions for clustering and dimensionality reduction, such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA), t-SNE, and many more.

Scikit-learn's Limitations:

- › Although scikit-learn provides many functions which can be used for the analysis of neuroimaging and time-series data, there are libraries, such as Nilearn, MNE, etc., which are used solely for these purposes.

statsmodels: *Statsmodels* is a library for statistical and econometric analysis in Python [77]. It was started by Jonathan Taylor, as part of the SciPy library under the name *models*. It includes packages related to the Regression and Linear models, Time Series Analysis, Statistics, and more. It includes statistical models and hypothesis tests. We mention below some of the advantages and disadvantages of this library.

Statsmodels' Benefits:

- › *Statsmodels* includes the package called *tsa*, which is focused on time series analysis and offers the possibility to the user to exploit univariate autoregressive models (AR), vector autoregressive models (VAR), and univariate autoregressive moving average models (ARMA). In addition, descriptive statistics are available via this package, including autocorrelation, partial autocorrelation function, periodogram, etc. It also offers functionalities for filtering, i.e., Baxter-King bandpass filter, Hodrick-Prescott filter, etc.
- › In comparison to the SciPy library, the *statsmodels* library provides more statistical tests and tools via the package called *stats*. More specifically, the user is able to apply multiple tests for p-value correction. Some of the available methods used for testing and adjustment of p-values are the following: Bonferroni, Benjamini-Hochberg [78], Simes-Hochberg, Holm-Sidak, etc.
- › In terms of the imputation of missing values, the *statsmodels* library implements the Multiple Imputation with Chained Equations (MICE) via the module called MICE. Also, one can exploit the Bayesian Imputation using a Gaussian model.

Statsmodels' Limitations:

- › *Statsmodels* does not offer some of the functionalities offered by SciPy, i.e., multidimensional image processing, peak finding, or spectral analysis of signals. Thus, it may be used in conjunction with SciPy.

pmdarima: *pmdarima* is a Python library providing implementations of ARIMA estimators to the user [79].

pmdarima's Benefits:

- › *pmdarima* provides the R's implementation of *auto.arima* in Python. More specifically, *auto.arima* discovers automatically the optimal order of an ARIMA model. Therefore, *pmdarima* renders Python suitable for data science without requiring from the users to be familiar with the R language.
- › *pmdarima* provides several statistical tests, including CH test for seasonality, KPSS test for stationarity, OCSB test for seasonality, and PP test for stationarity. In addition, it includes some plotting functions, including autocorrelation, partial autocorrelation, and decomposition of a time series.
- › *pmdarima* provides an easy-to-read documentation with a lot of examples.

pmdarima's Limitations:

- › The *pmdarima* library provides more functionalities for time series analysis and statistical tests. However, one should not overlook that *pmdarima* provides the implementation of *auto.arima* function.

sktime: sktime constitutes a scikit-learn compatible Python library with a unified interface for machine learning with time series [80], [81].

sktime's Benefits:

- › sktime provides functionalities for time series classification, time series regression, time series clustering, time series forecasting, and time series annotation.

sktime's Limitations:

- › Both the library and the documentation are under development. Therefore, there are not so many examples for the reader/user.

Pingouin: Pingouin constitutes a Python library including some of the main statistical tests that scientists use on a daily basis [82]. It is written in Python 3 and is based mainly on Pandas and NumPy. Pingouin has an extensive documentation and also includes workflows, which help the user choose which functions/statistical tests are suitable for the user's analysis.

Pingouin's Benefits:

- › Pingouin offers a great number of functions, including ANOVA, t-test, bayes factors, multivariate tests, and many more. Similar to the *statsmodels* library, the user has the ability to apply multiple tests targeting the correction of the p-values.
- › One advantage of Pingouin over SciPy is the fact that SciPy for example returns only the T-value and the p-value. By contrast, the *t-test* function of Pingouin returns the T-value, the p-value, the degrees of freedom, the effect size (Cohen's d), the 95% confidence intervals of the difference in means, the statistical power and the Bayes Factor (BF10) of the test.

Pingouin's Limitations:

- › The *statsmodels* library offers more statistical tests and methods for multiple tests than Pingouin.
- › Pingouin is used mainly for statistical analyses, in contrast to SciPy which includes also methods to apply transforms on signals, etc.

3.2.2.2 Tools/Libraries for Processing Neuroimaging and Electrophysiology Brain data

Nitime: Nitime [83] is an open-source Python library used mainly for time-series analysis of data derived by neuroimaging experiments. Although it has been mainly developed for time-series analysis of functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) data, the algorithms implemented via this library can be used in other applications too. Below, we mention some of the advantages and limitations of the Nitime library.

Nitime's Benefits:

- › Through the package *nitime.algorithms*, the user is able to apply a lot of algorithms, including spectral transforms, coherency, regularised coherency, and event-related analysis. Specifically, regarding the spectral transforms, algorithms towards the calculation of a standard periodogram and cross-spectral density estimates based on both the regular and multi-taper periodograms are provided. With regards to the coherency, it corresponds to an

analog of cross-correlation calculated between two time-series in the frequency domain. For a more robust computation of coherence in the presence of small denominators, the regularised coherency is also available. In terms of the event-related analysis, a set of univariate statistics is calculated separately for the time-series in each voxel or each Region of Interest (ROI), including standard least squares estimate of the hemodynamic response function, cross-correlation between a series of events and a time-series, etc.

Nitime's Limitations:

- › Nitime is a library focusing on the implementation of advanced algorithms rather than the pre-processing stages of MRI, time-series data, etc. Thus, other libraries need to be used for the purposes of the pre-processing stage.

MNE: MNE [84] is an open-source Python library for analysing human neurophysiological data, including MEG, EEG, sEEG, ECoG, NIRS, and many more. It provides a wide number of tools, including source estimation, machine learning, encoding models, statistics, connectivity, and visualisations.

MNE's Benefits:

- › Firstly, MNE includes a wide number of functions, which are used for reading data from several file formats. For example, one can read EEG data in the following formats: BrainVision (.vhdr, .vmrk, .eeg), European data format (.edf), BioSemi data format (.bdf), General data format (.gdf), Neuroscan CNT (.cnt), and more.
- › MNE provides many functions and utilities for preprocessing data. More specifically, one can use several filters via the MNE library, including the bad-pass, low-pass, high-pass, bad-stop, and notch filtering. In addition, MNE implements algorithms for the detection and removal of artifacts. More specifically, the removal of artifacts is implemented using regression [85], signal-space projection (SSP) [86], or independent component analysis (ICA).
- › MNE also offers a full and easy-to-read documentation, which provides guidelines regarding the usage of statistical tests, hypothesis testing, and correction of the p-values after multiple tests. It implements functions for statistical analysis, including parametric statistics, mass-univariate multiple comparison correction, non-parametric (clustering) resampling methods, and computation of adjacency matrices for cluster-level statistics.

MNE's Limitations:

- › As mentioned in the documentation, one can refer to `scipy.stats` and `statsmodels` libraries in Python for more options regarding the usage of functions for statistical analysis.

YASA: YASA (Yet Another Spindle Algorithm) [87] is a Python package used for analysing polysomnographic sleep recordings. YASA is accompanied with a full and easy-to-read documentation, which includes also a lot of examples.

YASA's Benefits:

- › YASA implements algorithms targeting the event detection, including sleep spindles, slow waves and rapid eye-movements, on single or multi-channel EEG data.
- › YASA offers also some functions pertinent to spectral analysis, such as the calculation of the spectral band power, separation of the aperiodic components of the EEG power spectrum

using the IRASA method [88], computation of epoch-per-epoch non-linear features, and many more.

- › YASA provides also the functionality of the automatic sleep staging of polysomnographic data. Specifically, the automatic sleep staging function requires that the data are loaded using the MNE python library. Finally, the automatic sleep stages classification can be done using the SleepStaging class.
- › Moreover, YASA implements various hypnogram tools, such as the creation of a state-transition matrix from an hypnogram, the conversion of a string hypnogram array to an integer, and more. One can also extract sleep statistics from an hypnogram, i.e., sleep efficiency, WASO, time in bed, sleep period time, latencies of sleep stages from the beginning of the record, and many more.

YASA's Limitations:

- › YASA does not apply preprocessing steps. Thus, MNE may be used for the purposes of the preprocessing stages.

WONAMBI[89]: WONAMBI constitutes a Python library used for the analysis of EEG, ECoG, and other electrophysiology modalities.

WONAMBI's Benefits:

- › WONAMBI can read files of many formats, including European Data Format (.edf), Fieldtrip (.mat), and many others.
- › It is used for the computation of frequency analysis (spectrogram), time-frequency analysis (short-time spectrogram, Morlet wavelet).
- › WONAMBI also provides algorithms for the detection of spindles and slow waves.

WONAMBI's Limitations:

- › WONAMBI offers less algorithms than those implemented by YASA.

SleepPy: SleepPy is an open-source Python library processing multi-day streams of raw accelerometer data (X, Y, and Z) from wrist-worn wearable devices and produces sleep reports for each recording day [90].

SleepPy's Benefits:

- › One can load raw accelerometer data via an input file and then SleepPy can split them into 24-hour segments and process them. The output of the SleepPy is a table, where one can have access to the total sleep time in minutes, percentage of the major rest period during the sleep state, wake after sleep onset (WASO) in minutes, the sleep onset latency (SOL), and the number of wake bouts, which indicates the number of times the subject transitioned from sleep to wake after the first sleep state. The SleepPy library plots also a visualisation report, which will be mentioned in detail in Section 3.2.3.2.

SleepPy's Limitations:

- › SleepPy can work with data generated by the GeneActiv wrist-worn devices (GeneActiv .bin files). It can also support .csv files generated by GeneActiv's software.

PyActigraphy: PyActigraphy constitutes an open-source Python library used for actigraphy data visualization and analysis [91]. Below, we mention some of the benefits of the PyActigraphy library as well as its main limitations.

PyActigraphy's Benefits:

- › PyActigraphy provides many functionalities and utilities for reading data from many file formats. More specifically, it supports output files from:
 - Actigraph: wGT3X-BT
 - CamNtech: Actiwatch 4 and MotionWatch 8
 - Condor Instrument: ActTrust 2
 - Daqtix: Daqtometer
 - Respironics: Actiwatch 2 and Actiwatch Spectrum (plus)
 - Tempatilumi (CE Brasil)
- › PyActigraphy also implements algorithms for detecting rest periods, including Cole-Kripke's [92], Oakley's [93], Sadeh's [94], Scripps' [95], Crespo's [96], and Roenne-berg's [97] algorithms.
- › It provides also advanced signal processing functions, including Cosinor analysis [98], Detrended Fluctuation Analysis [99], [100], Functional Linear Modelling [101], Locomotor Inactivity during sleep [102], Singular Spectrum Analysis [103], and many more.

PyActigraphy's Limitations:

- › PyActigraphy package is currently under progress and many more features are expected to be implemented.

Visbrain: Visbrain [104] constitutes an open-source Python package used for both neuroimaging and electrophysiological brain data. Visbrain comes with an easy-to-read documentation and is accompanied by examples and datasets.

Visbrain's Benefits:

- › Visbrain provides functions related to signal processing. More specifically, de-trending, de-meaning, or filtering, i.e., lowpass, highpass, bandpass, bandstop, are implemented via the submodule of the Visbrain called Signal. In addition, one can extract the amplitude, phase, or power in specific power bands.
- › Via the submodule of the Visbrain library, called Sleep, one can apply time-frequency methods to the signals for computing the fourier-based spectrogram, the morlet's wavelet, and the multitaper-based Wigner spectrogram. It must be noted that the fourier-based spectrogram is implemented in SciPy, while the multitaper-based Wigner spectrogram [105] is provided via the library *Isopot*[106]. Moreover, the Visbrain library implements semi-automatic algorithms for the detection of events, such as sleep spindles, K-complexes, rapid-eye movements, slow waves, muscle twitches, and peaks.
- › Regarding the utilities offered by the submodule called *Brain*, details are given in Section

3.2.3.2.

Visbrain's Limitations:

- › As mentioned in [104], Visbrain does not provide data analysis functions, which are available in other libraries, such as SciPy, Pandas, or statsmodels.

Neuropycon: Neuropycon [107] constitutes an open-source Python library used for the analysis of multimodal brain data and provides Python-based templates pipelines for multiprocessing of MEG, EEG, functional and anatomical MRI. It is focused mainly on connectivity and graph theoretical analyses. Neuropycon contains two packages, namely the ephypype and the graphpype, which are designed for electrophysiology analysis and functional connectivity respectively.

Neuropycon's Benefits:

- › The ephypype package provides algorithms for preprocessing, cleaning by automatic removal of eyes and heart related artefacts, etc. More specifically, one can perform filtering, downsample the MEG raw data, or run an ICA algorithm, which is implemented via the MNE library. One can also compute the Power Spectral Density for each frequency band. In addition, the computation of the connectivity matrices in the frequency domain is available, since Neuropycon provides functions implemented in the MNE library.
- › The graphpype package can be exploited for the computation of graph metrics for multiple modalities, including modular partitions.
- › Neuropycon can import raw MEG/EEG data, time-series, fMRI data, and connectivity matrices.
- › Neuropycon provides also the utilities for conducting group-level statistical analyses in a lot of ways. The graphpype package offers functions for calculating statistics on connectivity and graph data, including paired and unpaired t-test, binomial, Mann-Whitney, etc.

Neuropycon's Limitations:

- › One may face difficulties in creating workflows and thus choose other libraries for conducting their analyses.

Nilearn: Nilearn is a Python library aiming to simplify the use of scikit-learn in terms of neuroimaging [108]. Nilearn provides statistical and machine learning tools with instructive documentation. Also, it leverages the scikit-learn Python library for multivariate statistics with applications, such as predictive modelling, classification, decoding, or connectivity analysis.

Nilearn's Benefits:

- › Nilearn analyses fMRI data by employing Generalised Linear models. Nilearn provides also functions for setting up first- and second-level models, performing t-tests, multiple comparisons correction and thresholding. Nilearn outputs html reports, which include all the analyses conducted. These functions are available in the package *nilearn.glm*.
- › Some additional functionalities provided by the Nilearn library are the following: smoothing images by applying a Gaussian filter, computing the mean of the images over time or the 4th dimension (for fMRI), resampling an image to a template, independent component analysis of fMRI, and many more.

- › In addition, Nilearn comes with an easy-to-read documentation accompanied by a lot of examples pertinent to the advanced statistical analysis of brain images.

Nilearn's Limitations:

- › Nilearn does not provide support for reading MRI data. For this purpose, the Nibabel library will be used.

Dipy: Diffusion imaging in Python (Dipy) [109] is an open-source Python library used for the analysis of diffusion magnetic resonance imaging (dMRI) data. Dipy is built upon NumPy, SciPy, Nibabel and libraries for visualisations, including Matplotlib and Python-VTK.

Dipy's Benefits:

- › Dipy includes several methods for statistical analysis, reconstruction, registration, denoising, and preprocessing. More specifically, several metrics for streamlines are available in the Dipy library, including spline interpolation, curvature and torsion calculations along a streamline, the computation of the average length and standard deviation of the streamlines generated after the fiber tracking procedure, and many more. One can also remove the background and keep parts that are in the brain by using the function called *median_tsu*. In addition, one can denoise images by using Non-Local Means (NLMEANS), Local PCA via empirical thresholds, the Marcenko-Pastur PCA algorithm. Also, examples about the suppression of the Gibbs artefacts of MR images are provided. Patch2Self [110], which is a self-supervised learning method for denoising DWI data, is also implemented.

Dipy's Limitations:

- › No significant limitations.

Antropy: Antropy is a Python 3 package providing several time-efficient algorithms for computing the complexity of time-series. It can be used to extract features from EEG signals. Antropy was created and is maintained by Raphael Vallat.

Antropy's benefits:

- › It implements various specialised functions regarding entropy and fractal dimension, including permutation entropy, spectral entropy, Hjorth mobility and complexity, number of zero-crossings, Petrosian fractal dimension, katz fractal dimension etc.

Antropy's limitations:

- › It can extract features from electroencephalography signals but doesn't have much more usability than that.
- › As mentioned in the documentation, the results need to be double-checked.

UK Biobank accelerometer analysis: UK biobank accelerometer analysis [111]–[114] is a tool used for the extraction of information from large accelerometer datasets. It can be installed via Python and also needs Java to be installed.

Benefits:

- › This package can process data from raw GENEActiv. Bin files, raw Actigraph .gt3x files (both versions 1 and 2), raw gzipped CSV files. Moreover, this package provides the opportunity for

processing hundreds of accelerometer files.

- › Questions such as how much time is spent in sleep, sedentary behaviour, or doing physical activity are answered via this package.
- › This package provides functions for classifying different activity types. Some examples of activities are the following: sleep, sit/stand, vehicle, walking, mixed activity, and bicycling.

Limitations:

- › Limited support for various data formats.

PyEEG: PyEEG constitutes an open-source Python module used for extracting features from EEG data [115].

PyEEG's benefits:

- › One can compute the following features using the PyEEG library:
 - Power Spectral Intensity (PSI) and Relative Intensity Ratio (RIR)
 - Petrosian Fractal Dimension (PFD)
 - Higuchi Fractal Dimension (HFD)
 - Hjorth mobility and complexity
 - Spectral Entropy (Shannon's entropy of RIRs)
 - SVD Entropy, etc.

PyEEG's Limitations:

- › PyEEG does not include functions for reading data. Thus, other libraries must be exploited for this purpose.

Eeglib: eeglib is an open-source Python library used for feature extraction from EEG signals and is based on sliding windows [116].

Eeglib's Benefits:

- › Eeglib can import data from three different formats, namely csv files, EDF and NumPy arrays.
- › Regarding the preprocessing stage, the user is able to apply bandpass filter, Independent Component Analysis (ICA) [117], and z-scores normalisation to the raw EEG data.
- › One can also compute the Fast Fourier Transform, Discrete Wavelet Transform, Power Spectral Density, Band Power, Hjorth Parameters, Detrended Fluctuation Analysis, Sample Entropy, and many more.

Eeg's Limitations:

- › MNE imports data from more file formats and implements more algorithms than eeglib.

NiBabel: NiBabel is a Python library used for having access to neuroimaging file formats [118].

NiBabel's Benefits:

- › NiBabel provides access to the most common medical and neuroimaging file formats,

including ANALYZE (plain, SPM99, SPM2 and later), GIFTI, NIFTI1, NIFTI2, MINC1, MINC2, MGH and ECAT as well as Philips PAR/REC.

- › The user can have full or selective access to head information. Access to the image data is made available via the NumPy library.
- › Nibabel comes with a full and easy-to-read documentation with a lot of examples.

NiBabel's Limitations:

- › Very limited support for DICOM.

BIOPAC Systems Actigraphy: It is a toolkit used for sleep and activity analysis. It also correlates activity levels with GPS positioning providing in this way more information. It is a toolkit, which is not freely available and one must pay for having access to it.

BIOPAC Systems Actigraphy Benefits:

- › Regarding sleep analysis, one can compute the sleep onset, percentage of wake, sleep end, wake after sleep onset (WASO), total sleep period length, sleep bouts, sleep time, wake bouts, percentage of sleep, mean sleep bout, wake time, and mean wake bout.
- › In terms of the activity analysis, one can calculate the total low activity time, waking low activity time, total high activity time, total medium activity time, and more.

BIOPAC Systems Actigraphy Limitations:

- › It is not open-source and thus cannot be used.

Koneksa Actigraphy: It is a platform, where one can perform analysis, i.e., sleep and activity analysis, on raw accelerometer-based datasets.

Koneska Actigraphy Benefits:

- › Regarding sleep analysis, one can compute the total sleep time, sleep efficiency, and the number of wake bouts.
- › With regards to the activity analysis, one can compute the activity intensity level, count per worn epoch, etc.

Koneksa Actigraphy Limitations:

- › It is not open-source and thus cannot be used.

MotionWare: It is a software used for the analysis of sleep, circadian rhythm, and physical activity. It is not freely available.

MotionWare's Benefits:

- › MotionWare can import data captured with MotionWatch 8, MotionWatch Rugged, or PRO-Diary.
- › Regarding sleep analysis, one can compute the sleep latency, WASO, Sleep Efficiency, and Sleep Fragmentation.

- › It includes Non-Parametric Circadian Rhythm Analysis (NPCRA).
- › With regards to the analysis of the activity, one can calculate the amount of time spent within each activity category, the vigorous/moderate/low/sedentary activity time, the empty/non-zero/zero time, and more.

MotionWare's Limitations:

- › It is not open-source and thus cannot be used.

Actiware: Actiware is a software package used for the analysis of data derived by Actiwatch models. Several statistics are available through the Actiware software and are mentioned below.

Actiware's Benefits:

- › Regarding activity statistics, one can compute the total activity count, average activity count per minute, average activity count per epoch, standard deviation of activity count for epochs during an interval, and maximum activity count.
- › With regards to the sleep/wake statistics, one can compute the sleep time, percentage sleep, number of sleep bouts, average sleep bout, onset latency, snooze time, sleep efficiency, wake after sleep onset, wake time, percentage wake, number of wake bouts, and averaging wake bouts.
- › Regarding the mobility statistics, one can compute the immobile time, percentage immobile, number of immobile bouts, average immobile bouts, number of 1-minute immobile bouts, percentage of 1-minute immobile bouts, mobile time, percentage mobile time, number of mobile bouts, average mobile bouts, fragmentation index.

Actiware's Limitations:

- › It is a closed-source package.

MedPy: MedPy is a Python library used for reading, writing, and manipulating medical images. It includes image filters and methods for extracting features from images, which can be later used along with the scikit-learn library.

MedPy's Benefits:

- › MedPy provides the opportunity for having access to medical images being in the following formats: ITK MetaImage, Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative (NIFTI), DICOM, Medical Imaging NetCDF, etc.
- › One can also compute the mutual information between two images or the distance between histograms. These functionalities are offered via the module `medpy.metric`.
- › One can apply filters to medical images via the module `medpy.filter`. Also, this module provides the opportunity for image smoothing, hough transform, etc.
- › MedPy includes functions for extracting intensity based features.

MedPy's Limitations:

- › Less algorithms than the `nipy` library.

Skimage: scikit-image is an open-source Python library used for image processing [119].

Skimage's Benefits:

- › There is a forum, where users can ask questions regarding this library.
- › This package has an excellent documentation including examples about the implementation of the algorithms provided via the package.
- › This package provides algorithms for the detection of edges and lines, geometrical transformations and registration, filtering and restoration, detection of features and objects, segmentation of objects, and more.

Skimage's Limitations:

- › Skimage does not provide many functionalities used solely for medical images.

OpenCV: OpenCV is a library available in C++, Java, and Python and is used for image processing. We mention below some benefits and limitations of using this library.

OpenCV's Benefits:

- › OpenCV provides an easy-to-read documentation, which includes a great number of examples.
- › Via the OpenCV library, one can apply filters to smooth images, apply the two common morphological operators, i.e., erosion and dilation, apply transformations, including the Canny edge detector, Hough Line/Circle Transform, and Affine Transformations, and more. In addition, the OpenCV library provides the functionalities of histogram equalisation, calculation, and comparison. Moreover, one can find contours, create bounding boxes and circles for contours, and many more.
- › OpenCV provides a forum, where one could seek for help, if he/she faces difficulties using this library.

OpenCV's Limitations:

- › In contrast to other libraries, which provide functionalities solely for medical images, this library provides more general functionalities.

Fmriprep: fmriprep [120] is a functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) data preprocessing pipeline performing basic preprocessing steps, i.e., coregistration, normalisation, unwrapping, etc. Using many neuroimaging softwares, i.e., FSL, ANTs, FreeSurfer, and AFNI.

Fmriprep's Benefits:

- › It has an easy-to-read documentation and is straightforward to use with only one line of code. Thus, it saves time.
- › The user is not obliged to install the packages used by fmriprep, i.e., FSL, ANTs, FreeSurfer, since the developers of the fmriprep have released a docker container, which includes everything needed for executing the pipeline.

- › There is a forum called Neurostars, where one could ask for help regarding the usage of the fmripred package.

Fmripred's Limitations:

- › Although fmripred is extremely easy to use, it is not easily customisable. For instance, if one wants to change the steps of the pipeline, it may be difficult. In this case, the nipy library is highly recommended.

Nipype: Nipype [121] constitutes an open-source Python package providing interfaces to existing neuroimaging software, including ANTs, FSL, MIPAV (Medical Image Processing, Analysis, and Visualisation), etc.

Nipype's Benefits:

- › Nipype has an easy-to-read documentation at the following website: <https://nipype.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.
- › Due to the fact that it provides access to a lot of neuroimaging softwares, including, AFNI, ANTs, BrainSuite, BRU2NII, Convert3D, Camino, Camino-TrackVis, CAT12, Connectome Mapper (CMP), dcm2nii, DCMStack, Diffusion Toolkit, DIPY, DTITK, Elastix, FreeSurfer, FSL, MeshFix, MINC Toolkit, MIPAV, MNE, MRTrix, Nifty, Nilearn, NiPy, Nitime, PETPVC, QuickShear, SEM Tools, Statistical Parametric Mapping (SPM), VistaSoft, Connectome Workbench, and 3D Slicer, one can apply a great number of algorithms to the data and compare the algorithms provided by the aforementioned packages.
- › Nipype includes also a forum, where one can ask for help, if he/she faces difficulties using the software package.

Nipype's Limitations:

- › No significant limitations.

NLTools: NLTools is a Python package used for the analysis of neuroimaging data. We mention below some of the benefits and limitations of this package.

NLTools' Benefits:

- › NLTools provides modules for reading the neuroimaging data, applying statistical analyses, downloading datasets, applying masks, plotting, and simulating multivariate data.
- › Some examples of functions and algorithms provided via the NLTools library are the following: identification of spikes from time series data or fMRI time series data, getting the mean or median of each voxel or image, running a mass-univariate regression across voxels, where three types of regression can be run, including Standard OLS, Robust OLS, and ARMA, applying spatial smoothing, calculating one sample t-test across each voxel, performing convolutions using an arbitrary function, computing correlations, adjusting the p-values using the Holm-Bonferroni method, building the Design Matrix, and many more.

NLTools' Limitations:

- › No significant limitations.

ActiLife: ActiLife is ActiGraph's premier actigraphy data analysis software platform and is not freely available.

Actilife's Benefits:

- › One can calculate sleep statistics, including onset, sleep latency, amount of sleep, and sleep efficiency.
- › This software can also detect bouts of physical activity, occurrences, time spent within bouts, and total count levels. Details about a subject's sedentary behaviour can also be computed. It is worth mentioning that ActiLife can classify physical activity intensity using 10 available cut point sets.
- › Heart Rate Analysis is also performed by calculating heart rate variables, including ADL heart rate, average active heart rate, heart rate delta, etc.

Actilife's Limitations:

- › It is not freely available.

FreeSurfer: FreeSurfer is an open source neuroimaging toolkit for processing, analysing, and visualising human brain MR images.

FreeSurfer's Benefits:

- › FreeSurfer can be used for the analysis and visualisation of structural, functional, and diffusion neuroimaging data from cross-sectional and longitudinal studies.
- › FreeSurfer provides the algorithm of recon-all, which includes 31 processing stages, including motion correction and conform, skull strip, spherical mapping/registration, and many more.
- › FreeSurfer supports the functionality of SAMSEG, which is a tool to robustly segment dozens of brain structures from head MRI scans without preprocessing.

FreeSurfer's Limitations:

- › The running time of recon-all may range from some hours to days.

NeuroDesk¹: NeuroDesk constitutes a flexible, scalable and browser-based data analysis environment for reproducible neuroimaging.

NeuroDesk's Benefits:

- › NeuroDesk provides analyses of electrophysiological and neuroimaging data, including functional imaging, hippocampus, image reconstruction/registration/segmentation, structural imaging, spine, statistics, etc.
- › With regards to the electrophysiological data, NeuroDesk provides access to brainstorm,

¹ <https://www.neurodesk.org/>

eeglab, fieldtrip, and MNE.

- › Regarding neuroimaging data, the FreeSurfer is supported. All the analyses supported by FreeSurfer, including visualisation approaches, are provided in NeuroDesk.
- › 3D Slicer is also supported.
- › Documentation for using docker containers is supported.
- › NeuroDesk applications can be also exploited in Google Colab.

NeuroDesk's Limitations:

- › No significant limitations.

3.2.3 TOOLS USED FOR DATA VISUALISATIONS

In this section the tools that can be used for data visualizations are presented. It's divided in three subsections. In the first tools for general visualisations are shown and in the next two we dive deeper with specialised tools and frameworks for visualisations of EEG and MRI data.

3.2.3.1 General Visualisations

AmCharts: AmCharts is a JavaScript library for data visualisation that can work with modern web development toolkits like React, Angular and Vue out of the box. Of course, it can be used in plain JavaScript apps. It was created in 2006 by Antanas Marcelionis as a side project and is maintained by a small team spread out across the globe. Developer products are mainly aimed at web and application developers, looking for a way to add data visualization capabilities to the products they are developing. AmCharts Charts offers a wide variety of chart types such as line, pie, donut, column, bar, area, etc. It, also, provides an addon for full-fledged interactive maps called amCharts Maps.

AmCharts' benefits:

- › Amcharts offers any chart type that may be needed and it also includes date based charts that can be important for the MES-CoBraD project.
- › It works out of the box on all modern web browsers, even some older versions of Internet Explorer.
- › There is extensive documentation, huge configuration and customisation options and integration with the most popular web frameworks.
- › It is an open source and there are various pricing options. For the needs of our project it can be used for free (there will be an amCharts logo present at the corner of the charts)

AmCharts' limitations:

- › It can be slower than other charting frameworks available, especially when a large number of datapoints is involved.

D3.js[122]: D3 is a JavaScript library for manipulating documents based on data. It uses technologies such as HTML, SVG, and CSS. It supports a large number of visualizations, from bar charts and lines to maps and animations.

D3.js' benefits:

- › Many powerful visualization components
- › Data-driven DOM manipulation
- › It has good documentation and a large set of examples

D3.js' limitations:

- › It has generally complex syntax, so it is not suitable for beginners

Chart.js: Chart is a simple and flexible JavaScript library for visualizations.

Chart.js' benefits:

- › Offers all basic types of charts
- › Chart interactivity
- › Most of the times rendering is fast as charts are rendered on canvas elements

Chart.js' limitations:

- › Rendering can become slow for large datasets especially if they are not sorted and consistent

3.2.3.2 EEG and MRI Visualisations

MNE-Python: MNE is an open-source Python module for processing, analysis, and visualization of functional neuroimaging data (electroencephalography(EEG), magnetoencephalography(MEG), sEEG, EcoG, and fNIRS)[84]. It reimplements common M/EEG processing algorithms in pure Python. In addition, it also implements new algorithms, proposed and published by the MNE-Python authors.

MNE's benefits:

- › MNE can handle various types of file formats and it is suitable for processing and analysis of electroencephalography data that is one of the focuses of the project.
- › It can produce a variety of visualisations. Some examples include signal traces and butterfly plots, scalp topographies, arrow maps, joint plots, 3D field maps, etc.
- › Has function to export interactive HTML summaries of the data.

MNE's limitations:

- › It seems to be more tailored for MEG users than EEG users.

Visbrain[104]: Visbrain is an open-source Python 3 package dedicated to brain signals visualization. It is under heavy development and many functionalities are frequently added to the package. It is based on top of VisPy, a Python package providing high-performance 2D and 3D visualization by leveraging the computational power of the graphics card and PyQt, a set of Python bindings for The Qt Company's Qt application framework and is distributed under the 3-Clause BSD license. Visbrain consists of two levels of abstraction: (1) objects which represent highly configurable neuro-oriented visual primitives (3D brain, sources connectivity, etc.) and (2) graphical user interfaces for higher level interactions. Currently there are 4 graphical user interfaces: Brain for visualisations involving a MNI brain, Sleep for polysomnographic data visualization and sleep analysis, Signal for 72 visualisations of multi-dimensional datasets and figures for constructing figure layouts.

Visbrain's benefits:

- › It offers many functionalities that will be needed for the MES-CoBraD project. It has 18 objects (as of now) that are highly configurable (for example: brain object, hypnogram object, connectivity object, etc.) and offers graphical user interfaces to interact with these objects.
- › Additional implemented objects include time-frequency maps, phase-amplitude coupling comodulograms, topographic representations of EEG data, etc.
- › It is in constant development, so new features and functionalities are frequently added to the package.
- › Since it is in development there is a growing community that can help with issues and make our work easier.
- › The Brain gui is especially useful for the needs of MES-CoBraD. Its main features include templates for zoom and rotation of the volume, control of the transparency and appearance, addition and connection of sources to the scene, display of brain sections, volumes, time-series, vectors, etc.

WONAMBI: Wonabi is a Python package for the analysis of EEG, EcoG and other electrophysiology modalities. Allows for visualization of the data and sleep stage scoring in a GUI. Provides automatic detectors for spindles and slow waves.

WONAMBI benefits

- › WONAMBI gives the user the ability to plot 3D images and surfaces from freesurfer.
- › Multiple channel groups can be created. This is useful because each group can have its own reference, filter settings, color, etc. Moreover, montages can be created, saved and loaded. Montages are channel snapshots that are stored in .json format.

YASA[87]: Yasa is a command-line sleep analysis toolbox in Python. Some of its functions are spectral and hypnogram analyses, event detection (for example, rapid eye movements) on multi-channel EEG data and automatic sleep staging of polysomnography data. It was created and maintained by Raphael Varrat.

YASA benefits:

- › YASA can produce a wide variety of visualisations based on its functionalities. These include overlays of detected spindles on EEG data, spectrograms, hypnograms, sleep stage probability transition matrices, topographic plots, etc.

Sensor Motion: Sensor Motion is a python package for analysing sensor-collected human motion data that is developed and maintained by Simon Ho. It allows the user to extract human motion data, such as gait/walking dynamics, directly from accelerometer signals. Additionally, the package allows for the calculation of physical activity (PA) or moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (MVPA) counts. It, also, has a plot module that implements wrappers around various matplotlib pyplot plot calls.

Sensor Motion's benefits:

- › It offers functions for analysing time-series and accelerometer data. It can be especially useful

for filtering signals and finding peaks or valleys in them. Since it contains a plot module, it simplifies the creation of filter frequency response curves and general signal plots over time.

Sensor Motion's limitations:

- › It is developed and maintained by just one person so it is feature light and does not have the support of bigger packages.

PyEMD: PyEMD is a Python implementation of Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) and its variations. One of the most popular expansion is Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition (EEMD), which utilises an ensemble of noise-assisted executions.

PyEMD's benefits:

- › PyEMD contains a visualization helper that is used for quick and simple result visualization. It can plot and show intrinsic mode functions from a decomposed signal and instantaneous frequencies for the provided IMFs.

Nilearn[108]: Nilearn enables approachable and versatile analyses of brain volumes. It provides statistical and machine-learning tools, with instructive documentation & open community. It supports general linear model (GLM) based analysis and leverages the scikit-learn[123] Python toolbox for multivariate statistics with applications such as predictive modelling, classification, decoding, or connectivity analysis.

Nilearn benefits:

- › Nilearn has a lot of plotting functions to plot brain volumes. It can plot anatomical images, do echo-planar imaging (EPI), produce glass brain visualisations, plot network nodes (markers), etc. It offers various display modes and gives the scientist the ability to add cuts to specific locations. It, also, supports surface plotting
- › A nice benefit of Nilearn is that it has functions for making interactive plots that can be viewed in a web browser.

PySurfer: PySurfer is a Python library and application for visualizing brain imaging data. It is specifically useful for plotting data on a three-dimensional mesh representing the cortical surface of the brain. It offers a wide variety of visualisations ranging from simple to complex tasks. The aim of the library is to enable the user to create visualisations that are both scientifically accurate and beautiful.

PySurfer's benefits:

- › It has a large collection of visualisations that can be really useful for the needs of the project. These visualisations include plotting rgb values on brain surface, displaying fMRI activation and volume, plotting transparent brain, generating surface labels and displaying conjunction maps, ROI values, etc.
- › Gives the user the ability to animate the brain or create a movie from MEG inverse solution and save them as well as showing different brain views and saving set of views. These features add some form of interaction of the user with the results.

Scikit-image[119]: Scikit-image is a collection of algorithms for image processing. It is available free of charge and free of restriction. It builds on `scipy.ndimage` to provide a versatile set of image processing routines in Python and is designed to interoperate with both NumPy and SciPy. The scikit-image library is developed by its community.

Scikit-image's benefits:

- › It offers a lot of processing options regarding images that will certainly benefit the project. Examples include manipulating exposure and colour channels, get edges and lines from images, filtering, object and feature detection, segmentation, etc.
- › It uses NumPy arrays so it is expected to have efficient processing and be generally fast.
- › It incorporates most of the scikit-learn algorithms, namely PCA, clustering, segmentation, ensemble methods, various supervised and unsupervised algorithms, etc.
- › Since it is an open-source project with huge following it has great documentation and support.

Scikit-image's limitations:

- › Does not support video processing as OpenCV does. This will not be a problem though because we will use it as an image processing only library for the project needs.

OpenCV-Python: OpenCV is the Python API of OpenCV[124]. OpenCV is an open-source BSD-licensed library that includes several hundreds of computer vision algorithms. It is the biggest and most used library for image processing.

OpenCV Benefits:

- › Can be used for various computer vision and image processing tasks, such as filtering, background noise removal, object and face detection
- › It has visualisation capabilities, can load, save and show images and even offers a 3D Visualiser module.
- › OpenCV-Python is fast since it's a Python wrapper for the original OpenCV implementation that is written in C/C++
- › Has the ability to support video processing unlike scikit-image
- › Implements more than 2500 algorithms

DIPY[109]: DIPY is a 3D/4D+ imaging library. It contains generic methods for spatial normalisation, signal processing, machine learning, statistical analysis and visualization of medical images. Additionally, it contains specialised methods for computational anatomy including diffusion, perfusion and structural imaging.

DIPY's benefits:

- › Has many functions for visualisations. These include brain volume slicing, visualising bundles and metrics on bundles and an interface to access many of the capabilities available in the Visualization Toolkit framework (VTK) but tailored to the needs of structural and diffusion imaging
- › It's free and open source, implements many state-of-the-art algorithms and offers high

performance as many algorithms are implemented in Python

Nipype[125]: Nipype is a Python project that provides a uniform interface to existing neuroimaging software and facilitates interaction between these packages within a single workflow. It is an open-source, community-developed initiative under the umbrella of NiPy.

Nipype's benefits:

- › It allows for easy interaction with tools from different packages, so it gives a lot of flexibility on the tools used and encourages the exploration of various algorithms
- › Helps create a collaborative platform for neuroimaging software development by combining processing steps from different software packages into new workflows or reusing existing steps from old workflows.
- › It can be used to visualize the workflows so it's easier for the users to understand the flow of the steps taken and make research reproducible

BrainVISA[126]: BrainVISA is a neuroimaging software platform for mass data analysis. It is more of a set of tools than a single software. When using BrainVISA the software that runs is called Axon. Axon provides a graphical user environment, and integrates the different tools and data to make them available for end users. Visualization and interactive edition of data is already integrated in the Axon user interface. Axon can also facilitate the customisation and creation of new specialised visualization tools. Most of them make use of Anatomist, a library of data visualizations and high-level neuroimaging graphical components, specifically its Python adaptation, PyAnatomist. Anatomist offers a framework for interactive visualization of neuroimaging data.

BrainVISA's benefits:

- › Through PyAnatomist there are many visualization options. The user can load and view objects, change the camera parameters (zoom, orientation, etc), view meshes, use custom colour palettes and even do fusion between two volumes
- › BrainVISA is a modular environment, so it is possible to install, use and build on a subset of the tools.

Visualization Toolkit (VTK)[127]: The Visualization Toolkit is an open source software for manipulating and displaying scientific data. It comes with state-of-the-art tools for 3D rendering, a suite of widgets for 3D interaction, and extensive 2D plotting capability. VTK is part of Kitware's collection of supported platforms for software development.

VTK's benefits:

- › VTK provides various tools for 3D rendering and image processing
- › It can produce visualizations of scalar, vector and tensor fields as well as volume data (for example MRI scans) that will be the focus of our research. It, also, offers mesh and polygon processing, image analysis for both 2D and 3D images.

3D Slicer: 3D Slicer is a research software platform, which allows researchers to quickly develop and evaluate new methods and distribute them to clinical users. All features are available and extensible in Python. It is used for visualization and analysis (for example segmentation) of medical image computing data sets.

3D Slicer's benefits:

- › It supports all commonly used data sets and many types of images, segmentations, surfaces, transformations, in 2D, 3D and 4D.
- › Supports multi-modality imaging including, MRI
- › Real-time interface for medical devices, such as surgical navigation systems and sensors
- › It has a large and active community and new features are being added regularly

3.2.4 ANALYSIS - CONCLUSIONS

In this section, we present the tools, which will be used for the implementation of the MES-CoBraD project after the extensive state-of-the-art analysis conducted in Sections 3.2.2 and 3.2.3, as well as the up to date collected information.

- › Regarding electrophysiology signals, i.e., EEG, PSG, etc., the MNE library will be used for having access to the data. More specifically, MNE returns the list of channels, the data per channel, the sampling frequency, and many more information about the provided file. The data per channel are NumPy arrays. Next, for time-series analysis, the SciPy library will be used. More specifically, some functions that will be implemented via the SciPy library per channel are the following: estimation of the power spectral density (PSD) using a periodogram or the Welch's method, computation of the spectrogram with consecutive Fourier transforms, computation of the Short Time Fourier Transform, peak finding, etc. In addition, we will use the YASA library for event detection, including sleep spindles and slow waves. To be more precise, the YASA library returns a Pandas DataFrame, where each row is a detected event, and each column is a parameter (= feature or property) of this event. Due to the fact that the start and end times of the detected events are reported in seconds, we will multiply them with the sampling frequency for getting the starting and ending indexes of the detected events. The Visualization Component will receive these indexes and will assign a colour to the time-series. In addition, YASA provides a function, i.e., `bandpower_from_psd`, for extracting the average bandpower in specified bands from a pre-computed PSD. YASA returns a DataFrame, which will be passed in json format to the Visualization Component. Moreover, the user of the platform will be able to apply filters, including lowpass, bandpass, and highpass, to any channel. To achieve this, the SciPy library will be used. To be more precise, the `scipy.signal.butter` can be used, which receives as arguments the order of the filter, the critical frequency or frequencies, the type of the filter, the type of the output etc. and returns parameters depending on the argument passed to the output. For instance, if the output is equal to 'ba', then the numerator (b) and denominator (a) will be returned, which will be passed to the `scipy.signal.filter` for applying the filter to the data. In terms of the time-series forecasting, the `pmdarima` library will be used. More specifically, the `auto.arima` function will be exploited, since it automatically discovers the optimal order for an ARIMA model. The predictions of the `auto.arima` will be passed to the Visualization Component. Also, `auto.arima` returns the summary of the model, which will be also passed to the Visualization Component. Series' auto-correlation and partial auto-correlation can be achieved either by using the `pmdarima` library or the `statsmodels` library in Python. For the purposes of the visualizations of the electrophysiology signals, the `amCharts` library will be exploited.
- › Regarding actigraphy data analysis, the `pyActigraphy` library will be exploited, since one can read native actigraphy data files with various formats, including Actigraph (wGT3X-BT),

CamNtech (Actiwatch 4 and MotionWatch 8), and many more. Before analysing the data, spurious periods of inactivity, where the actigraph was most probably removed by the participant need to be discarded from the activity recordings. This can be achieved via this library, which automatically masks continuous periods of inactivity. After that, several variables can be calculated, including the day-to-day variance, the activity fragmentation, and the relative difference between the mean activity during the 10 most active hours and the 5 least active ones. The automatic detection of rest and activity periods can be also achieved via several approaches provided by the pyActigraphy library. Finally, pyActigraphy provides advanced signal processing functions. Results may be used for visualization purposes or further analyses.

- › With regards to the MRI processing, the NiBabel library will be exploited first, since it provides access to most neuroimaging file formats. Next, the Nilearn, Dipy, Nipype, and NLTools libraries can be used for statistical purposes and further analyses. The SciPy and OpenCV libraries can also be exploited, since they offer some general functionalities for image processing. Due to the fact that the Nipype library provides interfaces to existing neuroimaging software, including FSL, ANTs, SPM etc. it appears to be the most ideal toolkit. For instance, some of the functionalities, which are provided by these tools, are the following: undistortion, slice time correction, normalisation, smoothing, etc. In addition, NLTools can be used for identifying spikes from fMRI data. When it comes to visualization purposes, the Nilearn library appears to be the most ideal one, since it provides many functionalities for plotting, including plotting an anatomical image, an EPI glass brain visualization, statistical map, plotting Regions of Interest, etc. Plotting functions in Nilearn receive as input the data to be displayed, the name of an image output file, the display mode, the coordinated of the point where the cut is performed, and more. Nilearn supports also interactive plotting, where one can save the viewer as a stand-alone html file. This functionality renders Nilearn ideal for visualization of MRI data.
- › Regarding general statistical analyses, the SciPy, scikit-learn, and statsmodels libraries will be used. More specifically, both the SciPy and statsmodels libraries include statistical tests and correlation functions, which will be applied to the data. In terms of the multiple tests for the adjustment of the p-values, the statsmodels library will be used. In addition, scikit-learn can be used for applying dimensionality reduction techniques, i.e., PCA, t-SNE. These techniques can be used also for visualization purposes. At the same time, the scikit-learn library can be used for scaling the data before performing the analyses.

In Table 5, we present a comparative analysis of the aforementioned tools that could be used for the purposes of the analysis and visualizations of the data.

Table 5 – Data Analytics and Visualisation Tools

Tool	Features	Compatibility	Activity (Last Year)	Open-Source	Analytics	Visualisations
NumPy	Access to specific elements of the arrays. Very useful, since most data are in numpy arrays.		29,245 commits	✓	✓	
Pandas	Dataframes, imputation of missing values, apply transformations to columns/rows, merge/combine/join datasets similarly to SQL		29,078 commits	✓	✓	
DASK	Compute on arrays larger than memories, use of multiple threads or processes on a single machine, Does not implement all the functionalities provided by the Pandas library		7,026 commits	✓	✓	
SciPy	Signal Processing, including filtering, fourier transforms. Statistical tests via the stats package. Image Processing. Does not support multiple comparisons for the adjustment of the p-values.		27,422 commits	✓	✓	
Scikit-learn	Clustering methods, Dimensionality reduction techniques, methods for visualization, etc.		27,948 commits	✓	✓	
Statsmodels	Time-series analysis (ARMA, ARIMA, etc.), multiple tests for the adjustment of p-values, imputation of missing values (Multiple Imputation with Chained Equations)		14,507 commits	✓	✓	
Pmdarima	Time series analysis and forecasting. auto.arima: automatically discover the optimal order for an ARIMA model		1,047 commits	✓	✓	✓

Tool	Features	Compatibility	Activity (Last Year)	Open-Source	Analytics	Visualisations
Sktime	Time series analysis, forecasting, classification. Under development		2,323 commits	✓	✓	
Pinguin	Statistical tests. Multiple tests for the adjustment of p-values.		1,173 commits	✓	✓	
Nitime	Time series analysis of data derived by neuroimaging experiments. Spectral transforms, coherency, periodogram, etc.		1,274 commits	✓	✓	
MNE	Reads data from many formats, i.e., edf, vhdr, eeg, vmrk, etc., Functionalities for preprocessing data, i.e., filtering, repairing of artefacts, etc.	Export as HTML	16,698 commits	✓	✓	✓
YASA	Algorithms for event detection, i.e., sleep spindles/slow waves/rapid eye movements. Spectral analysis	Export predicted hypnogram and stage probabilities to text or csv with standard Python functions	326 commits	✓	✓	✓
WONAMBI	Detection of spindles and slow waves, frequency analysis, time-frequency analysis	Export channels as json	1,521 commits	✓	✓	✓
SleepPy	One can load raw accelerometer data via an input file (.bin or .csv). Extraction of sleep statistics.		70 commits	✓	✓	
PyActigraphy	Reads actigraphy data from many file formats. Detection of rest periods by applying many algorithms. Advanced signal processing techniques.		324 commits	✓	✓	

Tool	Features	Compatibility	Activity (Last Year)	Open-Source	Analytics	Visualisations
Visbrain	EEG, MEG, Fmri, signal plotting, objects animation, time-series, loading from multiple sources	Export hypnogram to png, export sleep statistics to csv, subplots can be animated and exported into a video file or images	3,898 commits	✓	✓	✓
Neuropycon	Pipelines for multiprocessing of MEG, EEG, functional and anatomical MRI.		Ephypype package: 355 commits Graphypype package: 270 commits	✓	✓	
Nilearn	Statistical and Machine Learning tools. Easy-to-read documentation with a lot of examples. A lot of plotting functions for visualising the MRI data.	Export plot as image(png, svg) and pdf	9,566 commits	✓	✓	✓
DIPY	Brain volume slicing, visualising bundles, metrics on bundles and an interface to access many capabilities of VTK		12,045 commits	✓	✓	✓
Antropy	Feature extraction from EEG data.		123 commits	✓	✓	
UK Biobank accelerometer analysis	Extraction of information from large accelerometer datasets. Process data from many file formats. Sleep/activity statistics.		854 commits	✓	✓	
PyEEG	Feature extraction from EEG data.		63 commits	✓	✓	
Eeglib	Feature extraction from EEG data		83 commits	✓	✓	
NiBabel	Read MRI data from many file formats.		5,115 commits	✓	✓	

Tool	Features	Compatibility	Activity (Last Year)	Open-Source	Analytics	Visualisations
	Limited support for DICOM.					
BIOPAC System Actigraphy	Sleep and Activity analysis				✓	
Koneksa Actigraphy	Sleep and Activity analysis				✓	
Motionware	Sleep and Activity analysis				✓	
Actiware	Analysis of data from Actiwatch models				✓	
MedPy	Read/Write/Manipulate medical images. Apply filters, transformations. Compute mutual information between two images or distance between histograms.		324 commits	✓	✓	
Scikit-image	Image processing. Does not provide algorithms and statistical analyses used in medical image processing.	Save images to files	13,106 commits	✓	✓	✓
OpenCV		Video stream, images to API	31,627 commits	✓	✓	✓
Fmriprep	fMRI data preprocessing pipeline		6,559 commits	✓	✓	
Nipype	Combine tools from various packages (FSL, ANTs, etc.), build and share workflows		14,316 commits	✓	✓	✓
NLTools	Analysis of neuroimaging data, Identification of spikes from time series data, Apply spatial smoothing, etc.		1,351 commits	✓	✓	
ActiLife	Actigraphy data analysis				✓	
FreeSurfer	MRIs		30,825 commits	✓	✓	✓
NeuroDesk	Electrophysiological data, MRI data		310 commits	✓	✓	✓
D3.js	Huge variety of charts, interactivity,		38 commits	✓		✓

Tool	Features	Compatibility	Activity (Last Year)	Open-Source	Analytics	Visualisations
	animations		99.4k stars 22.9k forks			
Chart.js	Basic Charts		500+ commits 55.5k stars 11.3k forks	✓		✓
SensorMotion	Analyse time-series, accelerometer data. contains a simple plot module for creation signal plots		No commits 56 stars 24 forks	✓		✓
PyEMD	EMD, EEMD, signal decomposition		24 commits 507 stars 167 forks	✓	✓	✓
PySurfer	Plot rgb values on brain surface, display fMRI activation and volume, plot transparent brain, generate surface labels conjunction		No commits 175 stars 91 forks	✓		✓
BrainVISA/Anatomist	Load and view objects, change camera parameters, view meshes, custom colour palettes, fusion between volumes, modular environment			✓		✓
Visualisation Toolkit (VTK)	3D rendering, image processing, visualizations of scalar, vector and tensor fields, visualization of volume data, mesh and polygon processing, image analysis for 2D, 3D images	Export to 3D model formats (GL2PS, IVE, OBJ, OOGL, RIB, VRML, POV, X3D)	2800+ commits 1.7k stars 924 forks	✓		✓
3D Slicer	Support for many types (images, segmentations, surfaces, transformations, in 2D+), MRI	ScreenCapture module, capture image sequences from slice and 3D views and export them as a	950+ commits 504 stars 229 forks	✓		✓

Tool	Features	Compatibility	Activity (Last Year)	Open-Source	Analytics	Visualisations
		sequence of images or a video file				

3.3 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND MACHINE LEARNING – COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

3.3.1 OVERVIEW

This section will analyse different Artificial Intelligence and machine learning techniques for the ideal combination of tools in our system. While our methodology distinguishes the elements to be used according to the variables available to us, Artificial Intelligence techniques are able to extend the analysis to more features as well as to greater depth. In our case, to increase the probability of choosing the right tools, we have thoroughly tested all the tools as well as their derivatives. The results are analysed below in detail for all possible scenarios.

3.3.2 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND MACHINE LEARNING TOOLS

TensorFlow[128]: is an opensource backwards-compatible platform made by Google that focused on machine learning methods and providing low-level tools and libraries for the end user. It supports execution via GPU, CPU or TPU and can be integrated with many higher-level libraries to help the development of the algorithms and it's very flexible and scalable. In medicine, TensorFlow can use 2D and 3D CNNs (Cascaded Neural Networks) for processing large medical image datasets [129].

Tensorflow's benefits:

- › Has ready-to-use pre-trained datasets
- › Provides math and linear algebra expressions
- › Analyses images, audio and text
- › Supports a wide variety toolbox with Machine Learning Algorithms
- › Provides different model types of Neural Networks

Tensorflow's limitations:

- › Architectural limitations that only allows to execute a model but not the ability to train it.
- › Lags at providing the symbolic loops for indefinite sequences.
- › Version 1 supports only NVIDIA for GPU and python for GPU programming. The updated version 2 can be used on a CPU, but TensorFlow's dependencies must be able to use version also.
- › It has low speed with respect to its competitors. It has less usability in comparison to other frameworks.

PyTorch[130]: is an open-source replacement for NumPy that can be used on Deep Learning applications. One of its key benefits is the GPU (Graphics Processing Unit) integration that can extend its potential and accelerate the process and reduce timings. PyTorch is also very easy to use with the wide variety of options it offers. It can be used by all operating systems (Linux, Mac, and Windows), can be accessed through three programming languages (Python, C++ and Java) and it can use a CPU (Central Processing

Unit) or a GPU to run the layers of a Neural Network. Finally, PyTorch uses a dynamic execution technique in a way that we can change how the network model behaves, at any given time, without starting from scratch and with almost with no delays [131].

PyTorch's Benefits:

- › End-to-End Machine Learning Tools
- › Uses torchServe to deploy PyTorch models
- › Supports multi-model serving, logging, metrics
- › Available RESTful API endpoints
- › Native support for asynchronous execution

PyTorch's Limitations:

- › PyTorch is very new to the research field and lack the high variety of features and the community that supports it is not highly developed. Also, it lacks the monitoring and visualization features that other solution, like TensorFlow, support.

Keras[132]: is a high-level Deep Learning API that extends TensorFlow, initially developed for fast Deep Learning experimentation. It is used by many big tech companies, and it's created to be user friendly and easy to integrate. It, also, supports execution with all possible ways (GPU, CPU or TPU) and provides pre-trained models such as (Xception, VGG16, VGG19, ResNet, ResNetV2, InceptionV3, InceptionResNetV2, MobileNet, MobileNetV2, DenseNet and NASNet) [133][134]

On the other hand, the main limitation of Keras is that it cannot support low-level modification of the system, as it's not designed to do so and if an error occurs it may be hard to debug and overcome. Finally, although it supports a lot of features, it lacks some other Machine Learning features like Clustering and PCA (Principal Component Analysis).

Keras's benefits:

- › API-designed Machine Learning tools
- › Tailored for Deep Learning applications
- › Used also in:
 - Computer Vision (image analysis, etc.)
 - Natural Language Processing
 - Structured Data Classification
 - Timeseries
 - Audio processing
 - Reinforcement Learning
 - Graph Neural Networks

Keras's limitations:

- › Using Keras you can face low-level backend errors continuously.
- › It is slow on GPU and takes longer time in computation compared with its backends.
- › Keras does not support features of dynamic chart creation.

NiBabel: is a library created by NIPY, a community of practice devoted to the use of the Python programming language in the analysis of neuroimaging data, and can provide read and write access to a variety of medical file formats, including ANALYZE (plain, SPM99, SPM2 and later), GIFTI, NiftI1, NiftI2, CIFTI-2, MINC1, MINC2, AFNI BRIK/HEAD, MGH and ECAT as well as Philips PAR/REC.

NiBabel's benefits:

- › Used to analyse neuroimaging data
- › Provide read / write access to a variety of medical formats:
 - ANALYZE (plain, SPM99, SPM2 and later)
 - GIFTI
 - NiftI1 and NiftI2
 - CIFTI-2
 - MINC1 and MINC2
 - AFNI BRIK/HEAD
 - MGH
 - ECAT
 - Philips PAR/REC

NiBabel's limitations:

- › Small capabilities and features
- › Steep learning curve while it has a small community supporting it

CEML: stands for Counterfactuals for Explaining Machine Learning models and is a Python toolbox for computing counterfactuals. Counterfactuals can be used to explain the predictions of machine learning models. This toolbox supports many a variety of machine learning frameworks like scikit-learn, PyTorch, Keras and Tensorflow. Furthermore, CEML is easy to use and can be extended and integrated very easily.

CEML's benefits:

- › Toolbox for computing counterfactuals
- › Used to explain the predictions of Machine Learning Models

- › Displays statistics for model optimisations
- › Integrated with Tensorflow, scikit-learn, PyTorch and Keras

CEML's limitations:

- › It doesn't have a detailed documentation and support for possible problems.

Clinica: is a software platform for clinical research studies involving patients with neurological and psychiatric diseases and the acquisition of multimodal data, most often with longitudinal follow-up. This tool works as a command-line driven and written in complete Python language. It supports a various integration with Nipype system for pipelining and combines widely used software packages for neuroimaging data analysis like FreeSurfer, FSL, PETPVC, SPM, ANTs, Scikit-learn and the BIDS standard for data organisation. Clinica can provide tools that convert publicly available neuroimaging datasets into BIDS (ADNI, AIBL, NIFD, OASIS, OASIS-3 etc.).

Clinica can process any BIDS-compliant dataset with a set of complex processing pipelines involving different software packages for the analysis of neuroimaging data. This tool can also provide integration between feature extraction and statistics, machine learning or deep learning.

Clinica's features:

- › Neuroimaging data analysis
- › Anatomical MRI
- › Diffusion MRI
- › PET
- › Statistical analysis
- › Machine learning
- › Data management made easy:
- › Standardised data structures for inputs
- › Standardised data structures for outputs
- › Conversion of datasets into BIDS (ADNI, AIBL, NIFD, OASIS, OASIS-3, etc.)

Theano: is a Python library that allows you to define, optimise, and efficiently evaluate mathematical expressions involving multi-dimensional arrays. Theano can have a tight integration with NumPy, can perform data-intensive computations up to 140x faster than on a CPU, can compute derivatives for functions of one or many inputs. Furthermore, can avoid a lot of bugs when computing expressions such as $\log(1+\exp(x))$ for large values of x , evaluate expressions faster and include detecting, plus diagnosing bugs or potential problems.

Theano's Features:

- › Define, Optimise and Evaluate mathematical expressions
- › Can process multi-dimensional arrays
- › Based on NumPy and accelerates its performance on CPU-based computations
- › Provides numerical stability when computes “heavy” expressions on large dataset

SNNTorch: is designed to be intuitively used with a variety of tools like PyTorch, as though each spiking neuron were simply another activation a sequence of layers. All spiking neuron classes are available to be used as activation units with PyTorch. Each of them, consists of an agnostic type to fully connected layers, convolutional layer, residual connections and more. The requirements of snntorch enable small and large networks to be viably trained on CPU when needed. The libraries that snntorch uses take advantage of GPU acceleration in the same way as PyTorch. The default use of PyTorch is unable to calculate the analytical derivative of the spiking neuron graph that is how snntorch overrides the default gradient, using the appropriate methods. The neurons available in snntorch are variants of the LEaky Integrate-and-Fire neuron model:

- › **Leaky** - 1st-Order Leaky Integrate-and-Fire Neuron
- › **Synaptic** - 2nd-Order Integrate-and-Fire Neuron (including synaptic conductance)
- › **Lapicque** - Lapicque’s RC Neuron Model
- › **Alpha** - Alpha Membrane Model

SNNTorch’s Features:

- › Simulates Spiking Neural Networks using PyTorch
- › Apply deep learning, gradient descent, backpropagation, and neuroscience to biologically plausible Spiking Neural Networks

BindsNET: A Python package used for simulating spiking neural networks (SNNs) on CPUs or GPUs using PyTorch Tensor functionality. BindsNET is a spiking neural network simulation library geared towards the development of biologically inspired algorithms for machine learning.

BindsNET’s Features:

- › Simulates Spiking Neural Networks using PyTorch
- › Used to develop biologically inspired algorithms for ML

MXNet: is an open-source python library designed for providing both efficiency and flexibility when developing deep learning frameworks. MXNet contains a dynamic dependency scheduler that automatically parallelises both symbolic and imperative operations on the fly. A graph optimisation layer on top of that makes symbolic execution fast and memory efficient. MXNet is portable and lightweight, scalable to many GPUs and machines (ref: <https://mxnet.apache.org>).

MxNet's Features:

- › Open-source deep learning framework
- › Scalable distributed training
- › Provides performance optimisation
- › Can be extended in computer vision, NLP, time series (and more) through 3rd party tools
 - D2L.ai
 - GluonCV
 - GluonNLP
 - GluonTS

SurPRISE: is a python library that depends on numpy and it's used for creating recommender systems. It is very good at handling datasets either the ones already build in, or custom ones the users may load. It, also, supports many predicting and neighboring algorithms and it can measure and analyse each algorithms performance.

SurPRISE's limitation may be that it's focused on movie recommendations and a rating system based on user input for each specific movie.

SurPRISE's Features:

- › Depends on NumPy
- › Used to create Recommender Systems
- › Supports Predicting and Neighbouring algorithms
- › Focuses on Rating Systems (mainly on movies)

Alibi Explain: is an open-source python library that assists with the monitoring and explaining of black-box and white-box ML models, and it can also expose local and global explanation methods for classification and regression models. Alibi provides a set of algorithms or methods known as explainers. Each explainer provides insight about a model. The set of insights available given a trained model is dependent on several factors. For instance, if the model is a regression model it makes sense to ask how the prediction varies for some regressor. Whereas it doesn't make sense to ask what minimal change is required to obtain a new class prediction.

Alibi's Features:

- › Open source
- › Can be integrated by all implementations
- › Provide high quality reference implementations of black-box ML model explanation algorithms

- › Support multiple use cases (e.g., tabular, text and image data classification, regression)
- › Provide a variety of ML model monitoring and interpretation methods.

Captum: is an open-source python module for explaining the ML models provided by PyTorch. Captum allows researchers to quickly benchmark their work against other existing algorithms available in the library. For model developers, Captum can be used to improve and troubleshoot models by facilitating the identification of different features that contribute to a model’s output to design better models and troubleshoot unexpected model outputs.

Captum’s Features:

- › Open source
- › Can be integrated with PyTorch
- › Provides a wide variety of gradient-based and perturbation algorithms
- › Provides visualizations
- › Provides ML model debugging and insights.

3.3.2.1 Overview

Table 6 – Artificial Intelligence Tools

Tool	Documentation	Activity	Open source	Ease of use
TensorFlow	Well	Active	Yes	Medium
PyTorch	Well	Active	Yes	Easy
Keras	Well	Active	Yes	Easy
Nipy/NiBabel	Well	Inactive (Last change 28 Noe 2020)	Yes	Easy
CEML	Good	Moderate	Yes	Medium
Clinica	Good	Active	Yes	Medium
Theano	Good	Archaic	Yes	Medium
SnnTorch	Good	Active	Yes	Medium
BindsNET	Good	Moderate	Yes	Easy
MXNet	Well	Active	Yes	Medium
SurPRISE	Good	Inactive	Yes	Difficult
Alibi Explain	Well	Active	Yes	Easy
Captum	Well	Active	Yes	Easy

[135], [136]

4 REQUIREMENTS' ELABORATION

The present section elaborates on the system requirements defining and coding the description. Integration aspects referring to Advanced Analytics components and the MES-CoBraD Platform are also reported.

4.1 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

Table 7- Expert System requirements

Code		ES-1
Title	Expert System	
User Facing	Yes	
User Roles	Clinician	
Priority	Must have	
Description and Rationale	The system shall provide an Expert System to guide clinical decisions by providing feedback from both patients and clinicians.	

Code		ES-2
Title	Flexible steps sequence within processes	
User Facing	Yes	
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician	
Priority	Should have	
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow for flexibility of relations of priority and posteriority between steps in processes.	

Code		ES-3
Title	Visualization per Step of DSS/ES output	
User Facing	Yes	
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician	
Priority	Must have	
Description and Rationale	The system shall provide to the user the ability to have a visual comprehension of the posterior probabilities of the proposed next step(s) - cutoff for highest probability next steps, for each decision(s) the ES makes.	

Code		ES-4
------	--	------

Title	User control over next step(s) of DSS/ES
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow the user to choose the next step (from the list or outside it), depending on options provided in Visualization per Step of DSS/ES output.

Code	ES-5
Title	Coordination aide module - scheduling
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Could have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow the coordinator/user to be informed of upcoming steps (e.g., scheduling a specific participant, or calling someone), based on the pilot protocol process of a study.

Code	ES-6
Title	Coordination aide module - progress/monitoring
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Could have
Description and Rationale	The system shall provide feedback on the progress of recruited participants and participants performing various tests.

Code	ES-7
Title	Option for randomisation of participants into an intervention
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Could have
Description and Rationale	The system shall randomise participants into an intervention.

Code	ES-8
Title	Developer tool - Protocols
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow to create a flow of actions that reflect a protocol (e.g., PUC1) including timelines, processes. Harmonised protocols can be achieved within and across sites, and ES can identify types of variables present (or missing), to pursue recommendations and analyses.

Code	ES-9
Title	Visualize flow of actions
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow to visualize flow of actions that reflect the protocol.

Code	ES-10
Title	Observed and latent variables
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The ES shall be able to consider / use both simple / observed and complex / latent decision variables.

Code	ES-11
Title	Selection and execution analytical processes
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow the user to create a workflow in which every step will have a function for performing a specific analysis task from modules/packages analysis.

Code	ES-12
Title	UI for selecting analytical processes
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow the user to create a workflow in which every step will have a function for performing a specific analysis task from modules/packages analysis.

Code	ES-13
Title	ES - Guided steps
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician, Caregiver, Patient
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall permit the user to be informed by the ES on the next recommended diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the ES at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct on accessing missing variables. Each task will be categorised and will allow to use metadata information for better future recommendations.

Code	ES-14
Title	Automated report/message generator
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician, Patient
Priority	Could have
Description and Rationale	The system shall generate a report either for feedback to the patient or for use by a clinician, based on the data entered in a specific function.

Code	ES-15
Title	Communicate with patients at key times
User Facing	Yes

User Roles	Scientist / Clinician, Patient
Priority	Would be nice
Description and Rationale	The system shall ensure communication with patients at key times.

Code	ES-16
Title	Diagnostic Guidelines Reference Links
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall permit to introduce diagnostic guideline libraries in the Platform for being referenced against by the ES in making possible diagnoses.

Code	ES-17
Title	Therapeutic Guidelines
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow to introduce specific recommended therapies according to specific diagnoses / phenotypes, so when using the platform, the user will be informed if a specific therapy can be considered.

Code	ES-18
Title	Labelling each task
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Would be nice
Description and Rationale	Each task will be labelled based of each feature to know how to structure it. This is a support feature to help you run the application better while using a tool of the ES.

Code	ES-19
Title	Create and manage interactive forms

User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	Build and edit forms that will introduce new ways of data manipulation and provide input on possible missing data.

Code	ES-20
Title	Metadata collection
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	Each task, process and executable in general should keep metadata for later process use, accordingly, to its type (statistical analysis, evaluation, etc.).

Code	ES-21
Title	Workflow / task duplication
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician, Caregiver
Priority	Could have
Description and Rationale	Each workflow should keep data of every workflow with the same variables when created to duplicate or transfer data.

Code	ES-22
Title	Unique identification of each process
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Would be nice
Description and Rationale	Each task and each process should have a unique id, followed by a folder / DB / storage that allows for a “process workspace” to exchange data globally and/or use specific data as input/output

4.2 QUERY BUILDER

Table 8 - Query Builder Requirement

Code	QRB-1
Title	Query Builder
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician/
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow to create an SQL Query taking as input data in JSON format. The current Query Builder works only with tabular data. It should be heavily extended to support health data for the project.

4.3 DATA ANALYTICS

Table 9 - Data Analytics Requirements

Code	DAN-1
Title	Time-Series Analysis
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The DAN Component will retrieve data from the Data Lake via the QRB Component. The purpose of the DAN-1 component is to develop models that best capture or describe an observed time series, in order to understand the underlying causes. To achieve this, the user will be able to select via the UI the algorithms to be applied to the time-series data. Examples include amongst others the short-time Fourier Transform (STFT), Discrete Wavelet Transform, etc. The user may be able to apply ARMA models to the time-series data for predicting future patient data. The system shall be able also to apply algorithms to actigraphy data. Results of the introduced approaches will be transferred to the VDS component for visualization or to the ML component for further analysis.

Code	DAN-2
Title	Posterior probabilities of next steps
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall calculate posterior probabilities of proposed next steps.

Code	DAN-3
Title	Option for randomisation of participants into an intervention
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/Clinician
Priority	Would be nice
Description and Rationale	Firstly, the DAN Component will retrieve the datasets from the Data Lake via the Query Builder. Then, the DAN-3 Component will apply a function, e.g., random, to the dataset, so that the participants in the datasets be randomised.

Code	DAN-4
Title	Support ES- Guided steps
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Clinician – Scientist, Patient/Caregiver
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall permit the user to be informed by the ES on the next recommended diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the ES at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct on accessing missing variables.

Code	DAN-5
Title	Recommend analyses' types
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have

Description and Rationale	The Data Analytics Component shall retrieve data from the Data Lake via the QRB Component. Next, the user will have the capability via the UI to choose which statistical function should be applied to the data, depending on the available ones based on the input data. This functionality will be provided to the user at the stage of data distribution (DAN-14), analysing the data (DAN-1), and Exploratory Data Analysis (DAN-12).
----------------------------------	--

Code	DAN-6
Title	Selection of cases based on inclusion and exclusion criteria
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow to select cases based on inclusion and exclusion criteria (upon performing an analysis, select whom you will study based on x, y, z criteria).

Code	DAN-7
Title	Data manipulation plug-ins
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Would be nice
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow scientists to install plug-ins that would provide black box functionalities offered by the community.

Code	DAN-8
Title	Integrate Opensource modules for EEG/PSG, but also MRI data
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The Data Analytics Component will retrieve the

data from the Data Lake using the QRB Component. Then, for each stage of the analysis, i.e., DAN-1, DAN-14, and more, the Data Analytics Component will include opensource libraries for analysing the data.

Code	DAN-11
Title	Generation of a report as output
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The Data Analytics Component will retrieve data from the Data Lake via the QRB Component. Next, at each stage of applying algorithms for analysing and processing the data, the Data Analytics Component should be able to save which programming language, i.e., Python, MATLAB, R, etc. and library, i.e., SciPy, Nilearn, MNE, etc. was used for conducting the respective experiments. Finally, after the user has completed all the analyses, the system shall be able to export a file, which will include the programming language and the libraries used for each specific analysis.

Code	DAN-12
Title	Support for Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The Data Analytics Component will retrieve data from the Data Lake via the QRB component. Next, the DAN will provide to the user the functionality of the Exploratory Data Analysis. Specifically, there will be an option in the User Interface (UI), where the user will be able to apply statistical functions, i.e., maximum, minimum, standard deviation, etc. to a specific column. Also, the DAN shall be able to apply correlations between columns, including the Pearson, Point-Biserial correlation, etc. Results of the EDA will be passed to the VDS component.

Code	DAN-13
Title	MRI Analysis
User Facing	No
User Roles	Scientist/Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The DAN Component will retrieve data from the Data Lake via the QRB Component. The purpose of the DAN-13 component is to provide algorithms for the MRI analysis. For instance, the user will be able to apply GLM to MRI data. Results of the introduced approaches will be transferred to the VDS component for visualization or to the ML component for further analysis.

4.4 HYPOTHESIS TESTING INTERFACE

Hypothesis testing is a Data Analytics interface.

Code	DAN-9
Title	Traits for steps in a process - selection of variables by class
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall permit while examining if a hypothesis can be rejected, then select one or more sets of variables according to the "class they have.

Code	DAN-10
Title	Hypothesis development and testing - High level associations
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have

Description and Rationale	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. DAN shall be able to retrieve data sets through the QRB (which retrieves datasets from the Data Lake). 2. DAN shall, additionally, receive specific input parameters determined by the user (e.g., statistical test selected, test's significance level defined). 3. DAN shall be able to apply a specific statistical test upon the retrieved data and conclude. 4. The data samples retrieved and involved in the test shall be also visualised through the VDS, in a way that the result is visually comprehensible to the user, indicating the critical parameters of the test. 5. All the parameters of the test (including users' parameters) shall be stored back in the data lake. This data will be used as an input to the DAN reporting module (DAN-11).
---------------------------	--

Code	DAN-14
Title	Applying methods that define data distribution
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The Data analytics component will retrieve data from the Data Lake. The purpose of the DAN-14 component is to apply methods, which define the data distribution, i.e., normality, homoscedasticity. The result of each method can be transferred to the VDS component. This component will help the clinician identify the optimal method per hypothesis.

4.5 DATA AND RESULTS VISUALISATION

Table 10 - Data and Results Visualisation requirements

Code	VDS-1
Title	Visualization Dashboards

User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician/ Patient/ Caregiver
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall store data collected from heterogenous outside data sources (RWD) and from outputs of the system in Data Lake solution.

Code	VDS-2
Title	Data visualization - time series
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall display time series (e.g., actigraphy data, wearable data, eeg) of n number of variables through bars or lines (x axis for time, y for metric)

Code	VDS-3
Title	Data visualization - interface - select data
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow to highlight a part of a graph that it's to be labelled. (Depending on the label data the user may decide what to do with it. This could be for example a period in a time series, a point in a scatterplot.)

Code	VDS-4
Title	Data visualization - interface - label data
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Should have

Description and Rationale	<p>The system shall allow user after selecting a part of a time series, as described in VDS-3, to be able to label the data, i.e. associate a text to the selection.</p> <p>Steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Write text in a field 2. Associate text with selection as it's described in VDS-3
----------------------------------	--

Code	VDS-5
Title	Data visualization - visualize patient data
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow the scientist to query all the data available from the patient in order to view them in dashboard.

Code	VDS-6
Title	Aggregate patient data visualization
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall permit to visualize aggregates of patient data in the visualization dashboard

Code	VDS-7
Title	Time-Series Analysis output visualization
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system shall display the results of time series analysis.

Code	VDS-8
-------------	--------------

Title	Data manipulation plug-ins
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist/ Clinician
Priority	Would be nice
Description and Rationale	The system shall allow scientists to install plug-ins that would provide black box functionalities offered by the community.

4.6 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Table 11 - Artificial Intelligence requirements

Code	AI-1
Title	Machine Learning based analysis of data lake
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system must use Machine Learning technique for delivering added value and analysis to data from data lake

Code	AI-2
Title	Machine Learning as a service via an open API
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Must have
Description and Rationale	The system has to offer Machine learning as a Service capability provided by a dedicated and Open API-based platform.

Code	AI-3
Title	AI based natural language processing
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Could have
Description and Rationale	The system shall include an open-source algorithm/platform (previously developed on the FITMAN project) which shall analyse natural

	language (via natural language processing) coming from social media content using techniques/algorithms like machine learning, sentiment analysis, correlation mining.
--	--

Code	AI-4
Title	AI based natural language processing reports
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist
Priority	Could have
Description and Rationale	The system shall produce customisable / configurable reports, dashboards and visualizations based on NLP analysis

Code	AI-5
Title	AI based process optimisation
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall optimise process steps sequences in Expert System based on prior information about steps effectiveness.

Code	AI-6
Title	Posterior probabilities of next steps
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall calculate posterior probabilities of proposed next steps.

Code	AI-7
Title	Support ES - Guided steps
User Facing	Yes
User Roles	Scientist / Clinician, Caregiver, Patient
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall permit the user to be informed

	by the ES on the next recommended diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the ES at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct on accessing missing variables.
--	---

Code	AI-8
Title	Input metadata parsing
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system can provide a parsing mechanism for given user input (e.g. the user, or even a workflow task can provide analysis metadata - if the expected input is CSD).

Code	AI-9
Title	Input data analysis / categorisation
User Facing	No
User Roles	None
Priority	Should have
Description and Rationale	The system shall be able to analyse and categorise input data to Single/Multiple Variable or Complex Data

4.7 INTEGRATION

The integration is an important aspect of the system. For this reason, we have developed in D7.1, as part of the architecture description, the integration View of the system.

Open standards and protocols are used for all components placed in the system both in terms of development and ease of use. The usage of open standards is the main enabler to the integration of all components.

4.7.1 ADVANCED ANALYTICS COMPONENTS' INTEGRATION

The integration of Advanced Analytics components is based on:

The usage of containers to host the components, and the placement of containers in an orchestrated environment run by Kubernetes.

The definition of communication protocols between components using open protocols. REST API and JSON format for data will be used in this perspective.

4.7.2 ADVANCED ANALYTICS AND MES-COBRA D PLATFORM INTEGRATION

All the components of Advanced Analytics will be placed as orchestrated containers in the overall architecture of the system.

Their integration will be considered on several layers of the system:

At the base layer, they will be placed in the same network defined by container orchestration.

At orchestration layer (Kubernetes) they will be part of the same Kubernetes setup.

At persistence layer they will all use the Data Lake.

At communication level, they will follow the same standard protocols to exchange data.

At function level, they will be placed on business flows, in relation with all the other components

At business level, they all will contribute to reach the project objectives.

The components will interact with external components thru Data Sharing Mechanism

5 ADVANCED ANALYTICS ARCHITECTURE

This section provides the overall architecture of the advanced analytics components and workflow management. Different features are presented as: UI Process Designer, Process Executor, Task Optimiser, Process Optimiser. The Query Builder serves as a connecting role in the MES-CoBraD ecosystem. Data Lake Interface specifications and Query Builder Modules providing also visualizations are reported.

5.1 OVERALL ARCHITECTURE

Advanced Analytics components are placed in the overall architecture of the system as containers managed by Kubernetes. The containers will be orchestrated as other containers part of the overall architecture.

The Advanced Analytics has an important place in the whole system, as presented in the next figure

Figure 20 - MES-CoBraD Architecture

5.2 COMPONENTS

5.2.1 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

Expert System is a set of tools that provide the ability for the end user to execute dynamically created processes and create potentially unlimited workflows.

The Expert System will be executed on a closed dockerised environment (i.e., uses the Docker² container platform), uses the python³ programming language and the Django⁴ web framework.

The Expert system contains a variety of tools and libraries based in python packages, that can manage workflows, workflow designer tools to create BPMN dynamic diagrams and other components that can be implemented via JSON standards.

² <https://www.docker.com/>

³ <https://www.python.org/>

⁴ <https://www.djangoproject.com/>

5.2.1.1 Task Manage

The Task Manager component can create, update, and delete tasks from the data collected. Every task can have multiple instances, including forms, third-party applications, or AI algorithm services.

This function provides different features, such as task creation with the ability for a user to create tasks and the corresponding integration “drivers”. Each task has a predefined structured input received by the previous or the initial step and produces an explicitly defined output for exchange with the following one.

- › As mentioned previously, each task will represent a specific function that will be executed when the workflow gets at that stage and all the available functions will be available for the user to select.
- › If the task executes an AI algorithmic process, then the corresponding Artificial Intelligence module (ref: chapter 5.5.5 Artificial Intelligence) is solely responsible for parsing the data and executes the algorithm.
- › If the task executes an API integration, then the call is made given the data input and the output is parsed to be harmonised.
- › The task executes a form or a data manipulation “engine”.

Furthermore, the capability for task view, task update and task delete is available.

5.2.1.2 Workflow Manager

Workflow Manager is the function that handles all workflow related features. Workflow is a set of tasks that may follow the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) specification and provides the end users the capability of executing any process that follows or resembles a protocol streamlines their work.

This function provides different features, such as the UI Process Designer which includes is a Graphical User Interface exposed on web that creates workflows with simple interactive tools.

The Process Executor which is a function tightly connected with a user interface and a backend service that handles the connection between the user and the work process. The created BPMN, or Non-BPMN workflow can be initiated by the user and each task is executed using the logic operators.

The Task Optimiser which is responsible for controlling the metadata of previous and next executed tasks and collect timeseries data that makes statistical analysis on each task and optimise its performance. It will, also, be connected to the therapeutic / diagnostic guideline and rule system to assist and generate next-task recommendations.

Finally, the Process Optimiser function which is responsible for controlling the metadata of executed workflows and collect timeseries data that makes statistical analysis on each task and optimise its performance (accuracy, timings, status, etc.).

5.2.2 QUERY BUILDER

5.2.2.1 Design and functionalities

Figure 21 – Query Builder Component diagram

Query Builder Sub-components

This component will provide endpoints for the creation as well as the execution of SQL queries. The component diagram of Query Builder is depicted in Figure 21.

Query Request Ingest

The Query Builder will receive GET HTTP Requests, in which there will be parameters that will define the desired SQL query in JSON format

Query Creator

The body of the request will include information about the table name, the selected column names, the aggregation functions, the limit, etc. The Query Builder will support all the basic SQL commands, such as SELECT, GROUP BY, ORDER BY, JOIN and all the aggregation functions (SUM, AVG, MAX, MIN, COUNT). Given the input, the Query Builder will construct the desired SQL query.

Query Executor

Afterwards, the Query Executor will communicate with the Data Lake, gathering the data from the respective buckets, and will execute the SQL query in order to retrieve/get the wanted data. As a final step, the Query Executor will return the extracted data to the component that made the request.

5.2.2.2 Technologies and Tools

The Query Builder will be developed using the FastAPI (Python-based Framework).

5.2.2.3 Interfaces

The interfaces specified in Figure 21 refer to the communication between the Query Builder component and the rest components in MES-CoBraD. Query Builder shall provide its results to other components (e.g. Data Analytics, Data Results and Visualisation components) but the coordination of such actions shall be done through the workflow manager of the expert system. These indirect communication channels are not included in this diagram.

The interfaces applicable to the Query Builder component, are:

- **QB.I.01: Data Lake Interface**
This interface allows the Query Builder component a) to retrieve datasets from the Data Lake for further processing and b) to save the results of the dataset processing in order to create a new dataset.
 - **Interface provider:** Data Lake component
 - **Input:** datasets;
 - **Output:** New dataset.
- **QB.I.02: Expert System Interface**
This interface allows the Query Builder component a) to send metadata of a dataset needed by the Task Manager to be used in a step in the BPMN builder or b) to send datasets specified by the metadata during an instance of the BPMN to be further used in other components.
 - **Interface provider:** Query Builder component
 - **Input:** Query request;
 - **Output:** datasets, dataset configuration data, or metadata.
- **QB.I.03: User Access Control System Interface**
This interface allows the Query Builder component to verify the identity of the user and whether they have access to the information they aim to query.
 - **Interface provider:** User Access Control System component
 - **Input:** not applicable;
 - **Output:** Keycloak tool metadata.

5.2.2.4 Performance Indicators

Response time: between the moment a new query is requested and the time when the SQL query is sent to the Data Lake, i.e. the maximum time duration: 1.000 ms.

Parallel Requests: number of parallel query building processes, i.e. the minimum parallel instances: 10

5.2.3 DATA ANALYTICS

5.2.3.1 Design and functionalities

The Data Analytics component will be used to implement statistical data analysis and hypothesis testing, analysis of time-series data, and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) image analysis. This multi-purpose analytics service will provide the end-users (scientists - clinicians) the ability to analyse patients' data, develop insights about patients' health conditions and implement scientific research formulating hypotheses.

When performing an analysis, it will be possible to select the cases in which the analysis will be performed, based on some inclusion and exclusion criteria. Following the completion of an analysis, the module will be able to generate a detailed report, which shall include a variety of information on how the analysis was performed (e.g., the method that was used, the version of the programming language, the version of the pipeline/package).

Figure 22 – Advanced Analytics Component diagram

Data Analytics Sub-components

The component diagram of the Advanced Analytics component is depicted in , which includes the following sub-components:

Time series pre-processing

The Advanced Analytics module will provide algorithms for processing time series data, i.e., electroencephalogram (EEG), polysomnography (PSG) data, etc.

Depending on the format of the data the appropriate library will be utilised, as it is presented in 3.2.4.

Time series analysis

When it comes to the analysis, time-series analysis and forecasting methods will be provided. Autoregressive integrated moving average model (ARIMA) constitutes an example, which is implemented via the library named *pmdarima* in Python. Also, spectral analysis via Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), Discrete Wavelet Decomposition (DWT), etc. are necessary and implemented in most open-source

libraries. The Advanced Analytics component will also provide algorithms for actigraphy data analysis, including the detection of rest periods, the implementation of advanced signal processing functions, and many more.

MRI pre-processing

The Advanced Analytics component will provide algorithms for processing MRI data. In case images are in *dicom* format, the component will enable the conversion into *nifty* files, if necessary, since this format is used by most libraries/tools.

MRI Analysis

The general linear model (GLM) can be implemented through the Advanced Analytics component. The GLM is used for making inferences about brain responses in a single subject. Also, the GLM can be used for making inferences about the group (second-level or group analysis). The available algorithms are presented in Section 3.2.4.

Statistical Analysis

The Advanced Analytics module will contain a series of statistical packages, which include functions that can be used in the analysis process. The focus of this component will be to provide interpretability of the data. For this purpose, methods for investigating the data, analysing the relationship between variables (e.g., correlation, regression algorithms) and processing datasets for identifying individual data points associations (e.g., clustering techniques) will be applied.

Hypothesis Testing

A specific Hypothesis Testing module will be created as part of the Advanced Analytics component development. This module will serve the requirements of clinical researchers to examine their research questions and investigate statistical differences in patients' sample data. The end-users will be able to formulate their hypotheses and evaluate them, using several statistical tests, proving if they can be accepted or not. Based on the assumptions and the purpose of each statistical test, several parametric (e.g., t-test, ANOVA, z-test) and non-parametric (e.g., Chi-squared test, Mann-Whitney U test, Wilcoxon signed-rank test) methods will be employed. Also, methods to adjust the p-values for multiple comparisons will be provided. The Hypothesis testing module is powered by the Advanced Analytics module using most of its tools and capabilities.

5.2.3.2 *Technologies and Tools*

The Data Analytics will be also implemented in FastAPI. FastAPI is a modern and fast (high-performance) web framework for building APIs with Python 3.6+

Various Python libraries will be used for the analysis of the data.

5.2.3.3 *Interfaces*

The interfaces specified in

refer to the communication between the Data Analytics component and the rest components in MES-CoBraD. Data Analytics processes depend on other components (e.g. Query Builder, Data Results and Visualisation components) but the coordination of such actions shall be done through the workflow

manager of the expert system. These indirect communication channels are not included in this diagram.

The interfaces applicable to the Data Analytics component, are:

- **AA.I.01: Expert System**

This interface allows the Data Analytics component a) to send metadata needed by the Task Manager to specify the details of a single step in the BPMN builder and b) to receive the metadata necessary to execute an action, as specified in the Task Manager of the Expert System. After the completion of the action, the results of the analysis along with any relevant metadata are returned to the Workflow Manager.

- **Interface provider:** Data Analytics component
- **Input:** Task Manager request;
- **Output:** Analysis configuration data, Analytics results, metadata.

- **AA.I.02: User Access Control System Interface**

This interface allows the Data Analytics component to verify the identity, role and access rights of the user that uses the module.

- **Interface provider:** User Access Control System component
- **Input:** Not applicable;
- **Output:** Keycloak tool metadata.

- **AA.I.03: DataLake Interface**

This interface allows the Data Analytics component a) to retrieve datasets/objects from the Data Lake for further processing and b) to save the results of the dataset/objects processing in order to create a new dataset.

- **Interface provider:** Data Lake component
- **Input:** datasets, objects;
- **Output:** New dataset or new objects.

5.2.3.4 *Performance Indicators*

Response time: between the moment a new analysis is requested and the time when the result is sent to the Expert System, i.e. the maximum time duration: 1.000 ms.

Parallel Requests: number of parallel analysis processes, i.e. the minimum parallel instances: 10

5.2.4 DATA AND RESULTS VISUALISATION

5.2.4.1 *Design and functionalities*

The Data and Results Visualisation component will provide plots, visualisations and dashboards to facilitate the exploration of the results of the Query Builder and the Advanced Analytics components. It will help clinicians develop insights about patients' condition and based on these, take the appropriate actions.

Figure 23 – Data and Results Visualisation Component diagram

Data and Results Visualisation Sub-components

The modules that formulate the Data and Results Visualisation component and its functionalities are depicted in Figure 23.

Data Parser

The resulting incoming data from the components we mentioned previously, will be available as a dashlet that the user can insert into a customisable dashboard.

Statistical Analysis – MRI – Timeseries Visualisation

The workflow will let the user choose the type of visualisation (simple chart of values, barchart, lineplot, etc) and the settings that will be used for this visualisation (range, axes, etc). Then, there will be an option to add the visualisation to the dashboard where the user can do various other actions (change titles, rearrange dashlets, etc) and another option for saving the visualisation.

5.2.4.2 Technologies and Tools

The Data and Results Visualisation module will be implemented using the FastAPI framework.

AmCharts (JavaScript-based library) will be used for the needs of more general visualisations (e.g. time-series data). It is especially useful as it offers a wide variety of visualisations and provides interactivity out of the box.

React (JavaScript library) is a declarative, efficient, and flexible JavaScript library for building user interfaces. It can compose complex UIs from small and isolated pieces of code called “components”. The design of simple views for each state in MES-CoBraD will enhance application’s responsiveness by letting only the relevant components be efficiently updated and rendered when data changes.

Various Python libraries will also be used for visualising scientific data (EEG, MEG, MRI, etc) and offer statistical analysis visualisations. Some examples of these libraries are Nilearn, Visbrain and MNE-Python.

5.2.4.3 Interfaces

The interfaces specified in Figure 23 refer to the communication between the Data Results and Visualisation component and the rest components in MES-CoBraD. Data Results and Visualisation functionalities depend on other components (e.g. Query Builder, Data Analytics components) but the coordination of such actions shall be done through the workflow manager of the expert system. These indirect communication channels are not included in this diagram.

The interfaces applicable to the Data and Results Visualisation component, are:

- **V.I.01: Expert System**
This interface allows the Data and Results Visualisation component a) to send metadata of visualisations needed by the Task Manager to be used in a step in the BPMN builder and b) to send visualisations to be displayed during an instance of a BPM step.
 - **Input:** Task Manager request;
 - **Output:** Visualisation configuration data, Visualisations, metadata.
- **AA.I.02: User Access Control System Interface**
This interface allows the Data and Results Visualisation component to verify the identity, role and access rights of the user that uses the module.
 - **Interface provider:** User Access Control System component
 - **Input:** Not applicable;
 - **Output:** Keycloak tool metadata.

5.2.4.4 Performance Indicators

Performance indicators shall be included in the next iteration of D6.1 in order to encapsulate better Users’ preferences on each different case.

5.2.5 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The Artificial Intelligence System is an autonomous service which consists of a series of sub-system services for providing data analysis. Analyses the input data, checks for execution options and finally executes the desired algorithm.

The AI System will be executed on a closed containerised environment (i.e. uses the Kubernetes container platform), uses the python⁵ ⁶Django python package.

The Artificial Intelligence system will, also, integrate the following tools which have been reviewed and

⁵ <https://www.docker.com/>

⁶ <https://www.python.org/>

qualified so far:

- > TensorFlow
- > PyTorch
- > Keras
- > Alibi Explain
- > Captum

All data exchanges between functions and features will be JSON compliant.

5.2.5.1 *Analyse data*

This function, the input data is analysed by type and separated based on Single Variable Data (SVD), Multi Variable Data (MVD) and Complex Structured Data (CSD).

5.2.5.2 *Parse options*

This function checks any parameters given during input initialisation. The parameters will be specified and will delimit the available solutions when selecting an algorithm. All the parameters that is used its, speed / accuracy, prediction / diagnosis / treatment, explainable true / false, a specific algorithm and they will be optional.

5.2.5.3 *Algorithm selection and execution*

In case no algorithm default is given, then it will check the input parameters, and will supply the appropriate algorithm with the data (see Algorithm as a Service).

5.2.5.4 *Algorithm as a Service*

In this function, all available algorithms are standardised to run under a common ecosystem, or a set of services that will host different algorithms, prepare the data to be in a form recognisable by them, and finally collect the information so that to transfer it to the next stage.

Each service will be compliant to REST API practices and will use a queueing mechanism (such as MQTT).

5.2.6 USER INTERFACE

This section provides an overview and snapshot of the current understanding and design of the Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the MES-CoBraD System. The GUI is a work in progress, and it will be detailed (and possibly modified) as our work toward the implementation and integration of the system progresses. Many of the mock-ups of the GUI presented below are still under discussion and will likely go through modifications. The mock-ups may either present schematically the functional elements of pages, or, in some cases, we went a step further providing also suggested graphical implementations.

The MES-CoBraD System will have an integrated common Graphical User Interface. The GUI will follow the logic of the broad process areas which are dealt with by the overall system and not necessarily the logic of component boundaries – since the components often need to work with each other to provide the various services. This means that the components and the switch between them will be broadly seamless for the end users. The main processes identified are:

Data (work): this involves processes related to data upload, access, data collection, etc.

(Data) Analysis: this involves data analysis processes and procedures available to end users mainly for research but possibly also for clinical processes.

Clinical Processes: these refer to processes referring to clinical trials (for research purposes) or procedures and protocols for diagnosis and treatment.

Knowledge Base: providing an organised way to share knowledge.

System Administration: various functionalities for use for system administration.

These process areas also become the principal elements of the main menu. Figure 24 below presents schematically the main menu of the GUI. We foresee at this moment that the main menu will have a depth of maximum 3 levels (possibly 2 based on further discussion among partners). The need for further splits may be satisfied by providing further options on actual pages (by means of clickable items, pictures plus text or widgets).

Figure 24 – Main Menu Presentation

In the following we explain the elements of the main menu (except for the primary items already explained). It should be noted that the elements of the main menu like other elements on pages and pages themselves will be visible depending on the user’s role and rights of access. So, for example, regular users will not see the System Administration item.

Data

- a. My datasets: allows the user to view a list of datasets and from there execute a series of

operations on the dataset.

- b. Data upload: allows the user to upload secondary datasets by following a strict procedure which respects rights of access, data licensing, and data privacy (this procedure is not fully defined yet, but we are working on it).
- c. Data collection: allows the user to collect primary data by means of questionnaires. The user can create questionnaires, apply them online or apply them by printing, on paper completion by respondents and further transcribing them into the system.

Analysis

- a. Various statistical analysis procedures (and possible machine learning algorithms) will be made available for data analysis.

Clinical processes:

- a. Clinical trials: Allows users to run clinical trials.
- b. Diagnosis and treatment: allow users to run various procedures and protocols for diagnosis and treatment.

Knowledge base

- a. Sub items have not been defined yet.

System administration

- a. Sub items have not been defined yet.

6 ADVANCED ANALYTICS MOCKUPS

The sections present the analysis of the advanced analytics mockups providing the presentation of user interface, information on the expert system and process modelling and management, query builder and data analytics. Information on the hypothesis testing interface, visualizations and AI are also reported.

6.1 USER INTERFACE

Based on the main menu discussed on 5.2.6 we present Figure 25 below a general mock-up of the main page as it appears after the user is logged in (and assuming for now that the user has broad rights (as a scientist or clinician) but not the rights of a system administrators.

Figure 25 – Home Page Mock-up

The items other than the main menu are largely self-explanatory. The MES-CoBraD logo will appear in the header, a search bar will be available for text content of the site (mainly the knowledge base), an alert bell will be available for alerts (primary on reaching some milestones on clinical processes) and a user icon will appear where, by clicking, the user can access some account management functionalities.

The other content on the main page is under discussion. While we were considering a dashboard like content, we decided that it may be inappropriate since the System is not based on continuous streams of data coming in. We are considering the content as being static text and pictures.

Prior to the full main page being displayed with an extended main menu, a page 0, or a barebones home page (with only the Knowledge Base and basic information about the MES-CoBraD System and Project)

will be shown for non-logged-in users. From there the user can register (sign up) or log in (sign in).

A proposed register form is provided in Figure 26 below. The data fields still need discussion and revisiting, and it is probably not final at this moment.as the overall process of registration of users is defined.

Register

First name

Last name

Adress

ID Number

Medic

Phone

E-mail

I hereby consent to the processing of the personal data that I have provided and declare my agreement with the data protection regulations

Figure 26 – Register Form Mock-up

Figure 27 below displays a mock-up of the login form.

Login

Username

Password

Login Register

[Forgot your password?](#)

Figure 27 – Login Form Mock-up

In the following we present some pages for various functionalities of the system which are early proposals for discussion.

Figure 28 - Incoming Data Monitoring Page Mock-up

Figure 29 below presents a page where several options are available in continuation of the main menu

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

(to avoid too many levels of depth of the menu). The proposal here is that these options are presented in the form of rectangles with suggestive graphics and text. This example is about diagnostic guidelines, but the style can be applied for any case where further depth of options than the main menu provides is necessary.

Figure 29 – Options Page Mock-up

Figure 30 below presents an example of a presentation of an article type page with text and possible graphics. To make it more readable the article is broken into several sections visible on the left side menu, these sections can be expanded/made visible or contracted/made invisible.

Multiple Sleep Latency Test Guidelines

- Overview >
- Symptoms >
- Causes >
- Diagnosis >
 - Polysomnogram
 - MSLT
- Treatments >

Overview

In the multiple sleep latency test (MSLT), a person is given 4-5 opportunities to sleep every two hours during normal wake times. The specialist uses the test to measure the extent of daytime sleepiness (how fast the patient falls asleep in each nap, also called sleep latency), and also how quickly REM sleep begins. A positive MSLT is obtained when the patient falls asleep with a mean sleep latency below 8 minutes in the naps, and had at least no more than 1 nap (for idiopathic hypersomnia) or 2 naps (for narcolepsy diagnosis) where REM sleep was reached.

In the multiple sleep latency test (MSLT), a person is given 4-5 opportunities to sleep every two hours during normal wake times. The specialist uses the test to measure the extent of daytime sleepiness (how fast the patient falls asleep in each nap, also called sleep latency), and also how quickly REM sleep begins. A positive MSLT is obtained when the patient falls asleep with a mean sleep latency below 8 minutes in the naps, and had at least no more than 1 nap (for idiopathic hypersomnia) or 2 naps (for narcolepsy diagnosis) where REM sleep was reached.

Figure 30 – Article Page Mock-up

A few other full graphics mockup pages are presented below as current proposals to facilitate further discussion.

Figure 31 below presents a proposal for a view patient profile page. While the page is fully graphically implemented, the exact details of the page (especially the data fields) need to be worked out. Furthermore, this variant of the page would be implemented in the Edge Module as it presents non-anonymised/pseudonymised data. An anonymised/ pseudonymised version of the page may be available on the platform.

Figure 31 – Patient Profile Page Mock-up

Figure 32 below presents a view patient list mock-up page. As explained for the previous figure, this page may need to have both anonymised/ pseudonymised and non-anonymised variants.

Add Patient

Search patients...

Filters

Search portal...

Account
Support
Logout

	First Name	Last Name	Record date	Public policy	Gender	Age		
	Alexander	John	16.02.2022	Anonymous	Female	36	View records	View patient
	Alexander	John	16.02.2022	Anonymous	Male	26	View records	View patient
	Alexander	John	16.02.2022	Anonymous	Male	31	View records	View patient
	Alexander	John	16.02.2022	Anonymous	Male	32	View records	View patient
	Alexander	John	16.02.2022	Anonymous	Female	28	View records	View patient
	Alexander	John	16.02.2022	Anonymous	Male	20	View records	View patient
	Alexander	John	16.02.2022	Anonymous	Female	40	View records	View patient

Figure 32 – View Patient List Mockup Page

6.2 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

The GUI of Expert System is based on the core interface of MES-CoBraD provided by 4 and just as the general GUI, the mockups presented in this chapter, are not in final stage and may change during the project.

Figure 33 shows the site used to create a workflow. The user has the freedom to create tasks, define operators and create connections to the Data Lake. The same image is displayed to the user when he wants to edit an existing workflow.

Figure 33 – Creation of a workflow

Figure 34 shows the list of all workflows that have been created, along with their descriptions, the ability to execute, edit and/or delete it.

Figure 34 – List of all available workflows

Finally, Figure 35 shows the ability of performing a clinical process where the available steps and the information of each step are displayed. Here, the user can interact with workflows and data transferred between steps.

Figure 35 – Clinical process execution

6.3 QUERY BUILDER

A mock-up of the interface of the Query Builder is presented below. A clinician/researcher using this Interface will be able to request specific data from the DataLake choosing the respective tables, columns and aggregations. For instance, in the Figure 36 below, a user has selected data from Table 2 and Table 4, the grouping of column B and Column D and applies the SUM aggregation function in column A. Also, the user has asked only the first 200 records that equals to “value” in Column A.

Figure 36 – Interface of the Query Builder

This mockup constitutes a first version of the Query Builder’s Interface. The next versions will include more functionalities and capabilities for more complex queries.

6.4 DATA ANALYTICS

A mock-up of the interface of the Data Analytics is presented below. In Figure 37 a list of the available analyses related with the electrophysiology signals is presented. In each “Analysis card” a short description is provided along with some basic functionalities (execute, modify and/or delete).

Figure 37 – List of all the available analyses for the electrophysiology signals

Moreover, in Figure 38, in Figure 39, Figure 40, Figure 41, Figure 41, and Figure 42 six representative instances of analysis are presented. In general, prior to performing each analysis several parameters must be provided to capture users' preferences.

More specifically, Figure 38 defines the list of the parameters that will be passed to the algorithm for the detection of spindles. The user has to define the spindles' frequency range, the broad band frequency range, and the duration of spindles. Next, the user clicks the "Execute" button for performing the analysis.

Detection of Spindles		
Please fill in	Spindles Frequency range	<i>range_min, range_max</i>
Please fill in	Broad Band Frequency range	<i>range_min, range_max</i>
Please fill in	Duration of the spindles	<i>minimum duration, maximum duration</i>
Execute		

Figure 38 – List of parameters for the detection of spindles

In Figure 39, the user must select and fill in the parameters, which are required for the computation of the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT). Specifically, the user has to choose the type of the window, which is available in the drop-down list. Also, the user must fill in the number of points to overlap between segments, the length of each segment, as well as the length of the FFT used. Finally, the user clicks the “Execute” button for performing the analysis.

Short-Time Fourier Transform		
<i>Please select</i>	window	<input type="text" value="Hann"/> Hamming etc.
<i>Please fill in</i>	Number of points to overlap between segments	<input type="text" value="int"/>
<i>Please fill in</i>	length of each segment	<input type="text" value="int"/>
<i>Please fill in</i>	length of the FFT used	<input type="text" value="int"/>
Execute		

Figure 39 – List of parameters for the computation of the STFT

In Figure 40, the user chooses the parameters required for the ARIMA model. Specifically, the user is able to define the test size, in order that the ARIMA model is trained using the train set. Thus, the error in the test set can be calculated. At the same time, the user is capable of choosing the future patient data in seconds (or samples). Next, the user is able to define the method and the information criterion, which is used to select the best ARIMA model. Finally, the user clicks the “Execute” button for starting the analysis.

MES-CoBraD

Time-series Forecasting using an ARIMA model

Please fill in **test_size**

Please fill in **future patient data (in seconds)**

Please select **method**
lbfgs
Newton-Raphson
etc.

Please select **information_criterion**
aic
bic
etc.

Execute

Figure 40 – List of parameters given to an ARIMA model

In Figure 41, the user defines the parameters for the calculation of the power spectral density using the Welch’s method. Specifically, the user is able to choose the window from a drop-down list, which includes all the available windows. Also, the user is capable of filling in the number of points to overlap between segments, the length of each segment, and the length of the FFT used. Finally, the user clicks the “Execute” button in order the analysis to be started.

Power Spectral Density (Welch's Method)		
Please select	window	<input type="text" value="Hann"/> Hamming etc.
Please fill in	Number of points to overlap between segments	<input type="text" value="int"/>
Please fill in	length of each segment	<input type="text" value="int"/>
Please fill in	length of the FFT used	<input type="text" value="int"/>

Execute

Figure 41 – List of parameters for the computation of the Power Spectral Density using the Welch's method

Figure 42 illustrates the interface for the autocorrelation function. More specifically, the user is able to define the alpha value, so that the confidence intervals be returned. Also, the user is able to select whether the autocorrelation function will be computed via FFT or not. At the same time, the user will be able to choose if the Ljung-Box q statistic will be returned for each autocorrelation coefficient. Finally, the user clicks the “Execute” button for conducting the analysis.

Autocorrelation		
<i>Please fill in</i>	alpha	<input type="text" value="scalar"/>
<i>Please select</i>	fft	<input type="text" value="True or False"/>
<i>Please select</i>	Ljung-Box q statistic for each autocorrelation coefficient	<input type="text" value="True or False"/>

Execute

Figure 42 – List of parameters for the computation of the autocorrelation function

6.5 HYPOTHESIS TESTING INTERFACE

A mock-up of the interface of the Hypothesis Testing is presented below. In Figure 43 a list of the hypothesis scenarios, created by the user, is presented. In each “Hypothesis card” a short description is provided along with some basic functionalities (present the result, modify/create a new instance, and/or delete).

Figure 43 – List of all the created hypothesis scenarios

The user selects the hypothesis that he/she wants to test. Then, as illustrated in Figure 44, the user selects samples from the Data Lake via the Query Builder Component. After that, the user is able to choose one of the following:

- > Correlations
- > Data Distribution
- > Homoscedasticity
- > Statistical Tests for Hypothesis Testing

Figure 44 – Initial Interface

In case that the user clicks the option “Data Distribution”, the user is transferred to another interface, which is shown in Figure 45, where there are available many techniques, which let the user check if the data sample deviates from a Gaussian distribution. This is a very important step before conducting a statistical test. As mentioned in Section 2.2.5, one assumption of t-test is the normality, which indicates that both samples are approximately normally distributed. As one can easily observe in Figure 45, the user chooses first the sample, which will be used for checking if it follows a normal distribution. Next, for checking the assumption of normality, the user is able to choose one of the following methods:

- › Visual Normality Checks
 - Quantile – Quantile (Q-Q) plot
 - Histogram
- › Statistical Normality Tests
 - Shapiro Wilk Test, which tests the null hypothesis that the data was drawn from a normal distribution. It returns the test statistic along with the p-value for the hypothesis test.
 - D’ Agostino’s K-squared test, which tests the null hypothesis that a sample comes from a normal distribution. It is based on D’Agostino and Pearson’s test [137][138] that combines skew and kurtosis to produce an omnibus test of normality. It returns the statistic and the p-value.
 - Anderson – Darling test, which tests the null hypothesis that a sample is drawn from

a population that follows a normal distribution. It must be also noted that the function implemented in SciPy library in Python works for normal, exponential, logistic, or Gumber distributions.

Figure 45 – Methods for checking whether the data samples follow a normal distribution

In case that the user clicks the option “Q-Q plot”, as shown in Figure 45, the user is transferred to another interface, which is illustrated in Figure 46. This interface shows a Q-Q plot of the quantiles of the data sample versus the quantiles of a normal distribution.

In case that the user clicks the option “Histogram”, as shown in Figure 45, the user is transferred to another interface, which is shown in Figure 47. In Figure 47, we can see a Gaussian-like shape to the data.

In case that the user clicks the other options, i.e., “Shapiro-Wilk test”, “D’ Agostino’s K-squared test”, and “Anderson-Darling test”, as shown in Figure 45, the user is transferred to another interface, which is shown in Figure 48, where the user can see the test statistic and the p-value.

Figure 46 – Q-Q plot

Figure 47 – Histogram

The form is titled "Hypothesis 1" and contains two input fields. The first field is labeled "Test statistic" and the second is labeled "p-value". Both fields have a placeholder text "Number".

Test statistic	<input type="text" value="Number"/>
p-value	<input type="text" value="Number"/>

Figure 48 – Test statistic and p-value

In case that the user clicks the option “Homoscedasticity”, as shown in Figure 44, the user is transferred

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

to another interface, which is illustrated in Figure 49. It is known that the assumption of homoscedasticity must be satisfied, in order for the associated p-value to be valid. For example, the ANOVA test includes the assumption of homoscedasticity, meaning that the population standard deviations of the groups are all equal. As shown in Figure 49, the user is able to choose two techniques for checking whether the population standard deviations of the groups are all equal. First, the user chooses the samples, which will be checked and then the user chooses one of the following techniques for checking the property of homoscedasticity:

- › Bartlett’s test. It must be noted that for samples from significantly non-normal populations, Levene’s test is more robust.
- › Levene test, which is an alternative to Bartlett’s test in the case where there are significant deviations from normality.

In case that the user clicks the option “Levene Test”, as shown in Figure 49, the user is transferred to another interface, which is illustrated in Figure 50, in order to choose one of the following parameters:

- › “mean”: Recommended for symmetric, moderate-tailed distributions [139]
- › “median”: Recommended for skewed (non-normal) distributions
- › “trimmed”: Recommended for heavy-tailed distributions

The options for “median” and “trimmed” refer to [140]. The test is known as Brown-Forsythe test.

Finally, after selecting the Levene test or the Bartlett’s test, the user is transferred to another interface, which is illustrated in Figure 48, where the user can see the test statistic and the p-value.

Figure 49 – Methods for checking the assumption of homoscedasticity

MES-CoBraD

Hypothesis 1

Choose one of the following

mean

median

trimmed

Figure 50 – Levene Test

In case that the user checks the option “Correlations”, as shown in Figure 44, the user is transferred to another interface, which is illustrated in Figure 51. Specifically, after selecting the samples, the user is able to choose one of the following methods for computing the correlations:

- › Pearson Correlation, which measures the linear relationship between two datasets
- › Spearman Correlation, which is a nonparametric measure of the monotonicity of the relationship between two datasets.
- › Kendall’s Tau, which is a measure of the correspondence between two rankings.
- › Point biserial correlation, which is used to measure the relationship between a binary variable, x , and a continuous variable, y .

By clicking one of these options, the user is transferred to an interface as illustrated in Figure 48, where the user sees the test statistic (correlation coefficient) and the p-value.

Figure 51 – Methods for calculating the correlations

In case that the user checks the option “Statistical Tests for Hypothesis Testing”, as shown in Figure 44, the user is transferred in another interface, which is shown in Figure 52. The user is able to choose which statistical test fits best the assumptions of normality, homoscedasticity, etc. Specifically, as one can easily observe, there are both parametric and non-parametric statistical tests. For instance, the ANOVA test has important assumptions, including (i) the samples are independent, (ii) each sample is from a normally distributed population, and (iii) homoscedasticity. If these assumptions are not true, then the user is able to exploit either the Kruskal-Wallis H-test or the Alexander-Govern test. To be more precise, the Alexander-Govern test does not assume on homoscedasticity.

In addition, the Mann-Whitney U rank test is for independent samples. For related/paired samples, one could use the Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

Figure 52 – Options for parametric and non-parametric statistical tests

After selecting the statistical test, the user is transferred in another interface, which is illustrated in Figure 53. More specifically, Figure 53 illustrates the interface for performing a specific statistical hypothesis test. In this case, the user performs an independent t-test. In this interface, the user is able to define some additional parameters for conducting the statistical test. For this purpose:

- › the user needs to choose the data samples to be compared.
- › enter some critical parameters for conducting the test, using a drop-down menu or a numeric input field. The “alternative” parameter defines the alternative hypothesis. The following options are available:
 - ‘two-sided’: the means of the distributions underlying the samples are unequal
 - ‘less’: the mean of the distribution underlying the first sample is less than the mean of the distribution underlying the second sample
 - ‘greater’: the mean of the distribution underlying the first sample is greater than the mean of the distribution underlying the second sample.

The ‘trim’ parameter defines the fraction of elements to be trimmed from each end of the input samples. If 0, no elements will be trimmed from either side.

After performing the test (by clicking “calculate”), the user can see the calculated test statistic and p-value.

Hypothesis 1

Choose samples

Sample 1

Sample 2

⋮

Choose parameters

Alternative: two-sided, less, greater

trim: Number [0, .5]

Results

Test statistic: Number

p-value: Number

Calculate

Figure 53 – Independent t-test

These mockups constitute a preliminary version of the hypothesis testing interface. In the next versions the parameters required by the user will be enriched and redefined. Also, in case of multiple tests, the user will be able to exploit some methods for testing and adjustment of p-values, including the Bonferroni correction, the Benjamini-Hochberg correction, and many more.

6.6 DATA AND RESULTS VISUALISATION

The results of the analyses, which are illustrated in Figure 37-Figure 42, are shown in Figure 54, Figure 55, Figure 56, Figure 57, and Figure 58.

More specifically, Figure 54 illustrates the visualization dashboard for the results obtained by the ARIMA model. The user is able to get a summary of the ARIMA model, see the future values of an electrophysiology signal, i.e., EEG, and get the diagnostic plots. To be more precise, the function `plot.diagnostics` produces a 2x2 plot grid with the following plots (ordered clockwise from top left):

- › Standardised residuals over time
- › Histogram plus estimated density of standardised residuals, along with a Normal(0,1) density plotted for reference.
- › Normal Q-Q plot, with Normal reference line.
- › Correlogram

Figure 54 – Visualization Output of the ARIMA model

In addition, Figure 55 illustrates the results of the analysis shown in Figure 42.

Figure 55 – Autocorrelation

In Figure 56, the results of the analysis illustrated in Figure 38 are presented.

Figure 56 – Detection of spindles

Figure 57 illustrates the results of the STFT algorithm shown in Figure 39.

Figure 57 – Short-Time Fourier Transform

Finally, Figure 58 illustrates the results of the analysis shown in Figure 41.

Figure 58 – Power Spectral Density using the Welch's method

7 APIS' SPECIFICATION

The sections present the APIs and their specifications that are available through the MES-CoBraD platform. These include the Query Builder, the Expert System, the Data Analytics, the Data Lake, the Data Visualization and the Artificial Intelligence. Each chapter consists of two parts, the “Overview Paths” and the “Component - Schemas”.

The first one provides all the information the API’s endpoints provide. Each path displays the API call method, the URI request path, and a small description. Additionally, they provide the different responses that we might get during the different use cases and the requirements needed to successfully execute each API call.

The “Component - Schemas” provide the definitions of an API model entity. These entities are the objects that are expected to be retrieved at a successful API call response.

Changes in this section

In all the following sections parts, there are significant changes related to the API implementation. There are minor changes, such as renaming, adding, or removing endpoints, parameters, responses, etc., that are not explicitly specified as updates, but their current state is presented accurately in the following sections. These changes were made after internal and external user feedback related to our modules' functionality and ease of use. Some of the updated documentation of the API has been moved outside the deliverable due to size considerations and is hosted in the applications code repository.

7.1 QUERY BUILDER AND MES-COBRA D DATA LAKE

7.1.1 QUERY BUILDER APIS

7.1.1.1 [POST /complex/select/query Complex Select Query](#)

Build a Select SQL query

Responses

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
	Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.2 [POST /complex/group/query Complex Group Query](#)

Build a Group by SQL query

Responses

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
	Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.3 [POST /complex/join/query Complex Join Query](#)

Build a Join query

Responses

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
	Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.4 [POST /execute_query Execute Query](#)

Execute query

Responses

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
	Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.5 [GET /tables](#) Get Tables

Get all the available tables

Responses

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.6 [GET /tables/{table}](#) Get Columns of Table

Get all the columns of a table

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	<i>table</i> <i>required</i>		string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
	Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.7 [GET /buckets](#) Get List of Buckets

Get all the available buckets

Responses

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.8 [GET /buckets/{bucket}](#) Get objects of a bucket

Get the objects of a bucket

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	bucket <i>required</i>		string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
	Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

7.1.1.9 [POST /buckets/{bucket}/save](#) Save Object as Csv in a bucket

Save the output after the execution of a query in a bucket

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	bucket <i>required</i>		string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
	Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links

New

7.1.1.10 *POST /variables*

Retrieve the different variables in a parquet file

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
body	<i>table required</i>		string

Response

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response	
200	<i>Content application/json</i>	No Links
	Validation Error	
422	<i>Content application/json</i>	No Links

New

7.1.1.11 *POST /variables/tables*

Retrieve the unique sources in parquet file that satisfy a condition.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
body	<i>table required</i>		string
body	<i>Variable required</i>		string
body	<i>Condition required</i>		string
body	<i>Value required</i>		string

Response

Code	Description	Links
------	-------------	-------

Successful Response

200	<i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
<hr/>		
422	Validation Error <i>Content</i> application/json	No Links
<hr/>		

7.1.1.12 Data Lake APIs

7.1.1.12.1 Metadata Manager APIs

The Metadata Manager is the component in charge of dealing with the questionnaires and variables metadata.

The APIs are totally RESTful and provide both GET, POST, DELETE and PATCH verbs over the following resources:

- Concepts
- Variables
- Languages
- Questionnaires
- Questions
- STS Categories

Moreover, it allows to manage the following relations:

- Concepts – Variables
- Questions – Variables
- STS Categories – Variables

The complete specification is available in OpenAPI v3 format in the Annex II.

7.1.1.12.2 Object Storage APIs

The MES-CoBraD Object Storage is entirely provided by the Digital Enabler platform. It exposes a set of APIs that are totally compliant with the AWS S3 APIs specifications.

For this reason, all the APIs exposed are compliant with the specification available in the [Amazon S3 API Reference](#).

7.1.2 COMPONENTS – SCHEMAS

7.1.2.1 GroupItem

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
aggregation_metrics <i>required</i>	Aggregation metric to be used as aggregation metric in GROUPS Title: Aggregation Metrics	< > array
aggregation_columns <i>required</i>	Column to apply aggregations Title: Aggregation Columns	< > array
grouping_columns <i>required</i>	List for declaring columns to be used in GROUP BY statement Title: Grouping Columns	< > array
table <i>required</i>	table to get data Title: Table	string
connection_name <i>optional</i>	connection from Presto Title: Connection Name Default: connection_name	string
schema_name <i>optional</i>	Connection schema from Presto Title: Schema Name Default: schema	string
where_column <i>optional</i>	column to use for filtering results Title: Where Column	string
where_clause_term <i>optional</i>	term to use for where condition value Title: Where Clause Term	string
limit <i>optional</i>	LIMIT parameter Title: Limit	integer
aggregation_metrics_alias_list <i>optional</i>	alias for aggregation output Title: Aggregation Metrics Alias List	< > array

<i>not_condition optional</i>	if True enable NOT condition Title: Not Condition Default: false	boolean
<i>in_values optional</i>	values for conditional WHERE IN statement Title: In Values	< > array
<i>between_values optional</i>	list with 2 values for BETWEEN statement Title: Between Values	< > array
<i>like_pattern optional</i>	string to use in LIKE pattern Title: Like Pattern	string
<i>where_symbol optional</i>	symbol to use checking where condition Title: Where Symbol	string
<i>order_by_column optional</i>	column to use for results ordering Title: Order By Column	string
<i>order optional</i>	ASC/DESC order Title: Order	string
<i>return_dict optional</i>	Return output as dictionary Title: Return Dict Default: true	boolean
<i>if_pandas optional</i>	Return output as pd.DataFrame Title: If Pandas Default: false	boolean
<i>if_column_chart optional</i>	Return output suitable for column chart Title: If Column Chart Default: false	boolean
<i>AND_ optional</i>	AND statement for having multiple WHERE clauses Title: And	< > array

OR statement for having multiple WHERE clauses

OR_optional < > array

Title: Or

username_optional user that performs the query string
Title: Username

7.1.2.2 *JoinItem*

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
<i>join_tables_required</i>	tables to join Title: Join Tables	< > array
<i>connection_name_optional</i>	connection from Presto Title: Connection Name Default: connection_name	string
<i>schema_name_optional</i>	Connection schema from Presto Title: Schema Name Default: schema	string
<i>columns_table1_optional</i>	columns from table 1 Title: Columns Table1	< > array
<i>columns_table2_optional</i>	columns from table 2 Title: Columns Table2	< > array
<i>columns_table3_optional</i>	columns from table 3 Title: Columns Table3	< > array
<i>columns_table_list_optional</i>	list columns from all tables Title: Columns Table List	< > array
<i>aggregation_metrics_table1_optional</i>	aggregation metrics to use AVG/SUM/COUNT for columns in table 1 Title: Aggregation Metrics Table1	< > array

aggregation_ m etrics_table2 <i>optional</i>	aggregation metrics to use AVG/SUM/COUNT for columns in table 2 Title: Aggregation Metrics Table2	< > array
aggregation_ m etrics_table3 <i>optional</i>	aggregation metrics to use AVG/SUM/COUNT for columns in table 3 Title: Aggregation Metrics Table3	< > array
aggregation_ m etrics_table_li st <i>optional</i>	aggregation metrics list to use AVG/SUM/COUNT for all columns Title: Aggregation Metrics Table List	< > array
aggregation_ m etrics_alias_lis t _table1 <i>optional</i>	alias for aggregation output for columns in table 1 Title: Aggregation Metrics Alias List Table1	< > array
aggregation_ m etrics_alias_lis t _table2 <i>optional</i>	alias for aggregation output for columns in table 2 Title: Aggregation Metrics Alias List Table2	< > array
aggregation_ m etrics_alias_lis t _table3 <i>optional</i>	alias for aggregation output for columns in table 3 Title: Aggregation Metrics Alias List Table3	< > array
aggregation_ m etrics_alias_lis <i>optional</i>	alias for aggregation output for all columns Title: Aggregation Metrics Alias List	< > array
grouping_colu mns <i>optional</i>	list of dicts of grouping columns Title: Grouping Columns	< > array
join_types <i>required</i>	list of dicts that describe the join Title: Join Types	< > array

<i>order_by_column optional</i>	column to use for results ordering Title: Order By Column	< > array
<i>where_column optional</i>	column to use for filtering results Title: Where Column	string
<i>where_table optional</i>	table to use for filtering results Title: Where Table	string
<i>where_symbol optional</i>	symbol to use checking where condition Title: Where Symbol	string
<i>where_clause_term optional</i>	term to use for where condition value Title: Where Clause Term	string
<i>in_values optional</i>	values for conditional WHERE IN statement Title: In Values	< > array
<i>not_condition optional</i>	if True enable NOT condition Title: Not Condition Default: false	boolean
<i>between_values optional</i>	list with 2 values for BETWEEN statement Title: Between Values	< > array
<i>like_pattern optional</i>	string to use in LIKE pattern Title: Like Pattern	string
<i>limit optional</i>	LIMIT parameter Title: Limit	integer
<i>AND_ optional</i>	AND statement for having multiple WHERE clauses Title: And	< > array
<i>OR_ optional</i>	OR statement for having multiple WHERE clauses Title: Or	< > array

7.1.2.3 SelectItem

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
<i>table required</i>	table to get data Title: Table	string
<i>connection_name optional</i>	connection from Presto Title: Connection Name Default: connection_name	string
<i>schema_name optional</i>	Connection schema from Presto Title: Schema Name Default: schema	string
<i>columns optional</i>	columns to get from table Title: Columns	< > array
<i>all optional</i>	select all columns for table if True Title: All Default: false	boolean
<i>aggregation_metrics optional</i>	aggregation metrics to use AVG/SUM/COUNT Title: Aggregation Metrics	< > array
<i>aggregation_columns optional</i>	aggregation columns to use for applying metrics Title: Aggregation Columns	< > array
<i>aggregation_metrics_alias_list optional</i>	alias for aggregation output Title: Aggregation Metrics Alias List	< > array
<i>where_clause_term optional</i>	term to use for where condition value Title: Where Clause Term	string
<i>in_values optional</i>	values for conditional WHERE IN statement Title: In Values	< > array

<i>not_condition optional</i>	if True enable NOT condition Title: Not Condition Default: false	boolean
<i>between_values optional</i>	list with 2 values for BETWEEN statement Title: Between Values	< > array
<i>like_pattern optional</i>	string to use in LIKE pattern Title: Like Pattern	string
<i>order optional</i>	ASC/DESC order Title: Order	string
<i>order_by_column optional</i>	column to use for results ordering Title: Order By Column	string
<i>limit optional</i>	LIMIT parameter Title: Limit	integer
<i>where_symbol optional</i>	symbol to use checking where condition Title: Where Symbol	string
<i>return_dict optional</i>	Return output as dictionary Title: Return Dict Default: true	boolean
<i>if_pandas optional</i>	Return output as pd.DataFrame Title: If Pandas Default: false	boolean
<i>many_aggregations optional</i>	Many aggregations to apply: <code>{' AGG(COLUMN_NAME)' : ' ALIAS' }</code> Title: Many Aggregations	object
<i>AND_optional</i>	AND statement for having multiple WHERE clauses Title: And	< > array

where_column <i>optional</i>	column to use for filtering results Title: Where Column	string
OR_ <i>optional</i>	OR statement for having multiple WHERE clauses Title: Or	< > array

7.2 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

7.2.1 OVERVIEW PATHS

7.2.1.1 Features

Retrieve, create, delete and update features with all their functionality inside the Expert System.

7.2.1.1.1 GET /feature

Retrieve features with their metadata. Params explain: order: The model's prop as str, e.g. id direction: asc | desc

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	limit	optional	integer
query	skip	optional	integer
query	order	optional	string
query	direction	optional	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
------	-------------	-------

200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response get features	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.1.2 *POST/feature*

Create features

Parameters

FeatureCreate {

```

    created_at    Created At[...]
    updated_at    Updated At[...]
    deleted_at    Deleted At[...]
    name *        Name[...]
    mapi_id       Mapi Id[...]
    info          Info{...}
    variables     Variables{...}

```

}

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response creates feature	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links

422

Validation Error
Content application/json

No Links

7.2.1.1.3 GET /feature/deleted

Retrieve deleted features. Params explain: order: The model's prop as str, e.g. id direction: asc | desc

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	limit	optional	integer
query	skip	optional	integer
query	order	optional	string
query	direction	optional	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response reads deleted features	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.1.4 GET /feature/deleted/{feature_id}

Get deleted feature by ID.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	feature_id	required	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
Successful Response		
200	<pre> { "created_at": "2023-12-21T15:10:02.971Z", "updated_at": "2023-12-21T15:10:02.971Z", "deleted_at": "2023-12-21T15:10:02.971Z", "id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6", "name": "string", "mapi_id": "string", "info": {}, "variables": [{ "created_at": "2023-12-21T15:10:02.971Z", "updated_at": "2023-12-21T15:10:02.971Z", "deleted_at": "2023-12-21T15:10:02.971Z", "id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6", "name": "string", "mapi_id": "string", "info": {} }] } </pre>	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
Validation Error		
422	<pre> { "detail": [{ "loc": ["string", 0], "msg": "string", "type": "string" }] } </pre>	No Links

7.2.1.1.5 GET /feature/{feature_id}

Get feature id.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	feature_id	required	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	<pre>{ "created_at": "2023-12-21T15:08:21.082Z", "updated_at": "2023-12-21T15:08:21.082Z", "deleted_at": "2023-12-21T15:08:21.082Z", "id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6", "name": "string", "mapi_id": "string", "info": {}, "variables": [{ "created_at": "2023-12-21T15:08:21.082Z", "updated_at": "2023-12-21T15:08:21.082Z", "deleted_at": "2023-12-21T15:08:21.082Z", "id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6", "name": "string", "mapi_id": "string", "info": {} }] }</pre>	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	<pre>{ "detail": [{ "loc": ["string", 0], "msg": "string", "type": "string" }] }</pre>	No Links

7.2.1.1.6 PUT /feature/{feature_id}

Retrieve features with their metadata. Params explain: order: The model's prop as str, e.g. id direction: asc | desc

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	feature_id	required	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response Content application/json Example response:	
200	<pre>{ "created_at": "2023-12-22T17:44:20.671Z", "updated_at": "2023-12-22T17:44:20.671Z", "deleted_at": "2023-12-22T17:44:20.671Z", "id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6", "name": "string", "mapi_id": "string", "info": {}, "variables": [{ "created_at": "2023-12-22T17:44:20.671Z", "updated_at": "2023-12-22T17:44:20.671Z", "deleted_at": "2023-12-22T17:44:20.671Z", "id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6", "name": "string", "mapi_id": "string", "info": {} }] }</pre>	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.1.7 DELETE /feature/{feature_id}

Delete a feature.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	feature_id	required	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	<p>Successful Response Content application/json Example response:</p> <pre> { "created_at": "2023-12-22T17:53:27.093Z", "updated_at": "2023-12-22T17:53:27.093Z", "deleted_at": "2023-12-22T17:53:27.093Z", "id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6", "name": "string", "mapi_id": "string", "info": {}, "variables": [{ "created_at": "2023-12-22T17:53:27.093Z", "updated_at": "2023-12-22T17:53:27.093Z", "deleted_at": "2023-12-22T17:53:27.093Z", "id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6", "name": "string", "mapi_id": "string", "info": {} }] } </pre>	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	<p>Validation Error Content application/json</p>	No Links

7.2.1.1.8 DELETE /feature/{feature_id}/revert

Revert the deletion of a feature.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	feature_id	required	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
	Successful Response Content application/json Example reponse:	
200	<pre> { "created_at": "2023-12-22T17:53:47.575Z", "updated_at": "2023-12-22T17:53:47.575Z", "deleted_at": "2023-12-22T17:53:47.575Z", "id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6", "name": "string", "mapi_id": "string", "info": {}, "variables": [{ "created_at": "2023-12-22T17:53:47.575Z", "updated_at": "2023-12-22T17:53:47.575Z", "deleted_at": "2023-12-22T17:53:47.575Z", "id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6", "name": "string", "mapi_id": "string", "info": {} }] } </pre>	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.2 Files

Retrieve files with their metadata.

7.2.1.2.1 GET /file

Retrieve features with their metadata. Params explain: order: The model's prop as str, e.g. id direction: asc | desc

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	term	optional	string
query	x-es-token	required	string
query	x-es-wsid	required	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response get file	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.3 Home

Route used to check if app is up and ready.

7.2.1.3.1 GET /healthcheck

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
------	------	-------------	--------

No parameters

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response get healthcheck	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

[7.2.1.4 Authentication](#)

ExpertSystem Authentication

[7.2.1.4.1 GET /oauth/login](#)

Get OAuth endpoint to redirect to log in.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
header	x-es-token	optional	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
------	-------------	-------

200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response get authentication	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.4.2 GET /oauth/callback

Route used to retrieve auth token.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
header	x-es-token	optional	string
Query	Code	required	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response gets the callback	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.4.3 GET /oauth/logout

Logout used.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
header	x-es-token	optional	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response logouts user	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.5 Run

Retrieve files with their metadata.

7.2.1.5.1 GET /run/{run_id}

Get OAuth endpoint to redirect to log in.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
------	------	-------------	--------

header x-es-token optional string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response get authentication	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.5.2 GET /run/{run_id} Read Run

Get specific workflow run by ID.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	run_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links

422 Validation Error
Content application/json No Links

7.2.1.5.3 GET /run/{run_id}/next Show Next Task

Retrieve running instance and return next task(s).

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	run_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.5.4 GET /run/{run_id}/step/{step_id} Run Specific Task

Initiate next step (specific task).

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	run_id required		string (uuid)
path	step_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.5.5 PUT /run/{run_id}/step/{step_id} Exec Specific Task Actions

Perform actions for a given execution step. The parameters needed in body depend on the step/task type. If you want to execute a "Gateway", then {"step_id": <uuid>} is needed. If you want to execute a "Task", then {"action": "exec"/"complete"} is needed. If you want to execute anything else, pass an empty body.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	run_id required		string (uuid)
path	step_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.5.6 GET /run/{run_id}/step/{step_id}/ping Ping Task Status

Get the status of specific task.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	run_id required		string (uuid)
path	step_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.6 Variables

CRUD for variables

7.2.1.6.1 GET /variable

Retrieve variables with their data.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	skip	optional	integer
query	limit	optional	integer

query	order	optional	string
query	direction	optional	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response Read variables	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
Code	Description	Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.6.2 *POST /variable*

Create new variable

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
No parameter			

Request body required eg. :

```
{
  "created_at": "2023-12-22T20:16:26.690Z",
  "updated_at": "2023-12-22T20:16:26.690Z",
  "deleted_at": "2023-12-22T20:16:26.690Z",
}
```



```

"name": "string",
"map_id": "string",
"info": {},
"features": [
  {
    "created_at": "2023-12-22T20:16:26.690Z",
    "updated_at": "2023-12-22T20:16:26.690Z",
    "deleted_at": "2023-12-22T20:16:26.690Z",
    "name": "string",
    "map_id": "string",
    "info": {},
    "variables": [
      {
        "created_at": "2023-12-22T20:16:26.690Z",
        "updated_at": "2023-12-22T20:16:26.690Z",
        "deleted_at": "2023-12-22T20:16:26.690Z",
        "name": "string",
        "map_id": "string",
        "info": {},
        "features": [
          "string"
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
]
}

```

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: response variable creation	No Links

404	Not Found	No Links
Code	Description	Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.6.3 [GET /variable/deleted](#)

Get Deleted variables

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	skip	optional	integer
query	limit	optional	integer
query	order	optional	string
query	direction	optional	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response Read variables	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
Code	Description	Links

422

Validation Error
Content application/json

No Links

7.2.1.6.4 [GET /variable/deleted/{variable_id}](#)

Get deleted variable by Id

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	variable_id	required	string(uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response Read variables	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
Code	Description	Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.6.5 [GET /variable/{variable_id}](#)

Retrieve variables by Id

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	skip	optional	integer
query	limit	optional	integer
query	order	optional	string
query	direction	optional	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response Read variables	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
Code	Description	Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.6.6 *PUT /variable/{variable_id}*

Update a variable

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
------	------	-------------	--------

path	variable_id	required	string(uuid)
------	-------------	----------	--------------

Request Body(required) eg. :

```
{
  "created_at": "2023-12-22T20:32:27.331Z",
  "updated_at": "2023-12-22T20:32:27.331Z",
  "deleted_at": "2023-12-22T20:32:27.331Z",
  "name": "string",
  "mapi_id": "string",
  "info": {},
  "features": [
    {
      "created_at": "2023-12-22T20:32:27.331Z",
      "updated_at": "2023-12-22T20:32:27.331Z",
      "deleted_at": "2023-12-22T20:32:27.331Z",
      "name": "string",
      "mapi_id": "string",
      "info": {},
      "variables": [
        {
          "created_at": "2023-12-22T20:32:27.331Z",
          "updated_at": "2023-12-22T20:32:27.331Z",
          "deleted_at": "2023-12-22T20:32:27.331Z",
          "name": "string",
          "mapi_id": "string",
          "info": {},
          "features": [
            "string"
          ]
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```


Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response Read variables	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
Code	Description	Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.6.7 DELETE /variable/{variable_id}

Delete a variable

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	variable_id	required	string(uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
------	-------------	-------

200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response Read variables	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
Code	Description	Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.6.8 *DELETE /variable/{variable_id}/revert*

Revert a deleted variable.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	variable_id	required	string(uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response Read variables	No Links

404	Not Found	No Links
Code	Description	Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

[7.2.1.7 Workflow categories](#)

[7.2.1.8 Workflow](#)

Retrieve, create, delete and update for workflows with their metadata and Params

[7.2.1.8.1 GET /workflow/ Read Workflows](#)

Retrieve workflows with their metadata.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	limit optional		integer
query	skip optional		integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json Title: Response Read Workflows Workflow Get	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
Code	Description	Links

422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links
-----	--	----------

7.2.1.8.2 [POST /workflow/ Create Workflow](#)

Create new workflow.

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.8.3 [GET /workflow/entity_types Read Entity Types](#)

Get all available workflow entity types.

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links

7.2.1.8.4 [GET /workflow/{workflow_id} Read Workflow](#)

Get workflow by ID.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	workflow_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.8.5 *PUT /workflow/{workflow_id} Update Workflow*

Update a workflow.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	workflow_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.8.6 *DELETE /workflow/{workflow_id} Destroy Workflow*

Delete a workflow.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	workflow_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.8.7 *DELETE /workflow/{workflow_id}/revert Revert Workflow*

Revert the deletion of a workflow.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	workflow_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links

422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links
-----	--	----------

7.2.1.8.8 [GET /workflow/{workflow_id}/run](#) Run Workflow

Initiate a workflow process

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	workflow_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.1.8.9 [GET /workflow/{workflow_id}/task/{task_name}](#) Read Task Details

Get task details given its name and workflow ID.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	task_name required		string
path	workflow_id required		string (uuid)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.2.2 COMPONENTS - SCHEMAS

7.2.2.1 Run

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
created_at optional	Title: Created At	String (date-time)
updated_at optional	Title: Updated At	String (date-time)
deleted_at optional	Title: Deleted At	String (date-time)
id optional	Title: Id	string (uuid)
workflow_id required	Title: Workflow Id	string (uuid)
state required	Title: State	Object
steps required	Title: Steps	< > array
queue required	Title: Queue	< > array

7.2.2.2 Workflow

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
------	-------------	--------

created_at optional	Title: Created At	String (date-time)
updated_at optional	Title: Updated At	String (date-time)
deleted_at optional	Title: Deleted At	String (date-time)
id optional	Title: Id	string (uuid)
name required	Title: Name	String
description optional	Title: Description	String
tasks optional	Title: Tasks	Object
raw_diagram_ data optional	Title: Raw Diagram Data	Object

7.2.2.3 *WorkflowCreate*

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
created_at optional	Title: Created At	String (date-time)
updated_at optional	Title: Updated At	String (date-time)
deleted_at optional	Title: Deleted At	String (date-time)
description optional	Title: Description	String
tasks optional	Title: Tasks	Object
raw_diagram_ data optional	Title: Raw Diagram Data	Object
name required	Title: Name	String

7.2.2.4 WorkflowUpdate

Properties

Name	Description	Schema
created_at optional	Title: Created At	String (date-time)
updated_at optional	Title: Updated At	String (date-time)
deleted_at optional	Title: Deleted At	String (date-time)
description optional	Title: Description	String
tasks optional	Title: Tasks	Object
raw_diagram_data optional	Title: Raw Diagram Data	Object

7.3 DATA ANALYTICS

In this version of the deliverable (D6.3), due to the length of the descriptions, this paragraph was not updated. Instead, the complete specification is available in OpenAPI v3.02 via the [link](#). It's hosted in the github page of the data analytics module.

The data analytics and data and results visualisation modules as mentioned already use FASTAPI for the backend and react for the frontend. The API endpoints of FASTAPI are indicated by the type of request, get, post, etc. The react frontend utilises client side routing and are indicated accordingly. At those therefore we only describe the endpoint and query parameters, they always return the html and javascript that form the page itself.

GET /

A fallback root page in case of an error, not meant to be used normally

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /read/users

Endpoint to get user used in Neurodesk application automatic sign in.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	name required	Username provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /add/user

Endpoint to write new user used in Neurodesk automatic sign in.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	password required	Automatic created password	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	name required	Username provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /list/channels

Endpoint that returns channels

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_autocorrelation

Endpoint that returns correlation of signal with delayed copy of itself.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_qstat <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_missing <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_alpha <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_adjusted <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_fft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_bartlett_confint <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_nlags <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_partial_autocorrelation

Partially correlates signal with delayed copy of itself.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_method <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_alpha <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_nlags <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_welch

Computes estimate of power spectral density.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_npers eg <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	tmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_return_onesided <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	tmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_axis <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_average <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_noverlap <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_window <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_scaling <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nfft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_stft

Calculates short term fourier function of signal

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_padded <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nperseg <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	tmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_return_onesided <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_boundary <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	tmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_axis <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_noverlap <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_window <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nfft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_peaks

Finds local maxima of neighbouring values of signal.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_width <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_threshold <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	
query	input_plateau_size <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	
query	input_height <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	
query	input_prominence <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	
query	input_distance <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_wlen <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_rel_height <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_width <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_periodogram

Computes a periodogram of the EEG signal.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	tmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_return_onesided <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	tmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_axis <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_window <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_scaling <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nfft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_power_spectral_density

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

Calculates the power spectral density of a given signal with the multi-taper methods.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_fmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_low_bias <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_fmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_output <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	tmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_norm alization <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	tmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_band width <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_verbo se <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_adapti ve <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_n_jobs <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_alpha_delta_ratio

Estimates power spectral density using welch.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nperseg <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	tmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_return_onesided <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	tmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_axis <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_average <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_noverlap <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_window <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_scaling <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nfft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_asymmetry_indices

Calculates the asymmetry indices values of a signal.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_name_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_nperseg <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_return_onesided <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	input_axis <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_average <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_noverlap <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_window <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_scaling <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nfft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_alpha_variability

Estimates the alpha variability of a channel in a specific timeframe.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nperseg <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	tmax <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_return_onesided <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	tmin <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	input_axis <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_average <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_noverlap <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	input_window <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_scaling <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	input_nfft <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_predictions

Predicts values of timeseries in specific timeframe.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	method <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	future_seconds <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	test_size <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	information _criterion <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	start_p <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	max_p <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	max_q <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	start_q <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /spindles_detection

Detects sleep spindles.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	freq_sp_low <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	freq_sp_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	<i>freq_broad_low</i> <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	<i>freq_broad_high</i> <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	<i>duration_low</i> <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	<i>duration_high</i> <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	<i>min_distance</i> <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	<i>thresh_rel_pow</i> <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	<i>thresh_cor</i> <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	<i>thresh_rms</i> <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	<i>multi_only</i> <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	<i>remove_outliers</i> <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	<i>run_id</i> required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	<i>step_id</i> required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json

Responses	
Code	Description
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /slow_waves_detection

Detects sleep slow waves.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	freq_sw_low <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	freq_sw_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	duration_neg_low <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	duration_neg_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	duration_pos_low <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	duration_pos_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	amp_neg_low <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	amp_neg_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	amp_pos_low <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	amp_pos_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	amp_peak_low <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	amp_peak_high <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	integer
query	coupling <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /mne/open/eeg

This function starts or restarts part of the EEG Visualisation UI

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_signal

This function returns a channel from an EEG file, to be used in various functions and visualisations

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	input_channel _name <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /mne/return_annotations

This function returns the annotations saved by the user whenever he edits or views them

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	file_name <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

POST /receive_notebook_and_selection_configuration

Receive notebook and selection configuration

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
body	input required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	<pre> json { "bipolar_references": ["string"], "type_of_reference": "string", "channels_reference": ["string"], "notches_enabled": boolean, "notches_length": "string", "selection_channel": "string", "selection_start_time": "string", "selection_end_time": "string", "channel_list": ["string"], "filtering_low": "string", "filtering_high": "string" } </pre>
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	<p>Successful Response</p> <p><i>Content</i> application/json</p>

Responses	
Code	Description
422	Validation Error <i>Content</i> application/json

POST /montage/save

This endpoint saves a montage and its configuration.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
body	input required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	<pre> json { "bipolar_references": ["string"], "type_of_reference": "string", "channels_reference": ["string"], "notches_enabled": boolean, "notches_length": "string", "channel_list": ["string"] } </pre>
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json

GET /montage/list

This endpoint retrieves a list of the saved montages

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json

GET /montage/load

This endpoint returns the information of a selected montage

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	montage_id required	Id of the selected montage	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /task/complete

This endpoint is activated when a function has been completed and communicates this to the workflow manager

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

PUT /function/navigation

This endpoint serves as the main communication point with the workflow manager. When the users need to access any function of either the data analytics or Data and Results Visualisation modules, the request is first forwarded to this endpoint so the user is redirected to the correct page and any additional data is loaded and setup before any other action is taken.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
body	navigation_item <i>required</i>	Json object containing all information about the run of a function	json <pre>{ "run_id": "string", "step_id": "string", "metadata": ["string": "string"] }</pre>

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /function/existing

This endpoint returns a list of existing functions currently existing in the modules.

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /freesurfer/status

This endpoint returns the logs for the recon-all and SAMSEG functions during the time they run in the backend.

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /free_surfer/samseg

This endpoint initiates the SAMSEG MRI function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json
422	Validation Error <i>Content</i> application/json

GET /free_surfer/recon

This endpoint initiates the recon-all MRI function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_columns

This endpoint returns the columns of a dataset

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /normality_tests

This endpoint executes the normality test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	<i>column required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	<i>name_test optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	<i>run_id required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	<i>step_id required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content application/json</i>
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content application/json</i>

GET /transform_data

This endpoint executes the transform data function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	<i>lmbd optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	<i>name_transform optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	alpha <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	column <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /compute_pearson_correlation

Compute pearson correlation

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	column_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /compute_spearman_correlation

Compute spearman correlation

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	column_2 required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /compute_kendalltau_correlation

Compute kendall tau correlation

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	method <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	alternative <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	variant <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	nan_policy <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /compute_point_biserial_correlation

Compute point biserial correlation

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	column_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

Responses	
Code	Description
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /check_homoscedasticity

Check homoscedasticity

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	name_of_test <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	center <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

Responses	
Code	Description
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /transformed_data_for_use_in_an_ANOVA

Get transformed data to be used in ANOVA

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	column_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /statistical_tests

This endpoint handles the initialisation of many statistical functions

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	mode <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	zero_method <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	method <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	alternative <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	correction <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	boolean
query	statistical_test <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	nan_policy <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_2 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	column_1 <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json

Responses	
Code	Description
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /multiple_comparisons

This endpoint handles the initialisation of many statistical functions

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	p_value <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	< number > array
query	method <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	alpha <i>required</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	number
query	run_id <i>required</i>	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id <i>required</i>	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_reconall_stats/whole_brain_measurements

Return recon all results measurements

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	hemisphere_requested <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	fs_dir <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
Successful Response	
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
Validation Error	
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_reconall_stats/structural_measurements

Return structural measurements

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	fs_dir <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_samseg_result

Return samseg results

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	fs_dir <i>optional</i>	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json
	Validation Error
422	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /return_actigraphy_data

Return actigraphy data

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

GET /classification_for_cutoff_determination

Return classification for cutoff determination

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string
query	dependent_ variable required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	independen t_variable required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	algorithm required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json

GET /principal_component_analysis

Return principal component analysis

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string
query	n_compone nts	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
	required		
query	independent_variables_required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response Content application/json

GET /kmeans_clustering

Return principal component analysis

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id_required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id_required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string
query	n_clusters_required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string
query	independent_variables_required	Parameter for the function execution given by the user	string

Responses	
Code	Description
	Successful Response
200	<i>Content</i> application/json

7.4 DATA AND RESULTS VISUALISATION

In this version of the deliverable (D6.3), due to the length of the descriptions, this paragraph was not updated. The complete list of implemented pages, as well as the necessary parameterization, is listed in detail in chapter 8.

(React) Get /

Fallback page, used if there is an error in the application

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /auto_correlation

Page containing the form and output of the auto correlation EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /partial_auto_correlation

Page containing the form and output of the partial auto correlation EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /filters

Page containing the form and output of the filters EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /welch

Page containing the form and output of the welch EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /stft

Page containing the form and output of the stft EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /find_peaks

Page containing the form and output of the find_peaks EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /periodogram

Page containing the form and output of the function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /power_spectral_density

Page containing the form and output of the power spectral density EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /freesurfer

Page containing the form and output of the MRI functions, recon-all and SAMSEG

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /eeg

Page containing the form and output of the EEG Visualisation function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /eeg/pre

Page containing the form and output of the EEG Visualisation and preprocessing function that precedes most EEG functions

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string
query	type required	Type of function provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /spindles

Page containing the form and output of the spindles EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /slowwaves

Page containing the form and output of the slowwaves EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /freesurfer_reconall_results

Page containing the output of the recon all MRI function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /freesurfer_samseg_results

Page containing the form and output of the SAMSEG MRI function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get normality_Tests

Page containing the form and output of the normality tests function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /transform_data

Page containing the form and output of the transform data function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /pearson_correlation

Page containing the form and output of the Pearson correlation function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /spearman_correlation

Page containing the form and output of the Spearman correlation function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /point_biserial_correlation

Page containing the form and output of the Point Biserial Correlation function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /kendalltau_correlation

Page containing the form and output of the Kendalltau correlation function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /welch t test

Page containing the form and output of the Welch t test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /independent_t_test

Page containing the form and output of the Independent t test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /two_related_samples_t_test

Page containing the form and output of the two related samples t test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /mann_whitney

Page containing the form and output of the Mann Whitney function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /wilcoxon_signed_rank_test

Page containing the form and output of the wilcoxon_signed_rank_test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /alexander_govern_test

Page containing the form and output of the Alexander Govern test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /kruskal_wallis_h_test

Page containing the form and output of the Kruskal Wallis H test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /one_way_ANOVA

Page containing the form and output of the one way ANOVA function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /wilcoxon_rank_sum_statistic

Page containing the form and output of the Wilcoxon rank sum statistic function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /one_way_chi_square_test

Page containing the form and output of the One way chi square test function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /Homoscedasticity

Page containing the form and output of the homoscedasticity function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /alpha_delta_ratio

Page containing the form and output of the alpha delta ratio eeg function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /alpha_variability

Page containing the form and output of the alpha variability EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /asymmetry_indices

Page containing the form and output of the asymmetry indices EEG function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /dashboard

Page containing the form and output of the Dashboard function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /level

Page containing the form and output of the level function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /actigraphy

Page containing the form and output of the actigraphy function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

(React) Get /actigraphy/general

Page containing the form and output of the actigraphy general data function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

GET /free_view

This endpoint initiates the backend part of the MRI Visualisaiton function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

Responses	
Code	Description
200	Successful Response <i>Content</i> application/json
422	Validation Error <i>Content</i> application/json

(React) Get /mri

Page containing the MRI visualisation function

Parameters			
Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	run_id required	Id of workflow run provided by workflow manager	string
query	step_id required	Id of step run provided by workflow manager	string

7.5 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

7.5.1 OVERVIEW PATHS

7.5.1.1 Regression

7.5.1.1.1 [GET/ai/regression/svr/train/instructions](#)

Endpoint Purpose: Retrieves guidelines for initializing the training of Support Vector Regression (SVR) models. It provides users with the required parameters and the format for submitting training data.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
No parameters			
	e.g	<code>"string"</code>	

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.1.2 GET/ai/regression/predict/instructions

Endpoint Purpose: Offers instructions for making predictions using trained regression models. It ensures users are familiar with input data requirements and can interpret the model's output effectively.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
------	------	-------------	--------

No parameters

e.g. `"string"`

Responses

Code	Description	Links
------	-------------	-------

200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
-----	---	----------

404	Not Found	No Links
-----	-----------	----------

422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links
-----	--	----------

7.5.1.1.3 POST/ai/regression/svr/train

Endpoint Purpose: Executes the training process for SVR models. Users can submit their data, and the endpoint will handle the training sequence, providing a model ready for predictive tasks. Train a dataset with SVR Regression algorithm Uses: sklearn.svm.SVR Request body schema is not clear enough. Example: { "workflow_id": UUID, "run_id": UUID, "step_id": UUID, "data": { "dataset": { <BpmnDataObject> | <BpmnDataStore> } }, "user_input": { "features_labels": ["f1", "f2", "fn"], "target_label": "target" }, "params": <RegressionTrainParams> }

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
------	------	-------------	--------

No parameters

e.g

```
{
  "workflow_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "run_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "step_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "data": {
    "additionalProp1": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    },
    "additionalProp2": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    },
    "additionalProp3": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    }
  },
  "user_input": {},
  "params": {
    "C": 1,
    "kernel": "rbf",
    "degree": 3,
    "gamma": "scale",
    "coef0": 0,
    "tol": 0.001,
    "epsilon": 0.1,
    "shrinking": true,
    "cache_size": 200,
    "verbose": false,
    "max_iter": -1
  }
}
```

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links

422

Validation Error
Content application/json

No Links

7.5.1.1.4 *POST/ai/regression/predict*

Endpoint Purpose: This endpoint is used for making predictions with a trained SVR model. Users can submit new data points and receive predictive outputs, which are crucial for continuous data forecasting.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
------	------	-------------	--------

No parameters

e.g

```
{
  "run_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "step_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "data": {
    "additionalProp1": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    },
    "additionalProp2": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    },
    "additionalProp3": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    }
  }
}
```

Responses

Code	Description	Links
------	-------------	-------

200

Successful Response
Content application/json

No Links

404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.2 Classification

7.5.1.2.1 GET/ai/classification/svc/train/instructions

Endpoint Purpose: Provides a comprehensive walkthrough for training Support Vector Classification (SVC) models. It covers data preparation, parameter selection, and submission guidelines.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
No parameters			
	e.g	<code>"string"</code>	

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.2.2 GET/ai/classification/lda/train/instructions

Endpoint Purpose: Delivers instructions for the training of Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) models. It includes details on data formatting, parameter settings, and model training initiation.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
No parameters			
	e.g	<code>"string"</code>	

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

[7.5.1.2.3 GET/ai/classification/predict/instructions](#)

Endpoint Purpose: Offers guidance on how to use classification models to predict outcomes. The instructions ensure users understand how to prepare and submit data for predictions and interpret results.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
No parameters			
	e.g	<code>"string"</code>	

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.2.4 [POST/ai/classification/svc/train](#)

Endpoint Purpose: Enables the training of SVC models by processing user-submitted data. The endpoint generates a model that can classify data into predefined categories.

Train a dataset with SVC Classification algorithm Uses: sklearn.svm.SVC Request body schema is not clear enough. Example: { "workflow_id": UUID, "run_id": UUID, "step_id": UUID, "data": { "dataset": { <BpmnDataObject> | <BpmnDataStore> } }, "user_input": { "features_labels": ["f1", "f2", "fn"], "target_label": "target" }, "params": <ClassificationSVC> | <ClassificationLDA> }

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
------	------	-------------	--------

No parameters

e.g

```
{
  "workflow_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "run_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "step_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "data": {
    "additionalProp1": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    },
    "additionalProp2": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    }
  }
}
```



```

"additionalProp3": {
  "bucket_name": "string",
  "object_name": "string"
},
"user_input": {},
"params": {
  "C": 1,
  "kernel": "rbf",
  "degree": 3,
  "gamma": "scale",
  "coef0": 0,
  "shrinking": true,
  "probability": false,
  "tol": 0.001,
  "cache_size": 200,
  "class_weight": {},
  "verbose": false,
  "max_iter": -1,
  "decision_function_shape": "ovr",
  "break_ties": false,
  "random_state": 0
}
}

```

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.2.5 [POST/ai/classification/lda/train](#)

Endpoint Purpose: Handles the training of LDA models. The endpoint uses input data to create a model adept at maximizing the ratio of between-class variance to within-class variance in the data.

Train a dataset with LDA Classification algorithm Uses: sklearn.discriminant_analysis.LinearDiscriminantAnalysis Request body schema is not clear enough. Example: { "workflow_id": UUID, "run_id": UUID, "step_id": UUID, "data": { "dataset": { <BpmnDataObject> | <BpmnDataStore> } }, "user_input": { "features_labels": ["f1", "f2", "fn"], "target_label": "target" },

"params": <ClassificationSVC> | <ClassificationLDA> }

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
------	------	-------------	--------

No parameters

e.g

```
{
  "workflow_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "run_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "step_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "data": {
    "additionalProp1": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    },
    "additionalProp2": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    },
    "additionalProp3": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    }
  },
  "user_input": {},
  "params": {
    "C": 1,
    "kernel": "rbf",
    "degree": 3,
    "gamma": "scale",
    "coef0": 0,
    "shrinking": true,
    "probability": false,
    "tol": 0.001,
    "cache_size": 200,
    "class_weight": {},
    "verbose": false,
    "max_iter": -1,
    "decision_function_shape": "ovr",
    "break_ties": false,
    "random_state": 0
  }
}
```

Responses

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.2.6 *POST/ai/classification/predict*

Endpoint Purpose: This endpoint is responsible for making classification predictions. Users provide feature data, and the endpoint returns the classification results based on the trained models.

Make predictions with Classification model Request body schema is not clear enough. Example: { "run_id": UUID, "step_id": UUID, "data": { "model": { <BpmnDataObject> | <BpmnDataStore> } } }

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
No parameters			

e.g

```
{
  "run_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "step_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "data": {
    "additionalProp1": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    },
    "additionalProp2": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    },
    "additionalProp3": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    }
  }
}
```

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.3 Clustering

7.5.1.3.1 [GET/ai/clustering/kmeans/train/instructions](#)

Endpoint Purpose: Outlines the procedures for training K-means clustering models. It guides users through preparing their data sets for unsupervised learning and model training.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
No parameters			
	e.g	<code>"string"</code>	

Responses

Code	Description	Links
------	-------------	-------

200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.3.2 GET/ai/clustering/predict/instructions

Endpoint Purpose: Provides instructions for using trained clustering models to assign new data points to existing clusters. It details how users should format and submit their data for predictions.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
No parameters			
	e.g	<code>"string"</code>	

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.3.3 POST/ai/clustering/kmeans/train

Endpoint Purpose: Trains a K-means model using the provided data. This endpoint is critical for identifying patterns and grouping data points without predefined labels.

Train a dataset with KMeans Clustering algorithm Uses: sklearn.cluster.KMeans Request body schema is not clear enough. Example: { "workflow_id": UUID, "run_id": UUID, "step_id": UUID, "data": { "dataset": { <BpmnDataObject> | <BpmnDataStore> } }, "user_input": { "features_labels": ["f1", "f2", "fn"] }, "params": <ClusteringTrainParams> }

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
------	------	-------------	--------

No parameters

e.g

```
{
  "workflow_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "run_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "step_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "data": {
    "additionalProp1": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    },
    "additionalProp2": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    },
    "additionalProp3": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    }
  },
  "user_input": {},
  "params": {
    "n_clusters": 8,
    "init": "k-means++",
    "n_init": 10,
    "max_iter": 300,
    "tol": 0.0001,
    "verbose": 0,
    "copy_x": true,
    "algorithm": "lloyd"
  }
}
```

Responses

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.3.4 [POST/ai/clustering/predict](#)

Endpoint Purpose: Used for predicting the cluster memberships of new data points. The model uses the characteristics of existing clusters to determine where new instances best fit.

Make predictions with Clustering model Request body schema is not clear enough. Example: { "run_id": UUID, "step_id": UUID, "data": { "model": { <BpmnDataObject> | <BpmnDataStore> } } }

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
------	------	-------------	--------

No parameters

e.g

```
{
  "run_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "step_id": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6",
  "data": {
    "additionalProp1": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    },
    "additionalProp2": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    },
    "additionalProp3": {
      "bucket_name": "string",
      "object_name": "string"
    }
  }
}
```

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.4 Data Lake Object Storage

7.5.1.4.1 [GET/datalake/objectstorage/](#)

Endpoint Purpose: Lists all available storage buckets within the data lake. It provides an overview of the data storage landscape for users and applications.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
No parameters			
	e.g	<code>"string"</code>	

Responses

Code	Description	Links
------	-------------	-------

200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.4.2 [GET/datalake/objectstorage/list/{bucket_name}](#)

Endpoint Purpose: Retrieves a list of all objects within a specified bucket. It allows users to navigate and manage their data stored in the data lake effectively.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
No parameters			
	e.g	<code>"string"</code>	

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.1.4.3 [GET/datalake/objectstorage/get/{bucket_name}](#)

Endpoint Purpose: Enables the retrieval of a specific object from within a bucket. This is essential for accessing and downloading data for analysis or model training.

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
------	------	-------------	--------

No parameters

e.g. `"string"`

Responses

Code	Description	Links
------	-------------	-------

200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
-----	---	----------

404	Not Found	No Links
-----	-----------	----------

422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links
-----	--	----------

7.5.1.4.4 [GET/datalake/objectstorage/info/{bucket_name}](#)

Endpoint Purpose: Provides metadata and statistics about a specific object within a bucket, offering insights into

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
------	------	-------------	--------

No parameters

e.g

"string"

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response Content application/json	No Links
404	Not Found	No Links
422	Validation Error Content application/json	No Links

7.5.2 CONCLUSION

The thorough explanation provided in Section 7.5 illustrates the extensive artificial intelligence capabilities built into the MES-CoBraD Expert System. The system facilitates advanced data analysis and decision-making processes in medical and scientific workflows by offering a comprehensive toolset for regression, classification, clustering, and data lake object storage operations through a complex array of endpoints.

Regression endpoints provide the foundation for predictive analytics, allowing users to accurately anticipate continuous variables and future trends. The classification endpoints provide a strong method for grouping complex data into distinct categories, which is essential for making decisions about diagnosis and treatment. Finding natural groupings within the data is made possible by the clustering endpoints, and this is a crucial first step in exposing hidden patterns and correlations.

Moreover, the data lake object storage endpoints ensure seamless data management, supporting the other AI functions by providing a reliable and structured data repository. This symbiotic relationship between data storage and analytical processing underscores the system's architectural synergy.

In essence, Section 7.5 stands as a testament to the system's readiness to handle diverse and complex analytical tasks. It showcases the seamless integration of AI technologies with user-centric workflows, enabling the MES-CoBraD Expert System to deliver actionable insights and support critical healthcare operations effectively.

As we continue to evolve and enhance the system's functionalities, these endpoints will be central to empowering users, driving innovation, and ultimately improving patient outcomes through intelligent and

data-driven approaches.

8 IMPLEMENTATION

8.1 OVERVIEW

The present chapter will show how Advanced Analytics functionalities are placed in specific modules integrated in the MES-CoBraD platform. We'll start by displaying the place in the overall architecture, then discuss hardware and software components. Finally, the Development of specific elements are considered.

8.1.1 PLACEMENT IN THE OVERALL ARCHITECTURE

The place in the overall architecture of the system is marked in the next figure (Figure 59). Advanced Analytics elements are the result of task T6.2 - data Analytics. They are implemented as containers (Docker containers), then they are placed under the container management system orchestrated by Kubernetes.

Data are exchanged with the Data Lake component through the sharing and reuse layer, implemented as result of task T5.3.

Data presentation is placed in the main portal of MES-CoBraD.

Figure 59 - Expert System, Data Analytics and AI in the overall architecture

8.1.2 HARDWARE INFRASTRUCTURE

Data Analytics modules are placed in Docker containers. They are deployed in several nodes orchestrated by Kubernetes. In the development and test environment, there is one master node and three worker nodes.

The specifications for nodes are:

Master node:

- > 2 CPU
- > 16 G RAM
- > 256 G SSD
- > 1 Gb Network

Worker nodes:

- > 6 CPU
- > 16 G RAM
- > 256 G SSD
- > 1 Gb Network

8.1.3 SOFTWARE INFRASTRUCTURE

The modules are placed in a Kubernetes managed cluster. The software infrastructure used is composed of

- > Operating System: Linux UBUNTU
- > Containers: Docker
- > Container management: Kubernetes
- > Java
- > Python

The version used are:

Linux:

- > Distributor ID: Ubuntu
- > Description: Ubuntu 20.04.3 LTS
- > Release: 20.04

> Codename: focal

Docker:

> Docker version 20.10.11, build dea9396

Kubernetes:

> kubeadm version: &version.Info{Major:"1", Minor:"23", GitVersion:"v1.23.3",
GitCommit:"816c97ab8cff8a1c72eccca1026f7820e93e0d25", GitTreeState:"clean",
BuildDate:"2022-01-25T21:24:08Z", GoVersion:"go1.17.6", Compiler:"gc",
Platform:"linux/amd64"}

> Client Version: version.Info{Major:"1", Minor:"23", GitVersion:"v1.23.3",
GitCommit:"816c97ab8cff8a1c72eccca1026f7820e93e0d25", GitTreeState:"clean",
BuildDate:"2022-01-25T21:25:17Z", GoVersion:"go1.17.6", Compiler:"gc",
Platform:"linux/amd64"}

Java:

> openjdk version "11.0.16" 2022-07-19
> OpenJDK Runtime Environment (build 11.0.16+8-post-Ubuntu-0ubuntu120.04)
> OpenJDK 64-Bit Server VM (build 11.0.16+8-post-Ubuntu-0ubuntu120.04, mixed mode,
sharing)

Python:

> Python versions 3.9 and 3.10

8.2 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

8.2.1 OVERVIEW

The Expert System is a web application that uses multiple sources to upload, integrate, analyse and assist in interpreting scientific data. The main purpose of the MES-CoBraD Expert System is to support diagnosis and therapeutic processes with the use of Artificial intelligence and other modules that are integrated with it.

This module consists of a back-end service developed with FastAPI, a front-end developed in ReactJS and multiple libraries used.

The back-end services application has the endpoints needed to successfully execute a given workflow and manage the connection between the various components available in the MES-CoBraD platform (data analytics, Data Lake, visualizations, etc.). The ES-1 requirement, presented in section 4.1, is addressed successfully by the described architecture since the Expert System exposes the steps needed in the most describable way to make the necessary decisions to reach the desired outcome of a given workflow.

The front-end module of the application is a single page application in which the user can create a process using the BPMN creator with diagram representation, which is called a workflow. The user fills in a form all the required data of a workflow and then creates the diagram BPMN for the process that must be followed.

- › Fill the form and create a BPMN diagram of the process:
 - Create a workflow using a workflow name, a small description and diagram that describes the route that will be followed step by step to achieve an end state. Each task that will be created using the diagram that was designed, can use an external module like, the Data Lake, the Data Analytics or the Questionnaire module to analyse data or create multiple algorithm results.

Figure 60 Create a workflow

- › View the XML of the BPMN diagram and save it:
 - There is an option to use the Diagram XML for other 3rd party applications to create a workflow representation or use.

Figure 63 Edit a workflow

› Delete a workflow:

- There is a on option to delete a workflow that you have created.

Figure 64 Delete a workflow

› View the Tasks that should be followed:

- There is an option to view Workflow's tasks with the characteristics that describe it, like the task's type, the input of the task, the output, if it's a manual task or if it uses an external module to be completed.

1.Create new Task here
[Create new Task](#)

2.Workflow "Neurological Diagnosis" Tasks

Task Name: Medical History
type: Manual task
input: Start
Clinical examination
Manual task:
Yes

Task Name: clinical examination
type: Manual task
input: medical history
output: movement disorder
Manual task:
Yes

Task Name: movement disorder
type: ExclusiveGateway
input: clinical examination
output: X_Questionnaire, MRI
Manual task:
No
Analytic module:
Yes

Figure 65 Tasks of the workflow

› Run a Workflow:

- The main feature of the system is the process Run Workflow. That means that a workflow that it is based on a BPMN diagram from the creation section, can be run step by step, using the tasks that are described on the diagram. On this process there is an option to run a step manually, automatically based on Artificial Intelligence algorithms, or use another module of the Expert System to achieve a result and move to the next step.

Figure 66 Run a workflow.

> Step of a workflow Run:

- Each step is running a specific task of the workflow using the available methods.

Figure 67 Step of a workflow.

> Step with redirect to external module:

Figure 68 Step with redirect to external module

> Choose the next Step of the Run:

- There is the option to choose between the next step, based on the diagram. If there is no condition to choose the next path, you are required to follow the next step accordingly.

Figure 69 Choose the next step of a workflow.

> Prediction result

- The module can provide a prediction based on the data provided including the redirects and the other modules that got involved.

Figure 70 Prediction

8.3 QUERY BUILDER

8.3.1 OVERVIEW

Query Builder is a complex component that is used for building and executing SQL queries over the stored data as well as selecting objects/files from the DataLake. This component consists of a back-end service,

developed in FastAPI, and a front-service, developed in ReactJS.

The back-end service provides a large variety of endpoints for building basic SQL queries (SELECT, GROUP BY, JOIN), for getting the available tables and columns names, for executing the query and saving this output. The QRB-1 requirement, which is presented in section 8.1.6, is addressed successfully by the described architecture, since Query Builder builds SQL queries receiving as input data in JSON format and the Query Builder is able to read tabular data as well as in csv format.

The front-end service is a single-page application in which the user selects the respective tab for building selection queries or join queries and for selecting objects from the Object Storage. The user fills in a form, which is converted in JSON format and acts as input in the back-end service. Then, the user is able to preview the data produced by the execution of the SQL query as well as to save the desired data (as a csv file in the Object Storage). When the user saves the data, Query Builder exits and Workflow Manager is informed about the completion of the step and the location of the saved data.

8.3.2 FUNCTIONALITIES

In a nutshell, the main functionalities of Query Builder are the following:

> Build Select SQL query

The screenshot shows the 'SELECT QUERIES' tab of the Query Builder interface. It features a table selection dropdown menu with 'postgresql.public.ntua_tb01_test_relational' selected. To the right, there is an unchecked checkbox for 'Aggregations'. Below this is a columns selection dropdown menu with 'country_id, pr_id' selected. A 'Filters' section contains two buttons: '+ADD FILTER' and 'CLEAR FILTERS'. At the bottom center, there is a 'SUBMIT' button.

Figure 71 Build Select SQL query

> Build Select SQL query with filtering

Figure 72 Build Select SQL query with filtering

› Preview the output of an executed Select SQL Query

country_id	pr_id
1	1
2	2

Figure 73 Preview the output of an executed Select SQL Query

- › Save the output in the Object Storage
- › Build Group by SQL query from one table

Figure 74 Build Group by SQL query from one table

› Build Group by SQL query from one table with filtering

Figure 75 Build Group by SQL query from one table with filtering

› Build Join SQL query

Figure 76 Build Join SQL query

› Build Join SQL query with filtering

Figure 77 Build Join SQL query with filtering

› Build Group by SQL query from multiple tables

Figure 78 Build Group by SQL query from multiple tables

› Build Group by SQL query from multiple tables with filtering

Figure 79 Build Group by SQL query from multiple tables with filtering

› Select file(s) from the Object Storage

Figure 80 Select file(s) from the Object Storage

› Query Builder completes the step, and the Workflow Manager receives a message about the completion of the task and the location of the saved data

Figure 81 Query Builder completes the step, and the Workflow Manager receives a message about the completion of the task and the location of the saved data

New

- › Query builder when receives a parquet file as input, retrieves the different sources-tables inside the parquet file and provide the list of the available sources to the user

Figure 82 Query builder provides the list of the available sources of iceberg.staging_area.test_data

New

- › Filter the tables based on a condition and retrieve the tables that satisfy this condition

Figure 83 Perform join query on tables that satisfy the condition PID = 'e7f6c011776e8db7cd330b54174fd76f7d0216b612387a5ffc81e6f0919683'

8.4 DATA AND RESULTS VISUALISATION

Update

In line with the acquired feedback from the end users of the project and the development of additional features, several changes have been made in the visualisation module.

Amcharts library is removed from most of functions. In many cases the functions required specific views that the library couldn't easily support. In other cases it was removed for consistency purposes, to avoid multiple plotting libraries within a single page.

Additionally, MNE visualisation module, is also removed, since it couldn't meet all the necessary requirements defined by the end users. Specifically, the most important issue was the lack of the basic functionality of modifying the scaling of the plot with precision and the inability of scaling to specific centimetres of the users monitor. It has been replaced by the Neurodesk application. The unified dashboard is also removed since the presentation of results in their own pages was deemed sufficient.

The data and results visualisation module creates different visualisations according to the data that need to be visualised in each case. During the development of the module, it became apparent that not a single library can cover all our needs for different visualisations. In this iteration of the module visualisations are handled mostly by:

> Amcharts5

Amcharts5 is the main library that handles most of our simple plots. These plots include simple

column, lollipop and line charts.

› Matplotlib

- Most functions produce a type of plot that is relevant to it. Such plots are saved as images and uploaded in the DataLake. The users can also download them from the page of the function they appear.

› Plotly

- Several Hypothesis testing functions and Actigraphy pages utilise this plotting library, for its resolution and simplicity. The *.svg output is uploaded to the DataLake for later use.

› Neurodesk

- Some data require specialised libraries to display them. In this specific case, to display the EEG signals. We use the Neurodesk open-source application which creates a virtual desktop environment through LXpanel. The use of this virtual desktop environment has been mostly automated and requires minimal input from the user to operate. It is shown through iframes whenever needed.

› Neurodesk-EDFBrowser

- EEG data require specialised libraries to display them. In this specific case, to display the eeg signals. We use the Neurodesk open-source application which creates a virtual desktop environment through LXpanel. The use of this virtual desktop environment has been mostly automated and requires minimal input from the user to operate. It is shown through iframes whenever needed. The application was not originally part of neurodesk, but we added it in the installation step of our module.

› Neurodesk-Freeview

- Similarly, to display MRI data, we have chosen the Freeview open-source application. It has the same limitation as the MNE library, which requires the existence of a virtual desktop environment. The neurodesk application also includes by default Freeview, which we use similarly, having automated most of the basic functions while allowing the user full access of the Freeview application.

Figure 84 Freeview example page

Data and Results Visualisation functionality is mainly provided in two different manners:

- First visualisations are delivered alongside the results of other modules. For example, in the data analytics module, when a function is completed, its results are returned and accompanied by a visualisation or the application to further explore it.
- Second, there are two specific functions whose main purpose is the visualisation of EEG signals and MRI visualisations respectively which allow the user to explore the data without having a specific purpose or output expected by the system itself. These are the MRI Viewer and EEG Viewer functions, specified in detail below.

8.5 DATA ANALYTICS

8.5.1 OVERVIEW

The data analytics component provides the capability to process, analyse and transform data from different data sources. The libraries and applications used to provide the functionality are the following:

- › MNE & Neurodesk MNE
 - MNE is used in Fast API backend and provides most of the functionality relating to the handling and processing of EEG signals. The MNE library in neurodesk is mostly used for visualisation and functionality relating to it, like annotating.
- › Neurodesk Freesurfer
 - Freesurfer is used for the processing of MRI data. While a standalone implementation of it can be used, it is already included in the neurodesk application itself, so we use the implementation in it.
- › Scipy & Statsmodel & YASA & Pmdarima & pinguin

- These libraries are used to provide various statistic related functions.

> Freesurfer Stats

- Used to handle output from Freesurfer functions.

It provides different functionality tailored to each different type of input data. These functions have been categorised to each different major type of input information sent by the rest of MES-CoBraD platform. Each function is accessed separately from the workflow manager which provides all the additional necessary information such as input data and location of files to the data analytics component. After the user provides any necessary parameterisation and completes any part of the functions that require manual input, each functions relevant output will be stored in the DataLake and the workflow manager.

Update

In all the following functions we specify in the update section, important changes related to their design and implementation. There may be other minor changes such as renaming, adding or removing of parameters, various UI changes etc. that are not explicitly specified as changes but their current state is presented accurately in the following sections. These changes were made after user feedback related to the functionality and ease of use of our functions.

8.5.2 FUNCTION FINALISATION AND AUTOMATIC RE-EXECUTION

New

When a function has finished, the results are uploaded to Trino and the datalake. Along with those results the data analytics modules provides the info.json file to the workflow module.

The file has the following format:

```
{  
  "date_created": "",  
  "workflow_id": "",  
  "run_id": "",  
  "step_id": "",  
  "workspace_id": "",  
  "test_name": "",  
  "test_params": [],  
  "test_results": [],  
  "Output_datasets": [],  
  "Saved_plots": []  
}
```

The file contains basic metadata about date, workflow IDs, the results uploaded to the datalake and finally the parameters used during the run, when applicable.

Following the development of the application it became clear that during the execution of the workflows, many functions do not need to be manually parametrised again and again. It would greatly help the users if they could repeat the execution of a function again without accessing the UI of the application. From the data analytics functions module this is accomplished by both making the API of the backend of the application available to the other modules and by providing the workflow manager the parameters of the executed function. These parameters can be reused as is, by the workflow to execute functions using the backend of the application without accessing the UI of the application. This type of execution doesn't allow changing parameters and won't use the visualisation module, but it allows running in quick succession multiple times. This is only available for functions that makes sense, for example this isn't available for the EEG Viewer and similar ones, because the user participation in it is a necessary part of the function.

8.5.3 EEG FUNCTIONS

EEG functions contain any functionality relevant to the results of electroencephalograms.

8.5.3.1 *The EEG Signal Pre-processing and Presentation*

Before proceeding with the actual functions researchers usually need to be able to view and examine the EEG signal themselves. The EEG Signal Pre-processing and Presentation function gives the option to interact and tinker with the presentation of the EEG data.

Update

This functionality has been further refined in this version and made more straightforward, now it's both a standalone function called EEG Viewer and is also accessible in every function that used EEG data. The function is available to be used from this widget:

Analytics Engine	Workflow Id:	Run Id:	Step Id:
	1	1	1

Back Average Parametirisation

[USE EEG FILE](#) [VIEW/EDIT EEG FILE](#)

OPEN EDF FILE EDITOR ?

Time Before Event (s)
Time before the event (s)

Time After Event (s)
Time after the event(s)

Min PTP Amplitude (V)
Minimum peak-to-peak amplitude

Max PTP Amplitude (V)
Maximum peak-to-peak amplitude

Annotation Name
Annotation name

Plot Display Volt Minimum (μ V)
Plot Display Volt Minimum (μ V)

Plot Display Volt Maximum (μ V)
Plot Display Volt Maximum (μ V)

[SUBMIT](#) [PROCEED >](#)

Figure 85 EEG Edit Widget

When used from this widget, besides accessing all the different viewing capabilities of the EDFBrowser, users can also select a subsection of the file, using either specific channels or specific timeframes. This selection is saved locally and automatically forwarded to the analytics function where it's used by the application automatically.

Figure 86 Opened EEG Edit Widget

8.5.3.2 EEG Viewer

Update

In previous versions of the application, we used the MNE library to visualise the EDF files. We decided to use the EDFbrowser application for the visualisation for several reasons, including better integration of functionalities and usability. The most important reason for the change was that MNE visualisation doesn't support changing the amplitude and timescale with specific values in mind as well as having no way to scale the size of the visualisation to the size of the screen used. All these reasons made it almost unusable for some of the end users therefore we used a new application that could support this functionality.

Currently the EEG Viewer can support the following:

- › Timescale Scaling
 - The User can change the time scaling of the viewer both as sec/page and as mm/sec

Figure 87 EEGViewer Timescale

› Amplitude Scaling

- The User can change the amplitude scaling of the viewer

Figure 88 EEGViewer Amplitude scaling

› Scaling Configuration

- The User can change the scaling based on the real life size of their screen.

Figure 89 EEGViewer Scaling Configuration

› Reference Channels & Bipolar References

- The user can choose to not assign a reference for the EEG signal or assign either an average reference from all the channels or assign specific channels as reference. The user can add new virtual channels which takes the difference between the specified anode and cathode channels.

Figure 90 EEGViewer Reference and Bipolar Channels

› Filtering

- The user can apply several different filters either to some or all the channels.

Figure 91 EEGViewer Add/Edit Filter Window

› Displaying and saving annotations

- The user can view, create and edit annotations through the application. Annotation can also be loaded from csv files instead of being saved in the file.

Figure 92 EEGViewer Annotation Editor and Viewer

› Saving/Loading Montage

- Finally the user can save all the relevant configurations we mentioned previously in a montage. The montage is saved in a file and can be reused later. In addition there are already pre created montages that cover both the common configuration and have been created for specific partners although other can reuse it too.

> Power Spectrum

- The functions displays the power spectrum of the selected signal. It can be opened both statically to compare signal or follow the view of the opened window.

Figure 93 EEGViewer Power Spectrum Window

> Colour Density Spectral Array

- The function displays the CDSA of a signal and can be parametrised.

Figure 94 EEGViewer CDSA Window

> aEEG

- aEEG is a technique for monitoring brain functions.

Figure 95 EEGViewer aEEG Window

> Tutorial

We have included tutorials presented through images, for all these different functionalities that can guide the users through the different steps.

8.5.3.3 Auto Correlation

Updated

- The auto-correlation function correlates the signal with a delayed copy of itself. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel/Column: Selected channel/column to use as time series data
 - Adjusted: If True, then denominators for autocovariance are n-k, otherwise n.
 - FFT: If True, fast fourier transform is used to compute the autocorellation

- Bartlet: If true, bartletts' formula is used
- Missing: specifying how missing values are to be treated. "None": "No checks", "Raise" : "Raises error" , "Drop" : "Remove missing observations"
- Alpha: The confidence intervals for the given level are returned
- Nlags: Number of lags to return autocorrelation for
- The functions returns the following:
 - Visualisations
 - A plot with the calculated lags
 - (Optionally: Only if the alpha parameter has a value) A plot of the confidence interval for each
 - Raw data
 - Calculated lags
 - (Optional) confidence intervals

Updates

The auto-correlation function has been updated to both handle generic csv files in addition to eeg data. The visualization of the function has been updated to use matplotlib library. For better integration with the analytical library and handling of different data types.

Figure 96 Autocorrelation Page

8.5.3.4 Partial Auto Correlation

Updated

- The partial auto-correlation function partially correlates the signal with a delayed copy of itself without taking into account. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Methods: Specifying method to be used for the calculations. The methods are:

- Yule-Walker with sample-size adjustment
- Yule-Walker without adjustment
- Regression of time series on lags of it and on constant
- Regression of time series on lags using a single common sample to estimate all pacf coefficients
- Regression of time series on lags with a bias adjustment.
- Levinson-Durbin recursion with bias correction
- Levinson-Durbin recursion without bias correction
- Burg's partial autocorrelation estimator
 - Alpha: The confidence intervals for the given level are returned
 - Nlags: Number of lags to return autocorrelation for
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - A plot with the calculated lags
 - (Optional: Only if the alpha parameter has a value) A plot of the confidence interval for each
 - Raw data:
 - Calculated lags
 - (Optional) confidence intervals

Updates

The partial auto-correlation function has been updated to both handle generic csv files in addition to eeg data.

The visualization of the function has been updated to use matplotlib library. For better integration with the analytical library and handling of different data types.

Figure 97 Partial auto correlation page

8.5.3.5 Find Peaks

- The find peaks function takes as input a channel of our EEG signal and finds all local maxima by comparing their neighbouring values. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Height of peaks: (Optional) Minimum required height of peaks.
 - Threshold: (Optional) The minimum vertical distance to its neighbouring samples.
 - Prominence: (Optional) Required prominence of peaks
 - Width: (Optional) The required width of peaks.
 - Plateau: (Optional) Required size of the flat top of peaks in samples
 - Distance: (Optional) Required minimal horizontal distance between neighboring continual peaks. Smaller peaks are removed first.
 - Wlen: (Optional) Only used if width or prominence parameters is given.
 - Rel Height: (Optional) Only used if width parameter is given
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - A plot showing the whole channel of the signal with highlighted red dot in every detected maxima. Due to technical limitations of the plotting library the peaks aren't shown at all levels of magnification when they exceed a certain number causing low performance. The user can always magnify the view of the plot to see them all. To avoid confusion the user is notified for the total number of detected maxima.
 - Raw data:
 - Calculated local peaks

Figure 98 Peak Detection page

8.5.3.6 Power Spectral Density

> Updated

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

- In this updated power spectral density function we have combined several previous functions that were separated. This was done because some the previous function were essentially the same function with different technique (**Periodogram**) or had limited use as a standalone function (**Alphadelta ratio, Alphavariability**). In addition we added new functionality including the **Multitaper** technique.
- The function takes as input a channel of an EEG signal and computes the power spectral of the signal. Along with the alphadelta ratio and its alphavariability. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - PSD Type:
 - Welch
 - Periodogram
 - Multitaper

Parameters for Welch

- Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
- Window: Selects the window function that will taper the signal. The options are:
 - Hann
 - Boxcar
 - Triang
 - Blackman
 - Bartlett
 - Flattop
 - Parzen
 - Bohman
 - Blackmanharris
 - Nuttall
 - Barthann
 - Exponential
 - Tukey
 - Taylor
- Nperseg: Length of each segment
- Nooverlap: Number of points to overlap between segments
- Nfft: Length of the FFT used, Nfft must be equal or higher than Nperseg
- Onesided: True to return an onesided spectrum
- Scaling: Density/Spectrum
- Axis: Axis along computation is done
- Average: Method to use when averaging: Mean/Median

Parameters for Periodogram

- Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
- Window: Selects the window function that will taper the signal. The options are: the same as the Welch function refer to that function for a full list.
- Fs: Sampling frequency of the signal, automatically detected if possible
- Nfft: Length of the fast fourier transform used if zero padded is desired, otherwise the length is the same as nperseg

- **Scaling:** Selects between computing the power spectral density or the power spectrum
 - Density
 - Spectrum
- **Axis:** The axis along which the periodogram is computed

Parameters for Multitaper

- **Channel:** Selected channel to use as time series data
- **Fmin/Fmax:** The lower and upper frequencies of interest
- **Bandwidth:** The bandwidth of the multi taper windowing function in Hz.
- **Adaptive:** If true, adaptive weights are used to combine the tapered spectra
- **Low Bias:** If true, only tapers with more than 90% spectral concentration within bandwidth are used.
- **Normalisation:** Normalisation strategy. If “full”, the power spectral density will be normalised by the sampling rate as well as the length of the signal. Otherwise only the length of the signal is used.
 - Full
 - Length

- The function returns the following:

- **Visualisations:**
 - Plots of the calculated power spectral densities, different for each technique used if multiple.
- **Raw data:**
 - Power spectral densities, alphadelta ratio and alpha variability

Figure 99 Power spectral density page

8.5.3.7 Short time Fourier Transform

The stft function uses scipy implementation of the stft algorithm. The algorithm itself is used to quantify the change of a nonstationary eeg channel's signal frequency and phase over time

- The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Window: : Selects the window function that will taper the signal. The options are: the same as the Welch function refer to that function for a full list.
 - Nperseg: Length of each segment.
 - Noverlap: Number of points to overlap between segments.
 - Nfft: Length of the fast fourier transform used if zero padded is desired, otherwise the length is the same as nperseg
 - Onesided: If enabled returns one sided spectrum of real data other returns two sided.
 - Boundary: Specifies whether the input signal is extended at both ends
 - Padded: Specifies whether the input signal is zero-padded at the end
 - Axis: The axis along which the periodogram is computed
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:

Figure 100 Short Time Fourier Transform Page

8.5.3.8 Assymetry indices

- The asymmetry indices function calculates the asymmetry indices value of a signal. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channels: Selected channels to use as time series data
 - Nperseg: Length if each segment.
 - Window: : Selects the window function that will taper the signal. The options are: the same as the Welch function refer to that function for a full list.

- Noverlap: Number of points to overlap between segments.
 - Nfft: Length of the fast fourier transform used if zero padded is desired, otherwise the length is the same as nperseg
 - Onesided: If enabled returns one sided spectrum of real data other returns two sided.
 - Scaling: Selects between computing the power spectral density or the power spectrum
 - Density
 - Spectrum
 - Axis: The axis along which the periodogram is computed
 - Average: The method to average periodograms
 - Mean
 - Median
- The function returns the following:
- Raw data: The calculated asymmetry indices

Figure 101 Asymmetry indices Page

8.5.3.9 Spindles Detection

- The spindle detection function takes as input a channel of an EEG signal and automatically detects the spindles according to the parameters. The function also calculates the phase amplitude coupling. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
- Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Spindle Freq Sp Low & High: Spindles frequency range. Default is 12 to 15 Hz
 - Spindle Freq Broad Low & High: Spindle Broad band frequency range. Default is 1 to 30 Hz.
 - Spindle Duration Low & High: The minimum and maximum duration of the spindles. Default is 0.5 to 2 seconds.

- Min Distance: If two spindles are closer than the specified minimum distance they are merged into a single spindles. Default is 500 ms.
 - Detection thresholds:
 - Threshold Rel Pow: Relative power (= power ratio freq_sp / freq_broad). Default is: 0.2
 - Pac window: Array of phases of shape
 - Pac step: Array of amplitudes of shape
 - Extra Pac window: Array of phases of shape
 - Extra pac step: Array of amplitudes of shape
 - The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - A plot of the averaged spindle in the data
 - PAC plot
 - Extra PAC plot
 -
 - Raw data:
 - Detected spindles

Figure 102 Spindle Detection Page

8.5.3.10 Slowwaves Detection

- The slowwave detection function takes as input a channel of an EEG signal and detects the slowwaves. It returns both the dataset and plots related to the phase at sigma peaks. The function also calculates the phase amplitude coupling. The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Freq Sw Low & High: Slow wave frequency range. Default is 0.3 to 1.5 Hz
 - Duration Negative Low & High: The minimum and maximum duration of the

- negative deflection of the slow wave. Default is 0.3 to 1.5 second
 - Duration Positive Low & High: The minimum and maximum duration of the positive deflection of the slow wave. Default is 0.3 to 1.5 second
 - Amplitude Positive Low & High: Absolute minimum and maximum positive peak amplitude of the slow-wave. Default is 10 uV to 150 uV.
 - Amplitude Negative Low & High: Absolute minimum and maximum negative trough amplitude of the slow-wave. Default is 40 uV to 200 uV.
 - Amplitude Peak to Peak Low & High: Minimum and maximum peak-to-peak amplitude of the slow-wave. Default is 75 uV to 350 uV.
 - Coupling: If True, will also calculate the phase-amplitude coupling between the slow-waves phase and the spindles-related sigma band amplitude.
 - Remove Outliers: If True, will automatically detect and remove outliers spindles using
 - Pac window: Array of phases of shape
 - Pac step: Array of amplitudes of shape
 - Extra Pac window: Array of phases of shape
 - Extra pac step: Array of amplitudes of shape
 - The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - A Visualisation of the detected Slowwaves in the signal
 - Phast at sigma peaks plot
 - PAC plot
 - Extra PAC plot
 - Raw data:
 - Detected Slowwaves

The screenshot displays the 'Analytics Engine' interface. The top navigation bar shows 'Workflow Id: 1', 'Run Id: 1', and 'Step Id: 4'. The main content is divided into two panels: 'Slowwave Parameterisation' and 'Result Visualisation'.

Slowwave Parameterisation Panel:

- General Parameterisation:**
 - Sampling Frequency of Hypogram: 0.0333333333333333
 - Current Sampling Frequency of Hypogram: [input field]
- Slowwaves Parameterisation:**
 - Slowwave freq sw Low: 0.3, Slowwave freq sw High: 1.5
 - Slowwave freq dur neg Low: 0.3, Slowwave dur neg High: 1.5
 - Slowwave Dur Neg Low: 0.1, Slowwave Dur Neg High: 1
 - Slowwave freq dur pos Low: 0.1, Slowwave dur pos High: 1
 - Slowwave Dur Pos Low: 0.1, Slowwave Dur Pos High: 1
 - Slowwave amp neg Low: 40, Slowwave amp neg High: 200
 - Slowwave Amp Neg Low: 10, Slowwave Amp Neg High: 150
 - Slowwave amp pos Low: 75, Slowwave amp pos High: 350
 - Slowwave Amp Pos Low: 75, Slowwave Amp Pos High: 350
 - Slowwave include Low: 2, Slowwave include High: 3
 - Slowwave Amp ptp Low: [input field], Slowwave Amp ptp High: [input field]
 - Slowwave Outliers: True
 - Slowwave Coupling: [input field]

Result Visualisation Panel:

- Navigation tabs: INITIAL DATASET, SLOWWAVES RESULTS (active), PAC RESULTS, EXTRA PAC RESULTS, ALL RESULTS
- Section: Slowwaves Results
- Visualisations:
 - A circular plot showing detected slowwaves with a red arrow pointing to a specific point.
 - A polar plot showing the phase-amplitude coupling (PAC) between slowwaves and spindles, with radial lines indicating coupling strength at various angles.
- EXPORT button

Figure 103 Slowwave Detection Page

8.5.3.11 Predictions

- The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Test Size: Test size to use
 - Future Seconds: Number of future seconds to calculate. Positive integer.
 - Start P: The starting value of p, the order (or number of time lags) of the autoregressive (“AR”) model. Must be a positive integer. (default = 1)
 - Start Q: The starting value of q, the order of the moving-average (“MA”) model. Must be a positive integer. (default = 1)
 - Max P: The maximum value of p, inclusive. Must be a positive integer greater than or equal to start_p (default = 5)
 - Max Q: The maximum value of q, inclusive. Must be a positive integer greater than start_q (default = 5)
 - Method: The method determines which solver to be used, and it can be chosen from among the following strings:
 - ‘newton’ for Newton-Raphson
 - ‘nm’ for Nelder-Mead
 - ‘bfgs’ for Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS)
 - ‘lbfgs’ for limited-memory BFGS with optional box constraints (default)
 - ‘powell’ for modified Powell’s method
 - ‘cg’ for conjugate gradient
 - ‘ncg’ for Newton-conjugate gradient
 - ‘basinhopping’ for global basin-hopping solver
 - Information Criterion: Selects which information criterion to use for the best ARIMA model. Available choices:
 - AIC (Akaike Information Criterion, default)
 - BIC (Bayesian Information Criterion)
 - HQIC (Hannan-Quinn Information Criterion)

- OOB (Out Of Bag)
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - Plots shown the predicted signal on its own and with the rest of it
 - Raw data:
 - Statistis on the predicted signal
 - Predicted signal

Figure 104 Prediction Page

8.5.3.12 Artifacts using the Independent Component Analysis (ICA) method

- The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - n_components: Number of principal components (from the pre-whitening PCA step) that are passed to the ICA algorithm during fitting: Number of principal components (from the pre-whitening PCA step) that are passed to the ICA algorithm during fitting
 - method: The ICA method to use in the fit method, namely *fastica*, *infomax*, and *picard*.
 - indices to exclude: which components to exclude
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations
 - Plot estimated latent sources given the unmixing matrix.
 - Plot the reconstructed data
 - Raw data
 - Reconstructed data

Figure 105 ICA Artifact Fix Page

8.5.3.13 Back Average

New

The Back Average function is used to select and compare averages of specific sections of an EEG. Annotations are used to indicate the events into question and along with the parameterisation the algorithm selects and averages the specified sections presenting side by side all the results per channel. The user can also select the height of the values in the produced plots. The plots can be downloaded and saved both as a single image or multiple.

- The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Time before and after event: How many seconds before and after annotation should be averaged
 - Min – Max ptp amplitude: The minimum and maximum peak to peak amplitude in the event
 - Annoation_name: The name of the annotation in question
 - Plot Volt Minimum – Maximum: The displayed minimum and maximum μV in the displayed plots
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - Visualisaiton of averages per channel

Figure 106 Back Average page

8.5.3.14 Sleep Statistics

New

The Sleep Statistics function uses as input both eeg data and an accompanying hypnogram and provides various statistics about sleep stages, sleep transition matrix and sleep stage stability.

- The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Sampling rate of the Hypnogram
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - Sleep Transition Matrix
 - Raw data:
 - Sleep Statistics
 - Sleep transition matrix and conditional probability data
 - Sleep stage stability data

Figure 107 Sleep Statistics Page

8.5.3.15 Spectrogram Bandpower

New

The function calculates the spectrogram of an eeg channel, presented alongside the sleep stages based on both eeg and hypnogram data. It also upsamples the hypnogram to calculate along the welch bandpower for each channel and each stage.

- The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Bandpower relative: If true bandpower is divided by bands
 - Bandpower Bandpass: If true applies a bandpass filter based on bands
 - Bands: List of frequency bands (Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta, Theta, Sigma)
 - Sleep Stages:
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - Visualisation of spectrogram with sleep stages
 - Raw data:
 - Bandpower data

Figure 108 Spectrogram Bandpower Page

8.5.3.16 Automatic Sleep Stage Classification

New

The automatic sleep stage classification uses a yasa function to automatically detect and create a hypnogram based on an EEG channel. EOG and EMG channels can also be provided for additional precision but those are optional. The user is further prompted to the manual sleep stage classification function if he wants to do any changes before saving the data.

- The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - EEG Channel: Selected channel to use
 - EOG Channel: Selected channel to use
 - EMG Channel: Selected channel to use
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - Visualisation of averages per channel
 - Raw data:
 - Detected spindles

Figure 109 Automatic Sleep Stage Classification page

8.5.3.17 Manual Sleep Stage Classification

New

The manual sleep stage classification function reuses the EEG viewer function. It takes advantage of the visualisation and editing of the EDFBrowser application. The function is also able to import hypnogram data from different applications and convert them into annotations, as specified in the edf+ specification and able to be read by our application. We have already created a preset for the setting of the EDFBrowser that allows the users to easily add and edit and the sleep stages.

- The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - User input in editor
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - Visualisation of hypnogram and EEG viewer
 - Raw data:
 - Produced or Edited hypnogram in saved as annotation in standalone file

Figure 110 Manual Sleep Stage Classification

8.5.3.18 Envelop Trend

New

The function Envelop Trend created a trend line of a channel of EEG data. It can use multiple methods to create those trend lines, such as moving average.

- The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channel: Selected channel to use as time series data
 - Window Size:
 - Percent: The percent of the moving average
 - Method: Simple, Cumulative, Exponential
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - Visualisation of envelop trend
 - Raw data:
 - Results of envelop trend

Figure 111 Envelop Trend page

8.5.3.19 Group Sleep Sensitivity Analysis

New

The Group Sleep Sensitivity Analysis function essentially combines several functionalities at once. It's a function that can handle groups of EEG files and does several different functions we mentioned before in sequence. These functions are: Sleep Statistics, Bandpower, display of hypnograms, worthless sensitivity.

- The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - Channels: The channel that will be selected for the
- The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations:
 - Hypnograms
 - Tables for all raw data
 - Raw data:
 - Most of these data is presented according to the groups specified by the user
 - Sleep Statistics
 - Sleep Matrix
 - Sleep Stability
 - Bandpower

0	1	2	3	4
0.75	0.083	0.167	0	0
0.438	0.438	0.125	0	0
0.75	0.167	0	0	0.083
0.722	0.111	0.019	0	0.148
0.954	0.031	0.015	0	0
0	1	0	0	0
0.972	0.021	0.007	0	0
0.545	0.364	0.091	0	0
0	0.5	0.4	0	0.1

Figure 112 Group Sleep Sensitivity page

8.5.4 MRI FUNCTIONS

The MRI functions contain any functionality relevant to the analysis and results of Magnetic resonance

imaging data. As already mentioned, we utilise the Freesurfer library in the neurodesk application. The user and system input is being sent as a series of commands via ssh to Neurodesk application. The following MRI functions were created:

8.5.4.1 *Recon-all*

The recon-all function of the Freesurfer library, implements a cortical reconstruction process. In our implementation we automatically run the full reconstruction process which follows these steps.

- > Motion Correction
- > Nu intensity correction
- > Talairach
- > Normalisation
- > Skull Strio
- > Automatic Subcortical Segmentation
- > EM Registration
- > CA Normalise
- > CA Register
- > Remove neck
- > EM Registration, with Skull
- > CA Label
- > Aseg Stats
- > Normalization2
- > WM Segmentation
- > Cut/Fill
- > Tesselation
- > Orgin Surface Smoothing
- > Inflation
- > QSphere
- > Automatic Topology Fixer
- > Final Surfaces
- > Cortical Ribbon Mask
- > Spherical Inflation
- > Ipsilateral Surface Registration
- > Contralateral Surface Registration
- > Average Curvature
- > Cortical Parcellation
- > Parcellation Statistics

This process can take a lot of time (more than 6 hours) so the user needs to provide some manual input. In the user interface, he/she can look at the current output of the process and check whether it's finalised. Upon the user confirmation that the process is finished, the output is automatically saved and loaded to the freeview application where the verification process starts. This process aims to ensure that the results of recon-all are valid. Several screenshots of slices are taken at different coordinates to be presented in the user interface, so the trained user can verify the accuracy of the output. In addition, the output files are also opened in the MRI visualisation function.

The recon-all results page is shown below. In this page we can see the various metrics of the files produced by the recon-all process and the verification screenshots taken as we specified previously.

- › The parameters expected from the user are the following:
 - User must select the file to be run
- › The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations
 - MRI visualisation.
 - Verification screenshots
 - Recon-all output table presentation
 - Raw data
 - recon-all output

Update

We have updated the presentation of the results of the recon-all function and the overall presentation of the pages. In addition, we added a file picker for the user to select the appropriate files. We opted for this choice because otherwise we would need to enforce specific naming conventions on the files, since the new functionality requires multiple files.

Figure 11.3 Recon-All function page

8.5.4.2 Recon-All Statistic Results

Additionally, the results page is accessible both after the run of the application and as a standalone function, in case the user needs to reload previous runs of the application. The function should be able to handle and display results of the recon-all function even if they were uploaded to the platform although that isn't guaranteed, results obtained in the previous runs of the recon all function are guaranteed to be displayed correctly.

Several statistics files are produced from recon-all. We have produced visualisations of these files.

> `aseg.stats`

This file contains statistics of the segmented subcortical structures found in `mri/aseg.mgz`. More specifically, it consists of some segmentation statistics, and also a table of structural measurements of various brain structures. These statistics are shown in our application, as illustrated in Figure 114. Furthermore, the volume of subcortical regions that is included in the aforementioned table is also plotted using the `plot_aseg` function of `ggseg` library (Figure 115).

Structural Measurements

Recon-All Results

Index	SegId	NVoxels	Volume_mm3	StructName	normMean	normStdDev	normMin	normMax	normRange
1	4	20418	20498.6	Left-Lateral-Ventricle	24.0275	10.5825	4.0000	85.0000	81.0000
2	5	994	1009.4	Left-Inf-Lat-Vent	37.2394	14.3268	7.0000	76.0000	69.0000
3	7	16279	17189.7	Left-Cerebellum-White-Matter	85.4124	6.1818	25.0000	101.0000	76.0000
4	8	60568	60243.2	Left-Cerebellum-Cortex	60.0515	12.1160	6.0000	96.0000	90.0000
5	10	7049	6769.3	Left-Thalamus	87.1299	9.6494	28.0000	107.0000	79.0000
6	11	3367	3309.9	Left-Caudate	78.4179	8.5603	42.0000	104.0000	62.0000
7	12	4157	4149.8	Left-Putamen	86.4917	5.3546	56.0000	103.0000	47.0000
8	13	2103	2080.5	Left-Pallidum	99.1778	4.3757	64.0000	115.0000	51.0000
9	14	2464	2525.2	3rd-Ventricle	23.9115	11.1227	6.0000	76.0000	70.0000
10	15	2705	2893.0	4th-Ventricle	25.4839	10.5942	4.0000	69.0000	65.0000
11	16	23849	23690.9	Brain-Stem	81.2475	9.8448	15.0000	106.0000	91.0000

1-12 of 45 < >

Figure 114 Aseg.Stats Tab

Aseg segmentation - Volume (mm3)

Figure 115 Aseg Segmentation Volume Plot

brainvol.stats

This file contains brain measurements statistics that have been obtained from recon-all. This

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

information is presented as shown in Figure 116.

Figure 116 brainvol.stats File

- › *h.aparc.a2009s, *h.aparc.DKAtlas, *h.aparc.pial.stats, *h.aparc.stats, *h.BA_exvivo.stats, *h.BA_exvivo.thresh.stats,

These files all have similar contents. They start with some statistics about brain measurements of the hemisphere they correspond to, and finish with a table consisting of structural measurements of various brain structures. This information is presented as shown in Figure 117. Each file name is referring to 2 files, one for each hemisphere (for example *h.aparc.a2009s refers to lh.aparc.a2009s and rh.aparc.a2009s). Every tab of our interface presents these 2 files' whole brain measurements separately and the structural measurements tables of these 2 files are merged into a single table. The information of which hemisphere each row is referring to is retained in the column 'Hemisphere'.

Structural Measurements

Recon-All Results

StructName	NumVert	SurfArea	GrayVol	ThickAvg	ThickStd	MeanCurv	GaussCurv	FoldInd	CurvInd	Hemisphere
G_and_S_occipital_Inf	1967	1467	4097	2.317	0.787	0.155	0.049	30	3.9	Left
G_and_S_paracentral	1783	1068	2772	2.313	0.486	0.119	0.039	19	2.4	Left
G_and_S_subcentral	1645	1143	3585	2.692	0.602	0.141	0.039	17	2.6	Left
G_and_S_transv_frontopol	682	456	1492	2.630	0.494	0.149	0.042	11	1.0	Left
G_and_S_cingul_Ant	2968	1860	5075	2.472	0.579	0.134	0.037	34	4.1	Left
G_and_S_cingul_Mid_Ant	1905	1253	2837	2.205	0.463	0.110	0.023	17	1.8	Left
G_and_S_cingul_Antd-Post	1481	1021	2553	2.428	0.627	0.111	0.024	13	1.5	Left
G_cingul-Post-dorsal	666	482	1480	2.400	0.576	0.153	0.039	10	1.1	Left
G_cingul-Post-ventral	422	290	775	2.299	0.508	0.117	0.027	4	0.5	Left
G_cuneus	2269	1510	3431	1.959	0.455	0.139	0.039	31	3.5	Left
G_front_inf-Opercular	1604	1051	3596	2.647	0.567	0.123	0.041	15	2.4	Left

1-12 of 148 < >

Figure 117 *h.aparc.a2009s.stats File

> *h.w-g.pct.stats

These files contain statistics about surface-wise gray/white contrast of various brain structures. Like above, this tab presents the statistics of both hemispheres together in one table (Figure 118).

Analytics Engine | Workflow id: 2 | Run id: 2 | Step id: 1

Recon-all Results

ASEG-STATS | BRAINVOL-STATS | *H-APARC-A2009S-STATS | *H-APARC-DKTATLAS-STATS | *H-APARC-PRAL-STATS | *H-APARC-STATS | *H-BA-EXVIVO-STATS | *H-BA-EXVIVO-THRESH-STATS | *H-W-G-PCT-STATS | WMPARC-STATS

Structural Measurements

Recon-All Results

Index	SegId	NVertices	Area_mm2	StructName	Mean	StdDev	Min	Max	Range	SNR	Hemisphere
1	1000	8710	5456.1	unknown	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-nan	Left
2	1001	1648	1163.8	bankssts	21.1606	7.2059	-9.5235	46.6581	56.1816	2.9366	Left
3	1002	1105	747.3	caudalanteriorcingulate	27.4096	7.5496	1.2977	52.3649	51.0672	3.6306	Left
4	1003	3942	2637.4	caudalmiddlefrontal	18.3664	7.0038	-6.3093	51.4329	57.7422	2.6223	Left
5	1005	2484	1676.4	cuneus	17.1552	6.8116	-6.5485	43.7644	50.3129	2.5185	Left
6	1006	832	579.1	entorhinal	20.8154	8.2936	-6.1626	43.3818	49.5444	2.5098	Left
7	1007	4698	3538.3	fusiform	21.5849	8.7740	-32.5325	51.5247	84.0572	2.4601	Left
8	1008	6218	4521.9	inferiorparietal	18.4101	7.4767	-40.1785	65.7514	105.9299	2.4603	Left
9	1009	4207	3047.5	inferiortemporal	20.4619	8.8705	-42.3075	49.0722	91.3797	2.3067	Left
10	1010	1946	1317.0	isthmuscingulate	21.2683	6.8549	-1.0763	43.1862	44.2626	3.1026	Left
11	1011	7437	5544.6	lateraloccipital	18.2136	7.7564	-29.8751	67.3120	94.1871	2.3482	Left

1-12 of 70 < >

Figure 118 *h.w-g.pct.stats File

> wmparc.stats

This file contains statistics about WM Parcellation. It starts with some general statistics and finishes with a table consisting of structural measurements of various brain structures (Figure 119).

Figure 119 wmparc.stats File

8.5.4.3 MRI Co-registration

New

In order to be able to handle multi contrast data, we included the coregistration functions of Freesurfer module. This is usually done before the SAMSEG function and its output can be used in that function.

The function used in practise two different methods “mri_coreg” and “mri_vol2vol”. The interim results of these functions can also be uploaded to the datalake if necessary.

After the function are run, the results are automatically opened with the MRI_Viewer function which open both the origin file and the co-registered flair file with specific settings that were specified by the end users.

Figure 120 Coreg function page

8.5.4.4 SAMSEG

The samseg function or Sequence Adaptive Multimodal SEGmentation (SAMSEG), is a function that segments brain structures from MRI scans without pre-processing. Its main advantage is that it accepts multi-contrast MRI data without prior assumptions on the specific type of scanner or pulse sequences used.

Figure 121 Samseg function page

Update

With the inclusion of the MRI Co-registration functions we enable the capability for the samseg function to be run with both the original file and the coregistered flair file produced by the MRI Co-registration function. Because of the presence of multiple files and to support multiple files the page now includes a file picker for the user to select the appropriate files. We opted for this choice because otherwise we would need to enforce specific naming conventions on the files.

› The parameters expected from the user are the following:

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

- User must select one or multiple files to be run
- › The function returns the following:
 - Visualisations
 - SAMSEG output table presentation
 - Raw data
 - SAMSEG output

Measure	Value	Unit
Unknown	676152.082035	mm³
Skull	209553.106998	mm³
Soft_Nonbrain_T1	520831.579403	mm³
Brain-Stem	11512.130368	mm³
CSF	215683.673334	mm³
Left-Cerebellum-Cortex	27361.713278	mm³
Right-Cerebellum-Cortex	30655.102753	mm³
4th-Ventricle	822.520029	mm³
Fluid_Inside_Ey	5261.768411	mm³

Figure 122 Samseg Results page

8.5.4.5 MRI Viewer

The MRI Viewer functions opens specified files using the Freeview application. Depending on where the function is called from different files are loaded with different configurations.

Figure 123 MRIVIEWER example page

The application allows users to view anatomical volumes, surfaces, rotations and segmentation while allowing the user to freely change the view.

8.5.5 ACTIGRAPHY FUNCTIONS

8.5.5.1 Actigraphy Function Page

New

The data analytics module can view and process actigraphy data exported from the capturing device (sample was acquired from a Philips Respironics | Actigraphy monitoring devices), in a dedicated function, before using them in other data analytics functions or as part of hypothesis testing.

First epoch by epoch data. This data is continuous and usually captured a few times every hour, measuring the state of the monitored person. The data includes values for the time it was captured, their activity, whitelight, sleep/wake, interval status and marker. This function allows the user through the plot to select a specific timeframe he wants to use in other data analytics functions and save it as a new file. Additionally, the user can select which assessment algorithm of the following: Crespo, Oakley, Sadeh-Scripp, Cole-Kripke; he wants to run on the raw data.

› Output:

- Visualisations:
 - Initial Actigraphy Datatable
 - Initial Activity, Sleep/wake plot
 - Assessment Algorithms
 -
- Raw data
 - Specified timeframe of actigraphy data

Analytics Engine				Actigraphy Assessment Algorithms Results											
Workflow Id:	Run Id:	Step Id:													
1	1	6		Actigraphies Parameterisation			Actigraphy Assessment Algorithms Results								
Data Preview				INITIAL DATASET	INITIAL VISUALISATION RESULTS	ASSESSMENT ALGORITHMS	FINAL DATASET	FINAL VISUALISATION RESULTS							
File Name:															
0345-024_18_07_2022_13_00_00_New_Analysis.csv															
Selected Variables															
Dates: 2022-07-18 12:00:00 - 2022-07-22 12:00:00															
Assessment Algorithm: Cole - Kripke															
Start Date: 2022-07-18 12:00:00															
Select the dates to visualise the actigraphy data.															
End Date: 2022-07-22 12:00:00															
Select the dates to visualise the actigraphy data.															
Assessment Algorithm: Cole - Kripke															
Select the assessment algorithm to run on the dataset.															
SUBMIT															
Line	Date	Time	Off-Wrist Status	Activity	Marker	White Light	Red Light	Green Light	Blue Light	Sleep/Wake	Interval Status				
1	18/07/2022	13:00:00	0		0						ACTIVE				
2	18/07/2022	13:00:15	0	0	0	5377.42	123	88	84.6		ACTIVE				
3	18/07/2022	13:00:30	0	0	0	2228.08	122	82.9	82.3		ACTIVE				
4	18/07/2022	13:00:45	0	0	0	1932.85	123	81.3	81.9		ACTIVE				
5	18/07/2022	13:01:00	0	0	0	155.54	150	57.1	67		ACTIVE				
6	18/07/2022	13:01:15	0	5	0	46.81	127	16.5	30.9		ACTIVE				
7	18/07/2022	13:01:30	0	73	0	88.55	85.4	32.1	37.6		ACTIVE				
8	18/07/2022	13:01:45	0	67	0	77.58	108	28	39.2		ACTIVE				
9	18/07/2022	13:02:00	0	12	0	532.89	134	76.7	79.1	1	ACTIVE				
10	18/07/2022	13:02:15	0	0	0	481.44	136	73	76.7	1	ACTIVE				
11	18/07/2022	13:02:30	0	0	0	595.24	139	72.6	77.8	1	ACTIVE				
12	18/07/2022	13:02:45	0	0	0	571.1	137	73	77.5	0	ACTIVE				
13	18/07/2022	13:03:00	0	44	0	618.81	112	64.2	67.1	1	ACTIVE				
14	18/07/2022	13:03:15	0	25	0	0	61	103	55.9	1	ACTIVE				
15	18/07/2022	13:03:30	0	0	0	0	100	104	69	0	ACTIVE				
16	18/07/2022	13:03:45	0	4	0	1302.33	107	69.5	68.5	1	ACTIVE				

Figure 124 - Dataframe displaying initial actigraphy dataset

Figure 125 - Initial visualization results with marked sleep period

Figure 126 - Graphic representation of activity and assessment algorithm applied to the dataset

After performing the initial visualizations of this page, the user will be able to alter the activity status of the dataset. Using the 3rd tab on the tab panel (aka ASSESSMENT ALGORITHMS), they can select a specific time-period using the select box provided by Plotly in the visualization. After that, they can select one out of four activity status given (ACTIVE, REST, REST-S) and apply that to the selected time-period of the dataset using the submit button. Eventually, the 2 last tabs will now present 2 new outputs.

› Output:

- Visualisations:

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

- Final Actigraphy Datable
- Final Activity, Sleep/wake plot

Figure 127 - Dataframe displaying the data after the user has altered the activity status

Figure 128 - Final visualization results after the user has altered the activity status

8.5.5.2 Actigraphy Functional Linear Modelling Page

New

The actigraphy functional linear modelling functions presents a smooth representation of the data for any

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

subsequent analysis. There is no option given to select a timeframe, because there was no need due to the type of the data.

The general actigraphy data functions, on the other hand, presents an overview of statistics of the data gathered by the devices. There is no option given to select a timeframe, because there was no need due to the type of the data.

› Output:

○ Visualisations:

- Fourier “smoothed” activity vs raw activity

Figure 129 - Functional Linear Modelling applied to a single dataset

8.5.5.3 Actigraphy Singular Spectrum Analysis Page

New

The actigraphy singular spectrum analysis function, which is related to the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for timeseries, presents four visualizations. The singular spectrum analysis is used to decompose the activity signal into additive components and quantify their relative importance.

› Output:

○ Visualisations:

- Scree diagram (Singular value decomposition)
- Correlation matrix (displays the reconstructed components which are “correlated” so that they can be grouped together)
- Diagonal averaging
- Compare the original signal with its reconstruction

Actigraphy Analysis Results

SINGULAR SPECTRUM ANALYSIS

Figure 130 - Scree diagram of the Singular Spectrum Analysis

Figure 131 - W-Correlation matrix

Figure 132 - Graph showing the diagonal averaging

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

Figure 133 - Comparison between the original signal and its reconstruction

8.5.5.4 Actigraphy Detrended Fluctuation Analysis Page

New

Scale-invariant, or fractal, patterns over time scales characterize a temporal organization which is exhibited by human activity. The actigraphy detrended fluctuation analysis function allows the user to quantify these fractal patterns. It produces 3 visualizations.

› Output:

○ Visualisations:

- Detrended and integrated data profile
- Signal segmentation into non-overlapping windows
- Signal segmentation with various q-orders

Figure 134 - Data profile of the Detrended Fluctuation Analysis

Figure 135 - Signal segmentation

Figure 136 - Graph displaying signal segmentation with various q-orders

8.5.5.5 *Cosinor analysis*

New

The Actigraphy Cosinor Analysis aims at estimating key parameters of the actigraphy count series by fitting these data with a cosine or a sine curve with a time period of 24 hours. The user only needs to input the filename for this function.

Figure 137 – Cosinor analysis.

8.5.5.6 Actigraphy Metrics

New

The Actigraphy Metrics function aims at calculating various variables. Firstly, non-parametric, such as Interdaily stability (IS), Intradaily variability (IV) and Relative amplitude (RA). Furthermore, it can calculate the mean IS and IV. Lastly, IS, IV and RA can be calculated per period. Except for the dataset to be used, in this function the user has to also input the frequency, the frequency offsets, the period, the period offsets, whether to binarize (True or False) and the threshold.

Figure 138 - Actigraphy Metrics results

8.5.5.7 Actigraphy Masking Page

New

In many time series and activity visualizations, there are specific windows that seem “suspicious” because there appears to be continuous inactivity (activity equals to 0). The actigraphy masking page allows the user to check for such windows from 5 minutes up to 12 hours and 55 minutes.

- › Output:
 - Visualisations:
 - Inactivity masking check

Figure 139 - Visualization of inactivity masking in the dataset (check for continuous inactivity for 20 minutes) Additionally, the user can input their own start time and end time to mask inactivity periods.

- > Output:
 - Visualisations:
 - Manually add mask periods

Figure 140 - User adding a masking period for 19th of July 2022 from 9:30 to 17:30

8.6 HYPOTHESIS TESTING INTERFACE

8.6.1 OVERVIEW

In this section, an overview of the implemented functions and methods to support the hypotheses testing defined in the deliverable D4.5 is provided.

The following nine (9) general categories are defined, including 60 basic functions with the relevant sub-methods. The implementation of these functions required several classes and auxiliary functions (dealing mostly with data handling, data plotting, etc.), which are beyond the scope of the deliverable.

Update

Compared to the previous version (D6.2), this section has been updated in total. The UI content has been modified in all existing functions, while the implementation of Correlation, Classification, Regression and Survival Analysis tests has been added. Additionally, the functionality discussed in section 8.5.2, applies to all functions.

8.6.2 FUNCTIONS AND METHODS

For demonstrating each of the following tests and methods, the “1000_test_cases_.csv” sample dataset – provided by Rabin Medical Center - is utilised.

In each test page the “INITIAL DATASET” tab is added, to provide some basic information regarding the descriptive statistics of the selected dataset.

Index	dummy_id	CORNUM	CORGL0B	COMFORT	CORLANG	BILLS	TAXES	SHOPPING	GAMES	STOVE	MEALPREP	EVENTS	PIRATTH	REMARKS	TRAVEL	MOCACOMP	MOCARE	
count	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	
mean	532	1.62793979	0.3480714958	0.1420507996	0.160391082	0.9031044214	1.103480715	0.4232119651	0.6669802446	0.2483337159	0.7722831609	0.3367629005	0.3217309501	0.5296331138	0.528701787	1	-4	
std	307.9059717117	2.8444166491	0.5113712102	0.4109323	0.3693921304	2.237545167	2.4645342033	1.3540151644	2.1313084824	1.4341919052	2.2296187291	1.4605932668	1.4607121084	1.3896362945	1.5347262795	0	0	
min	1	0	0	0	0	-4	-4	-4	-4	-4	-4	-4	-4	-4	-4	1	-4	
25%	266.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	-4	
50%	532	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	-4	
75%	797.5	2	0.5	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	-4	
max	1063	17	3	3	2	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	1	-4
Non Null Count	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	1063	
Dtype	int64	float64	float64	float64	float64	int64	int64	int64										

8.6.2.1 General methods

8.6.2.1.1 Average

New

Calculates the average values of the selected variables. Multiple variables from multiple datasets can be selected.

CORNUM	CORGL0B	Age	ALB	ALT
1.62793979	0.3480714958	47.4178575458	416.2427843893	265.755820034

Figure 141 - Average.

8.6.2.1.2 *Min*

New

Calculates the min values of the selected variables. Multiple variables from multiple datasets can be selected.

Figure 142 - Min.

8.6.2.1.3 *Max*

New

Calculates the max values of the selected variables. Multiple variables from multiple datasets can be selected.

Figure 143 - Max.

8.6.2.1.4 *Standard deviation*

New

Calculates the standard deviation values of the selected variables. Multiple variables from multiple datasets can be selected.

Figure 144 – Standard deviation.

8.6.2.1.5 Z score

New

Calculates the z-score of the selected variables. Multiple variables from multiple datasets can be selected.

Figure 145 – Z-score.

8.6.2.2 Normality Tests

Updated

Scipy.stats library is used as the basis for the implementation of the following five methods.

Shapiro-Wilk

The Shapiro-Wilk test is used to calculate whether a random sample of data comes from a normal distribution which is a common assumption used in many statistical tests including regression, ANOVA, t-test, etc. The Shapiro-Wilk test is an appropriate method for small sample sizes (<50 samples). Decision Rule:

- If the p-value $\leq \alpha$, then we reject the null hypothesis i.e., we assume the distribution of our variable is not normal/gaussian.

- If the p-value $> \alpha$, then we fail to reject the null hypothesis i.e., we assume the distribution of our variable is normal/gaussian.
where α is a significance level.

Input:

- Array of sample data.

> Kolmogorov-Smirnov

Performs the one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for goodness of fit. The one-sample test compares the underlying distribution $F(x)$ of a sample against a given normal distribution. The test is valid only for continuous distributions. Compared to the Shapiro-Wilk test, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used for $n \geq 50$.

Input:

- Array of sample data.
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’

> D’Agostino’s K^2

Performs the D’Agostino test, which tests whether a sample differs from a normal distribution.

Input:

- The array containing the sample to be tested.
- The “axis” parameter with which to compute test. Default is 0. If None, compute over the whole array a.
- The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

> Jarque-Bera

The Jarque-Bera test tests whether the sample data has the skewness and kurtosis matching a normal distribution. This test only works for a large enough number of data samples (>2000) as the test statistic asymptotically has a Chi-squared distribution with 2 degrees of freedom.

Input:

- The array containing the sample to be tested.

Figure 146 Common interface for methods “Shapiro-Wilk”, “Kolmogorov-Smirnov”, “D’Agostino’s K^2 ” and “Jarque-Bera”

All the above Methods return:

- The characteristics of the selected array of values (Number of rows, Mean and Median values, Std Deviation and Error values, confidence level, skewness, and kurtosis).
- The extreme values of the sample
- The statistic and p-value for the hypothesis test.
- The significance level and the result description.
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 147 Result interface example using Shapiro-Wilk method.

Anderson-Darling

Performs the Anderson-Darling test which tests the null hypothesis that a sample is drawn from a population that follows a particular distribution. In general, the hypothesis can be tested with normal, exponential, logistic, or Gumbel (Extreme Value Type I) distributions, however, in the context of normality test only the normal distribution is selected.

Input:

- Array of sample data.

Returns:

- The characteristics of the selected array of values (Number of rows, Mean and Median values, Std Deviation and Error values, confidence level, skewness, and kurtosis).
- The extreme values of the sample
- The statistic value for the hypothesis test.
- The significance level and Critical values
- The result description for each level.
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 148 - Result interface example using Anderson-Darling method.

8.6.2.3 Transformation

8.6.2.3.1 Data Transformation

Updated

Scipy.stats library is used as the basis for the implementation of the following two methods.

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

> Box-Cox

Returns a dataset transformed by a Box-Cox power transformation. The Box-Cox requires the input data to be positive.

Input:

- The array to be transformed.
- The “lmbda” parameter.
- The “alpha” parameter which returns the confidence interval for lmbda parameter

Returns:

- The Box-Cox power transformed array.
- If the lmbda parameter is None, the lmbda that maximises the log-likelihood function.
- A tuple of floats which represents the minimum and maximum confidence limits given alpha, in case of lmbda parameter is None and alpha is not None
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

> Yeo-Johnson

Returns the requested dataset transformed by a Yeo-Johnson power transformation. Unlike Box-Cox, Yeo-Johnson does not require the input data to be positive.

Input:

- The 1-dimensional array to be transformed.
- The “lmbda” parameter.

Returns:

- The Yeo-Johnson power transformed array.
- If the lmbda parameter is None, the lambda that maximises the log-likelihood function.
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

Numpy library is used as the basis for the implementation of the following two methods.

> Log

The natural logarithm log is the inverse of the exponential function, so that $\log(\exp(x)) = x$. The natural logarithm is logarithm in base e.

Input:

- The array to be transformed.

> Squared-root

Return the non-negative square-root of an array.

Input:

- The array to be transformed.

> Cube-root

Return the cube-root of an array.

Input:

- The array to be transformed.

All three methods return:

- The transformed array.

- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 149 - Result interface example using Log method.

8.6.2.3.2 Data Transformation for use in an ANOVA

Scipy.stats library is used as the basis for the implementation of the following five methods.

> O'Brien Transform

Returns the O'Brien transform on input data. Used to test for homogeneity of variance prior to running one-way stats.

Input:

- Any number of arrays.

Returns:

- Transformed data for use in an ANOVA. The first dimension of the result corresponds to the sequence of transformed arrays.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

The screenshot shows the 'Analytics Engine' interface. On the left, under 'Select columns', the file '1000_test_cases_csv' is selected, and the variable 'BILLS' is chosen. Below this, a table of 'Selected variables' is shown, including '1000_TEST_CASES_CSV-CDRSUM' and '1000_TEST_CASES_CSV-CDROLOB'. On the right, the 'Result Visualisation' tab is active, displaying a table of transformed variables. The table has three columns: 'CDRSUM', 'CDROLOB', and 'BILLS'. The data is as follows:

CDRSUM	CDROLOB	BILLS
0.7574782435	0.0229916599	50.4347504839
2.6498479521	0.1212017618	0.8143909112
2.6498479521	0.1212017618	0.8143909112
54.4199960376	2.7326013049	50.4347504839
1.2699606935	0.0229916599	4.4008259981
11.3827749957	0.4254882165	4.4008259981
28.8957322492	0.4254882165	4.4008259981
0.0123061517	0.0229916599	0.0070426398
5.6305363195	0.0229916599	0.0070426398
2.6498479521	0.1212017618	0.8143909112
2.6498479521	0.1212017618	0.8143909112
1.2699606935	0.0229916599	24.0720503343

Figure 150 - Result interface example using O'Brien Transform.

8.6.2.4 Homoscedasticity

Updated

Scipy.stats library is used as the basis for the implementation of the following three methods.

› Levene

Computes the Levene test statistic for equal variances. The Levene test tests the null hypothesis that all input samples are from populations with equal variances.

Input:

- 1-D Arrays of sample data. The sample data, possibly with different lengths.
- The “center” parameter, which determines the function of the data to be used in the test, with the following three options: ‘mean’, ‘median’, ‘trimmed’

› Bartlett

Computes the Bartlett’s test statistic for equal variances. The Bartlett’s test tests the null hypothesis that all input samples are from populations with equal variances. For samples from significantly non-normal populations, Levene’s test is more robust.

Input:

- 1-D Arrays of sample data, that may have different lengths..

› Fligner-Killeen

Computes the Fligner-Killeen test statistic for equality of variance. The Fligner’s test tests the null hypothesis that all input samples are from populations with equal variances.

Input:

- 1-D Arrays of sample data.
 - The “center” parameter, which determines the function of the data to be used in the test, with the following three options: ‘mean’, ‘median’, ‘trimmed’
- Returns:

- Variance table of the sample data
- The test statistic.
- The p-value of the test.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 151 - Result interface example using Fligner-Killeen method.

8.6.2.5 Statistical Tests

Updated

Scipy.stats library is used as the basis for the implementation of the following methods.

8.6.2.5.1 Independent t-test

Computes the T-test for the means of two independent samples of scores. This is a test for the null hypothesis that 2 independent samples have identical average (expected) values. This test assumes that the populations have identical variances by default.

Input:

- Arrays of sample data. The arrays must have the same shape, except in the dimension corresponding to axis.
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’
- The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

Returns:

- The test statistic.
- The p-value of the test.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 152 - Independent t-test

8.6.2.5.2 Welch t-test

Computes the T-test for the means of two independent samples of scores. This is a test for the null hypothesis that 2 independent samples have identical average (expected) values. This test does not assume equal population variance.

Input:

- Arrays of sample data. The arrays must have the same shape, except in the dimension corresponding to axis.
- The “axis” parameter, which is used to compute test.
- equal_var: False (Default). Does not assume equal population variance.
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’
- The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

Returns:

- The test statistic.
- The p-value of the test.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 153 - Welch t-test

8.6.2.5.3 *t*-test on TWO RELATED samples of scores

Computes the *t*-test on TWO RELATED samples of scores. This is a test for the null hypothesis that two related or repeated samples have identical average (expected) values.

Input:

- Arrays of sample data. The arrays must have the same shape.
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’
- The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

Returns:

- The test statistic.
- The p-value of the test.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 154 - RELATED samples *t*-test

8.6.2.5.4 *Mann-Whitney U* rank test

Perform the Mann-Whitney U rank test on two independent samples. The Mann-Whitney U test is a nonparametric test of the null hypothesis that the distribution underlying sample x is the same as the distribution underlying sample y. It is often used as a test of difference in location between distributions. The Mann-Whitney U test is a non-parametric version of the *t*-test for independent samples. When the means of samples from the populations are normally distributed, then the independent *t*-test can be used.

Input:

- N-d Arrays of sample data.
- The “axis” parameter, which is used to compute test.
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’
- The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’
- The “method” parameter, which defines the method to be used to calculate the p-value, with the following three options: ‘auto’, ‘asymptotic’, ‘exact’

Returns:

- The Mann-Whitney U statistic corresponding with sample x.
- The associated p-value for the chosen alternative.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 155 - Mann-Whitney U rank test

8.6.2.5.5 Wilcoxon signed-rank test

Computes the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test tests the null hypothesis that two related paired samples come from the same distribution. It tests whether the distribution of the differences $x - y$ is symmetric about zero. It is a non-parametric version of the paired T-test.

Input:

- Two 1-D Arrays of sample measurements.
- The “zero_method” parameter, which is used for handling pairs of observations with equal values (“zero-differences”, or “zeros”), with the following three options: “wilcox”, “pratt”, “zsplitt”
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’
- The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’
- The “method” parameter, which defines the method to be used to calculate the p-value, with the following three options: ‘auto’, ‘asymptotic’, ‘exact’
- The “correction” parameter, for applying continuity correction. If set to True, the Wilcoxon rank statistic shall be adjusted by 0.5 towards the mean value when computing the z-statistic if a normal approximation is used.

Returns:

- The test statistic. If alternative is “two-sided”, the sum of the ranks of the differences above or below zero, whichever is smaller. Otherwise, the sum of the ranks of the differences above zero.
- The associated p-value for the chosen alternative.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 156 - Wilcoxon signed-rank test

8.6.2.5.6 one-way ANOVA

Computes the one-way ANOVA. The one-way ANOVA tests the null hypothesis that two or more groups have the same population mean. The test is applied to samples from two or more groups, possibly with differing sizes.

The ANOVA test has some important assumptions, which need to be satisfied including: (i) The samples are independent, (ii) Each sample is from a normally distributed population, and (iii) the property of homoscedasticity. If these assumptions are not satisfied, then the Kruskal-Wallis H-test or the Alexander-Govern test can be used (with some loss of power).

Input:

- Arrays of sample measurements for each group.

Returns:

- The computed F statistic of the test.
- The associated p-value from the F distribution.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 157 - one-way ANOVA test

8.6.2.5.7 Kruskal-Wallis H-test

Computes the Kruskal-Wallis H-test for independent samples. The Kruskal-Wallis H-test tests the null hypothesis that the population median of all of the groups is equal. It is a non-parametric version of ANOVA.

Input:

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

- 1-D Arrays of sample measurements.
- The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

Returns:

- The Kruskal-Wallis H statistic, corrected for ties.
- The p-value for the test using the assumption that H has a chi square distribution.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 158 - Kruskal-Wallis H-test

8.6.2.5.8 Alexander Govern test

Computes the Alexander Govern test. The Alexander-Govern approximation tests the equality of k independent means over the heterogeneity of variance. The test is applied to samples from two or more groups, possibly with differing sizes. Unlike one-way ANOVA, this test does not assume on homoscedasticity.

Input:

- Arrays of sample measurements.
- The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

Returns:

- The test statistic.
- The associated p-value.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 159 - Alexander Govern test

8.6.2.5.9 Wilcoxon rank-sum statistic

Compute the Wilcoxon rank-sum statistic for two samples. The Wilcoxon rank-sum test tests the null hypothesis that two sets of measurements are drawn from the same distribution. The alternative hypothesis is that values in one sample are more likely to be larger than the values in the other sample.

Input:

- Two arrays of sample from continuous distributions.
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’
- The “nan_policy” parameter, which defines how to handle when input contains nan, with the following three options: ‘propagate’, ‘raise’, ‘omit’

Returns:

- The test statistic under the large-sample approximation that the rank sum statistic is normally distributed.
- The p-value of the test.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 160 - Wilcoxon rank-sum test

8.6.2.5.10 one-way chi-square test

Compute the one-way chi-square test. The chi-square test tests the null hypothesis that the categorical data has the given frequencies.

Input:

- Two arrays (observed and expected) of frequencies in each category. If expected is missing it is assumed that the expected frequencies are uniform and given by the mean of the observed frequencies.

Returns:

- The chi-squared test statistic.
- The p-value of the test.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 161 - One-way chi-square test

8.6.2.5.11 Anova Repeated Measures

New

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

Penguin library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

It Computes One-way and two-way repeated measures ANOVA. It tests the null hypothesis that there are no significant differences between the dependent groups. This function was tested on a different dataset (Sample_rep_measures) that describes the memory of subjects across 3 years.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for anova repeated measures.
- Within Variable(s). The column name to be considered as the within factor for anova repeated measures.
- Subject Variable(s). The column name to be considered as the subject identifier for anova repeated measures.
- Correction. If True, also return the Greenhouse-Geisser corrected p-value.
- Effect size. Must be one of 'np2' (partial eta-squared), 'n2' (eta-squared) or 'ng2'(generalized eta-squared, default). Note that for one-way repeated measure ANOVA, eta-squared is the same as the generalized eta-squared.

Returns:

Table with a summary of the execution of the function. It contains, for each within variable the following statistics:

- Degrees of Freedom (numerator), Degrees of Freedom (denominator), The F-values, The uncorrected p-values, Greenhouse-Geisser corrected p-value, Effect Size, Greenhouse-Geisser epsilon factor, Sphericity, Sphericity test statistic, Sphericity p-value

Figure 162 - Anova Repeated Measures

8.6.2.5.12 Mixed Anova

New

Penguin library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

It computes mixed-design (split-plot) ANOVA. It tests the null hypothesis that there is no significant interaction between the between factor (Group) and the within factor on the dependent variable. This function was tested on a different dataset (Sample_rep_measures_group) that describes the memory of subjects across 3 years.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for mixed anova.
- Within Variable. The column name to be considered as the within factor for mixed anova
- Subject Variable. The column name to be considered as the subject identifier mixed anova
- Between Factor. The column name to be considered as the between factor for mixed anova
- Correction. If True, return Greenhouse-Geisser corrected p-value. If 'auto' (default), compute Mauchly's test of sphericity to determine whether the p-values needs to be corrected.
- Effect size Effect size. Must be one of 'np2' (partial eta-squared), 'n2' (eta-squared) or 'ng2'(generalized eta-squared).

Returns:

Table with a summary of the execution of the function. It contains, for each within variable and between factor the following statistics:

- Sums of squares, Degrees of freedom (numerator), Degrees of freedom (denominator), Mean squares, The F-values, The uncorrected p-values, Partial eta-square effect sizes, Epsilon factor

The screenshot shows the 'Mixed Anova Parameterisation' interface. On the left, there are dropdown menus for 'File' (Sample_rep_measures_group.csv), 'Dependent Variable' (Memory), 'Subject Variable' (Subject), 'Within Variable' (Year), 'Between factor' (Sex), and 'Correction' (True). The 'Effect size' is set to 'np2'. At the bottom, there are 'SUBMIT' and 'PROCEED >' buttons. On the right, the 'Result Visualisation' tab is active, showing a table with the following data:

Names of the factor consider...	SS	DF1	DF2	MS	F-values	p-unc	np2	epsilon factor
Sex	0.253	1	18	0.253	0.283	0.601	0.016	
Year	31.733	2	36	15.866	17.514	0	0.493	0.988
Interaction	2.106	2	36	1.053	1.162	0.324	0.061	

Figure 163 - Mixed Anova

8.6.2.5.13 Pairwise Tests

New

Penguin library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

It conducts pairwise tests for a dataset. This function was tested on a different dataset (Sample_rep_measures_group) that describes the memory of subjects across 3 years.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for pairwise tests.
- Within Variable(s). The column name(s) to be considered as the within factor(s) for pairwise tests
- Subject Variable. The column name to be considered as the subject identifier pairwise tests
- Between Factor(s). The column name(s) to be considered as the between factor(s) for pairwise tests
- Marginal. If True, the between-subject pairwise T-test(s) will be calculated after averaging across all levels of the within-subject factor in mixed design
- Alpha.
- Alternative. Defines the alternative hypothesis, or tail of the test. Possible options are 'two-sided', 'greater', 'less'.
- P adjust. Method used for testing and adjustment of pvalues. Possible options are 'none', 'bonf', 'sidak', 'holm', 'fdr_bh', 'fdr_by'
- Effect size. Effect size type. Possible options are 'none', 'cohen', 'hedges', 'r', 'eta-square', 'odds-ratio', 'AUC', 'CLES'.
- Correction. For independent two sample T-tests, specify whether or not to correct for unequal variances using Welch separate variances T-test
- Nan policy. Can be 'listwise' for listwise deletion of missing values in repeated measures design (= complete-case analysis) or 'pairwise' for the more liberal pairwise deletion (= available-case analysis)

Returns:

Table with a summary of the execution of the several t-tests run by the function. It contains, for each combination of within variable and between factor values the following statistics:

- T statistic
- Degrees of freedom
- Alternative (tail of the test)
- Uncorrected p-values
- Bayes factor
- Effect size

Analytics Engine
Workflow Id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6
Run Id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6
Step Id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6

Pairwise Tests

File: Sample_rep_measures_group.csv

Select dataset.

Dependent Variable: Memory

Name of column in data with the dependent variable.

Between Variable(s): Sex

Select between variable(s)

Within Variable(s): Year

Select within variable(s)

Subject: Subject

Name of column in data with the subject.

marginal: True

If True, the between-subject pairwise T-test(s) will be calculated after averaging across all levels of the within-subject factor in mixed design

Alpha: 0.05

Significance level

Alternative: two-sided

Defines the alternative hypothesis, or tail of the test

adjust: none

Method used for testing and adjustment of p-values

effsize: hedges

Effect size type

correction: auto

For independent two sample T-tests, specify whether or not to correct for unequal variances using Welch separate variances T-test

nan policy: listwise

Can be 'listwise' for listwise deletion of missing values in repeated measures design (= complete-case analysis) or 'pairwise' for the more liberal pairwise deletion (= available-case analysis)

SUBMIT
PROCEED >

Dependent variable = SAMPLE_REP_MEASURES_GROUP.CSV-MEMORY

Subject = SAMPLE_REP_MEASURES_GROUP.CSV-SUBJECT

Selected between variables [click to remove]

SAMPLE_REP_MEASURES_GROUP.CSV-SEX

CLEAR ALL

Selected within variables [click to remove]

SAMPLE_REP_MEASURES_GROUP.CSV-YEAR

CLEAR ALL

Result Visualisation

INITIAL DATASET
RESULTS

id	Contrast	Year	1st measur...	2nd measur...	Paired	Parametric	T	Deg. of Fr.	alternative	p-un
0	Year	-	2010	2014	true	true	1.6294731...	19	two-sided	0.11
1	Year	-	2010	2018	true	true	5.7618806...	19	two-sided	0.00
2	Year	-	2014	2018	true	true	4.2283439...	19	two-sided	0.00
3	Sex	-	Men	Women	false	true	-0.532389...	18	two-sided	0.60
4	Year * Sex	2010	Men	Women	false	true	-1.399482...	18	two-sided	0.17
5	Year * Sex	2014	Men	Women	false	true	0.7527214...	18	two-sided	0.46
6	Year * Sex	2018	Men	Women	false	true	-0.168947...	18	two-sided	0.86

1-7 of 7
< >

Figure 164 - Pairwise Tests

8.6.2.5.14 Welch Anova

New

Penguin library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Compute the Welch ANOVA, which is an adaptation of Student's t-test, and is more reliable when the two samples have unequal variances and/or unequal sample sizes.

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

Input:

- The entire dataset.
- The name of the column containing the dependent variable.
- The name of column containing the between factor

Returns:

- The factor names
- The sums of squares
- The degrees of freedom
- The mean squares
- The F-values
- The uncorrected p-values
- The partial eta-squared
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 165 – Welch Anova

8.6.2.5.15 Ancova

New

Penguin library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) is a general linear model which blends ANOVA and regression. ANCOVA evaluates whether the means of a dependent variable (dv) are equal across levels of a categorical independent variable (between) often called a treatment, while statistically controlling for the effects of other continuous variables that are not of primary interest, known as covariates or nuisance variables (covar).

Input:

- The entire dataset.
- The name of the column containing the dependent variable.
- The name of column containing the between factor
- The name(s) of column(s) in dataset with the covariate.
- The effect size. Must be 'np2' (partial eta-squared) or 'n2' (eta-squared).

Returns:

- The factor names
- The sums of squares
- The degrees of freedom

- The mean squares
- The F-values
- The uncorrected p-values
- The partial eta-squared
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 166 –Ancova

8.6.2.5.16 Multiple Testing and P-Value Correction

Updated

Statsmodels library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

The correction methods aim to counteract the multiple comparisons problem.

Input:

- 1-D Array of uncorrected p-values
- The “alpha” parameter, which determines the family-wise error rate
- The “method” parameter, with which one of the following methods is selected for the test:
 - > Bonferroni: one-step correction of p-values.
 - > Šidák: one-step correction of p-values.
 - > Holm: step-down method using Bonferroni adjustments.
 - > Holm-Sidak: step down method using Sidak adjustments
 - > Simes-Hochberg: step-up method (independent)
 - > Hommel: closed method based on Simes tests (non-negative)
 - > FDR Benjamini-Hochberg: Benjamini/Hochberg (non-negative)
 - > FDR Benjamini-Yekutieli: Benjamini/Yekutieli (negative)

Select Variable for Multiple Tests and P-Value Correct...

File: 1000_test_cases_csv

Select dataset:

Column: CDRSUM

Select Variable

Method: **Bonferroni: one-step correction**

- Bonferroni: one-step correction
- Sidak
- Holm-Sidak
- Holm
- Simes-Hochberg
- Benjamini-Hochberg
- Benjamini-Yekutieli
- fdr_tsbh
- fdr_tsbky: two stage fdr correction (non-negative)

- > **FDR 2-stage Benjamini-Hochberg:** two stage fdr correction (non-negative)
- > **FDR 2-stage Benjamini-Krieger-Yekutieli:** two stage fdr correction (non-negative)
- > **FDR adaptive Gavrilov-Benjamini-Sarkar:**

Returns:

- True if a hypothesis is rejected, False if not
- The adjusted p-values for multiple hypothesis testing.
- [Šidák] The corrected alpha for Sidak method
- [Bonferroni] The corrected alpha for Bonferroni method
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 167 - Multiple Testing and P-Value Correction

8.6.2.6 Correlation Tests

New

8.6.2.6.1 Pearson Correlation

Pinguin library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Computes the Pearson correlation coefficient and p-value for testing non-correlation.

The Pearson correlation coefficient measures the linear relationship between two datasets. Strictly speaking, Pearson’s correlation requires that each dataset be normally distributed. Correlations of -1 or +1 imply a perfect negative and positive linear relationship, respectively, with 0 indicating the absence of association.

Input:

- First and second set of observations. x and y must be independent. Rows with missing values (NaN) are automatically removed.
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’

Returns:

- The Sample size (after removal of missing values)
- The number of outliers, only if a robust method was used.
- The Correlation coefficient
- The 95% parametric confidence intervals around
- The p-value
- The Bayes Factor of the alternative hypothesis

- The achieved power of the test with an alpha of 0.05.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 168 - Pearson Correlation test

8.6.2.6.2 Spearman Correlation

Penguin library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Computes the Spearman ρ rank-order correlation.

The Spearman correlation coefficient is a non-parametric measure of the monotonicity of the relationship between two datasets. Unlike the Pearson correlation, the Spearman correlation does not assume that both datasets are normally distributed. Correlations of -1 or +1 imply an exact negative and positive monotonic relationship, respectively. Mathematically, the Spearman correlation coefficient is defined as the Pearson correlation coefficient between the rank variables.

Input:

- First and second set of observations. x and y must be independent. Rows with missing values (NaN) are automatically removed.
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’

Returns:

- The Sample size (after removal of missing values)
- The number of outliers, only if a robust method was used
- The Correlation coefficient
- The 95% parametric confidence intervals around
- The p-value
- The achieved power of the test with an alpha of 0.05.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 169 - Spearman Correlation test

8.6.2.6.3 Biweight midcorrelation

Pinguin library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

The biweight midcorrelation is a robust method that protects against univariate outliers by down-weighting observations that deviate too much from the median.

Input:

- First and second set of observations. x and y must be independent. Rows with missing values (NaN) are automatically removed.
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’.

Returns:

- The Sample size (after removal of missing values)
- The number of outliers, only if a robust method was used.
- The Correlation coefficient
- The 95% parametric confidence intervals around
- The p-value
- The achieved power of the test with an alpha of 0.05.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 170 - Biweight midcorrelation

8.6.2.6.4 Percentage Bend

Pinguin library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

The percentage bend correlation is also a robust method that protects against univariate outliers by down-

weighting observations that deviate too much from the median.

Input:

- First and second set of observations. x and y must be independent. Rows with missing values (NaN) are automatically removed.
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’.

Returns:

- The Sample size (after removal of missing values)
- The number of outliers, only if a robust method was used.
- The Correlation coefficient
- The 95% parametric confidence intervals around
- The p-value
- The achieved power of the test with an alpha of 0.05.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 171 - Percentage bend correlation

8.6.2.6.5 Shephrd's PI

Pinguin library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

The Shepherd pi correlation is a robust method that returns the Spearman correlation coefficient after removing bivariate outliers. Briefly, the Shepherd pi uses a bootstrapping of the Mahalanobis distance to identify outliers. This method is significantly slower than the previous ones.

Input:

- First and second set of observations. x and y must be independent. Rows with missing values (NaN) are automatically removed.
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’.

Returns:

- The Sample size (after removal of missing values)
- The number of outliers, only if a robust method was used.
- The Correlation coefficient
- The 95% parametric confidence intervals around
- The p-value

- The achieved power of the test with an alpha of 0.05.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 172 - Shephrd's PI correlation

8.6.2.6.6 Skipped Spearman

Penguin library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

The skipped correlation is also a robust method that returns the Spearman correlation coefficient after removing bivariate outliers. The method is based on the minimum covariance determinant (which requires scikit-learn). This method is significantly slower than the previous ones.

Input:

- First and second set of observations. x and y must be independent. Rows with missing values (NaN) are automatically removed.
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’.

Returns:

- The Sample size (after removal of missing values)
- The number of outliers, only if a robust method was used.
- The Correlation coefficient
- The 95% parametric confidence intervals around
- The p-value
- The achieved power of the test with an alpha of 0.05.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 173 - Skipped Spearman correlation

8.6.2.6.7 Kendalltau Correlation

Pinguin library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Computes the Kendall's tau correlation measure for ordinal data. The Kendall correlation coefficient is a measure of the correspondence between two rankings. Values also range from -1 (perfect disagreement) to 1 (perfect agreement), with 0 indicating the absence of association.

Input:

- First and second set of observations. x and y must be independent. Rows with missing values (NaN) are automatically removed.
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’.

Returns:

- The Sample size (after removal of missing values)
- The number of outliers, only if a robust method was used.
- The Correlation coefficient
- The 95% parametric confidence intervals around
- The p-value
- The achieved power of the test with an alpha of 0.05.
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 174 - Kendall's tau Correlation test

8.6.2.6.8 Point Biserial Correlation

Scipy library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Computes the point biserial correlation coefficient and its p-value.

The point biserial correlation is used to measure the relationship between a binary variable, x, and a continuous variable, y. Like other correlation coefficients, this one varies between -1 and +1 with 0 implying no correlation. Correlations of -1 or +1 imply a determinative relationship.

Input:

- Two arrays. (One Dichotomous and one continuous variable)

Returns:

- The correlation value.
- Two-sided p-value.
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 175 - Point Biserial Correlation

8.6.2.6.9 Canonical correlation

Scikit-learn library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Performs the Canonical Correlation Analysis, also known as “Mode B” PLS. Cross decomposition algorithms find the fundamental relations between two matrices (X and Y). They are latent variable approaches to modeling the covariance structures in these two spaces. They will try to find the multidimensional direction in the X space that explains the maximum multidimensional variance direction in the Y space. It projects both X and Y into a lower-dimensional subspace such that the covariance between transformed(X) and transformed(Y) is maximal.

Input:

- Two arrays. (Training vectors and Target vectors)
- Number of components

Returns:

- Correlation Matrix between the selected features of this dataset.
- CCA coefficients.
- Correlations between the pairs of each dimension.
- X singular vectors of the cross-covariance matrices of each iteration.
- Y singular vectors of the cross-covariance matrices of each iteration.
- Scatterplots of two pairs of canonical variates.
- The loadings of X and Y
- The projection matrix used to transform X and Y
- Transformed X and Y datasets
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 176 - Canonical Correlation

8.6.2.6.10 Mediation Analysis

Penguin library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Performs the Mediation analysis using a bias-correct non-parametric bootstrap method.

Input:

- Column name in data containing the predictor variable. The predictor variable must be continuous.)
- Column name(s) in data containing the mediator variable(s). The mediator(s) can be continuous or binary (e.g. 0 or 1). This function supports multiple parallel mediators.
- Column name in data containing the outcome variable. The outcome variable must be continuous.
- Covariate(s). If not None, the specified covariate(s) will be included in all regressions.

Returns:

- The regression model.
- The regression estimates.
- The standard error.
- The lower confidence interval.
- The upper confidence interval.
- The two-sided p-values.
- The statistical significance.
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 177 - Mediation Analysis

8.6.2.6.11 Structural equation models Optimization

Semopy library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Structural equation modeling (SEM) is a multivariate statistical technique for estimating complex relationships between observed and latent variables. SEM involves a model representing how various aspects of some variables are thought to causally connect to each other. Structural equation models often contain postulated causal connections among some latent variables (variables thought to exist but which can't be directly observed). Additional causal connections link those latent variables to observed

variables whose values appear in a data set.

Input:

- Dataset.
- Latent variables.
- Rules (using dataset and latent variables and operators)
- Optimization method

Returns:

- Fitted model optimization results.
- The Instance of SEM.
- The parameters estimate.
- Variables mean.
- The Factor scores estimation.
- The Fit indices.
- The robust standard errors (apply Huber-White correction to standard errors estimation).
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

The screenshot shows the 'SEM Parameterisation' interface. On the left, the 'Selected Model' section lists the following rules: Stage1 == MEALPREP+CDRSUM, Stage2 == CDRSUM+CDRLOB+COMPOR, Stage2 == Stage3, CDRLOB ~ CDRSUM, and Stage3 == CDRLOB+COMPOR+BILLS. The main area is titled 'Add new rule to the Model' and features a 'Create new Model' checkbox. Below it, there are dropdown menus for 'Select Variable(s)' (set to Stage3), 'Select Operator' (set to Measurement...), and 'Select Variable(s)' (set to CDRLOB, COMPOR, BILLS). A 'New Rule' box displays 'Stage3 == CDRLOB+COMPOR+BILLS'. At the bottom, there are buttons for 'INSERT RULE TO THE MODEL', 'List of created rules', and 'CLEAR ALL RULES'.

Figure 178 - Structural equation Model Creation

The screenshot displays the 'Fitted model optimization results' and the 'Instance of SEM' path diagram. The optimization results section includes: Name of objective: MLW, Optimization method: SLQP, Optimization successful, Optimization terminated successfully, Objective value: 0.137, Number of iterations: 43, and Params: 1.259 -0.407 -0.036 0.640 0.436 2.751 0.154 3.925 0.024 0.105 3.484 2.325 0.006 1.048 1.453 1.020. The path diagram shows latent variables Stage1, Stage2, and Stage3 influencing observed variables. The paths are: Stage1 to MEALPREP (1.259, p-val: 0.00), Stage1 to CDRSUM (1.000), Stage2 to CDRLOB (0.436, p-val: 0.00), Stage2 to COMPOR (0.640, p-val: 0.15), Stage2 to BILLS (2.751, p-val: 0.00), Stage3 to COMPOR (0.154, p-val: 0.00), Stage3 to CDRLOB (-0.036, p-val: 0.86), and Stage3 to BILLS (1.000). Error terms for MEALPREP, CDRSUM, and CDRLOB are 1.000.

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

Figure 179 - Structural equation models Optimization

8.6.2.6.12 Exploratory factor analysis extract latent structure

Semopy library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is a statistical method used to uncover the underlying structure of a relatively large set of variables. EFA is a technique within factor analysis whose overarching goal is to identify the underlying relationships between measured variables.

Input:

- Dataset.
- Selected variables.
- Modelling method (Confirmatory Factor Analysis or Pine)
- Min loadings – the expected minimal number of indicators per latent factor.

- P-value cutoff
- Levels - number of levels. If 1, the result will be the same as CFA. Higher values allow for a more hierarchical model.

Returns:

- Fitted model optimization results.
- The Instance of SEM.
- The parameters estimate.
- Variables mean.
- The Factor scores estimation.
- The Fit indices.
- The robust standard errors (apply Huber-White correction to standard errors estimation).
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 180 - Exploratory factor analysis extract latent structure

8.6.2.7 Classification – Clustering - Dimensionality reduction techniques

New

8.6.2.7.1 K-means Clustering

Sklearn library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

K-means clustering constitutes an unsupervised technique, where similar data points are grouped together, i.e., into the same cluster. Then, the underlying patterns can be discovered.

Input:

- Dataset
- Independent variables
- n_clusters: The number of clusters to form as well as the number of centroids to generate.

Returns:

- Coordinates of cluster centers.
- Labels of each point
- inertia: Sum of squared distances of samples to their closest cluster center.
- Number of iterations

- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 181 - K-means clustering

8.6.2.7.2 Classification analysis - Linear Discriminant Analysis, Classification for cut-off determination

Sklearn library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

This method is a classifier with a linear decision boundary, generated by fitting class conditional densities to the data and using Bayes' rule.

Input:

- Dataset
- Independent variables
- Dependent Variable
- Solver: Singular value decomposition, Least squares solution or Eigenvalue decomposition
- Shrinkage

Returns:

- Percentage of variance explained by each of the selected components
- Class-wise means
- Class priors
- Coefficients and Intercept term
- Content for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 182 - Linear Discriminant Analysis

8.6.2.7.3 Principal Component Analysis

Sklearn library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Principal Component Analysis is a statistical technique for reducing the dimensionality of the dataset, in order to increase the interpretability while preserving the maximum information.

Input:

- Dataset
- Categorical variable
- Number of components to keep
- Svd solver
- Independent Variables

Returns:

- Principal axes in feature space, representing the directions of maximum variance in the data.
- The amount of variance explained by each of the selected components.
- Percentage of variance explained by each of the selected components.
- The singular values corresponding to each of the selected components.
- The estimated noise covariance following the Probabilistic PCA model from Tipping and Bishop 1999.
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component

Figure 183 - Principal Component Analysis

8.6.2.7.4 Factor Analysis

FactorAnalyzer library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Performs factor analysis using MINRES or ML, with optional rotation using Varimax or Promax.

Input:

- Dataset
- Variables to be included in the analysis.
- n_factors – The number of factors to select.
- rotation – The type of rotation to perform after fitting the factor analysis model. If set to None, no rotation will be performed, nor will any associated Kaiser normalization.
- method – The fitting method to use, either MINRES or Maximum Likelihood.
- use_smc – Whether to use squared multiple correlation as starting guesses for factor analysis.
- impute – How to handle missing values, if any, in the data: (a) use list-wise deletion ('drop'), or (b) impute the column median ('median'), or impute the column mean ('mean').

Returns:

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

- The factor loadings matrix.
- The original correlation matrix.
- The Rotation Matrix
- Communalities, Eigenvalues and Uniquenesses, given the factor loading matrix
- Factor Variance Information
- Latent Variables
- Content and plots for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 184 - Factor Analysis

8.6.2.8 Regression tests

New

8.6.2.8.1 Linear Regression

Computes the linear regression of a dataset by using the Ordinary Least Squares method. It uses OLS from statsmodels.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for the linear regression
- Independent Variables. The column names to be considered as independent variables for the linear regression

Returns:

- Information about the dataset and this run of the function (Model, Method, date and time of run etc)
- R-squared
- F-statistic
- AIC
- BIC
- Other general statistics (Omnibus, skew, kurtosis etc)
- Array with coefficients of the independent variables along with their p-values
- Arrays with tests for heteroscedasticity (White, Goldfeld-Quandt, Breusch-Pagan)
- Widget for scatterplot of residuals and other intermediate results

Figure 185 - Linear Regression analytics

8.6.2.8.2 Lasso Regression

Constructs a linear regression model train with L1 prior as its regulariser. It uses the Lasso function from sklearn library.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for lasso regression.
- Independent Variables. The column names to be considered as independent variables for lasso regression.
- Alpha. non-negative float that controls regularisation strength
- Max-iter. The maximum number of iterations permitted.

Returns:

- Array with coefficients of the independent variables
- General statistics of the regression (Intercept, skew, kurtosis etc)
- Widget for scatterplot of residuals and other intermediate results

Figure 186- Lasso Regression

8.6.2.8.3 Elastic net

Constructs a linear regression model trained with combined L1 and L2 priors as its regulariser. It uses

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

the ElasticNet function from sklearn library.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for elastic -net regression.
- Independent Variables. The column names to be considered as independent variables for elastic -net regression.
- Alpha. non-negative float that controls regularisation strength. alpha = 0 is equivalent to an ordinary least square
- l1-ratio. The parameter that chooses the ratio that L1 and L2 are used for the penalty. If 0, the penalty is L2 only. If it is 1, it uses only L1. If it is a number between 0 and 1, the penalty is a combination of L1 and L2.
- Max-iter. The maximum number of iterations permitted.

Returns:

- Array with coefficients of the independent variables
- General statistics of the regression (Intercept, skew, kurtosis etc)

Figure 187 - Elastic Regression

8.6.2.8.4 Generalized Estimating Equations

This function constructs a marginal regression model using generalized estimating equations. The data used should be uncorrelated across clusters, but possibly correlated within them. This implementation uses the statsmodels library, and more specifically statsmodels.formula.api.gee.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for generalized estimating equations.
- Independent Variables. The column names to be considered as independent variables for generalized estimating equations.
- Group. The column names to be considered as group variables for generalized estimating equations.

- Covariance Structure. The options supported are: 'independence', 'autoregressive', 'exchangeable', 'nested'.
- Family. The exponential distribution family to use. The options supported are: 'poisson', 'gamma', 'gaussian', 'inverse_gaussian', 'negative_binomial', 'binomial', 'tweedie'.

Returns:

- Array with Information about the dataset and this run of the function (Model, Method, date and time of run etc)
- Array with coefficients of the independent variables along with their p-values
- Array with general statistics of the regression (skew and kurtosis).

Figure 188 - Generalized Estimating Equations

8.6.2.8.5 Ridge Regression

Constructs a linear regression model which uses the linear least squares function as its loss function and the L2-norm for regularisation. It uses the Ridge function from sklearn.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for ridge regression.
- Independent Variables. The column names to be considered as independent variables for ridge regression.
- Alpha. non-negative float that controls regularisation strength. alpha = 0 means the objective is equivalent to ordinary least squares
- Max-iter. The maximum number of iterations permitted.

- Solver to use. The options supported are: 'auto', 'svd', 'cholesky', 'sparse', 'lsqr', 'sag', 'lbfgs'
- Returns:
- Array with coefficients of the independent variables
 - General statistics of the regression (Intercept, skew, kurtosis etc)
 - Widget for scatterplot of residuals and other intermediate results.

Figure 189 - Ridge Regression Parameterisation

8.6.2.8.6 Sgd Regression

This function produces a linear model which is trained by minimizing a regularized loss function with Stochastic Gradient Descent. The regulariser makes model parameters shrink towards zero using either L2 or L1 norm, or a combination of the 2. This function uses sklearn's SGDRegressor.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for ridge regression.
- Independent Variables. The column names to be considered as independent variables for ridge regression.

- Alpha. non-negative float that controls regularisation strength. Also might be used to compute the learning rate (if learning_rate = 'optimal')
- Max-iter. The maximum number of iterations permitted.
- epsilon. Only applies if loss is 'huber', 'epsilon_insensitive', or 'squared_epsilon_insensitive'.
- eta0. Initial learning rate. Applicable for 'constant', 'invscaling' or 'adaptive' learning rate.
- L1-ratio. The parameter that chooses the ratio that L1 and L2 are used for the penalty. If 0, the penalty is L2 only. If it is 1, it uses only L1. If it is a number between 0 and 1, the penalty is a combination of L1 and L2.
- Loss. Loss function that is used. The options supported are: 'squared_error', 'huber', 'epsilon_insensitive', or 'squared_epsilon_insensitive'
- Learning rate. The type of learning rate schedule used. The options supported are: 'constant', 'optimal', 'invscaling', 'adaptive'
- Penalty. Regularization term that is used. The options supported are: 'l1', 'l2', 'elasticnet'
- Solver to use. The options supported are: 'auto', 'svd', 'cholesky', 'sparse', 'lsqr', 'sag', 'lbfgs'

Returns:

- Array with coefficients of the independent variables
- General statistics of the regression (Intercept, skew, kurtosis etc)
- Widget for scatterplot of residuals and other intermediate results.

Analytics Engine
Workflow id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6
Run id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6
Step id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6

SGD Regression Parameterisation

File:

Select dataset:

Dependent Variable:

Select Dependent Variable:

Columns:

Select Independent Variables:

alpha:

Alpha:

max-iter:

Max iterations:

epsilon:

Epsilon:

eta0:

eta0:

l1-ratio:

l1-ratio:

Loss:

Specify which loss to use:

Learning Rate:

Specify which learning rate to use:

Penalty:

Specify which penalty to use:

Solver:

Select Solver:

Selected independent variables (click to remove)

1000_TEST_CASES_1_CSV-REMDATES

[CLEAR ALL](#)

SGD Regression Result

INITIAL DATASET **RESULTS** NEW DATASET

variables coefficients	
REMDATES	0.864192
Intercept:	-0.02869
Skew:	4.50933
Kurtosis:	32.69639
Jarque-Bera statistic:	50952.70061
Jarque-Bera p-value:	NaN
Omnibus test statistic:	1035.51674
Omnibus test p-value:	0.00000
Durbin Watson:	1.87328
Coefficient of determination (R ²):	0.58645

Figure 190 - SGD Regression Parameterisation

8.6.2.8.7 Huber Regression

Constructs a linear regression model that uses L2 for regularization and is robust to outliers. This does not mean that it completely ignores these outliers. It uses the HuberRegressor function from sklearn library.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for huberhuberridge regression.
- Independent Variables. The column names to be considered as independent variables for huberhuberridge regression.
- Alpha. non-negative float that controls regularisation strength. Must be positive or 0. Must be positive or 0. $\alpha = 0$ means the objective is equivalent to ordinary least squares
- Max-iter. The maximum number of iterations permitted.
- Epsilon. Parameter that controls how many samples will be considered as outliers. Must be greater than 1.
- Solver to use. The options supported are: 'auto', 'svd', 'cholesky', 'sparse', 'lsqr', 'sag', 'lbfgs'

Returns:

- Array with coefficients of the independent variables
- General statistics of the regression (Intercept, skew, kurtosis etc)
- Widget for scatterplot of residuals and other intermediate results.

Figure 191 - SGD Regression Parameterisation

8.6.2.8.8 LinearSVR Regression

Constructs a linear regression model that uses a Linear Support Vector model. This function uses LinearSVR function from sklearn library.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for linearsvr

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

regression.

- Independent Variables. The column names to be considered as independent variables for linearsvr regression.
- Max-iter. The maximum number of iterations permitted.
- C. Controls regularisation strength. The bigger C is the smaller the regularisation. C must be greater than 0.
- Loss. The loss function. The options supported are: 'epsilon_insensitive'(L1 loss), 'squared_epsilon_insensitive' (L2 loss).
- Epsilon. Top of Form
- Epsilon. Applicable only is loss='epsilon-insensitive'. This parameter's value depends on the scale of the target variable.

Returns:

- Array with coefficients of the independent variables
- General statistics of the regression (Intercept, skew, kurtosis etc)
- Widget for scatterplot of residuals and other intermediate results.

Analytics Engine | Workflow id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6 | Run id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6 | Stop id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6

LinearSVR Parameterisation

File: 1000_test_cases_1.csv

Select dataset: SHOPPING

Dependent Variable: REMDATES

Select Independent Variables: max-iter: 1000, C: 1, Loss: epsilon_insensitive, epsilon: 0

SUBMIT **PROCEED >**

Selected independent variables [click to remove]: 1000_test_cases_1.csv-REMDATES

[CLEAR ALL](#)

LinearSVR Result

INITIAL DATASET | **RESULTS** | NEW DATASET

variables	coefficients
REMDATES	1

Intercept:	0.00000
Skew:	4.03246
Kurtosis:	30.19071
Jarque-Bera statistic:	43251.77309
Jarque-Bera p-value:	0.00000
Omnibus test statistic:	963.80378
Omnibus test p-value:	0.00000
Durbin Watson:	1.85778
Coefficient of determination (R ²):	0.56694

Figure 192 - LinearSVR Regression

8.6.2.8.9 *Linearsvc*

Constructs a Linear Support Vector Classification model. This function uses LinearSVC function from sklearn library.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for linearsvr regression.
- Independent Variables. The column names to be considered as independent variables for linearsvr regression.
- Max-iter. The maximum number of iterations permitted.
- C. Controls regularisation strength. The bigger C is the smaller the regularisation. C must be greater than 0.
- Loss. The loss function. The options supported are: 'hinge', 'squared_hinge'.
- Epsilon. Top of Form
- Penalty. The norm used as penalty. The options supported are: 'l1', 'l2'.

Returns:

- Array with coefficients of all the independent variables.
- Array with intercepts.
- Widget for scatterplot of intercepts and the independent variables.

Figure 193 - LinearSVC

8.6.2.8.10 Logistic Regression

Conducts binary logistic regression. It supports both simple and multiple binary classification. This function uses logistic regression function from pingouin library.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for logistic regression. Must be binary
- Independent Variables. The column names to be considered as independent variables for logistic regression.
- Alpha. Value for the confidence intervals

Returns:

- Array with coefficients of all the independent variables along with their p-values and confidence intervals.

Figure 194 - Logistic Regression

8.6.2.8.11 Cox Regression

This function implements Cox’s proportional hazard model. It uses CoxPHFitter function from the lifelines library. It should be noted that to test this function Rossi recidivism dataset was used, available in lifelines as load_rossi().

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Covariate(s). The column name(s) of the covariate(s) in the original dataset that we wish to vary.
- Duration column. The name of the column in the dataset that contains the subjects’ lifetimes.
- Alpha. The level in the confidence intervals
- Penaliser. Penalty to be attached to the size of the coefficients during regression.
- L1 ratio. The ratio to assign to a L1 vs L2 penalty.
- n baseline knots. Used when baseline_estimation_method='spline'. Set the number of knots (interior & exterior) in the baseline hazard, which will be placed evenly along the time axis.
- Breakpoints. Used when baseline_estimation_method='piecewise'. Set the positions of the baseline hazard breakpoints.
- Event column: The name of the column in the dataset that contains the subjects’ death observation. If left as None, assume all individuals are uncensored.
- Weights Column: Column in the dataset, that denotes the weight per subject. This column is expelled and not used as a covariate, but as a weight in the final regression.
- Cluster Column: Column in the dataset, that specifies what column has unique identifiers for clustering covariances. Using this forces, the sandwich estimator (robust variance estimator) to be used
- Entry column: Column denoting when a subject entered the study, i.e. left truncation.
- Strata: Specifies a list of columns to use in stratification. This is useful if a categorical covariate does not obey the proportional hazard assumption.
- Baseline Estimation Method: Specify how the fitter should estimate the baseline. The options supported are: 'breslow', 'spline', 'piecewise'.
- Hazard Ratios: If false, plot will present the log-hazard ratios (the coefficients). If true, the hazard ratios are presented instead.

Returns:

- Concordance Index

- Akaike information criterion (AIC) (partial log-likelihood)
- Table with coefficients, p-values, CIs, etc.
- Plot with a visual representation of the coefficients (i.e. log hazard ratios), including their standard errors and magnitudes.
- Plot comparing the baseline curve of the model versus what happens when a covariate(s) is varied over values in a group
- Table of proportional hazard test.

Figure 195 - Cox Regression

8.6.2.8.12 Linear mixed effects model

This function produces a Linear Mixed Effects Model. It uses MixedLM from statsmodels library.

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for linear mixed effects model.
- Groups. The column name to be considered as group.
- Use sqrt. If True, optimization is carried out using the lower triangle of the square root of the random effects covariance matrix, otherwise it is carried out using the lower triangle of the random effects covariance matrix.
- Independent Variables. The column names to be considered as independent variables

Returns:

- Table with general information about the model and the dataset
- Table with coefficients of all the independent variables along with their p-values and confidence intervals.

Analytics Engine	Workflow Id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6	Run Id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6	Step Id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6
------------------	--	---	--

Linear Mixed Effects Model Para...

File: 1000_test_cases_1.csv

Select dataset.

Dependent Variable: **BILLS**

Select Dependent Variable

Groups: **EVENTS**

Specify group.

Use sqrt: **True**

If True, optimization is carried out using the lower triangle of the square root of the random effects covariance matrix, otherwise it is carried out using the lower triangle of the random effects covariance matrix.

Columns: **TRAVEL**

Select Independent Variables

SUBMIT **PROCEED >**

Dependent variable = 1000_TEST_CASES_1.CSV-BILLS

Group variable = 1000_TEST_CASES_1.CSV-EVENTS

Selected variables (click to remove)
1000_TEST_CASES_1.CSV-TRAVEL

CLEAR ALL

Mixed Linear Model Regression Results

INITIAL DATASET **RESULTS**

Model:	MixedLM	Dependent Variable:	BILLS
No. Observations:	1063	Method:	REML
No. Groups:	7	Scale:	2.9433
Min. group size:	7	Log-Likelihood:	-2095.5069
Max. group size:	812	Converged:	Yes
Mean group size:	151.9		

	Coef.	Std.Err.	z	P> z	[0.025	0.975]
Intercept	1.220	0.593	2.057	0.040	0.057	2.382
TRAVEL	0.588	0.051	11.428	0.000	0.487	0.689
Group Var	2.281	0.872				

Figure 196 - Mixed Linear Effects Model Regression

8.6.2.8.13 Granger Analysis

This function conducts 4 tests for granger non causality of 2 time series. All 4 tests give similar results. `params_ftest` and `ssr_ftest` are equivalent based on F test which is identical to `lmtest:grangertest` in R. It uses [grangercausalitytests](#) from [statsmodels](#) library.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Predictor variable. The 2nd timeseries will be extracted from this column.
- Response variable. The 1st timeseries will be extracted from this column.
- Max lags. The number of max lags to be considered. If a single integer, the function computes the test for all lags up to this number. If more than one integer is provided, it computes the tests only for the lags provided.

Returns:

- Table with the results of the 4 tests performed on all the lags that they were performed for.

Figure 197 - Granger Analysis

8.6.2.8.14 Poisson Regression

Constructs a generalized linear model with a poisson distribution. This regressor uses the 'log' link function. This function uses `PoissonRegressor` function from `sklearn` library.

Input:

- Dataset csv file. The file will be used to extract the variables from its columns.
- Dependent Variable. The column name to be considered as the dependent variable for poisson regression.
- Independent Variables. The column names to be considered as independent variables for poisson regression.
- Max-iter. The maximum number of iterations permitted.
- Epsilon. Top of Form
- Alpha. Constant that multiplies the L2 penalty term and determines the regularization strength. $\alpha = 0$ is equivalent to unpenalized GLMs. In this case, the design matrix X must have full column rank (no collinearities). Values of alpha must be in the range $[0.0, \text{inf})$.

Returns:

- Table with coefficients of the independent variables
- General statistics of the regression (Intercept, skew, kurtosis etc)
- Widget for scatterplot of residuals and other intermediate results.

Analytics Engine
Workflow Id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6
Run Id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6
Step Id: 3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6

Poisson Regression Parameterisation

File:

Select dataset:

Dependent Variable:

Select Dependent Variable:

Independent Variables:

Select Independent Variables:

alpha:

max-iter:

SUBMIT **PROCEED >**

Selected independent variables [click to remove]

1000_TEST_CASES_1.CSV-EVENTS
1000_TEST_CASES_1.CSV-SHOPPING
1000_TEST_CASES_1.CSV-BILLS

CLEAR ALL

Poisson Regression Results

INITIAL DATASET **RESULTS** NEW DATASET

variables	coefficients
BILLS	0.0392774409
SHOPPING	0.0291074336
EVENTS	0.0236150855

Intercept:	-1.08803
Skew:	2.28648
Kurtosis:	6.74053
Jarque-Bera statistic:	2938.60244
Omnibus test statistic:	526.12928
Omnibus test p-value:	5.655601528283965e-115
Durbin Watson:	2.00279
Coefficient of determination (R ²):	0.00906

Available Variables

Select X-axis:

Select Variable for X axis of scatterplot:

Select Y-axis:

Select Variable for Y axis of scatterplot:

SUBMIT

Figure 198 - Poisson Regression

8.6.2.9 Survival Analysis tests

New

Zepid library is used as the basis for the implementation of the following six (6) Survival Analysis methods.

8.6.2.9.1 Risk ratio

Estimation of Risk Ratio with a $(1-\alpha) \times 100\%$ Confidence interval. Depending on the available data, two options are provided, thus, estimation based on the Frequencies or the Entire dataset.

Input:

Frequencies

- Count of exposed individuals with outcome
- Count of unexposed individuals with outcome
- Count of exposed individuals without outcome
- Count of unexposed individuals without outcome
- Alpha value to calculate two-sided Wald confidence intervals.

Dataset

- Exposure variable
- Outcome variable
- Reference category for comparisons.
- Alpha value to calculate two-sided Wald confidence intervals.

Returns:

Outcome must be coded as (1: yes, 0:no). Only supports binary outcomes.

- Calculate the risk ratio, lower & upper confidence intervals, standard error, credit loss ratio.

Figure 199 - Risk ratio (L: using the dataset, R: using only the frequencies)

8.6.2.9.2 Risk difference

Calculates the risk difference and confidence intervals from count data. Depending on the available data, two options are provided, thus, estimation based on the Frequencies or the Entire dataset.

Input:

The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422

Frequencies

- Count of exposed individuals with outcome
- Count of unexposed individuals with outcome
- Count of exposed individuals without outcome
- Count of unexposed individuals without outcome
- Alpha value to calculate two-sided Wald confidence intervals.

Dataset

- Exposure variable
- Outcome variable
- Reference category for comparisons
- Alpha value to calculate two-sided Wald confidence intervals.

Returns:

Outcome must be coded as (1: yes, 0:no). Only supports binary outcomes.

- Calculate the risk difference, lower & upper confidence intervals, standard error, credit loss difference.

Figure 200 - Risk Difference (L: using the dataset, R: using only the frequencies)

8.6.2.9.3 The number needed to treat.

Calculates the number needed to treat and confidence intervals. Depending on the available data, two options are provided, thus, estimation based on the Frequencies or the Entire dataset.

Input:

Frequencies

- Count of exposed individuals with outcome
- Count of unexposed individuals with outcome
- Count of exposed individuals without outcome
- Count of unexposed individuals without outcome
- Alpha value to calculate two-sided Wald confidence intervals.

Dataset

- Exposure variable
- Outcome variable
- Reference category for comparisons.

- Alpha value to calculate two-sided Wald confidence intervals.

Returns:

Outcome must be coded as (1: yes, 0:no). Only works supports binary outcomes.

- Calculate the number needed to treat, lower & upper confidence intervals, standard error.

Figure 201 – Number needed to treat(L: using the dataset, R: using only the frequencies)

8.6.2.9.4 Odds ratio

Calculates the odds ratio and confidence interval. Depending on the available data, two options are provided, thus, estimation based on the Frequencies or the Entire dataset.

Input:

Frequencies

- Count of exposed individuals with outcome
- Count of unexposed individuals with outcome
- Count of exposed individuals without outcome
- Count of unexposed individuals without outcome
- Alpha value to calculate two-sided Wald confidence intervals.

Dataset

- Exposure variable
- Outcome variable
- Reference category for comparisons.
- Alpha value to calculate two-sided Wald confidence intervals.

Returns:

Outcome must be coded as (1: yes, 0:no). Only supports binary outcomes.

- Calculate the Odds ratio, lower & upper confidence intervals, standard error, credit loss ratio.

Figure 202 - Odds Ratio(L: using the dataset, R: using only the frequencies)

8.6.2.9.5 Incidence rate ratio

Calculates the incidence rate ratio and confidence intervals. Depending on the available data, two options are provided, thus, estimation based on the Frequencies or the Entire dataset.

Input:

Frequencies

- Count of exposed individuals with outcome
- Count of unexposed individuals with outcome
- Person-time contributed by those who were exposed
- Person-time contributed by those who were unexposed
- Alpha value to calculate two-sided Wald confidence intervals.

Dataset

- Exposure variable
- Outcome variable
- Time variable
- Reference category for comparisons.
- Alpha value to calculate two-sided Wald confidence intervals.

Returns:

Outcome must be coded as (1: yes, 0:no). Only supports binary outcomes.

- Calculate the Incidence rate ratio, lower & upper confidence intervals, standard error, credit loss ratio.

Figure 203 - Incidence Risk Ratio(L: using the dataset, R: using only the frequencies)

8.6.2.9.6 Incidence rate difference

Calculates the incidence rate difference and confidence intervals. Depending on the available data, two options are provided, thus, estimation based on the Frequencies or the Entire dataset.

Input:

Frequencies

- Count of exposed individuals with outcome
- Count of unexposed individuals with outcome
- Person-time contributed by those who were exposed
- Person-time contributed by those who were unexposed
- Alpha value to calculate two-sided Wald confidence intervals.

Dataset

- Exposure variable
- Outcome variable
- Time variable
- Reference category for comparisons.
- Alpha value to calculate two-sided Wald confidence intervals.

Returns:

Outcome must be coded as (1: yes, 0:no). Only supports binary outcomes.

- Calculate the Incidence Rate Difference, lower & upper confidence intervals, standard error, credit loss difference.

Figure 204 – Incidence Rate Difference(L: using the dataset, R: using only the frequencies)

8.6.2.9.7 Kaplan-Meier

Lifelines library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Provides the class for fitting the Kaplan-Meier estimate for the survival function.

Input:

- Dataset
- Durations variable.
- Observed Event variable.
- alpha- The alpha value associated with the confidence intervals.
- label- Provide a new label for the estimate - useful if looking at many groups.
- at_risk_counts - show group sizes at time points.

Returns:

- The survival_function

- The confidence interval
- The event table.
- The conditional time to event
- The confidence interval cumulative density
- The cumulative density
- The median survival time.
- Content and plot for the Data Visualisation component.

Figure 205 – Kaplan & Meier test

8.6.2.9.8 Fisher exact test

Scipy library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Perform a Fisher exact test on a 2x2 contingency table. The null hypothesis is that the true odds ratio of the populations underlying the observations is one, and the observations were sampled from these populations under a condition: the marginals of the resulting table must equal those of the observed table.

Input:

- Dataset
- Variables to be included in the analysis, used for constructing the 2x2 contingency table
- The “alternative” parameter, which defines the null and alternative hypotheses, with the following three options: ‘two-sided’, ‘less’, ‘greater’.

Returns:

- The contingency table
- The test statistic value.
- The test p-value

Figure 206 – Fisher exact test

8.6.2.9.9 Mc Nemar test

Statsmodels library is used as the basis for the implementation of this method.

Perform a Fisher exact test on a 2x2 contingency table. The null hypothesis is that the true odds ratio of the populations underlying the observations is one, and the observations were sampled from these populations under a condition: the marginals of the resulting table must equal those of the observed table.

Input:

- Dataset
- Variables to be included in the analysis, used for constructing the contingency table
- The “exact” parameter - If exact is true, then the binomial distribution will be used. If exact is false, then the chisquare distribution will be used, which is the approximation to the distribution of the test statistic for large sample sizes.

Returns:

- The contingency table
- The test statistic value.
- The test p-value

Figure 207 – Mc Nemar test

8.7 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The Artificial Intelligence module provides the capability to analyse, detect similarities and predict the next steps of the Expert System. Access to big data for model training and optimisation will be necessary for the creation of AI solutions that are both replicable and adaptable to clinical practice. However, it's important to know that algorithms are trained on several complex data, that is why the system just gives a recommendation to the scientists and not a sure solution.

The AI module, with the help of the workflow module it is embedded on, will mimic human intelligence to perform medical diagnosis using a set of known algorithms and tools. Based on the scientific protocol and methods, each diagnosis and treatment process will be redirected through the known path of actions, in order to use the possible AI algorithms to support clinicians in making an appropriate decision.

As the workflow system proceeds to the next step each time, there is an option to use AI techniques to analyse the input data based on previous experience.

Figure 208 - AI Initialisation Page

Update

The following sections are entirely new and reflect the additions of clustering, classification, regression, and more algorithms and methods. The Classification Class focuses on categorizing data, employing algorithms like SVM (Support Vector Machine) and LDA (Linear Discriminant Analysis) for various industry-specific cases. Such methods include training the model, making predictions, and saving/loading models for efficiency and reproducibility. In the Regression Class, the emphasis is on predicting numerical outcomes. It also uses SVM, highlighting its advantages and limitations for such tasks. This class similarly covers training, prediction, and model management, emphasizing its significance in predicting numerical data accurately. The Clustering Class is tailored for unsupervised learning and data grouping, with a detailed look at the K-means algorithm. It explains the training process and how the class assigns new data points to existing clusters, underscoring the importance of model persistence in large-scale data analysis. The chapter concludes with future directions for the Artificial Intelligence module, focusing on its scalability and adaptability to new data types and machine learning techniques.

8.7.1 AI INTEGRATION AND INTEROPERABILITY FOR DATA ANALYTICS AND QUERY

The Data Analytics and Query Builder modules of the MES-CoBraD Expert System are essential for expanding the boundaries of patient care and medical research. The ability of these modules to work together seamlessly facilitates the exchange of information, allowing artificial intelligence to greatly enhance analytical capabilities in addition to complementing them.

8.7.1.1 Enriched Data Analytics

The Data Analytics module, equipped with a plethora of EEG, MRI, and Actigraphy functions, serves as a fertile ground for the AI module to apply its predictive and analytical prowess. For example:

EEG Functions: AI algorithms enhance signal processing, identifying patterns such as peaks or asymmetry indices, and make predictive analyses more accurate. Machine Learning models can learn from artifacts identified using ICA to improve signal cleaning processes.

MRI Functions: AI supports image recognition and segmentation tasks, bolstering functions like SAMSEG and aiding in the accurate co-registration of multimodal imaging data.

Actigraphy Functions: Advanced algorithms interpret activity patterns, optimizing functions like cosinor analysis for circadian rhythm assessment, which is crucial for personalized medicine.

8.7.1.2 Hypothesis Testing Synergy

The Hypothesis Testing Interface is a testament to the integration of AI with statistical methods. AI complements traditional hypothesis testing by providing:

Predictive Models: Integration with regression and classification tests, such as logistic regression and LDA, allows for the development of predictive models that can anticipate outcomes from complex datasets.

Advanced Correlation Analysis: AI enhances correlation functions by discovering non-linear relationships and complex patterns in the data, transcending the capabilities of traditional Pearson or Spearman correlations.

Dimensionality Reduction: Techniques like PCA and factor analysis are bolstered by AI to uncover the most significant predictors from high-dimensional data, enabling clearer interpretations and more robust conclusions.

8.7.1.3 Query Builder Collaboration

The Query Builder module's AI interoperability ensures that queries are not just data retrievals but intelligent requests that can predict, classify, and cluster information for advanced decision-making. AI transforms raw data into insightful, actionable knowledge, which can then be queried to support real-time clinical decisions.

8.7.1.4 Unified Data Ecosystem

The AI module's integration with Data Analytics and Query Builder creates a unified data ecosystem that:

Enhances Decision-Making: By providing clinicians and researchers with tools to make data-driven decisions supported by AI-augmented analytics.

Facilitates Research: By accelerating the pace of discovery through the automation of data analysis and hypothesis testing.

Improves Patient Outcomes: By enabling the prediction of disease progression and the personalization of treatment plans through advanced modeling and analysis.

The fusion of AI with the Data Analytics and Query Builder modules signifies a transformative leap in the MES-CoBraD Expert System's capabilities. This collaboration is not merely an addition but a multiplicative factor, enhancing the system's utility and efficiency. As we continue to refine these interactions, the system will become increasingly indispensable in the pursuit of medical excellence and the delivery of high-quality patient care.

AI OVERVIEW OF ES

 The MES-CoBraD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 965422.

Expert System

- [Dashboard](#)
- [Create Workflow](#)
- [List of Workflows](#)
- [Deleted Workflows](#)
- [Workflow Categories](#)
- [Module Categories](#)
- [Modules](#)

Demo 5

Give this run a name!

Train dataset with SVR regression

Edit Parameters

```
{ "C":1, "kernel": "rbf", "degree":3, "gamma": "scale", "coef0":0, "tol":0.001, "epsilon":0.1, "shrinking":true, "cache_size":200, "verbose":false, "max_iter":-1 }
```

Edit feature_labels

Edit target_label

Selected dataset:

Bucket: demo

Object: expertsystem/workflow/demo/heart_failures_cleaned.csv

back

Submit

Expert System

- [Dashboard](#)
- [Create Workflow](#)
- [List of Workflows](#)
- [Deleted Workflows](#)
- [Workflow Categories](#)
- [Module Categories](#)
- [Modules](#)

Demo 5

Give this run a name!

Wait for SVR results

Object Details

- Bucket:** demo
- Object:** expertsystem/workflow/4d0a27f6-5c71-40f8-869f-23790c0c5053/9c293f20-d99b-4cb1-8891-1c534a3bca9b/60b28bfa-8da1-4fbd-bb44-e50d6ee7b8a1/heart_failures_cleaned.pkl
- URL (will expire soon):** https://storage.mescobrad.digital-enabler.eng.it/demo/expertsystem/workflow/4d0a27f6-5c71-40f8-869f-23790c0c5053/9c293f20-d99b-4cb1-8891-1c534a3bca9b/60b28bfa-8da1-4fbd-bb44-e50d6ee7b8a1/heart_failures_cleaned.pkl?X-Amz-Algorithm=AWS4-HMAC-SHA256&X-Amz-Credential=OW3ND5BJWTKTR82XHOM%2F20221218%2Fus-east-1%2Fs3%2Faws4_request&X-Amz-Date=20221218T192444Z&X-Amz-Expires=180&X-Amz-SignedHeaders=host&X-Amz-Signature=3947accce6ad4b5cccfbd69f3f82b7a322ee778ad01955efa614d0d3a2c60b0

Algo executed!

Evaluation metrics

- Fit time:** 0.1985255241394043
- Score time:** 0.05784902572631836
- Train negative mean absolute error:** -3.9741977143254426
- Train negative mean squared error:** -66.87396818034487
- Train r2:** -0.03765706272337303
- Test negative mean absolute error:** -3.982854179239434
- Test negative mean squared error:** -66.97727889596942
- Test r2:** -0.039257708258304234

Refresh

Proceed

The final result of the system using artificial intelligence, is to give a recommendation to the scientist in order to perform another workflow or processes or get an end result.

The AI module operates as a microservice within the broader Expert System architecture. Its role is to add a layer of intelligent data analysis and pattern recognition, which significantly augments the system's diagnostic and therapeutic capabilities. Specifically, the AI module contributes to the Expert System by:

- › Employing machine learning models to interpret complex datasets, like the Sleep EDF Extended Sleep Cassette, for predictive analytics.
- › Providing endpoints for model training, prediction, and management, thereby enabling dynamic learning and decision support.
- › Facilitating the seamless integration of AI with existing services, ensuring that the insights generated are readily available for workflow incorporation.

8.7.2 AI ALGORITHMS AND MODULES

8.7.2.1 Introduction

The latest iteration of our MES-CoBraD Artificial Intelligence Module introduces a revolutionary Machine Learning (ML) module, designed with versatility and user empowerment at its core. This plug-and-play feature represents a significant leap in the system's analytical capabilities, offering a data-agnostic solution that caters to a multitude of use cases across various domains.

The ML module is structured into three distinct submodules—Classification, Regression, and Clustering—each equipped with a suite of state-of-the-art algorithms:

- Support Vector Classification (SVC): Provides robust and versatile classification capabilities, adept at handling linear and non-linear data with high accuracy.
- Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA): Offers a reliable method for dimensionality reduction while maintaining the class separability, which is essential for classification tasks.
- Support Vector Regression (SVR): Delivers precision in predicting continuous outcomes, making it invaluable for forecasting and trend analysis.
- K-Means Clustering: Allows for the efficient partitioning of datasets into distinct, non-overlapping groups based on similarity, which is vital for pattern discovery and data segmentation.

The design philosophy of the ML module centers on user accessibility. It enables end-users to seamlessly train, evaluate, and deploy ML models without requiring deep technical expertise in machine learning. The integration of this module within the Expert System is complemented by an intuitive UI, ensuring that sophisticated ML operations are just a few clicks away for our users.

At the foundation of the AI module lies the sophisticated algorithms and logic that empower the Expert System to process vast amounts of data. The system not only analyzes information but also synthesizes it to make informed decisions and generate actionable recommendations. This intelligent engine uses the knowledge base provided to deliver solutions tailored to the specific challenges and questions posed by users.

A crucial aspect of this innovation is the seamless integration of the ML module into the Expert System. The careful development of the user interface ensures that end-users can easily interact with the module,

selecting methods, datasets, and hyperparameters without the need for extensive machine learning knowledge. This user-centric approach democratizes access to advanced data analysis, fostering a culture of informed decision-making across the user base.

The ML module represents a quantum leap in the functionality of the MES-CoBraD Expert System, marrying sophistication with simplicity. It encapsulates our commitment to providing cutting-edge tools that are both powerful and accessible, empowering users to unlock the full potential of their data. As we move forward, we will continue to refine this module, adding more methods and functionalities to extend its capabilities and enhance the user experience.

8.7.2.2 *Classification Class*

8.7.2.2.1 *Detailed Overview*

Elaborate on the role of the Classification class. Discuss its importance in categorizing data and its applicability in various industries or research fields.

8.7.2.2.2 *Key Features*

Target Use-Cases: Elaborate on examples like "DestinationDischarge", explaining how the Classification class can be applied to similar categorical targets.

Algorithms Supported: Delve into the specifics of SVM and LDA, discussing their strengths, ideal use-cases, and why they were chosen for this module.

8.7.2.2.3 *Methods and Functionalities*

- `train(features, targets)`: Describe the training process, how the class handles data, the kind of metrics returned, and the importance of each metric in evaluating model performance.
- `predict(features)`: Discuss the prediction capabilities, including potential use-cases and how predictions can inform decision-making.
- `save_model(file_path)` and `load_model(file_path)`: Explain the process and importance of saving and loading models, particularly in terms of efficiency and reproducibility.

8.7.2.3 *Regression Class*

8.7.2.3.1 *Comprehensive Overview*

Provide a thorough explanation of the Regression class, highlighting its significance in predicting numerical outcomes.

8.7.2.3.2 *Key Features*

Target Use-Cases: Offer detailed examples, such as "urea", and how the Regression class can be effectively utilized in similar scenarios.

Algorithm Used: Discuss the choice of SVM for regression, including its advantages and potential limitations.

8.7.2.3.3 *In-Depth Methodology*

`train(features, targets)`: Explore the training methodology, discussing how the Regression class processes numerical data and the relevance of the metrics it provides.

`predict(features)`: Elucidate on the predictive analysis capabilities and their practical implications.

`save_model(file_path)` and `load_model(file_path)`: Detail the significance of model management in long-term projects and operational settings.

8.7.2.4 *Clustering Class*

8.7.2.4.1 *Detailed Overview*

Outline the Clustering class's purpose, focusing on its utility in unsupervised learning scenarios and data grouping.

8.7.2.4.2 *Key Features*

Algorithm Used: Provide an in-depth look at K-means clustering, its algorithmic nuances, and why it's suited for this class.

8.7.2.4.3 *Comprehensive Method Description*

`train(features, targets)`: Delve into the training process for clustering, discussing how the algorithm identifies patterns and the types of insights that can be derived.

`predict(features)`: Clarify how the class assigns new data points to existing clusters and the potential applications of this feature.

`save_model(file_path)` and `load_model(file_path)`: Emphasize the importance of model persistence in clustering, especially in large-scale or ongoing data analysis projects.

8.7.2.5 *Conclusion and Future Directions*

Conclude with a summary of the Expert System module's capabilities, its impact on data analysis, and potential future enhancements. Discuss the scalability of the system, its adaptability to new types of data, and any plans for integrating additional machine learning techniques or algorithms.

This detailed and comprehensive deliverable format should effectively communicate the complexities and capabilities of your Expert System module, providing a clear understanding of its functionality and potential applications.

8.7.3 *DATA ACQUISITION AND PREPROCESSING*

In this section, we detail the dataset utilized, the preprocessing steps undertaken, and the initial classification models applied to the data.

8.7.3.1 *Dataset Description*

For our analysis, we have employed the Sleep EDF Extended Sleep Cassette dataset, which consists of comprehensive overnight polysomnographic recordings. These recordings encompass a range of signals including EEG from two electrode locations (Fpz-Cz and Pz-Oz), horizontal EOG, submental chin EMG, and

an event marker. Notably, some of the recordings also monitor oro-nasal respiration and rectal body temperature, providing a multifaceted view of sleep patterns.

Annotations within the *Hypnogram.edf files delineate sleep stages labeled W, R, 1, 2, 3, 4, M (representing Movement time), and undefined stages, all scored according to the standardized 1968 Rechtschaffen and Kales manual, yet tailored to the specific EEG electrode locations used in our dataset, as recommended by recent research.

8.7.3.2 *Feature Extraction and Labeling*

For the task of classification, we define each 30-second epoch of the recording as a distinct sample. The labels—'awake' or 'sleeping'—are derived from the sleep stage annotations accompanying the data. We construct feature vectors by concatenating the values from each signal within these epochs. For instance, with two signals such as EEG and EMG each providing 30 data points (one per second), we amalgamate them into a single 60-point feature vector for each sample.

8.7.3.3 *Model Experimentation*

Post preprocessing, we conducted experimental trials with several classification models: Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest, and Neural Networks. These models were chosen for their diverse approaches to pattern recognition—SVM for its effectiveness in high-dimensional spaces, Random Forest for its ensemble learning capability, and Neural Networks for their proficiency in capturing complex nonlinear relationships.

Each model was tasked to learn from the feature vectors to accurately classify the state of wakefulness. The performance of these models was then evaluated to determine their efficacy in distinguishing between the 'awake' and 'sleeping' states, setting the stage for more in-depth analysis and optimization.

8.7.3.4 *Conclusion*

This section of the deliverable offers a clear description of the data used, the rationale behind feature selection, and the initial set of classification models applied to the dataset. It sets the foundation for subsequent sections that may delve into model optimization, evaluation metrics, and interpretation of results.

8.7.4 PREDICTIVE MODELLING

In the realm of predictive analytics, our primary focus is to forecast an outcome based on historical data. This outcome, known as the target, can vary significantly in nature—it may be a quantitative number, such as a price or age, or a qualitative category, such as a medical diagnosis.

8.7.4.1 *Defining the Target*

The target of our predictive model is the variable we aim to predict. In the context of our current project, the target could manifest in various forms:

- › Numerical Value: For instance, predicting the concentration of a drug in the bloodstream.
- › Category: Such as identifying whether a sleep stage is REM or Non-REM.
- › Text: Like classifying customer feedback into positive, neutral, or negative sentiments.
- › Sequence: Predicting the next sequence of brain disorder.

8.7.4.2 *Feature Selection*

Features are the predictors that our models use to make informed predictions about the target. They are the individual measurable properties or characteristics of the phenomenon being observed. For example:

- In a healthcare setting predicting patient outcomes, features could be vital signs, laboratory test results, and patient demographics.

Features should be chosen based on their relevance to the target and their ability to help the model discern patterns that lead to accurate predictions.

8.7.4.3 *Compilation of Training Examples*

- › A robust predictive model relies on a substantial dataset of examples that link features to their corresponding targets. Each example acts as a lesson for the model, from which it learns to associate certain feature patterns with specific outcomes. For instance:
 - › In an age prediction system, we would compile a dataset of images (the features) paired with the actual ages of the individuals (the targets).
 - › For sleep stage classification, as in our current project, the dataset comprises polysomnographic recordings (features) and the corresponding sleep stages (targets) they represent.

8.7.4.4 *Machine Learning Process*

With a target defined, relevant features selected, and a dataset of examples at hand, we apply machine learning algorithms to discern the underlying patterns. These algorithms are trained on the dataset, adjusting their parameters to minimize prediction errors. Over time, they become adept at making accurate predictions on new, unseen data, thus fulfilling the predictive aim of the model.

8.7.5 APPLICATION OF EXPERT SYSTEM IN MEDICAL WORKFLOW DESIGN AND PREDICTION

8.7.5.1 Integration of AI in Clinical Workflows

The MES-CoBraD Expert System, with its advanced AI module, stands at the forefront of transforming clinical workflow design and management. The system's capability to incorporate BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation) enables healthcare professionals to create precise, logical sequences for diagnoses and treatment plans, especially for complex brain disorders.

8.7.5.2 Workflow Creation and Visualization

Leveraging the ReactJS-based front-end, users can construct detailed BPMN diagrams that map out each stage of the clinical process. This visual approach ensures that all necessary steps are clearly defined and followed, enhancing the reliability of the diagnostic and therapeutic pathway.

8.7.5.3 Dynamic Workflow Adaptation through AI

Within these workflows, the AI algorithms become pivotal when encountering decision points that require data-driven insights. For instance:

- › At a decision node concerning the progression of a brain disorder, the system can deploy machine learning models trained on datasets like the Sleep EDF Extended Sleep Cassette to predict the patient's next phase.
- › The AI module, utilizing classification, regression, or clustering algorithms, can analyze patient data in real-time to provide prognostic information, aiding in the decision of the subsequent course of action.

8.7.5.4 Predictive Analytics in Clinical Decision Support

The AI's predictive analytics capability is integrated within the BPMN workflows to serve as a clinical decision support tool. By processing complex medical data, it can:

- Suggest potential diagnoses based on symptomatology and historical patient data.
- Forecast the efficacy of treatment plans, allowing for personalized medicine approaches.
- Identify risk factors for disease progression, enabling preventive care strategies.

8.7.5.5 Case-Based Utilization of AI Algorithms

In specific scenarios, the Expert System can harness the power of SVM, Random Forest, and Neural Network models to:

- › Train on new data gathered from ongoing cases, thereby continuously improving its predictive accuracy.
- › Predict next steps in the management of brain disorders, such as anticipating changes in

disease status or patient response to treatment.

- › Provide healthcare professionals with actionable insights, grounded in AI's deep pattern recognition abilities.

8.7.5.6 *Continuous Learning and Improvement*

As the Expert System is utilized across various cases, it collects data that feeds back into the AI algorithms, allowing for a cycle of perpetual learning and refinement. This ensures that:

- › The system's predictive models evolve with the accumulating experience.
- › The BPMN workflows are dynamically updated to reflect the latest evidence-based practices.
- › Healthcare providers are equipped with a tool that becomes progressively more adept at assisting in complex clinical decisions.

8.8 USER INTERFACE

8.8.1 TECHNOLOGIES, PACKAGES

The user interface is hosted by the main portal, The main portal is implemented using JSF technologies, and in particular «Primefaces 10» package.

8.8.2 PORTAL UI

The portal is the place where the whole visualisation of the system is hosted. There are specific pages for components used, and there are pages generally used by the system, like the dashboard, alerts, notifications, administration, login/logout.

The landing page is presented in the next figure:

Figure 209 - Landing page

The main dashboard, presented in the next figure, contains:

- › Portal menu
- › Main dashboard elements displaying a global image of the system
- › Alerts and notifications

Figure 210 - Main dashboard

The dataset page contains elements for visualization and editing of the datasets used by the system. It is presented in the next figure and the areas of the page refer to:

- › Menu
- › Data table with dataset content
- › Actions column (Download, delete)
- › Upload area

Figure 211 - Dataset page

The analysis page is the place where results of running analytics procedures will be displayed. The page has as main area, the placement of specific iFrames produced by Advanced Analytics tools. The areas of the page, displayed in the next figure, are:

- › Main menu
- › iFrames area

Figure 212 - Analysis page

Clinical processes page, manages the data used during the clinical processes, like clinical trials or diagnosis. The page displayed in the next figure has as main areas:

- › Menu
- › Wizard page
- › Specific submenus and commands

Figure 213 - Clinical processes page

9 INTEGRATION

The present chapter will show how the Expert System modules are integrated together to achieve a high-level sharing capability. The data that are inserted as a data input in all modules are transferred via application programming interface (API) in the MES-CoBraD platform. The integration is capable because of the general architecture of the modules, which is generic microservices and require more fragmented functionalities. That means that each service is a modular, unique process that can be deployed independently.

9.1 INTEGRATION BETWEEN COMPONENTS

The whole MES-CoBraD system is designed to use many components, developed in different technologies, with a very well-defined functional role. They are all placed on the same platform, using a distributed architecture, and all are cooperating to reach a common goal. For this reason, a deep integration mechanism is designed and implemented, and this integration is based on:

- › Integration at data level, by using the same Data Lake
- › Integration at process level, by implementing a choreography mechanism based on message exchanges
- › Integration at UI level, by placing specific HMI in the same Portal.

In the next subchapters, we will describe in detail how the integration was designed.

9.1.1 INTEGRATION CHALLENGES

Before treating the integration process, we have identified several challenges specific for such a complex system.

- › There is a large number of **functionalities specific** to only one pilot use case (PUC). The following PUCs are considered:
 - PUC 1: MES-CoBraD Multidisciplinary Multisource Real-World Data Assessment Protocol
 - PUC 2: MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics Deep-Phenotyping and Prognostication
 - PUC3: MES-CoBraD Real-World Therapy Repurposing and Approved Indication Reassessment
 - PUC4: Development and Validation of a multidisciplinary expert system for the assessment and management of complex brain disorders – MES-CoBraD”
- › There are strong system **security** requirements related to **pilot(s)**. Few data can be used by several pilots (or are relevant to several pilots)
- › There is a need for some **common data collection** and normalisation for all or for many pilots
- › There are **common rules** which all pilots should comply with, and which should be monitored at central level

- › There is a need for **governance** of all pilots, at the same time with a big autonomy of each one

9.1.2 INTEGRATION PRINCIPLES

As already presented in D7.1, the MES-CoBraD project develops an integrated system covering the complete value chain. The construction of this toolkit is as follows the steps:

- › Create an optimised framework
- › Place all the tools in the framework
- › Place Edge plug-ins on client systems

Open standards and protocols are used for all components placed in the system both in terms of development and ease of use.

As integration principles we have establish that:

- › Raw data is stored only on edge components. Anonymised data only is stored on the central platform
- › All data for the central platform is stored in a data Lake
- › Communication between components is done exclusively via REST API

9.1.3 INTEGRATION MECHANISMS

The usage of technologies and tools deployed as the standalone supporting environment is considering the following rationale:

- › The operating system chosen is Linux Ubuntu[141], since it is an open source and proven reliable operating system
- › The containers are managed by Docker[142]. We have chosen Docker as it is open source and a widely used container management system.
- › **Docker container** (or docker) is a lightweight, standalone, executable package of software that includes everything needed to run an application: code, runtime, system tools, system libraries, and settings)
- › **Docker Engine** is an open-source containerisation technology for building and containerising your applications. Docker Engine acts as a client-server application with:
 - A server with a long-running daemon process called **dockerd**[143].
 - APIs specify interfaces that programs can use to talk to and instruct the Docker daemon.
 - A command-line interface (CLI) client called Docker.

- › The CLI uses Docker APIs[144] to control or interact with the Docker daemon through scripting or direct CLI commands. Many other Docker applications use the underlying API and CLI. The daemon creates and manages Docker objects, such as images, containers, networks, and volumes.
- › The docker engine will run all the containers developed as part of the MES-CoBraD project.
- › User Authentication and Authorisation are based on Keycloak [145].
- › **Keycloak** is an open-source identity and access management solution which mainly aims at applications and services. Users can authenticate with Keycloak rather than individual applications. So, the applications don't have to deal with login forms, authenticating users, and storing users. Once logged in to Keycloak, users don't have to log in again to access different applications. The same thing applies to sign-out. Keycloak offers identity management as a sophisticated user management tool, without having to log on repeatedly with every login and into every system-as well as system security, social logins, support for mobile apps, and integration into other solutions. Keycloak has implementations to LDAP and Active Directory as well. Trying Keycloak is quick and easy.
- › The web Server and beans container used is Apache Tomee[xx]. It is used to run the Portal.
- › **Apache TomEE** [146] is the Java Enterprise Edition of **Apache** Tomcat that combines several Java enterprise projects including **Apache** OpenEJB [147], **Apache** OpenWebBeans [148], **Apache** OpenJPA [149], **Apache** MyFaces [150], and others. It is community-led development since 1999. It is the most used JEE web server.
- › The reverse proxy used is NGINX [151].
- › **NGINX** is open-source software for web serving, reverse proxying, caching, load balancing, media streaming, and more. In addition to its HTTP server capabilities, NGINX can also function as a proxy server for email (IMAP, POP3, and SMTP) and a reverse proxy and load balancer for HTTP, TCP, and UDP servers.

The Portal is a monolithic web JEE application, developed as part of the project and deployed on top of Apache Tomee. The security is offered by Keycloak.

- › **APIs.** All technology providers have included in the chapter below the extended documentation about the API functions that will be exposed in the dashboard
- › **Docker images.**

9.1.3.1 *Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD)*

Considering the complexity of the system, and the necessity to have a running system in each phase of the development process, we are considering a CI/CD system based on:

- Source code placement on GIT
- Usage of Github Actions CI/CD tool

- Deployment on the platform of each new release, run automated tests, and create release notes.

9.2 INTEGRATION WITH THE MES-COBRA D PLATFORM

9.2.1 READ DATA FROM OTHER SYSTEMS

It is possible to have input from external systems. The input can be received as:

- › Offline files, which can be uploaded in the system. There is no restriction on the file formats, but the interpretation of data is specific for each component.
- › JSON messages, accepted by a Kafka Message Broker
- › REST API calls

10 TESTING

This section provides the testing methodologies of all the components inside WP6. Application testing is an activity that almost all software testers do regularly to check if the application modules operate as intended. In this section, we will focus on Functional tests and specifically on Unit Tests, which a software engineer creates, to check each component of the application for its proper operation. Testing methodologies, in more details will be analysed on deliverables “7.3 Overall system testing report – v1” and its final release “7.5 Overall system testing report – final”.

Specifically in the following tables, the test actions describe the unit tests, which need to be executed to ensure the functions operate correctly. Distinctions in their implementation will be expanded upon in the actual testing in the next iteration.

Updates in this section

The testing in Data Analytics and Expert System has been conducted using both the pytest module and the integrated TestClient function of FastApi that does mock http call the endpoints of our application. The following successful tests, ensure both that the functions run successfully, and that the resulting information is the one expected. Part of the functions are designed to validate that the error handling procedures can properly address missing information, errors, etc. to secure the stability of the applications. The utility testing functions handle the necessary background actions of our application such as downloading, uploading data, initialising functions etc. To conduct these tests in Data Analytics, we used specific mock datasets with expected outputs. Testing that involves other modules of the MES – CoBraD platform such as workflow manager, datalake etc. is only testing the functionality internal to our application and when possible, mocks the communication with the other modules. In some cases, as mentioned in the previous version of this deliverable, functions have been split into respective areas. The Data and Results Visualisation section that was in the previous version of the deliverable has been removed and instead its content has been integrated into the other tests of the other sections since their functionality is entwined and can't be tested on its own in a meaningful manner.

10.1 EXPERT SYSTEM - PROCESS MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT

10.1.1 DATABASE MODEL TESTING

Functions	Description	Executed test cases	Percentage of test cases Passed
Features			
Create feature	Add a feature instance in DB	1	100%
Read one feature	Get a specific feature instance from DB	1	100%
Read many features	Get a list of feature instances from DB	1	100%
Update feature	Update a feature instance in DB	1	100%
Delete feature	Delete a feature instance from DB	1	100%
Files			
Create file	Add a file instance in DB	1	100%
Read one file	Get a specific file instance from DB	1	100%
Read many files	Get a list of file instances from DB	1	100%

Update file	Update a file instance in DB	1	100%
Delete file	Delete a file instance from DB	1	100%
Module categories			
Create module category	Add a module category instance in DB	1	100%
Read one module category	Get a specific module category instance from DB	1	100%
Read many module categories	Get a list of module category instances from DB	1	100%
Update module category	Update a module category instance in DB	1	100%
Delete module category	Delete a module category instance from DB	1	100%
Modules			
Create module	Add a module instance in DB	1	100%
Read one module	Get a specific module instance from DB	1	100%
Read many modules	Get a list of module instances from DB	1	100%
Update module	Update a module instance in DB	1	100%
Delete module	Delete a module instance from DB	1	100%
Runs			
Create run	Add a run instance in DB	1	100%
Read one run	Get a specific run instance from DB	1	100%
Read many runs	Get a list of run instances from DB	1	100%
Update run	Update a run instance in DB	1	100%
Delete run	Delete a run instance from DB	1	100%
Users			
Create user	Add a user instance in DB	1	100%
Read one user	Get a specific user instance from DB	1	100%
Read many users	Get a list of user instances from DB	1	100%
Update user	Update a user instance in DB	1	100%
Delete user	Delete a user instance from DB	1	100%
Variables			
Create variable	Add a variable instance in DB	1	100%
Read one variable	Get a specific variable instance from DB	1	100%
Read many variables	Get a list of variable instances from DB	1	100%
Update variable	Update a variable instance in DB	1	100%
Delete variable	Delete a variable instance from DB	1	100%
Workflow categories			
Create workflow category	Add a workflow category instance in DB	1	100%
Read one workflow category	Get a specific workflow category instance from DB	1	100%
Read many workflow categories	Get a list of workflow category instances from DB	1	100%
Update workflow category	Update a workflow category instance in DB	1	100%
Delete workflow category	Delete a workflow category instance from DB	1	100%
Workflows			
Create workflow	Add a workflow instance in DB	1	100%
Read one workflow	Get a specific workflow instance from DB	1	100%
Read many workflows	Get a list of workflow instances from DB	1	100%
Update workflow	Update a workflow instance in DB	1	100%
Delete workflow	Delete a workflow instance from DB	1	100%

10.1.2 ENDPOINT RESPONSE TESTING

Functions	Description	Executed test cases	Percentage of test cases Passed
Features			
Read features	Get a list of feature instances	1	100%
Create feature	Add a feature instance	1	100%
Read deleted features	Get a list of deleted feature instances	1	100%
Read deleted feature	Get a specific deleted feature instance	1	100%
Read feature	Get a specific feature instance	1	100%
Update feature	Update a feature instance	1	100%
Destroy feature	Mark a feature instance as deleted	1	100%
Revert feature	Mark a feature instance as non-deleted	1	100%
Files			
Read files	Get a list of file instances	1	100%
Module categories			
Read module categories	Get a list of module category instances	1	100%
Create module category	Add a module category instance	1	100%
Read deleted module categories	Get a list of deleted module category instances	1	100%
Read deleted module category	Get a specific deleted module category instance	1	100%
Read module category	Get a specific module category instance	1	100%
Update module category	Update a module category instance	1	100%
Destroy module category	Mark a module category instance as deleted	1	100%
Revert module category	Mark a module category instance as non-deleted	1	100%
Modules			
Read modules	Get a list of module instances	1	100%
Create module	Add a module instance	1	100%
Read deleted modules	Get a list of deleted module instances	1	100%
Read deleted module	Get a specific deleted module instance	1	100%
Read module	Get a specific module instance	1	100%
Update module	Update a module instance	1	100%
Destroy module	Mark a module instance as deleted	1	100%
Revert module	Mark a module instance as non-deleted	1	100%
Runs			
Run workflow	Initiate a workflow running instance	1	100%
Read run	Get a specific workflow running instance	1	100%
Name a run	Update the name of a workflow running instance	1	100%
Show next task	Show next task of a workflow running instance	1	100%
Get dataobjects from stored data	Get a list of datasets from data lake that are linked with the workflow running instance	1	100%
Get datastores from stored data	Get a list of datasets from trino that are linked with the workflow running instance	1	100%
Run specific task	Select a task of a workflow running instance from waiting list and run it	1	100%
Select next task	Select next task of a workflow running instance	1	100%

Init parallel gateway	Execute parallel gateway task and get next tasks	1	100%
Exec script task	Execute a script task	1	100%
Exec call activity	Execute a call activity task	1	100%
Send task	Execute a send task	1	100%
Receive task	Execute a receive task	1	100%
Complete task	Complete a task	1	100%
Complete script task	Complete a script task	1	100%
Call activity is completed	Complete a call activity task	1	100%
Exec event task actions	Execute an event task	1	100%
Ping task status	Get details of a task	1	100%
Get task metadata	Get the metadata of a task	1	100%
Get completed tasks	Get a list of completed tasks	1	100%
Variables			
Read variables	Get a list of variable instances	1	100%
Create variable	Add a variable instance	1	100%
Read deleted variables	Get a list of deleted variable instances	1	100%
Read deleted variable	Get a specific deleted variable instance	1	100%
Read variable	Get a specific variable instance	1	100%
Update variable	Update a variable instance	1	100%
Destroy variable	Mark a variable instance as deleted	1	100%
Revert variable	Mark a variable instance as non-deleted	1	100%
Workflow categories			
Read workflow categories	Get a list of workflow category instances	1	100%
Create workflow category	Add a workflow category instance	1	100%
Read deleted workflow categories	Get a list of deleted workflow category instances	1	100%
Read deleted workflow category	Get a specific deleted workflow category instance	1	100%
Read workflow category	Get a specific workflow category instance	1	100%
Update workflow category	Update a workflow category instance	1	100%
Destroy workflow category	Mark a workflow category instance as deleted	1	100%
Revert workflow category	Mark a workflow category instance as non-deleted	1	100%
Workflows			
Read workflows	Get a list of workflow instances	1	100%
Create workflow	Add a workflow instance	1	100%
Read entity types	Get a list of workflow instance's entity types	1	100%
Read deleted workflows	Get a list of deleted workflow instances	1	100%
Read deleted workflow	Get a specific deleted workflow instance	1	100%
Search workflows	Get a list of workflow instances using free text and other filters	1	100%
Read workflow	Get a specific workflow instance	1	100%
Update workflow	Update a workflow instance	1	100%
Destroy workflow	Mark a workflow instance as deleted	1	100%
Revert workflow	Mark a workflow instance as non-deleted	1	100%
Read task details	Get a task's information details of a specific workflow instance	1	100%
Read workflow runs	Get a list of workflow run instances	1	100%

10.1.3 UTILITY FUNCTIONS TESTING

Functions	Description	Executed test cases	Percentage of test cases Passed
Save object storage to files	Map objects from data lake to ES's file model	1	100%
Paginate	Parse response and add pagination to list	1	100%
Append query in uri	Append search query to response url	1	100%
Get workflow entity types	Get workflow entity types	1	100%
Parse xml	Parse BPMN xml to JSON format	1	100%

10.2 HYPOTHESIS TESTING & DATA ANALYTICS TESTING

10.2.1 END POINT TESTING AND CONTENT VISUALISATIONS

Functions	Description	Executed test cases	Percentage of test cases Passed
Query Builder			
Select query	Create a select statement	5	100%
Filtering	Apply filter clauses to the query	3	100%
Group query	Use grouping in the query	5	100%
Join query	Create a Join query using more than one datasource table	8	100%
Get Tables	Retrieve tables from the DataLake/Trino	5	100%
Get Variables	Retrieve variables from the selected datasources	3	100%
Execute query	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Execute query Success response Save results in *.csv 	15	100%
EEG			
Auto correlation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check data results created successfully. Check visualisations created successfully Check parameterisation that causes major differences in executions 	1	100%
Partial Auto Correlation		1	100%
Find Peaks		1	100%
Power Spectral Density		9	100%
STFT		1	100%
Predictions		1	100%
Artifacts		1	100%
Asymmetry indices		2	100%
Sleep statistic		1	100%
Spectrogram bandpower		1	100%
Slowwave		1	100%
Spindles		1	100%
Sleep stage classification		1	100%
Manual_sleep stage classification		1	100%
Group sleep sensitivity analysis		1	100%
Back average		1	100%
Envelop trend analysis	1	100%	
Eeg viewer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check ssh connection established. 	3	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check initial creation of logs • Check auxiliary function of annotations and montages 		
Utility Functions			
Step Completion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check Test completes in workflow 	1	100%
Upload Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check data uploaded correctly in all different supported functions with different data 	3	100%
Function Navigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check if correct function is returned 	2	100%
MRI			
MRI Utility Tests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check local contents created correctly 	3	100%
Neurodesk Functions Run Test	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check ssh connection established. • Check initial creation of logs • Check error handling 	4	100%
Neurodesk Check Progress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check logs of functions are created correctly • Check logs content is correct in each case progress or not 	4	100%
MRI Results Test	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check local data loaded correctly 	4	100%
Actigraphy			
Actigraphy assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Success response (HIGH) • Error response (HIGH) • Input Variables validation (MEDIUM) • Content for Visualisations (HIGH) • Sub-functions result verification (HIGH) • Output file creation (HIGH) 	6	100%
Functional Linear Modellingv		3	100%
Singular Spectrum Analysis		3	100%
Detrended Fluctuation Analysis		3	100%
Masking		5	100%
Cosinor		8	100%
Metrics		3	100%
Hypothesis Testing			
Normality functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Success response (HIGH) • Error Handling & response (HIGH) • Input Variables validation (MEDIUM) • Content for Visualisations (HIGH) • Sub-functions result verification (HIGH) • Output file creation (HIGH) 	11	100%
Data transformation		18	100%
Homoscedasticity		9	100%
Statistical tests		23	100%
Correlation		39	100%
Clustering functions		9	100%
Classification functions		30	100%
Regression functions		72	100%
Survival Analysis functions		68	100%

10.2.2 UI PERFORMANCE TESTING

For the performance testing of this component, Google Chrome Lighthouse is being used, a well-known and established tool, which is pre-installed in Google Chrome browser, and analyses web app performance and best practises.

10.2.2.1 Navigation report

The test results were similar in most of the pages since they operate in a similar manner, so here we present some indicative results from the page Normality Testing.

Figure 214 - Lighthouse Navigation Testing results overview

10.2.2.1.1 Performance

The acquired score for the performance is only 35. The main reason for this low score regards the authentication process through the Keycloak mechanism, which forced some redirects and the initialisation of the required dataset. Without these two factors, the relevant score was 89.

Figure 215 - Lighthouse Navigation Testing results Performance

Performance indicator evaluates different aspects which are enlisted and explained below:

First Contentful Paint: It is an important, user-centric metric for measuring perceived load speed. It marks the first point in the page load timeline where the user can see anything on the screen. A fast FCP helps reassure the user that something is happening. **Result: 0.9 s**

Speed index: Speed Index shows how quickly the contents of a page are visibly populated. **Result: 26,6s** – This poor score is because the frontend initially searches and tries to introspect any existing token in order to determine if the current user is authenticated or not.

Total Blocking Time: Sum of all time periods between the *First Contentful Paint* and *Time to Interactive*, when task length exceeded 50ms, expressed in milliseconds. **Result: 7,660 ms**

Largest Contentful Paint: Largest Contentful Paint marks the time at which the largest text or image is painted. **Result: 36.1 s** – This poor score is due to the required dataset that is being initialised for the test.

Cumulative Layout Shift: Cumulative Layout Shift measures the movement of visible elements within the viewport. **Result: 0**

10.2.2.1.2 Accessibility

Figure 216 - Lighthouse NavigationTesting results Accessibility

10.2.2.1.3 Best Practices

Figure 217 - Lighthouse Navigation results Best Practices

No remarkable suggestions provided.

10.2.2.1.4 SEO (Search Engine Optimization)

Figure 218 - Lighthouse Navigation results SEO

10.2.2.2 Timespan report

Timespan report is started manually and analyses the performance of the pages while a user is navigating and using it. It measures layout shifts and javascript execution time during user interaction.

In this test we simulate the user selecting data, executing the function, seeing the results and re executing the function with other data.

Figure 219 - Lighthouse Timespan results

10.2.2.2.1 Performance

Figure 220 - Lighthouse Timespan results Performance

The only metric of note that bothers us is the total blocking time which happens due to retrieving the

results of the function from the backend.

10.2.2.2.2 Best Practices

6/8

Best Practices

GENERAL

- ▲ Browser errors were logged to the console
- ▲ Issues were logged in the `Issues` panel in Chrome Devtools

Figure 221 - Lighthouse Timespan results Best Practices

The only issues here are some errant warning and error logging, that shouldn't be displayed in the browser, caused by some modules internal reporting. Those will be removed and addressed by the final release of the platform.

10.2.2.3 Snapshot report

Snapshot report is used to analyse pages at specific states.

In our testing the state with the biggest differences after the initialisation is the result displaying page which we capture here

The screenshot shows the Lighthouse Snapshot report interface. On the left, there are controls for selecting a normality test and a sample size. The main area displays 'Result Visualisation' with a table for 'Sample characteristics' and 'Extreme values'. Below the table, there are four score indicators: Performance (3/4), Accessibility (24/25), Best Practices (4/4), and SEO (6/7). The Best Practices score is highlighted in orange, indicating a warning level.

Figure 222 - Lighthouse Snapshot results

There are no major suggestions, besides the high number of elements in the pages due to the displayed results which are necessary for the results to be presented in table format.

10.3 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

10.3.1 MODULE TESTING

Functions	Description	Executed test cases	Percentage of test cases Passed
Classification test	Read, preprocess, evaluate, train, and predict using classification algorithm	5	100%
Clustering test	Read, preprocess, evaluate, train, and predict using classification algorithm	5	100%
Regression test	Read, preprocess, evaluate, train, and predict using classification algorithm	5	100%

10.3.2 ENDPOINT RESPONSE TESTING

Functions	Description	Executed test cases	Percentage of test cases Passed
Classification			
Get instructions for classification svc train	Get instructions for classification svc train	1	100%
Get instructions for classification lda train	Get instructions for classification lda train	1	100%
Get instructions for classification predict	Get instructions for classification predict	1	100%
Classification svc train	Train a dataset with SVC Classification algorithm	1	100%
Classification lda train	Train a dataset with LDA Classification algorithm	1	100%
Classification predict	Make predictions with Classification model	1	100%
Clustering			
Get instructions for clustering k-means train	Get instructions for clustering k-means train	1	100%
Get instructions for clustering predict	Get instructions for clustering predict	1	100%
Clustering k-means train	Train a dataset with K-Means Clustering algorithm	1	100%
Clustering predict	Make predictions with Clustering model	1	100%
Regression			
Get instructions for regression svr train	Get instructions for regression svr train	1	100%
Get instructions for regression predict	Get instructions for regression predict	1	100%
Regression svr train	Train a dataset with SVR Regression algorithm	1	100%
Regression predict	Make predictions with Regression model	1	100%

11 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The present deliverable provides the basic structure of the algorithm that includes all variables that have been identified and result in the creation of the basic structure that hosts the data analysis. The system can receive a variety of variables analysed through AI algorithm and provide the end users with the appropriate results.

The Landscape Analysis has been reported including Evidence-Based Medicine, Hypothesis Testing in Medicine, Process Modelling and Management, Data Analytics and Processing and Artificial Intelligence Landscape analysis provides an overview of the clinical decision-making process of evidence-based medicine with reference to the historical background, the methodological process, observation studies and advantages and limitations. Moreover, hypothesis testing is stated, indicating the significance and statistical analysis of the procedure. A state of the art of process modelling and management is reported with reference to healthcare systems, clinicians, and medical research. Data analytics and processing is provided including analysis of structured, inhomogeneous, and multimodal data, feature selection, diagnosis Classification and visualisation and statistical overview. Artificial Intelligence and its role and benefits in medical systems in analysed with reference to explainable and trustworthy AI.

The State-Of-The-Art Analysis has also been reported providing Expert System - Process Modelling and Management – Comparative Analysis, Data Analytics and Visualisations – Comparative Analysis, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning – Comparative Analysis.

In this chapter a state of the art of expert systems is provided, identifying, analysing, and comparing their characteristics. Comparative analysis of process modelling management tools including data analytics and visualizations is also provided giving an overview of weaknesses and strengths. For each tool the features, compatibility, activity, open-Source information, analytics, and visualisations are summarised. A comparative analysis of Artificial Intelligence and machine learning is also provided.

Requirements' Elaboration: Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence, Integration.

The present section elaborates on the system requirements defining and coding the description. Integration aspects referring to Advanced Analytics components and the MES-CoBraD Platform are also reported.

The section of Advanced Analytics Architecture provides the overall architecture of the advanced analytics components and workflow management. Different features are presented as: UI Process Designer, Process Executor, Task Optimiser, Process Optimiser. The Query Builder serves as a connecting role in the MES-CoBraD ecosystem. Data Lake Interface specifications and Query Builder Modules providing also visualizations are reported.

Advanced Analytics Mockups: User Interface, Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data, and Results Visualisation. The section presents the analysis of the advanced analytics mockups providing the presentation of user interface, information on the expert system and process modelling and management, query builder and data analytics. Information on the hypothesis testing interface, visualizations and AI are also reported.

APIs' Specification has been analysed providing Query Builder and MES-CoBraD Data Lake, Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Data Analytics, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence.

The section of Implementation provided the Overview, Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence, User Interface.

Integration: Integration between components, Integration with the MES-CoBraD Platform.

Testing: Expert System - Process Modelling and Management, Query Builder, Data Analytics, Hypothesis Testing Interface, Data and Results Visualisation, Artificial Intelligence, Integration Testing.

Next Steps

Expansion of ML Algorithms: Future versions of the system will see the inclusion of additional machine learning algorithms, expanding beyond SVC, LDA, SVR, and K-Means, to embrace more diverse and advanced analytical methods.

Integration with Emerging Technologies: The system will explore the integration with emerging technologies such as natural language processing and computer vision, to further enhance its analytical capabilities.

User Interface and Experience: Continuous improvement of the user interface will ensure that the system remains intuitive and accessible. The user experience will be a focal point, with the aim of making complex data analysis as user-friendly as possible.

Conclusion

The MES-CoBraD Expert System is more than a tool; it is a testament to the transformative power of artificial intelligence in healthcare. As we look to the future, we are committed to further enhancing its capabilities, ensuring that it continues to serve as an asset in neurological research and beyond. The system's evolution will be guided by the principles of innovation, user-centric design, and the relentless pursuit of excellence in data analytics.

12 REFERENCES

- [1] H. Kang, "How to understand and conduct evidence-based medicine," *Korean J Anesthesiol*, vol. 69, no. 5, 2016, doi: 10.4097/kjae.2016.69.5.435.
- [2] I. Masic, M. Miokovic, and B. Muhamedagic, "Evidence Based Medicine - New Approaches and Challenges," *Acta Informatica Medica*, vol. 16, no. 4, p. 219, 2008, doi: 10.5455/aim.2008.16.219-225.
- [3] I. Masic, M. Miokovic, and B. Muhamedagic, "Evidence Based Medicine - New Approaches and Challenges," *Acta Informatica Medica*, vol. 16, no. 4, p. 219, 2008, doi: 10.5455/aim.2008.16.219-225.
- [4] H. Kang, "How to understand and conduct evidence-based medicine," *Korean J Anesthesiol*, vol. 69, no. 5, 2016, doi: 10.4097/kjae.2016.69.5.435.
- [5] I. Masic, M. Miokovic, and B. Muhamedagic, "Evidence Based Medicine - New Approaches and Challenges," *Acta Informatica Medica*, vol. 16, no. 4, p. 219, 2008, doi: 10.5455/aim.2008.16.219-225.
- [6] J. Shreffler and M. R. Huecker, *Hypothesis Testing, P Values, Confidence Intervals, and Significance*. 2021.
- [7] A. F. Siegel, "Introduction," *Practical Business Statistics*, pp. 3–17, 2012, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-385208-3.00001-8.
- [8] A. Banerjee, S. Jadhav, and J. Bhawalkar, "Probability, clinical decision making and hypothesis testing," *Ind Psychiatry J*, vol. 18, no. 1, 2009, doi: 10.4103/0972-6748.57864.
- [9] A. Banerjee, U. Chitnis, S. Jadhav, J. Bhawalkar, and S. Chaudhury, "Hypothesis testing, type I and type II errors," *Ind Psychiatry J*, vol. 18, no. 2, 2009, doi: 10.4103/0972-6748.62274.
- [10] S. Bhalerao and S. Parab, "Choosing statistical test," *Int J Ayurveda Res*, vol. 1, no. 3, 2010, doi: 10.4103/0974-7788.72494.
- [11] S. Bhalerao and S. Parab, "Choosing statistical test," *Int J Ayurveda Res*, vol. 1, no. 3, 2010, doi: 10.4103/0974-7788.72494.
- [12] J. Shreffler and M. R. Huecker, *Hypothesis Testing, P Values, Confidence Intervals, and Significance*. 2021.
- [13] R. A. Reese and W. J. Conover, "Practical Nonparametric Statistics. 2nd Edition.," *Appl Stat*, vol. 32, no. 1, 1983, doi: 10.2307/2348049.
- [14] A. W. Bowman, R. B. D'Agostino, and M. A. Stephens, "Goodness-of-Fit Techniques.," *J R Stat Soc Ser A Stat Soc*, vol. 151, no. 1, 1988, doi: 10.2307/2982198.
- [15] S. Siegel and N. J. Castellan Jr., "Nonparametric statistics for the behavioral sciences, 2nd ed.," *Nonparametric statistics for the behavioral sciences, 2nd ed.*, no. 36, 1988.
- [16] T. K. Kim, "Understanding one-way anova using conceptual figures," *Korean J Anesthesiol*, vol. 70, no. 1, 2017, doi: 10.4097/kjae.2017.70.1.22.
- [17] T. M. Franke, T. Ho, and C. A. Christie, "The Chi-Square Test: Often Used and More Often Misinterpreted," *American Journal of Evaluation*, vol. 33, no. 3, 2012, doi: 10.1002/eval.1000.

10.1177/1098214011426594.

- [18] M. P. Fay and M. A. Proschan, “Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney or T-test? on assumptions for hypothesis tests and multiple interpretations of decision rules,” *Stat Surv*, vol. 4, 2010, doi: 10.1214/09-SS051.
- [19] K. T. Director and S. Siegel, “UK Public Sector Health Lead Partner.”
- [20] E. Mathisen and J. Krogstie, “Modeling of Processes and Decisions in Healthcare - State of the Art and Research Directions,” 2012, pp. 101–116. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-34549-4_8.
- [21] M. Andellini *et al.*, “Experimental application of Business Process Management technology to manage clinical pathways: A pediatric kidney transplantation follow up case,” *BMC Med Inform Decis Mak*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 1–9, 2017, doi: 10.1186/s12911-017-0546-x.
- [22] J. Gomes, F. Portela, and M. F. Santos, “Introduction to BPM approach in healthcare and case study of end user interaction with EHR interface,” in *Procedia Computer Science*, 2018, vol. 141, pp. 519–524. doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2018.10.132.
- [23] J. Chae, B. H. Park, M. Jones, M. Ward, and J. Nebeker, “Converting clinical pathways to bpm+ standards: A case study in stable ischemic heart disease,” *Proc IEEE Symp Comput Based Med Syst*, vol. 2020-July, pp. 453–456, 2020, doi: 10.1109/CBMS49503.2020.00092.
- [24] S. Buttigieg, P. K. Dey, and D. Gauci, “Business process management in health care: current challenges and future prospects,” *Innov Entrep Health*, p. 1, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.2147/ieh.s68183.
- [25] Villanova University, “3 Ways BPM Can Improve Healthcare Processes,” Pennsylvania, Nov. 2021.
- [26] Carlo Combi, Giuseppe Pozzi, and Pierangelo Veltri, Eds., *PROCESS MODELING AND MANAGEMENT FOR HEALTHCARE*. CRC Press, 2018.
- [27] S. Ferrante, S. Bonacina, G. Pozzi, F. Pincirolì, and S. Marceglia, “A Design Methodology for Medical Processes.,” *Appl Clin Inform*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 191–210, 2016, doi: 10.4338/ACI-2015-08-RA-0111.
- [28] Kerrie L. Holley and M. D. Siupo Becker, *AI-First Healthcare: AI Applications in the Business and Clinical Management of Health*, First. O’Reilly Media, Inc., 2021.
- [29] M. Szelaǳowski and J. Berniak-Woźny, “A Process-Centered Approach to the Description of Clinical Pathways—Forms and Determinants,” *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, vol. 16, no. 15, p. 2638, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.3390/ijerph16152638.
- [30] E. Mathisen and J. Krogstie, “Modeling of Processes and Decisions in Healthcare - State of the Art and Research Directions,” 2012, pp. 101–116. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-34549-4_8.
- [31] A. Vellido, “The importance of interpretability and visualization in machine learning for applications in medicine and health care,” *Neural Comput Appl*, vol. 32, no. 24, pp. 18069–18083, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s00521-019-04051-w.
- [32] G. ; Bhanot, M. ; Biehl, T. ; Villmann, and Zühlke, “Biomedical data analysis in translational research,” Ciaco - i6doc.com, 2017.
- [33] D. Altman, *Practical statistics for medical research*. 1990.
- [34] T. Swinscow and M. Campbell, *Statistics at square one*. 2002.

- [35] K. Witz, “ Book Reviews: Applied Statistics for the Behavioral Sciences Dennis E. Hinkle, William Wiersma, and Stephen G. Jurs Boston: Houghton Mifflin Co., 1988. xix + 682 pp ,” *Journal of Educational Statistics*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 84–87, Mar. 1990, doi: 10.3102/10769986015001084.
- [36] T. J. Cleophas and A. H. Zwinderman, “Regression analysis in medical research: For starters and 2nd levelers,” *Regression Analysis in Medical Research: For Starters and 2nd Levelers*, pp. 1–426, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-71937-5.
- [37] P. Armitage, G. (Geoffrey) Berry, and J. N. S. Matthews, “Statistical methods in medical research,” p. 817, 2002.
- [38] D. K. Lee, J. In, and S. Lee, “Standard deviation and standard error of the mean,” *Korean J Anesthesiol*, vol. 68, no. 3, p. 220, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.4097/KJAE.2015.68.3.220.
- [39] “Handbook of Clinical Neurology 3rd Series,” *Handb Clin Neurol*, vol. 116, no. C, p. v, Jan. 2013, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-444-53497-2.09992-7.
- [40] “Spatial Smoothing - Support BrainVoyager.” <https://support.brainvoyager.com/brainvoyager/functional-analysis-preparation/29-pre-processing/86-spatial-smoothing> (accessed Jan. 24, 2022).
- [41] D. B. Parker and Q. R. Razlighi, “The benefit of slice timing correction in common fMRI preprocessing pipelines,” *Front Neurosci*, vol. 13, no. JUL, 2019, doi: 10.3389/FNINS.2019.00821/FULL.
- [42] D. J. Buysse *et al.*, “EEG Spectral Analysis in Primary Insomnia: NREM Period Effects and Sex Differences,” *Sleep*, vol. 31, no. 12, pp. 1673–1682, Dec. 2008, doi: 10.1093/SLEEP/31.12.1673.
- [43] W. Raghupathi and V. Raghupathi, “Big data analytics in healthcare: promise and potential,” *Health Inf Sci Syst*, vol. 2, no. 1, Dec. 2014, doi: 10.1186/2047-2501-2-3.
- [44] “3 Applications of Data Analytics in Healthcare.” <https://online.hbs.edu/blog/post/data-analytics-in-healthcare> (accessed Nov. 26, 2021).
- [45] N. Lavrač, “Selected techniques for data mining in medicine,” *Artif Intell Med*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 3–23, May 1999, doi: 10.1016/S0933-3657(98)00062-1.
- [46] M. K. Goel, P. Khanna, and J. Kishore, “Understanding survival analysis: Kaplan-Meier estimate,” *Int J Ayurveda Res*, vol. 1, no. 4, p. 274, 2010, doi: 10.4103/0974-7788.76794.
- [47] “Narcolepsy,” in *Synopsis of Sleep Medicine*, Toronto ; New Jersey : Apple Academic Press, 2016.: Apple Academic Press, 2016, pp. 303–336. doi: 10.1201/9781315366340-26.
- [48] O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, and T. Brox, “U-Net: Convolutional Networks for Biomedical Image Segmentation,” May 2015, [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1505.04597>
- [49] D. A. Neu, J. Lahann, and P. Fettke, “A systematic literature review on state-of-the-art deep learning methods for process prediction,” *Artif Intell Rev*, vol. 55, no. 2, pp. 801–827, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s10462-021-09960-8.
- [50] R. Liu, Y. Rong, and Z. Peng, “A review of medical artificial intelligence,” *Global Health Journal*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 42–45, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.glohj.2020.04.002.

- [51] S. Wu *et al.*, “Application of artificial intelligence in clinical diagnosis and treatment: an overview of systematic reviews,” *Intelligent Medicine*, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.imed.2021.12.001.
- [52] M. Nagendran *et al.*, “Artificial intelligence versus clinicians: systematic review of design, reporting standards, and claims of deep learning studies,” *BMJ*, p. m689, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1136/bmj.m689.
- [53] R. v. Zicari *et al.*, “Co-Design of a Trustworthy AI System in Healthcare: Deep Learning Based Skin Lesion Classifier,” *Frontiers in Human Dynamics*, vol. 3, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.3389/fhumd.2021.688152.
- [54] H. Liu *et al.*, “Trustworthy AI: A Computational Perspective,” Jul. 2021.
- [55] High-Level Expert Group on AI (AI HLEG)., “Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI ,” *Publication Office of the European Union*. Nov. 08, 2019.
- [56] S. Thiebes, S. Lins, and A. Sunyaev, “Trustworthy artificial intelligence,” *Electronic Markets*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 447–464, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s12525-020-00441-4.
- [57] Lars Hulstaert, “Black-box vs. white-box models,” *towards data science*, Mar. 2019. <https://towardsdatascience.com/machine-learning-interpretability-techniques-662c723454f3> (accessed Nov. 20, 2021).
- [58] A. Holzinger, C. Biemann, C. S. Pattichis, and D. B. Kell, “What do we need to build explainable AI systems for the medical domain?,” Dec. 2017.
- [59] A. Holzinger, G. Langs, H. Denk, K. Zatloukal, and H. Müller, “Causability and explainability of artificial intelligence in medicine.,” *Wiley Interdiscip Rev Data Min Knowl Discov*, vol. 9, no. 4, p. e1312, doi: 10.1002/widm.1312.
- [60] Dr. Matt Turek, “Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI),” *DARPA*. <https://www.darpa.mil/program/explainable-artificial-intelligence> (accessed Nov. 21, 2021).
- [61] Himabindu Lakkaraju and Cynthia Rudin, “Learning Cost-Effective and Interpretable Treatment Regimes,” *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*, 2017, Accessed: Nov. 21, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v54/lakkaraju17a/lakkaraju17a.pdf>
- [62] A. B. Tosun, F. Pullara, M. J. Becich, D. L. Taylor, J. L. Fine, and S. C. Chennubhotla, “Explainable AI (xAI) for Anatomic Pathology,” *Adv Anat Pathol*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 241–250, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1097/PAP.0000000000000264.
- [63] A. Adadi and M. Berrada, “Peeking Inside the Black-Box: A Survey on Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI),” *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 52138–52160, 2018, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2870052.
- [64] J.-M. Fellous, G. Sapiro, A. Rossi, H. Mayberg, and M. Ferrante, “Explainable Artificial Intelligence for Neuroscience: Behavioral Neurostimulation,” *Front Neurosci*, vol. 13, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.3389/fnins.2019.01346.
- [65] Aleksandra Mojsilovic, “Introducing AI Explainability 360,” *IBM Research Blog*, Aug. 08, 2019. <https://www.ibm.com/blogs/research/2019/08/ai-explainability-360/> (accessed Nov. 21, 2021).

- [66] A. Shaban-Nejad, M. Michalowski, and D. L. Buckeridge, Eds., *Explainable AI in Healthcare and Medicine*, vol. 914. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-53352-6.
- [67] Scott Clark, “4 Reasons Why Explainable AI Is the Future of AI,” Sep. 2021.
- [68] The Apache Software Foundation, “Apache Airflow.” 2022.
- [69] “N8n.”
- [70] “Lighflow.”
- [71] C. R. Harris et al., “Array programming with NumPy,” *Nature*, vol. 585, no. 7825. Nature Research, pp. 357–362, Sep. 17, 2020. doi: 10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2.
- [72] W. McKinney, “pandas: a Foundational Python Library for Data Analysis and Statistics.”
- [73] Dask Development Team, “Dask: Library for dynamic task scheduling.” 2016.
- [74] M. Rocklin, “Dask: Parallel Computation with Blocked algorithms and Task Scheduling,” *Proceedings of the 14th Python in Science Conference*, no. Scipy, pp. 126–132, 2015, doi: 10.25080/majora-7b98e3ed-013.
- [75] P. Virtanen et al., “SciPy 1.0: fundamental algorithms for scientific computing in Python,” *Nat Methods*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 261–272, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41592-019-0686-2.
- [76] F. Pedregosa et al., “Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in Python,” *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 12, no. 85, pp. 2825–2830, 2011.
- [77] S. Seabold and J. Perktold, “Statsmodels: Econometric and Statistical Modeling with Python,” 2010.
- [78] Y. Benjamini and Y. Hochberg, “Controlling the False Discovery Rate: A Practical and Powerful Approach to Multiple Testing Author (s): Yoav Benjamini and Yosef Hochberg Source : Journal of the Royal Statistical Society . Series B (Methodological) , Vol . 57 , No . 1 (1995) , Publi,” *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 289–300, 1995.
- [79] T. G. Smith and others, “pmdarima: ARIMA estimators for Python.” 2017.
- [80] M. Löning et al., “alan-turing-institute/sktime: v0.10.1,” Feb. 2022, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.6191159.
- [81] M. Löning, A. Bagnall, S. Ganesh, V. Kazakov, J. Lines, and F. J. Király, “sktime: A Unified Interface for Machine Learning with Time Series,” no. NeurIPS, 2019.
- [82] R. Vallat, “Pingouin: statistics in Python,” *J Open Source Softw*, vol. 3, no. 31, p. 1026, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.21105/joss.01026.
- [83] A. Rokem, M. Trumpis, F. Pérez, and F. Perez@berkeley, “Nitime: time-series analysis for neuroimaging data Diffusion MRI Analysis View project Nitime: time-series analysis for neuroimaging data,” 2009.
- [84] A. Gramfort et al., “MEG and EEG data analysis with MNE-Python,” *Front Neurosci*, no. 7 DEC, 2013, doi: 10.3389/fnins.2013.00267.
- [85] G. Gratton, M. G. H. Coles, and E. Donchin, “A new method for off-line removal of ocular artifact,”

- Electroencephalogr Clin Neurophysiol*, vol. 55, no. 4, pp. 468–484, 1983, doi: 10.1016/0013-4694(83)90135-9.
- [86] M. E. Centre, “Signal-space projection method for separating MEG or EEG into components,” no. September 1996, pp. 135–140, 1997.
- [87] R. Vallat and M. P. Walker, “An open-source, high-performance tool for automated sleep staging,” vol. 10, p. 70092, 2021, doi: 10.7554/eLife.
- [88] H. Wen and Z. Liu, “Separating Fractal and Oscillatory Components in the Power Spectrum of Neurophysiological Signal,” *Brain Topogr*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 13–26, 2016, doi: 10.1007/s10548-015-0448-0.
- [89] “Wonambi.”
- [90] Y. Christakis, N. Mahadevan, and S. Patel, “SleepPy: A python package for sleep analysis from accelerometer data,” *J Open Source Softw*, vol. 4, no. 44, p. 1663, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.21105/joss.01663.
- [91] G. Hammad *et al.*, “pyActigraphy: Open-source python package for actigraphy data visualization and analysis,” *PLoS Comput Biol*, vol. 17, no. 10, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009514.
- [92] R. J. Cole, D. F. Kripke, W. Gruen, D. J. Mullaney, and J. C. Gillin, “Automatic sleep/wake identification from wrist activity,” *Sleep*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 461–469, 1992, doi: 10.1093/sleep/15.5.461.
- [93] N. R. Oakley, “Validation with polysomnography of the Sleepwatch sleep/wake scoring algorithm used by the Actiwatch activity monitoring system,” *Bend: Mini Mitter, Cambridge Neurotechnology*, 1997.
- [94] A. Sadeh, K. M. Sharkey, and M. A. Carskadon, “Activity-based sleep-wake identification: An empirical test of methodological issues,” *Sleep*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 201–207, 1994, doi: 10.1093/sleep/17.3.201.
- [95] D. F. Kripke *et al.*, “Wrist actigraphic scoring for sleep laboratory patients: Algorithm development,” *J Sleep Res*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 612–619, 2010, doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2869.2010.00835.x.
- [96] C. Crespo, M. Aboy, J. R. Fernández, and A. Mojón, “Automatic identification of activity-rest periods based on actigraphy,” *Med Biol Eng Comput*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 329–340, 2012, doi: 10.1007/s11517-012-0875-y.
- [97] T. Roenneberg, L. K. Keller, D. Fischer, J. L. Madera, C. Vetter, and E. C. Winnebeck, “Human activity and rest in situ,” *Methods Enzymol*, vol. 552, pp. 257–283, 2015, doi: 10.1016/bs.mie.2014.11.028.
- [98] R. Refinetti, G. Cornélissen, and F. Halberg, *Procedures for numerical analysis of circadian rhythms*, vol. 38, no. 4. 2007. doi: 10.1080/09291010600903692.
- [99] C. K. Peng, S. Havlin, H. E. Stanley, and A. L. Goldberger, “Quantification of scaling exponents and crossover phenomena in nonstationary heartbeat time series,” *Chaos*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 82–87, 1995, doi: 10.1063/1.166141.
- [100] W. F. Bottke, R. J. Walker, J. M. D. Day, D. Nesvorny, and L. Elkins-Tanton, “Mosaic organization of DNA nucleotides,” *Science (1979)*, vol. 330, no. 6010, pp. 1527–1530, 2010.

- [101] T. Auton, *Applied Functional Data Analysis: Methods and Case Studies*, vol. 167, no. 2. 2004. doi: 10.1111/j.1467-985x.2004.t01-5-x.
- [102] E. C. Winnebeck, D. Fischer, T. Leise, and T. Roenneberg, “Dynamics and Ultradian Structure of Human Sleep in Real Life,” *Current Biology*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 49-59.e5, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.cub.2017.11.063.
- [103] R. Vautard, P. Yiou, and M. Ghil, “Singular-spectrum analysis: A toolkit for short, noisy chaotic signals,” *Physica D*, vol. 58, no. 1–4, pp. 95–126, 1992, doi: 10.1016/0167-2789(92)90103-T.
- [104] E. Combrisson et al., “Visbrain: A multi-purpose GPU-accelerated open-source suite for multimodal brain data visualization,” *Front Neuroinform*, vol. 13, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.3389/fninf.2019.00014.
- [105] M. Hansson-Sandsten, “Optimal multitaper wigner spectrum estimation of a class of locally stationary processes using Hermite functions,” *EURASIP J Adv Signal Process*, vol. 2011, 2011, doi: 10.1155/2011/980805.
- [106] “Lspopt.”
- [107] D. Meunier et al., “NeuroPycon: An open-source python toolbox for fast multi-modal and reproducible brain connectivity pipelines,” *Neuroimage*, vol. 219, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.neuroimage.2020.117020.
- [108] A. Abraham et al., “Machine learning for neuroimaging with scikit-learn,” *Front Neuroinform*, vol. 8, no. FEB, Feb. 2014, doi: 10.3389/fninf.2014.00014.
- [109] E. Garyfallidis et al., “Dipy, a library for the analysis of diffusion MRI data,” *Front Neuroinform*, vol. 8, no. FEB, Feb. 2014, doi: 10.3389/fninf.2014.00008.
- [110] S. Fadnavis, J. Batson, and E. Garyfallidis, “Patch2Self: Denoising diffusion MRI with self-supervised learning,” *Adv Neural Inf Process Syst*, vol. 2020-Decem, no. NeurIPS, pp. 1–11, 2020.
- [111] A. Doherty et al., “Large scale population assessment of physical activity using wrist worn accelerometers: The UK biobank study,” *PLoS One*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1–14, 2017, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0169649.
- [112] A. Doherty et al., “GWAS identifies 14 loci for device-measured physical activity and sleep duration,” *Nat Commun*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 2018, doi: 10.1038/s41467-018-07743-4.
- [113] R. Walmsley et al., “Reallocating time from device-measured sleep, sedentary behaviour or light physical activity to moderate-to-vigorous physical activity is associated with lower cardiovascular disease risk,” *medRxiv*, 2020, doi: 10.1101/2020.11.10.20227769.
- [114] M. Willetts, S. Hollowell, L. Aslett, C. Holmes, and A. Doherty, “Statistical machine learning of sleep and physical activity phenotypes from sensor data in 96,220 UK Biobank participants,” *Sci Rep*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 1–10, 2018, doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-26174-1.
- [115] F. S. Bao, X. Liu, and C. Zhang, “PyEEG: An open source python module for EEG/MEG feature extraction,” *Comput Intell Neurosci*, vol. 2011, 2011, doi: 10.1155/2011/406391.
- [116] L. Cabañero-Gomez, R. Hervas, I. Gonzalez, and L. Rodriguez-Benitez, “eeglib: A Python module for EEG feature extraction,” *SoftwareX*, vol. 15, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.softx.2021.100745.
- [117] S. Mirzaei, H. Van Hamme, and Y. Norouzi, “Blind audio source counting and separation of anechoic mixtures using the multichannel complex NMF framework,” *Signal Processing*, vol. 115,

- pp. 27–37, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.sigpro.2015.03.006.
- [118] M. Brett *et al.*, “nipy/nibabel: 3.2.1 (3.2.1).” Zenodo, 2020. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4295521.
- [119] S. Van Der Walt *et al.*, “Scikit-image: Image processing in python,” *PeerJ*, vol. 2014, no. 1, 2014, doi: 10.7717/peerj.453.
- [120] O. Esteban *et al.*, “fMRIPrep: a robust preprocessing pipeline for functional MRI,” *Nat Methods*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 111–116, 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41592-018-0235-4.
- [121] K. Gorgolewski *et al.*, “Nipype: A flexible, lightweight and extensible neuroimaging data processing framework in Python,” *Front Neuroinform*, vol. 5, no. August, 2011, doi: 10.3389/fninf.2011.00013.
- [122] M. Bostock, “D3.js - Data-Driven Documents.” 2012.
- [123] F. Pedregosa *et al.*, “Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in Python,” *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 12, no. 85, pp. 2825–2830, 2011.
- [124] G. Bradski, “The OpenCV Library,” *Dr. Dobb’s Journal of Software Tools*, 2000.
- [125] K. J. Gorgolewski *et al.*, “Nipype: a flexible, lightweight and extensible neuroimaging data processing framework in Python. 0.12.0-rc1.” 2016. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.50186.
- [126] D. Rivière, D. Geffroy, I. Denghien, N. Souedet, and Y. Cointepas, “BrainVISA: an extensible software environment for sharing multimodal neuroimaging data and processing tools,” *Neuroimage*, vol. 47, 2009, doi: 10.1016/S1053-8119(09)71720-3.
- [127] W. Schroeder, K. Martin, and W. Lorensen, *The Visualization Toolkit, An Object-Oriented Approach To 3D Graphics*, 4th ed. Kitware, 2006.
- [128] “Tensorflow.”
- [129] Abadi Martin *et al.*, “TensorFlow: A System for Large-Scale Machine Learning,” *Proceedings of the 12th USENIX Symposium on Operating Systems Design and Implementation (OSDI ’16)*, Nov. 2016.
- [130] Adam Paszke *et al.*, “PyTorch: An Imperative Style, High-Performance Deep Learning Library,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 32*, Wallach H, Larochelle H, Beygelzimer A, d’Alché-Buc F, Fox E, and Garnett R, Eds. Curran Associates, Inc., 2019, pp. 8024–8035. Accessed: Nov. 23, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://papers.neurips.cc/paper/9015-pytorch-an-imperative-style-high-performance-deep-learning-library.pdf>
- [131] Gulli Antonio and Pal Sujit, *Deep learning with Keras*, First. Packt Publishing Ltd, 2017.
- [132] “Keras.”
- [133] Anshik, *AI for Healthcare with Keras and Tensorflow 2.0*. Berkeley, CA: Apress, 2021. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4842-7086-8.
- [134] F. and others Chollet, “Keras,” *GitHub*, 2015. <https://github.com/fchollet/keras> (accessed Nov. 23, 2021).
- [135] M. Brett *et al.*, “nipy/nibabel: 3.2.1 (3.2.1).” Zenodo, 2020. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4295521.
- [136] F. Bodria, F. Giannotti, R. Guidotti, F. Naretto, D. Pedreschi, and S. Rinzivillo, “Benchmarking and

Survey of Explanation Methods for Black Box Models,” Feb. 2021.

- [137] R. B. d’Agostino, “An omnibus test of normality for moderate and large size samples,” *Biometrika*, vol. 58, no. 2, pp. 341–348, 1971.
- [138] R. D’AGOSTINO and E. S. Pearson, “Tests for departure from normality. Empirical results for the distributions of b^2 and \sqrt{b} ,” *Biometrika*, vol. 60, no. 3, pp. 613–622, 1973.
- [139] H. Levene and others, “Contributions to probability and statistics,” *Essays in honor of Harold Hotelling*, pp. 278–292, 1960.
- [140] M. B. Brown and A. B. Forsythe, “Robust tests for the equality of variances,” *J Am Stat Assoc*, vol. 69, no. 346, pp. 364–367, 1974.
- [141] Canonical Ltd., “Ubuntu Linux,” <https://ubuntu.com/desktop/features>.
- [142] Docker Inc., “Docker,” <https://www.docker.com/>.
- [143] Docker, “Dockerrd,” <https://docs.docker.com/engine/reference/commandline/dockerd/>.
- [144] Docker, “Docker API,” <https://docs.docker.com/engine/api/>.
- [145] Red Hat, “Keycloak | Open Source Identity and Access Management,” <https://www.keycloak.org/>.
- [146] The Apache Software Foundation, “Apache TomEE,” <https://tomee.apache.org/>.
- [147] The Apache Software Foundation, “Apache OpenEJB,” <https://openejb.apache.org/hello-world.html>.
- [148] The Apache Software Foundation, “OpenWebBeans,” <https://openwebbeans.apache.org/>.
- [149] The Apache Software Foundation, “Apache Open JPA,” <https://openjpa.apache.org/>.
- [150] The Apache Software Foundation, “Apache MyFaces,” <https://myfaces.apache.org/#/>.
- [151] F5 Inc., “NGINX,” <https://www.nginx.com/>.

ANNEX I : Data Analytics Tools Information Collection

Table 12 – Statistical Methods & Data Processing for Electrophysiology Data

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
1	Spectral analysis (wavelet transform) - topoplots	The WT can be thought of as an extension of the classic Fourier transform, except that, instead of working on a single scale (time or frequency), it works on a multi-scale basis. This multi-scale feature of the WT allows the decomposition of a signal into a number of scales, each scale representing a particular coarseness of the signal under study.	absolutely. All packages have some level of FFT or something similar	Must have		power-frequency plot and power-frequency-time plot	
2	Time series forecasting	Forecasting whether an EEG trace in seconds indicates a patient is having a seizure or not. (ARIMA, etc.)	past use	Good to have	SPSS has a good one. FORTRAN is crap. Matlab used to be ok. Not sure of python quality of ARIMA	bar chart for residuals and line for time series	
3	Time series analysis	Time series analysis involves developing models that best capture or describe an observed time series in order to understand the underlying causes. This field of study seeks the "why" behind a time series dataset. This often involves making assumptions about the form of the data and decomposing the time series into constituent components. Examples: Autocorrelation	the AR part of ARIMA is that. I would combine it with the above.. Would add also things like a periodogram	Must have	I guess for these R or Python packages should be good. Not aware of specifics.	line chart mostly	
4	Actigraphy Data analysis	(i) detection of rest periods, (ii) advanced signal processing functions (Cosinor Analysis, Detrended Fluctuation Analysis, Locomotor Inactivity during sleep, Singular Spectrum Analysis), (iii) Calculation of typical wake/sleep cycle-related variables, including sleep regularity index, activity of rest fragmentation, and more.	in clinical practice and research for people with insomnia or circadian disorders	Must have	Philips tools for now. I believe I had forwarded an email in the past with a link to such a toolbox either to ENG, NTUA, or EVOL.	line chart and radar chart can work.	
5	Event detection in sleep	Sleep spindles, slow waves, rapid-eye movements	use it for fun through Compumedics software, but not as helpful in practice, since we score manually/visually. Helpful though for automated scoring tools.	Good to have	again, I had send a link to an EU Horizon project that focused exactly on that.	highlight the respective event	
6	Automatic sleep staging	Correctly identifying sleep stages is important in diagnosing and treating sleep disorders.	not using it, but would be useful to have an example as a use case	Good to have	enso	hypnogram	

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
e	Signal processing	(i) filtering, i.e., bandpass, lowpass, highpass, etc.	always!!!	Must have	all packages usually have something. Would be nice to have one that gives you more options in the approach the use (first, second etc. order of tapering etc.)		
8	Repairing artifacts	Artifacts are parts of the recorded signal that arise from sources other than the source of interest (i.e., neuronal activity in the brain). As such, artifacts are a form of interference or noise relative to the signal of interest. There are 3 basic options when faced with artifacts in your recordings: (i) Ignore the artifact and carry on with analysis (ii) Exclude the corrupted portion of the data and analyze the remaining data (iii) Repair the artifact by suppressing artifactual part of the recording while (hopefully) leaving the signal of interest intact	cardiac artifact correction is useful. Notch filtering also important. Many use ICA approaches and event synchronous subtraction (for cardiac), i.e., option iii mostly in clinical practice. Option ii when looking at a steady state analysis of time series data for other automated analyses)	Good to have	many packages have something	detrended signal	
9	Correlations	(i) Pearson, (ii) Spearman, (iii) Point-Biserial, (iv) Kendall Tau	absolutely.	Must have		tables	
10	Average/Relative bandpower of an EEG signal using (i) Welch and (ii) multitaper spectral estimation methods	The average bandpower is also a very relevant metric for sleep research because it allows to differentiate between the different sleep stages. For instance, deep sleep is characterized by its predominance of slow-waves with a frequency range comprised between 0.5 to 4 Hz (i.e. delta band), which reflects a synchronized brain activity. Conversely, wakefulness is characterized by very little delta activity and much more higher-frequencies activity. Therefore, if you were to compute the delta bandpower for both deep sleep and wakefulness, the former would be very high and the latter very low.	I would consider this in relation to spectral analyses above.				

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
11	Time frequency analysis	The time frequency analysis of EEG signals provide the correct visualization of EEG signals to extract the various rhythms of frequencies like alpha, beta, gamma waves. Examples: (i) spectrograms (STFT) (ii) Sleep is a continuous, dynamic neural process involving the complex interaction of many different networks within the brain. Long-standing clinical practice, however, breaks up sleep into discrete sleep stages through time-consuming, subjective, visual inspection of 30-second segments of electroencephalogram (EEG) data. As a result, vital information about brain activity is lost. Multitaper spectral analysis is therefore a powerful tool for finding new insights into the physiological mechanisms underlying sleep and for developing new ways of diagnosing and tracking sleep and diagnosing related disorders.	again, similar to spectral above				
12	Down-up sampling	As the name suggests, the process of converting the sampling rate of a digital signal from one rate to another is Sampling Rate Conversion. Increasing the rate of already sampled signal is Upsampling whereas decreasing the rate is called downsampling.	would not trust upsampling (if there is no data present, then you still get the original information with redundant (duplicate) information. Maybe only useful when trying to compare time series. Have not used it.				

Table 13 – Statistical Methods & Data Processing for MRI

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
1	Method of least squares	The least-squares method is a statistical procedure to find the best fit for a set of data points by minimizing the sum of the offsets or residuals of points from the plotted curve.					

#	Statical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
2	6-parameter rigid-body spatial transformation (Realignment)	Within modality coregistration – usually this means realigning each of the images in a functional time series so that they're all in the same orientation	Very important to register within-individuals multimodal data	Must have	Several Neuroimaging package. Freesurfer, FSL, ANTS	Specific visualization toolbox. (freeview, fsleyes)	This should go BEYOND 6-degrees of freedom. Till 12 for linear
3	Undistortion	Deals with similar problem as unwarping – adjust images to correct for distortions caused by magnetic field inhomogeneities.	Very important for EPI-based MRI (such as DW-MRI).	Good to have	eddy function (from FSL package)		
4	Slice time correction	Adjust the values in the image to make it appear that all voxels have been acquired at the same time	Important for rsfMRI	Good to have	AFNI package		
5	Coregistration	Cross modality registration – realigning images collected using different acquisition sequences. Most commonly registering T1 weighted structural image to T2* weighted functional images.	Very similar to #2.	Must have	Several Neuroimaging package. Freesurfer, FSL, ANTS	Specific visualization toolbox. (freeview, fsleyes)	
6	Normalisation	Registration between different brains. Transforming one brain so its shape matches that of a different brain.	Very similar to #2 and #5. I would add non-linear registrations (local-deformations) that are useful for high-resolution MRI data	Must have	Several Neuroimaging package. Freesurfer, FSL, ANTS	Specific visualization toolbox. (freeview, fsleyes)	
7	Smoothing	Spatial averaging - replace the value at each voxel with a weighted average of the values in surrounding voxels	Last step of preprocessing prior to statistical analyses	Must have	fslmaths (from FSL package), or mri_smooth (Freesurfer)		
8	Clustering	Cluster analysis is a data-driven method that can assist in identifying voxels exhibiting similar patterns of task-related brain activity. Neuroimaging applications currently use several clustering algorithms, including the K-means approach, fuzzy clustering, hierarchical clustering methods, a hybrid hierarchical K-means DuBois Bowman approach, and dynamical cluster analysis (DCA). The performances of clustering methods are largely influenced by characteristics of the data. Many algorithms are capable of detecting well-separated clusters.	-				Same tools that described in General. At the end, MRI data is just a 3D matrix, which can be treat as "general data" and perform the clustering afterwards

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
9	Independent Component Analysis	The basic goal of ICA is to express the observed 3D brain images as linear combinations of statistically independent latent component signals.	Important, specially for data-driven analyses, and for rsfMRI analyses	Good to have	FSL package and AFNI package (also ANTs)		
10	Diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (DW-MRI)	Diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (DWI or DW-MRI) is the use of specific MRI sequences as well as software that generates images from the resulting data that uses the diffusion of water molecules to generate contrast in MR images.	This is a data type, not a tool per-se. I would change the view and propose a pipeline with basic preprocessing steps to have an outcome from this image-type that might be useful				
11	Correlation	correlation or dependence is any statistical relationship, whether causal or not, between two random variables or bivariate data.	Commonly used. However, in neuroimaging, 99% of times we include nuisance factors (so a GLM is preferred)	Must have			
12	Regression - General Linear Model (GLM)	GLM can be thought of as an extension of a more familiar statistical technique: linear regression. Linear regression, sometimes called trend-line analysis, is a method used to calculate the "best fitting" line for a set of experimental data.	To assess relationships between neuroimaging measures and demographics, controlling by nuisance factors (e.g age or sex)	Must have	Most neuroimaging softwares (FSL, Freesurfer)		
13	Bayesian Hierarchical Modeling	Bayesian hierarchical modelling is a statistical model written in multiple levels (hierarchical form) that estimates the parameters of the posterior distribution using the Bayesian method.	Never used				
14	Spatial and temporal filter	Spatial filter is one method by convolving an image with a filter in spatial domain. This technique reduces the variance in the image but blurs sharp edges by an amount related to the shape of the function used in the convolution. This process is equivalent to reduce high spatial frequencies in the image.	The spatial filter is similar to smoothing. The temporal filter is not as commonly used	Not important			
15	Anisotropic Diffusion filter	In this approach the image u is only convolved in the direction orthogonal to	Never used				

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
		the gradient of the image which ensures the preservation of edges.					
16	Nonlocal means filter	The NLM filter exploits the redundancy of information contained within the images to remove the noise. The restored intensity value of the voxel is calculated as the weighted average of all the voxel intensities within the image.	Might be useful to correct some distortion/noise and improve SNR	Good to have	DIPY (python packages), Mtrix package		
17	Wavelet transformation	Wavelets are mathematical functions that decompose data into different frequency components that can be studied with a resolution matched to their scale. Wavelet transforms are multiresolution representations of signals and images.	Never used	Not important			
18	Contourlet transform	The contourlets have the property of capturing contours and fine details in images. The Contourlet transform by Do and Vetterli is a geometrical image transform, which represents images containing contours and textures, and provides sparse representation at both spatial and directional resolutions. It offers a flexible multiresolution and directional decomposition for images, since it allows for a different number of directions at each scale.	Never used	Not important			
19	ROC	The receiver operator characteristic (ROC) method is used to compare the efficacy of various steps in calculating an activation map in the study of a single subject based on optimizing the ratio of the number of detected activations to the number of false-positive findings.	-	Must have	Several python and R packages		I don't think this is unique to neuroimaging. Its very important to have this tool, but for general use (any data, not just neuroimaging)
20	PCA	Principal components analysis (PCA) is a classical multivariate statistical tool, developed primarily by Hotelling (1933). The goal of PCA is to find linear combinations of the original variables	Might be useful for data-driven analyses. No super commonly used	Good to have			

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
		that parsimoniously describe the dependence structure of the data.					
NEW	Non parametric statistical tests	Statistical tests that do not assume normality of the data to test an hypothesis.	When the data is not normal (specially, demographics, since the smoothing step is performed to guarantee normalization of the neuroimaging data) we need to use non-parametric tests	Must have	PALM, randomise (from FSL) package		

Table 14 – Statistical Methods & Data Processing for General Analysis

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
1	Benchmarking	Benchmarking is a way of standardising – levelling the playing field – so that your data and results are meaningful in context. It involves taking outside factors into account so that you can adjust the parameters of your research and have a more precise understanding of what’s happening.	Almost never	Not important			
2	Regression Analysis	Regression is a statistical technique used for working out the relationship between two (or more) variables.	Most statistical analyses w/ continuous variables	Must have	Several R and python packages. Freesurfer and FSL for neuroimaging.	Scatterplot; beta-visualization	

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
3	T-test	The T-test is a tool for comparing two data groups which have different mean values. For example, do women and men have different mean heights? The T-test allows the user to interpret whether differences are statistically significant or merely coincidental	Parametric data	Must have	Several R and python packages. Freesurfer and FSL for neuroimaging.	Violin/Box plots	
4	Analysis of variance (ANOVA) tests	Like the T-test, ANOVA (analysis of variance) is a way of testing the differences between groups to see if they're statistically significant. However, ANOVA allows you to compare three or more groups rather than just two.	Parametric data	Must have	Several R and python packages. Freesurfer and FSL for neuroimaging.	Violin/Box plots	
5	Cluster Analysis	Cluster analysis is a way of processing datasets by identifying how closely related the individual data points are. Using cluster analysis, you can identify whether there are defined groups (clusters) within a large pool of data, or if the data is quite evenly spread out.	Data-driven analyses to differentiate between groups without a-prioris	Good to have	antspy (neuroimaging), pytorch, several other packages	tSNE	
6	Factor Analysis	Factor analysis is a way to reduce the complexity of your research findings by trading a large number of initial variables for a smaller number of deeper, underlying ones. In performing factor analysis, you uncover "hidden" factors that explain variance (difference from the average) in your findings.	Never used	Good to have	-		

#	Statistical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you may know) that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
7	z-test	A z-test is a statistical test to determine whether two population means are different when the variances are known and the sample size is large. A z-test is a hypothesis test in which the z-statistic follows a normal distribution.	Very similar to t-test? Specific case scenario?	Good to have		Violin/Box plots	
8	chi-square test	The Chi Square statistic is commonly used for testing relationships between categorical variables. The null hypothesis of the Chi-Square test is that no relationship exists on the categorical variables in the population; they are independent.	Prior to statistical analyses. Important to differentiate between groups. Mainly demographics data.	Must have	Several R packages		
9	MacNemar test	McNemar's test assesses the dependence of categorical data that are matched or paired.	Never heard of this one	Not important			
10							
11	Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test	Non-parametric version of ANOVA	Crucial when data do not follow a normal distribution	Must have	Several R and python packages. A very useful one is R package StatsExpressions	Violin/Box plots	
12	Permutation test	Use a bootstrap permutation of data to generate an actual/real null distribution to test if the hypothesis is true or rejected	Crucial when data do not follow a normal distribution	Must have			
13	Robust Correlation	Perform several iterations of a same correlation analyses with different subsamples of the initial sample	Correlation analyses might be driven/biased due to few outliers. With a robust correlation, one can have a more reliable measure on the	Must have	StatsExpressions in R		

#	Statical Methods & Data Processing	Short Description	How and when do you use this method in your medical research?	Importance	Tools (you know) may that implement this method	Visualisations for this method (Line chart, Bar chart, Image, Radar Chart, Heat map, Hypnogram, Table etc.)	Comment
			correlation between two continous variables				
14	Spearman's rank correlation coefficient	Association between two variables, that follow non-normal distribution, based on ranks	Crucial to study the association between two non-normal continous variables	Must have	Several packages in R and python		

ANNEX II : Metadata Manager OpenAPI v3

```
{
  "swagger": "2.0",
  "info": {
    "version": "9.0.0",
    "title": "PostgREST API",
    "description": "standard public schema"
  },
  "host": "api-metadata.mescobrad.digital-enabler.eng.it:443",
  "basePath": "/",
  "schemes": [
    "https"
  ],
  "consumes": [
    "application/json",
    "application/vnd.pgrst.object+json",
    "text/csv"
  ],
  "produces": [
    "application/json",
    "application/vnd.pgrst.object+json",
    "text/csv"
  ],
  "paths": {
    "/": {
      "get": {
        "tags": [
          "Introspection"
        ],
        "summary": "OpenAPI description (this document)",
        "produces": [
          "application/openapi+json",
          "application/json"
        ],
        "responses": {
          "200": {
            "description": "OK"
          }
        }
      }
    },
    "/concepts": {
      "get": {
        "tags": [
          "concepts"
        ],
        "parameters": [
          {

```



```
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts.concept_id"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts.name"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts.parent_id"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts.type"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/order"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/range"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rangeUnit"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/offset"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/limit"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/preferCount"
  }
],
"responses": {
  "200": {
    "schema": {
      "items": {
        "$ref": "#/definitions/concepts"
      },
      "type": "array"
    },
    "description": "OK"
  },
  "206": {
    "description": "Partial Content"
  }
}
},
"post": {
```



```
"tags": [
  "concepts"
],
"parameters": [
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/body.concepts"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
  }
],
"responses": {
  "201": {
    "description": "Created"
  }
},
"delete": {
  "tags": [
    "concepts"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts.concept_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts.name"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts.parent_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts.type"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "204": {
      "description": "No Content"
    }
  }
},
"patch": {
  "tags": [
```



```
    "concepts"  
  ],  
  "parameters": [  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts.concept_id"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts.name"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts.parent_id"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts.type"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.concepts"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"  
    }  
  ],  
  "responses": {  
    "204": {  
      "description": "No Content"  
    }  
  }  
},  
"/concepts_variables": {  
  "get": {  
    "tags": [  
      "concepts_variables"  
    ],  
    "parameters": [  
      {  
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts_variables.concept_id"  
      },  
      {  
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts_variables.variable_id"  
      },  
      {  
        "$ref": "#/parameters/select"  
      },  
      {  
        "$ref": "#/parameters/order"  
      },  
      {  
        "$ref": "#/parameters/range"  
      }  
    ]  
  }  
}
```



```
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rangeUnit"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/offset"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/limit"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferCount"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "200": {
      "schema": {
        "items": {
          "$ref": "#/definitions/concepts_variables"
        },
        "type": "array"
      },
      "description": "OK"
    },
    "206": {
      "description": "Partial Content"
    }
  }
},
"post": {
  "tags": [
    "concepts_variables"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.concepts_variables"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "201": {
      "description": "Created"
    }
  }
}
```



```
    },
    "delete": {
      "tags": [
        "concepts_variables"
      ],
      "parameters": [
        {
          "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts_variables.concept_id"
        },
        {
          "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts_variables.variable_id"
        },
        {
          "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
        }
      ],
      "responses": {
        "204": {
          "description": "No Content"
        }
      }
    },
    "patch": {
      "tags": [
        "concepts_variables"
      ],
      "parameters": [
        {
          "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts_variables.concept_id"
        },
        {
          "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.concepts_variables.variable_id"
        },
        {
          "$ref": "#/parameters/body.concepts_variables"
        },
        {
          "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
        }
      ],
      "responses": {
        "204": {
          "description": "No Content"
        }
      }
    }
  },
  "/languages": {
    "get": {
```



```
"tags": [
  "languages"
],
"parameters": [
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.languages.language_id"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.languages.name"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/order"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/range"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rangeUnit"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/offset"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/limit"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/preferCount"
  }
],
"responses": {
  "200": {
    "schema": {
      "items": {
        "$ref": "#/definitions/languages"
      },
      "type": "array"
    },
    "description": "OK"
  },
  "206": {
    "description": "Partial Content"
  }
}
},
"post": {
  "tags": [
```



```
    "languages"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.languages"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "201": {
      "description": "Created"
    }
  }
},
"delete": {
  "tags": [
    "languages"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.languages.language_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.languages.name"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "204": {
      "description": "No Content"
    }
  }
},
"patch": {
  "tags": [
    "languages"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.languages.language_id"
    },
    {

```



```
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.languages.name"
    },
    {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/body.languages"
    },
    {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
],
"responses": {
    "204": {
        "description": "No Content"
    }
}
},
"/questionnaires": {
    "get": {
        "tags": [
            "questionnaires"
        ],
        "parameters": [
            {
                "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questionnaires.questionnaire_id"
            },
            {
                "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questionnaires.creation_date"
            },
            {
                "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questionnaires.respondent"
            },
            {
                "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questionnaires.language_id"
            },
            {
                "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
            },
            {
                "$ref": "#/parameters/order"
            },
            {
                "$ref": "#/parameters/range"
            },
            {
                "$ref": "#/parameters/rangeUnit"
            },
            {
                "$ref": "#/parameters/offset"
            }
        ],
```



```
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/limit"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/preferCount"
}
],
"responses": {
  "200": {
    "schema": {
      "items": {
        "$ref": "#/definitions/questionnaires"
      },
      "type": "array"
    },
    "description": "OK"
  },
  "206": {
    "description": "Partial Content"
  }
}
},
"post": {
  "tags": [
    "questionnaires"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.questionnaires"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "201": {
      "description": "Created"
    }
  }
}
},
"delete": {
  "tags": [
    "questionnaires"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
```



```
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questionnaires.questionnaire_id"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questionnaires.creation_date"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questionnaires.respondent"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questionnaires.language_id"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
  }
],
"responses": {
  "204": {
    "description": "No Content"
  }
}
},
"patch": {
  "tags": [
    "questionnaires"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questionnaires.questionnaire_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questionnaires.creation_date"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questionnaires.respondent"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questionnaires.language_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.questionnaires"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "204": {
      "description": "No Content"
    }
  }
}
```



```
    }
  }
},
"/questions": {
  "get": {
    "tags": [
      "questions"
    ],
    "parameters": [
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions.question_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions.question_en"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions.questionnaire_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/order"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/range"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rangeUnit"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/offset"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/limit"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/preferCount"
      }
    ],
    "responses": {
      "200": {
        "schema": {
          "items": {
            "$ref": "#/definitions/questions"
          },
          "type": "array"
        },
        "description": "OK"
      }
    }
  }
}
```



```
    },
    "206": {
      "description": "Partial Content"
    }
  }
},
"post": {
  "tags": [
    "questions"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.questions"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "201": {
      "description": "Created"
    }
  }
},
"delete": {
  "tags": [
    "questions"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions.question_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions.question_en"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions.questionnaire_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "204": {
      "description": "No Content"
    }
  }
}
```



```
    }
  },
  "patch": {
    "tags": [
      "questions"
    ],
    "parameters": [
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions.question_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions.question_en"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions.questionnaire_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/body.questions"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
      }
    ],
    "responses": {
      "204": {
        "description": "No Content"
      }
    }
  }
},
"/questions_variables": {
  "get": {
    "tags": [
      "questions_variables"
    ],
    "parameters": [
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions_variables.question_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions_variables.variable_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/order"
      }
    ]
  }
}
```



```
    "$ref": "#/parameters/range"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rangeUnit"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/offset"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/limit"
  },
  {
    "$ref": "#/parameters/preferCount"
  }
],
"responses": {
  "200": {
    "schema": {
      "items": {
        "$ref": "#/definitions/questions_variables"
      },
      "type": "array"
    },
    "description": "OK"
  },
  "206": {
    "description": "Partial Content"
  }
}
},
"post": {
  "tags": [
    "questions_variables"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.questions_variables"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "201": {
      "description": "Created"
    }
  }
}
```



```
    }
  },
  "delete": {
    "tags": [
      "questions_variables"
    ],
    "parameters": [
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions_variables.question_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions_variables.variable_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
      }
    ],
    "responses": {
      "204": {
        "description": "No Content"
      }
    }
  },
  "patch": {
    "tags": [
      "questions_variables"
    ],
    "parameters": [
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions_variables.question_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.questions_variables.variable_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/body.questions_variables"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
      }
    ],
    "responses": {
      "204": {
        "description": "No Content"
      }
    }
  }
},
"/stscategories": {
```



```
"get": {
  "tags": [
    "stscategories"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories.category_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories.name"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories.parent_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/order"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/range"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rangeUnit"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/offset"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/limit"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferCount"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "200": {
      "schema": {
        "items": {
          "$ref": "#/definitions/stscategories"
        },
        "type": "array"
      },
      "description": "OK"
    },
    "206": {
      "description": "Partial Content"
    }
  }
}
```



```
    }
  },
  "post": {
    "tags": [
      "stscategories"
    ],
    "parameters": [
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/body.stscategories"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
      }
    ],
    "responses": {
      "201": {
        "description": "Created"
      }
    }
  },
  "delete": {
    "tags": [
      "stscategories"
    ],
    "parameters": [
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories.category_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories.name"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories.parent_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
      }
    ],
    "responses": {
      "204": {
        "description": "No Content"
      }
    }
  },
  "patch": {
    "tags": [
```



```
    "stscategories"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories.category_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories.name"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories.parent_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.stscategories"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "204": {
      "description": "No Content"
    }
  }
},
"/stscategories_variables": {
  "get": {
    "tags": [
      "stscategories_variables"
    ],
    "parameters": [
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories_variables.category_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories_variables.variable_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/order"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/range"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rangeUnit"
      }
    ]
  }
}
```



```
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/offset"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/limit"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferCount"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "200": {
      "schema": {
        "items": {
          "$ref": "#/definitions/stscategories_variables"
        },
        "type": "array"
      },
      "description": "OK"
    },
    "206": {
      "description": "Partial Content"
    }
  }
},
"post": {
  "tags": [
    "stscategories_variables"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.stscategories_variables"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "201": {
      "description": "Created"
    }
  }
},
"delete": {
  "tags": [
```



```
    "stscategories_variables"  
  ],  
  "parameters": [  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories_variables.category_id"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories_variables.variable_id"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"  
    }  
  ],  
  "responses": {  
    "204": {  
      "description": "No Content"  
    }  
  }  
},  
"patch": {  
  "tags": [  
    "stscategories_variables"  
  ],  
  "parameters": [  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories_variables.category_id"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.stscategories_variables.variable_id"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.stscategories_variables"  
    },  
    {  
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"  
    }  
  ],  
  "responses": {  
    "204": {  
      "description": "No Content"  
    }  
  }  
}  
},  
"/translations": {  
  "get": {  
    "tags": [  
      "translations"  
    ],  
  }  
}
```



```
"parameters": [  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.translation_id"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.question"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.question_id"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.language_id"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/select"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/order"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/range"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/rangeUnit"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/offset"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/limit"  
  },  
  {  
    "$ref": "#/parameters/preferCount"  
  }  
],  
"responses": {  
  "200": {  
    "schema": {  
      "items": {  
        "$ref": "#/definitions/translations"  
      },  
      "type": "array"  
    },  
    "description": "OK"  
  },  
  "206": {  
    "description": "Partial Content"  
  }  
}
```



```
    },  
    "post": {  
      "tags": [  
        "translations"  
      ],  
      "parameters": [  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/body.translations"  
        },  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/select"  
        },  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"  
        }  
      ],  
      "responses": {  
        "201": {  
          "description": "Created"  
        }  
      }  
    },  
    "delete": {  
      "tags": [  
        "translations"  
      ],  
      "parameters": [  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.translation_id"  
        },  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.question"  
        },  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.question_id"  
        },  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.language_id"  
        },  
        {  
          "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"  
        }  
      ],  
      "responses": {  
        "204": {  
          "description": "No Content"  
        }  
      }  
    }  
  },  
}
```



```
"patch": {
  "tags": [
    "translations"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.translation_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.question"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.question_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.translations.language_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.translations"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "204": {
      "description": "No Content"
    }
  }
},
"/variables": {
  "get": {
    "tags": [
      "variables"
    ],
    "parameters": [
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.variable_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.name"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.creation_date"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.measure_level"
      }
    ],
```



```
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.data_type"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.measure_unit"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.direct"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.formula"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.answer_number"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/order"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/range"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/rangeUnit"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/offset"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/limit"
},
{
  "$ref": "#/parameters/preferCount"
}
],
"responses": {
  "200": {
    "schema": {
      "items": {
        "$ref": "#/definitions/variables"
      },
      "type": "array"
    },
    "description": "OK"
  },
  "206": {
    "description": "Partial Content"
  }
}
```



```
    }
  },
  "post": {
    "tags": [
      "variables"
    ],
    "parameters": [
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/body.variables"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/select"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
      }
    ],
    "responses": {
      "201": {
        "description": "Created"
      }
    }
  },
  "delete": {
    "tags": [
      "variables"
    ],
    "parameters": [
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.variable_id"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.name"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.creation_date"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.measure_level"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.data_type"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.measure_unit"
      },
      {
        "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.direct"
      }
    ]
  }
}
```



```
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.formula"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.answer_number"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "204": {
      "description": "No Content"
    }
  }
},
"patch": {
  "tags": [
    "variables"
  ],
  "parameters": [
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.variable_id"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.name"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.creation_date"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.measure_level"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.data_type"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.measure_unit"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.direct"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.formula"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/rowFilter.variables.answer_number"
    }
  ],

```



```
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/body.variables"
    },
    {
      "$ref": "#/parameters/preferReturn"
    }
  ],
  "responses": {
    "204": {
      "description": "No Content"
    }
  }
}
},
"definitions": {
  "concepts": {
    "required": [
      "concept_id",
      "name"
    ],
    "properties": {
      "concept_id": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string",
        "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"
      },
      "name": {
        "format": "text",
        "type": "string"
      },
      "parent_id": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string"
      },
      "type": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string"
      }
    }
  },
  "type": "object"
},
"concepts_variables": {
  "required": [
    "concept_id",
    "variable_id"
  ]
}
```



```
    ],
    "properties": {
      "concept_id": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string",
        "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>\nThis is a Foreign Key to `concepts.concept_id`.<fk table='concepts' column='concept_id'/>"
      },
      "variable_id": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string",
        "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>\nThis is a Foreign Key to `variables.variable_id`.<fk table='variables' column='variable_id'/>"
      }
    },
    "type": "object"
  },
  "languages": {
    "required": [
      "language_id"
    ],
    "properties": {
      "language_id": {
        "maxLength": 2,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string",
        "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"
      },
      "name": {
        "format": "text",
        "type": "string"
      }
    }
  },
  "type": "object"
},
"questionnaires": {
  "required": [
    "questionnaire_id",
    "creation_date",
    "respondent"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "questionnaire_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"
    }
  }
}
```



```
    },
    "creation_date": {
      "format": "date",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "respondent": {
      "format": "text",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "language_id": {
      "maxLength": 2,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Foreign Key to `languages.language_id`.<fk
table='languages' column='language_id'/>"
    },
    "type": "object"
  },
  "questions": {
    "required": [
      "question_id",
      "question_en"
    ],
    "properties": {
      "question_id": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string",
        "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"
      },
      "question_en": {
        "format": "text",
        "type": "string"
      },
      "questionnaire_id": {
        "maxLength": 8,
        "format": "character",
        "type": "string",
        "description": "Note:\nThis is a Foreign Key to
`questionnaires.questionnaire_id`.<fk
column='questionnaire_id'/>"
      }
    },
    "type": "object"
  },
  "questions_variables": {
    "required": [
      "question_id",
```



```
    "variable_id"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "question_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>\nThis is a Foreign Key to
`questions.question_id`.<fk table='questions' column='question_id'/>"
    },
    "variable_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>\nThis is a Foreign Key to
`variables.variable_id`.<fk table='variables' column='variable_id'/>"
    }
  },
  "type": "object"
},
"stscategories": {
  "required": [
    "category_id",
    "name"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "category_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"
    },
    "name": {
      "format": "text",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "parent_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string"
    }
  },
  "type": "object"
},
"stscategories_variables": {
  "required": [
    "category_id",
    "variable_id"
  ],
  "type": "object"
},

```



```
"properties": {
  "category_id": {
    "maxLength": 8,
    "format": "character",
    "type": "string",
    "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>\nThis is a Foreign Key to
`stscategories.category_id`.<fk table='stscategories' column='category_id'/>"
  },
  "variable_id": {
    "maxLength": 8,
    "format": "character",
    "type": "string",
    "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>\nThis is a Foreign Key to
`variables.variable_id`.<fk table='variables' column='variable_id'/>"
  }
},
"type": "object"
},
"translations": {
  "required": [
    "translation_id"
  ],
  "properties": {
    "translation_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"
    },
    "question": {
      "format": "text",
      "type": "string"
    },
    "question_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Foreign Key to `questions.question_id`.<fk
table='questions' column='question_id'/>"
    },
    "language_id": {
      "maxLength": 8,
      "format": "character",
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Foreign Key to `languages.language_id`.<fk
table='languages' column='language_id'/>"
    }
  },
  "type": "object"
}
```



```
},  
"variables": {  
  "required": [  
    "variable_id",  
    "name",  
    "creation_date"  
  ],  
  "properties": {  
    "variable_id": {  
      "maxLength": 8,  
      "format": "character",  
      "type": "string",  
      "description": "Note:\nThis is a Primary Key.<pk/>"  
    },  
    "name": {  
      "format": "text",  
      "type": "string"  
    },  
    "creation_date": {  
      "format": "date",  
      "type": "string"  
    },  
    "measure_level": {  
      "format": "text",  
      "type": "string"  
    },  
    "data_type": {  
      "format": "text",  
      "type": "string"  
    },  
    "measure_unit": {  
      "format": "text",  
      "type": "string"  
    },  
    "direct": {  
      "format": "boolean",  
      "type": "boolean"  
    },  
    "formula": {  
      "format": "text",  
      "type": "string"  
    },  
    "answer_number": {  
      "format": "integer",  
      "type": "integer"  
    }  
  },  
  "type": "object"  
}
```



```
},
"parameters": {
  "preferParams": {
    "name": "Prefer",
    "description": "Preference",
    "required": false,
    "in": "header",
    "type": "string",
    "enum": [
      "params=single-object"
    ]
  },
  "preferReturn": {
    "name": "Prefer",
    "description": "Preference",
    "required": false,
    "in": "header",
    "type": "string",
    "enum": [
      "return=representation",
      "return=minimal",
      "return=none"
    ]
  },
  "preferCount": {
    "name": "Prefer",
    "description": "Preference",
    "required": false,
    "in": "header",
    "type": "string",
    "enum": [
      "count=none"
    ]
  },
  "select": {
    "name": "select",
    "description": "Filtering Columns",
    "required": false,
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "on_conflict": {
    "name": "on_conflict",
    "description": "On Conflict",
    "required": false,
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "order": {
```



```
    "name": "order",
    "description": "Ordering",
    "required": false,
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "range": {
    "name": "Range",
    "description": "Limiting and Pagination",
    "required": false,
    "in": "header",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rangeUnit": {
    "name": "Range-Unit",
    "description": "Limiting and Pagination",
    "required": false,
    "default": "items",
    "in": "header",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "offset": {
    "name": "offset",
    "description": "Limiting and Pagination",
    "required": false,
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "limit": {
    "name": "limit",
    "description": "Limiting and Pagination",
    "required": false,
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.concepts": {
    "name": "concepts",
    "description": "concepts",
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/concepts"
    },
    "in": "body"
  },
  "rowFilter.concepts.concept_id": {
    "name": "concept_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
```



```
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.concepts.name": {
    "name": "name",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.concepts.parent_id": {
    "name": "parent_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.concepts.type": {
    "name": "type",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.concepts_variables": {
    "name": "concepts_variables",
    "description": "concepts_variables",
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/concepts_variables"
    },
    "in": "body"
  },
  "rowFilter.concepts_variables.concept_id": {
    "name": "concept_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.concepts_variables.variable_id": {
    "name": "variable_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.languages": {
    "name": "languages",
    "description": "languages",
```



```
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/languages"
    },
    "in": "body"
  },
  "rowFilter.languages.language_id": {
    "name": "language_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.languages.name": {
    "name": "name",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.questionnaires": {
    "name": "questionnaires",
    "description": "questionnaires",
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/questionnaires"
    },
    "in": "body"
  },
  "rowFilter.questionnaires.questionnaire_id": {
    "name": "questionnaire_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.questionnaires.creation_date": {
    "name": "creation_date",
    "required": false,
    "format": "date",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.questionnaires.respondent": {
    "name": "respondent",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  }
```



```
},
"rowFilter.questionnaires.language_id": {
  "name": "language_id",
  "required": false,
  "format": "character",
  "in": "query",
  "type": "string"
},
"body.questions": {
  "name": "questions",
  "description": "questions",
  "required": false,
  "schema": {
    "$ref": "#/definitions/questions"
  },
  "in": "body"
},
"rowFilter.questions.question_id": {
  "name": "question_id",
  "required": false,
  "format": "character",
  "in": "query",
  "type": "string"
},
"rowFilter.questions.question_en": {
  "name": "question_en",
  "required": false,
  "format": "text",
  "in": "query",
  "type": "string"
},
"rowFilter.questions.questionnaire_id": {
  "name": "questionnaire_id",
  "required": false,
  "format": "character",
  "in": "query",
  "type": "string"
},
"body.questions_variables": {
  "name": "questions_variables",
  "description": "questions_variables",
  "required": false,
  "schema": {
    "$ref": "#/definitions/questions_variables"
  },
  "in": "body"
},
"rowFilter.questions_variables.question_id": {
  "name": "question_id",
```



```
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.questions_variables.variable_id": {
    "name": "variable_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.stscategories": {
    "name": "stscategories",
    "description": "stscategories",
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/stscategories"
    },
    "in": "body"
  },
  "rowFilter.stscategories.category_id": {
    "name": "category_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.stscategories.name": {
    "name": "name",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.stscategories.parent_id": {
    "name": "parent_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.stscategories_variables": {
    "name": "stscategories_variables",
    "description": "stscategories_variables",
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/stscategories_variables"
    }
  },
}
```



```
    "in": "body"
  },
  "rowFilter.stscategories_variables.category_id": {
    "name": "category_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.stscategories_variables.variable_id": {
    "name": "variable_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.translations": {
    "name": "translations",
    "description": "translations",
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/translations"
    }
  },
  "in": "body"
},
"rowFilter.translations.translation_id": {
  "name": "translation_id",
  "required": false,
  "format": "character",
  "in": "query",
  "type": "string"
},
"rowFilter.translations.question": {
  "name": "question",
  "required": false,
  "format": "text",
  "in": "query",
  "type": "string"
},
"rowFilter.translations.question_id": {
  "name": "question_id",
  "required": false,
  "format": "character",
  "in": "query",
  "type": "string"
},
"rowFilter.translations.language_id": {
  "name": "language_id",
  "required": false,
```



```
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "body.variables": {
    "name": "variables",
    "description": "variables",
    "required": false,
    "schema": {
      "$ref": "#/definitions/variables"
    },
    "in": "body"
  },
  "rowFilter.variables.variable_id": {
    "name": "variable_id",
    "required": false,
    "format": "character",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.variables.name": {
    "name": "name",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.variables.creation_date": {
    "name": "creation_date",
    "required": false,
    "format": "date",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.variables.measure_level": {
    "name": "measure_level",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.variables.data_type": {
    "name": "data_type",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.variables.measure_unit": {
```



```
    "name": "measure_unit",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.variables.direct": {
    "name": "direct",
    "required": false,
    "format": "boolean",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.variables.formula": {
    "name": "formula",
    "required": false,
    "format": "text",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  },
  "rowFilter.variables.answer_number": {
    "name": "answer_number",
    "required": false,
    "format": "integer",
    "in": "query",
    "type": "string"
  }
},
"externalDocs": {
  "url": "https://postgrest.org/en/v9.0/api.html",
  "description": "PostgREST Documentation"
}
}
```

